

RURITAGE

Heritage for Rural Regeneration

RURITAGE Heritage-led regeneration plans for Replicators

D1.4

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Background Information

Table 1: technical Information

Project Full title		Rural regeneration through systemic heritage-led strategies	
Project Acronym		RURITAGE	
Grant Agreement No.		776465	
Coordinator		University of Bologna (UNIBO)	
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		24/01/2020	January 2020 (month 20)
Work Package No		3	
Work Package Title		Co-developing and co-implementing heritage-led rural regeneration plans in Replicators	
Responsible		University of Bologna (UNIBO)	
Author(s)		<p>UNIBO</p> <p>Development of the deliverable as a whole. Contribution to the draft of the 6 regeneration plans. Coordination of the link with WP3 and other WPs. Onsite support in several local workshops.</p> <p>Authors (in alphabetical order): Hanna Elisabet Åberg, Elisa Conticelli, Claudia de Luca, Angela Santangelo, Simona Tondelli (UNIBO).</p>	
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	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (CO)	

Table 2: List of abbreviations

D	Deliverable
WP	Work Package
M	Month
RHH	Rural Heritage Hub
RM	Role Model
R	Replicator
KFP	Knowledge Facilitator Partner
SIA	Systemic Innovation Area
CNH	Cultural and Natural Heritage
CHMP	Community based Heritage Management and Planning
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
DRHH	Digital Rural Heritage Hub
C	Challenges
O	Objectives
SC	Steering Committee

1. Executive Summary

This deliverable summarizes the results of Task 3.3 “Co-development of innovative heritage-led regeneration Plans” in Replicators and builds on findings and activities coming from WP1, WP2, WP3, WP4 and WP7, as detailed explained in the following paragraph. The heritage-led regeneration plans presented in this deliverable will be then implemented in the framework of Task 3.5.

RURITAGE 6 Replicators represent six very diverse rural areas in Europe and beyond (Austria, Norway, Germany, Slovenia, Italy and Turkey) and are acting as the main laboratories to test the RURITAGE approach.

By working on the 6 identified Systemic Innovation Areas (SIAs) - Pilgrimage, Local Food, Migration, Art&Festival, Resilience, Landscape-, the Replicators are demonstrating local Cultural and Natural Heritage (CNH) as a driver for regeneration and sustainable growth.

These 6 SIAs have been detailed and studied in WP1. Based on the identification and analysis of Role Models’ good practices, the identification of Lessons Learned from the Role Models’ experience and the definition Replicators’ baseline (WP1), after the establishment of the Rural Heritage Hubs (RHH, Task 3.1) and according to the Community-based Heritage Management and Planning (CHMP) methodology developed within WP2, this task has been devoted to the co-development of the heritage-led regeneration plan in each of the 6 RURITAGE Replicators. During the co-development phase, that started in March 2019 and will close in March 2020 with the launch event of the implementation phase, RURITAGE Replicators, following the guidelines of the CHMP methodology, implemented several workshops, open public events, and other meetings with their local stakeholders. Along this process, Replicators have been assisted by all the 13 RURITAGE Role Models (RMs) and by the Knowledge Facilitator Partners (KFPs) through remote bilateral and group meetings, face-to-face knowledge transfer workshops (Task 2.4) and mentoring and learning visits (Task 2.3). This framework of activities created a constant and fluent collaboration from RMs and KFPs to Replicators and through Rs themselves. Also, the learning and mentoring visits and the knowledge transfer workshops contributed to increase the Replicators’ capacity and to make them aware of the potential of their rich Cultural and Natural Heritage, allowing them to undertake and facilitate a complex and rich process of rural regeneration. To monitor and further assess the effectiveness and the impact of each heritage-led regeneration plan, the monitoring programme developed in WP4 (Key Performance Indicators – KPIs, co-monitoring tools, modalities and timeline for reporting) has been integrated into each plan and in the overall report.

At local level, within the Rural Heritage Hubs (RHHs), a total of more than 2300 people attended the launch events of the Replicators, while numerous stakeholders actively participated to the workshops that followed, such as the Serious Game workshop (Del 2.4, expected in May 2020), the Participatory workshop (Guidelines attached to this deliverable), the Business Model workshop (Del 3.3), and several Round Table meetings. Throughout this process, Replicators have worked hard to engage their stakeholders, that demonstrated a great interest in the project and committed to support the co-implementation and co-monitoring phase. More than 100 of these stakeholders will also cover an active role in the co-implementation phase through public-private partnerships, public-public partnerships and voluntary agreements. The exact features of this collaboration, methodologies used, and results achieved will be reported M48 in Del. 3.6 ‘Report on the involvement of communities in cultural heritage’. In a nutshell, the heritage led-regeneration plans developed by the Replicators can be considered as the main result of an extremely intense joint work done by the Replicators and their local stakeholders, the KFPs and RMs and by UNIBO that, as coordinator and leader of WP3, supervised and facilitated the whole process. This deliverable aims at summarizing this whole process.

The heritage-led regeneration plans presented below are conceived to enable rural regeneration through Cultural and Natural Heritage in the Replicators’ rural territories. According to the European framework for Action on Cultural Heritage (2018), there is a clear and urgent need for emphasizing the value and potential of cultural heritage as a resource for sustainable growth and quality of life in a constantly evolving society. The European Framework for Action on Cultural Heritage looks at the tangible, intangible and digital dimensions of cultural heritage as inseparable and interconnected. The understanding of tangible, intangible and digital heritage within

the RURITAGE heritage-led regeneration plans is in accordance to the UNESCO definitions. Tangible heritage is the physical leavings of previous generations as well as the concrete of new, including built and natural heritage, tangible artefacts and archaeological leavings. The intangible heritage related actions include traditions, inherited and living, that has shaped and is shaping communities. Learning, knowledge and heritage ownership and awareness are among the focus of the heritage-led regeneration plans. Beyond this, RURITAGE recognizes digital heritage as an important tool for the sustainable development of rural communities, for today and for the future.

Figure 1: Classification of the actions in the Replicators’ Plans according with the three main types of Heritage

Figure 2: Classification of the actions in the Replicators’ Plans according with a more detailed classification of Heritage

As illustrated in Fig.1, 58% of the actions included in the 6 Replicators’ plans addressed intangible heritage, while 36% are related with tangible and 6% with digital.

More specifically, as detailed in the chart in Fig.2, the following heritage has been considered:

- **Tangible Heritage:** 27% Natural Heritage, 6% Built Heritage and 3% Artefacts
- **Intangible Heritage:** 20% Knowledge and practices, 18% Social practices Rituals and festive events, 9% Performing Arts, 6% Oral traditions, and 5% Traditional Craftmanship
- **Digital Heritage** 6%

Also, Replicators built on RMs' experiences, Good practices and Lessons learned, based on the RURITAGE paradigm constituted by the 6 identified Systemic Innovation Areas (SIAs)- Pilgrimage, Local Food, Migration, Art&Festival, Resilience, Landscape. Even though each Replicator focused on one main SIA to develop its action plan, all of them touched upon several of them to build their heritage-led strategy and actions (Fig. 3). Each action is related and builds on one or more Systematic Innovation Areas, as summarized in Fig.3.

Figure 3: SIAs included in the developed actions

The challenges presented by the economic crisis, such as rising unemployment, civic disengagement, and social exclusion - phenomena which are even more intense in rural areas - added to the threats imposed by climate changes and environmental degradation are leading to increasing depopulation and abandonment of rural areas. From the Replicators' baselines developed in Task 1.4 and through a further assessment of the Replicators' partner organizations, the 6 rural territories identified their main challenges, among which some are common, such as depopulation, lack of visibility in a wider context, lack of collaboration among local stakeholders and lack of social inclusion. Through their heritage-led regeneration plans the Replicators will tackle these challenges with diverse and tailored specific actions.

Being one of the main EU funded project working on heritage- led regeneration in rural areas, RURITAGE aims at making the Replicators' plans and the overall methodologies and tools developed to build those, a reference for all rural areas and communities around Europe and beyond.

1.1 Structure of the document

To widely present the heritage-led regeneration plans and the process that led to their development, this report is structured as follows:

Chapter 2 Introduction - it presents an introduction to the report, highlighting the main objectives and the contributions from project partners;

Chapter 3 Summary of the co-development phase – it provides a first overview of the activities organised in the 6 RURITAGE Replicators' Rural Heritage Hub (including the setting of the Hub foreseen in Task 3.1).

All Replicators have undertaken so far at least 5 workshops to co-develop their heritage-led regeneration plans:

1. One **launch event** of the Rural Heritage Hub where the project has been present to the local community and the space of the RHH has been opened
2. one workshop with the integration of **RURITAGE serious games** (Task 2.2) – to develop together with their local stakeholders, a shared vision of the future of the rural territory in each Replicator;
3. one **Participatory workshop** – to present to local stakeholders the Replicators' baseline and challenges

(Del 1.4) and to get familiar, discuss and decide with them on possible Role Models' Actions (Del. 1.1) and Lessons Learned (Del 1.2) relevant for each Replicator territory;

4. one event to define **Business models (Del 3.3)** – to develop detailed business models for the actions chosen during the Participatory workshops
5. **Round tables with the key stakeholders** - to define the role of the stakeholders in the implementation of the actions and to draft agreements and partnerships with them for the co-implementation phase

Chapter 4. Collaboration among RS, RMs and KFPs in the implementation of the plans – thanks to the knowledge transfer mechanisms developed within the project, the 6 Replicators included some active partners in their action plans to support them in the implementation phase. This chapter presents the different mechanism foreseen to facilitate and boost their collaboration and networking. Specifically, the collaboration will happen through the Digital Heritage Hub, learning and mentoring visits, remote and the face to face consortium meetings, and through bilateral calls and email exchange.

Chapter 5. Monitoring of the plans – it describes the monitoring process of the plans implementation through the identified KPIs and the monitoring programme developed in WP4 and here briefly described. Moreover, it introduces a progress report template that will be used for a more qualitative monitoring of the plan implementation by UNIBO.

Chapters from 8 to 13 presents the Heritage-led regeneration plans of the 6 Replicators, where the Replicators describe their heritage-led regeneration strategy starting from their actual situation, their challenges and opportunities. All the plans have been developed according to the same structure:

- the background information on the Replicator, concerning its main SIA, the other SIAs that the Replicator considered as relevant for its heritage-led regeneration strategy; the Replicator's diagnosis and baseline that has been defined in Task 1.4;
- the challenges that the Replicator is facing;
- the main objectives of the heritage-led regeneration plan;
- the operational programme for the implementation of the plan, where all the actions have been described in detail;
- the risks for the implementation of the heritage-led regeneration plan.

Chapter 6 R1 Karavanke/Karawanken UNESCO Global Geopark (ARGE GK) Heritage-Led regeneration plan

Geopark Karavanke/Karawanken developed its heritage-led regeneration plan working with the SIA Pilgrimage as its main reference. The plan includes a total of 5 actions; the Pilgrimage SIA is addressed by 3 of them; the Local Food SIA is addressed by 4 actions and the Landscape SIA by 4 actions.

ARGE managed to raise 107.966,26 additional euro coming from an agreement between Geopark Karavanke/Karawanken and the municipality of Globasnitz/Globasnica and managed to sign 1 PPPs and voluntary agreements with 5 stakeholders.

4 RMs (RM1, RM2, RM3, RM8) and 3 KFPs (ICLEI, UoP, ACIR) will be actively involved in the implementation phase.

Chapter 7 R2 Magma UNESCO Global Geopark (Magma UGG) Heritage-Led regeneration plan

Magma Geopark developed its heritage-led regeneration plan working with the SIA Local Food as its main reference. The plan includes a total of 3 actions; the Local Food SIA is addressed by 2 of them and the Landscape SIA by all the 3 actions.

The additional funding, mainly coming from local municipalities, is currently being raised. Magma Geopark managed to sign 6 PPPs with 5 local municipalities and one region and voluntary agreements with 8 stakeholders. 3 RMs (RM4, RM11, RM13) and 1 KFP (ACIR) will be actively involved in the implementation phase.

Chapter 8 R3 Geo-Naturpark Bergstraße-Odenwald UNESCO Global Geopark (Geo-N) Heritage-Led regeneration plan

Geo-N developed its heritage-led regeneration plan working with the SIA Migration as its main reference. The plan includes a total of 9 actions, all of them related with the Migration SIA and also with the Landscape SIA. The SIA Art&Festival is addressed by 3 of those actions.

The additional funding, coming from different partners such as UNESCO WHS Messel pit and the International Forest Art Association local municipalities, is currently being raised. Geo-N managed to sign 1 PPPs, 9 support agreements and a voluntary agreement with 1 stakeholder.

10 RMs (RM1, RM2, RM3, RM5, RM6, RM7, RM8, RM9, RM10, RM11) and 1 KFP (UoP) will be actively involved in the implementation phase.

Chapter 9 R4 Negova Castle Heritage-Led regeneration plan

Kibla and Kultprotur developed their heritage-led regeneration plan working with the SIA Art&Festival as their main reference. The plan includes a total of 5 actions. The Art&Festival SIA is addressed by 4 actions, Pilgrimage SIA is addressed by 2 actions; the Food SIA is addressed by 4 actions and Landscape SIA by 2.

Kibla and Kultprotur already managed to raise around 26.000 additional euros coming from Kultprotur and other local stakeholders' own resources and managed to sign 18 PPS and voluntary agreements with 15 stakeholders.

4 RMs (RM2, RM3, RM7, RM8) and 1 KFP (UoP) will be actively involved in the implementation phase.

Chapter 10 R5 Appignano del Tronto Heritage-Led regeneration plan

The municipality of Appignano del Tronto developed its heritage-led regeneration plan working with the SIA Resilience as their main reference. The plan includes a total of 11 actions, 6 of which are directly related with Resilience SIA; the Pilgrimage SIA is addressed by 1 action; the Local Food SIA and the Landscape SIA are addressed by 6 actions; Migrants SIA and Art&Festival SIA are addressed by 2 actions.

CoApp managed to raise around 4.000 additional euros coming from local stakeholders' own resources and managed to sign 40 PPS and voluntary agreements with local stakeholders.

7 RMs (RM1, RM2, RM3, RM7, RM8, RM9, RM10) and 7 KFPs (Savonia, APRE, UNESCO, BITN, ICLEI, ACIR, CARTIF) will be actively involved in the implementation phase.

Chapter 11 R6 IZMIR Heritage-led regeneration plan

The Izmir Metropolitan Area, the Technical University of Izmir and DEM Energy developed their-heritage led regeneration plan working with the SIA Integrated Landscape as their main reference. The plan includes a total of 9 actions; the Landscape SIA is directly addressed by 6 of them; the Pilgrimage SIA is addressed by 1 action; the Food SIA and the Art&Festival SIA are addressed by 2 actions and the Resilience SIA by 3 of them.

IZM managed to raise around 20.000 additional euros coming from Izmir Metropolitan Area and other local stakeholders' own resources and managed to sign 48 PPS and voluntary agreement with local stakeholders.

10 RMs (RM1, RM2, RM3, RM6, RM7, RM8, RM9, RM10, Rm12, RM13) and 3 KFPs (UNESCO, UoP, BITN) will be actively involved in the implementation phase

List of References and **List of Figures** close the report.

Annex I - contains all the detailed tables for the implementation of the activities to be undertaken under each action

Annex II - includes all the detailed guidelines of the workshops (Launch Workshop, Serious Game Workshop, Participatory workshop, Business Model Workshop and Round table of stakeholders).

2. Introduction

2.1 Objectives

WP3 puts in practices the RURITAGE paradigm, based on the 6 identified Systemic Innovation Areas (SIAs) - Pilgrimage, Local Food, Migration, Art&Festival, Resilience, Landscape- interpreting local Cultural and Natural Heritage as a driver of regeneration of rural areas.

The selected 6 Replicator represent six very diverse rural areas in Europe and beyond (Austria, Norway, Germany, Slovenia, Italy and Turkey) that will act as laboratories for testing the RURITAGE paradigm that will be further upscaled through WP6 activities. Replicators are represented by very diverse organizations, geoparks, municipalities, SMEs, and no-profit organizations, guaranteeing the possibility to apply RURITAGE paradigm in very diverse geographical, economic and social contexts.

The overall objective of WP3, where this report is embedded, is to support Replicators (R) and Role models (RMs) in building and implementing heritage-led regeneration strategies and actions. Specific WP3 objectives are:

- establishing one Rural Heritage Hubs (RHH) in each Replicators and Role Models (Task 3.1);
- supporting the co-development of heritage-led regeneration strategies within the Replicators RHHs (Task 3.2 and 3.3);
- co-implement large-scale demonstration projects in Replicators (Task 3.4);
- supporting further enhancement of RMs heritage-led regeneration strategies (Task 3.5).

This report summarizes the results of the co-development phase in Replicators (Task 3.3), setting up the basis for the co-implementation and co-monitoring of the heritage-led regeneration plans developed. Specific objectives of this report are:

- present and explain the overall co-development process that involved the Rs, their local stakeholders and the support of some KFPs (UNIBO, CE, CARTIF, UoP SAVONIA, ICLEI, CRS)
- highlighting the collaboration of the diverse partners of the consortium in terms of knowledge exchange, capacity building and technical support, as one of the main added value of the RURITAGE project
- present each heritage led regeneration plan, providing details about objectives, challenges and actions of each Rs

3. Summary of the co-development phase

During the co-development phase, that started in March 2019 and will close in March 2020 with the launch event of the implementation phase, RURITAGE Replicators implemented several workshops, open public events, and other meetings with their local stakeholders.

Within RURITAGE, according to the guidelines of the CHMP methodology, a minimum set of activities have been defined for the co-development phase of the heritage-led regeneration strategies. This chapter is aimed at explaining the overall objectives of the different events and workshops that has been organised, and the main outcomes.

3.1 Rural Heritage Hub: the launch event

The primary objective of the launch of the hub is to officially launch the RURITAGE Hub space and gather additional stakeholders to take part in the coming Hub activities. This activity, conceived as an open public event, contributed to raise awareness about the local area and community benefit from the involvement in the RHH and thus in the RURITAGE project. Specific guidelines have been developed by UNIBO and CE to give tips to rural communities on how to organize their launch event (Annex II). More than 2,300 people attended the 6 events in total, one in each Replicator.

Figure 4: Launch of the RHH in Appignano del Tronto

© Appignano del Tronto

Figure 5: Launch event of RHH in Izmir area

© IZM, DEM, IZTECH

3.2 The Serious Game workshop

This second workshop has been an occasion to develop a shared vision of rural regeneration, to build connection and trust between stakeholders as well as illuminate the interconnections between different aspects of rural regeneration. In particular, the general objectives of the serious game have been to:

- Develop Systems Thinking: allow participants to experience and reflect on trade-off and synergies between various strategies of developing rural areas relevant to their situation.
- Nurture Collaboration: support stakeholders in developing a shared understanding of the major challenges and opportunities for their areas.

In the case of rural regeneration, there are many competing areas of potential investment: the chosen Strategic Innovation Area (SIA) is only a launching point. Embedded in each SIA is income generation, workforce development, social inclusion / activation of local communities, and disaster preparedness. The serious game helps participants understanding the trade-offs and synergies in achieving their goals.

Developed by CRS, it consists in a board and role game where various scenarios can be developed. An average number of 10 stakeholders per Replicator has been participating to the game, while the RHH coordinator has been tutored by CRS to get a good knowledge of the game dynamics.

Figure 6: Serious Game workshop in Negova

© Zavod Kultprotur

3.3 The Participatory workshop

This workshop aimed at entering into the core of the co-development phase of the heritage-led regeneration plan and it has been the first occasion to let the stakeholders familiarize with the concept of the SIAs and with the Good Practices collected in the Inventory (Del. 1.1) from RURITAGE Role Models, presented here in form of playing cards. Developed by UNIBO and CE, it consisted in a participated workshop where stakeholders used RURITAGE cards to discuss Good practices from RURITAGE RMs and tailor those to their territory. The main outcomes have been

the Role Model Action selection as the more relevant by local stakeholders, and the definition of new practices and ideas coming from the stakeholders.

The participatory workshop has been indeed a crucial step to start defining, for the first time together with the stakeholders, possible actions to be included in the action plan and to be implemented in Replicators' territories. As in previous events, this one should also serve as an occasion to attract and engage further stakeholders into the RHHs.

Figure 7: Participatory workshop in Magma Unesco Global Geopark and in Appignano del Tronto

© Magma UGG

© Appignano del Tronto

3.4 The Business Model workshop

Following the Participatory Workshop, the Business Models Workshop has been the following step in the co-development of heritage-led regeneration strategies for Replicators. The task aimed to develop detailed business models for the actions that Replicators have chosen to implement in their territories. Using an innovative business model framework develop by SAVONIA UAS and WESTBIC, that consists in an adaptation of the traditional Canva Business model with the integration of an online tool, stakeholders within the six Replicators have been supported in developing tailored opportunities and initiatives, and in making the prioritization of the different possibilities to be undertaken within a regeneration action. The results of this process have been gathered in the Del 3.3.

Figure 8: Participatory workshop and Business Model workshop

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© GEO-N

Figure 9: Business Model workshop in Karavanke/Karawanken Geopark

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3.5 The Round Table with key stakeholders

The general objective of the round tables with local stakeholders has been to define and detail the activities necessary to carry out the actions of the heritage-led strategies. After the participatory and the business models workshops, Replicators have selected the actions to be included in their Action Plan. The round tables with key stakeholders helped in carefully detail how to co-implement and co-monitor the actions.

During these meetings, RURITAGE partners have prepared the basis for building the agreements with relevant stakeholders, to define in detail their roles, responsibilities and contribution (financial, human, in kind, etc.). Based on this, Replicators drafted the agreements with their stakeholders (public-private partnerships, voluntary agreement, etc.). Guidelines for the meetings have been developed by UNIBO (see Annex II).

Figure 10: Round table meetings with key stakeholders in Karavanke/Karawanken Geopark

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4. Collaboration among RS, RMs and KFPs in the implementation of the plans

One of the main RURITAGE objectives is to foster capacity building, knowledge transfer and exchange from RMs and KFPs to Replicators, and among RMs, Rs and KFPs themselves. Most of the activities of WP2 (Task 2.3, 2.4 and 2.5) aims at facilitating this process enabling on one side the face-to-face bilateral knowledge transfer (learning and mentoring visits) and at consortium level (knowledge transfer workshops). On the other side, through Task 2.5, UNESCO, POLITO and APRE built a dedicated digital platform within the RURITAGE resources ecosystem (<http://www.RURITAGE-ecosystem.eu/>), the so-called Digital Rural Heritage Hub (DRHH) for facilitating and boosting knowledge transfer among KFPs, RMs, Rs, additional RMs and additional Rs.

These various ways of knowledge exchange will be further boosted in the co-implementation and co-monitoring phase. RMs and KFPs have been involved as active partner in the co-development of the heritage-led regeneration plans and will support the continuous knowledge transfer through the following tools and activities:

- Digital Rural Heritage Hub (DRHH): it will be the main platform for knowledge exchange; relevant expertise of RMs will be shared through dedicated *posts*, webinars, bilateral discussions, or further email exchange. Analysing the heritage-led regeneration plans, UNIBO already identified some topics that would be useful for Replicators: *how to make an effective call for artist? (RM7 TAKEART) How to digitalize your pilgrimage and what is the added value? (RM1 FSMLRH + ACIR) How to involve local farmers in your activities (RM3 DARE)?* More topics will be explored at the beginning of the co-implementation phase by APRE and UNESCO, as leader of the knowledge exchange and platform. The discussion in the platform will be moderated by APRE. The DRHH will also be the main space to facilitate the exchange between full RURITAGE partners and Additional Replicators and Role Models.
- Monthly Replicator Forum: Knowledge transfer from KFPs for common challenges.
- Mentoring and learning visits, as detailed through Task 2.3 and in the Protocol of Knowledge Transfer
- Knowledge transfer workshops: the Training workshop (M9, in Valladolid, Spain) aimed at training the coordinators of the Replicators' RHH regarding the CHMP methodology implementation; the Development workshop (M12 in Psiloritis UNESCO Global Geopark, Greece) allowed to advance in the development and the implementation phase, providing training for Rs and RMs on business model development and fund raising; Launch workshop (M17 in Appignano del Tronto, Italy) supported the Rs in the launching of the implementation phase. The 4th knowledge transfer workshop will take place in the Karavaken/Karavanke ARGE Geopark at the end of October 2020. The workshop will be dedicated to tailor the action under implementation. Also, the consortium is thinking about having a dedicated session of knowledge transfer during the General Assembly in Magma UNESCO Geopark, taking place in May 2020.

The following figures summarizes the active involvement of RMS and KFPs in specific actions of the heritage led regeneration plans of the Replicator. UNIBO is included in all the figures since it will provide continuous support on the overall implementation of the action plan during the whole co-implementation and co-monitoring phase.

Figure 11-12-13: Knowledge transfer from RMs and KFP to R1, R2, R3

Figure 14-15-16: Knowledge transfer from RMs and KFP to R4, R5, R6

5. Monitoring of the plans

Relevant Key Performance Indicators developed within WP4 have been identified to monitor the overall performance of the plan, detailing relevant indicators per actions.

This will take place through two different campaigns:

- Continuous monitoring, where Replicators will have the possibility to fill the platform with the values referring only to KPIs relevant to events they punctually run;
- Periodic monitoring; taking place every 6 months and asking the Replicators to report on all the identified KPIs. This will allow to get an overall assessment of the progresses made towards the regeneration objectives, basing on a comparison with the data collected for the baseline (Task 1.4).

This monitoring programme will be able to assess the impact of the heritage-led regeneration plan.

Moreover, to have a constant monitoring and contact with Replicators throughout the implementation phase, UNIBO will supervise the actions implementation through a more qualitative approach. According to the timeline and the list of activities foreseen in each action, Replicators will thus have to fulfil the Action plan progress report and will be called to discuss it in bilateral call with their reference person at UNIBO and during the remote Replicator Forum. Replicators are free to contact the responsible person at UNIBO in any moment during the implementation phase to clarify doubts or ask for advice. UNIBO will help them directly or address them to the relevant RM/KFP, also through the DRHH.

The progress report will be submitted to UNIBO every three months and will be structured as follows. The first progress report is expected at the end of April 2020 and then periodically every 3 months.

Action Name	
Action N.	<i>Include the code of the action</i>
Foreseen timeframe	<i>Include here the foreseen timeline of the activities as stated in the action template</i>
Activities completed	<i>List the activities that have been completed</i>
Activities started	<i>List the activities that started</i>
Deviations from planned activities and justifications	<i>Describe deviations from the initial plan, if any, in terms of planned activities, timeline, budget, etc. and justify those</i>
Target reached	<i>Include here the foreseen target and define what you have reached so far (% of accomplishment)</i>

6. Karavanke/Karawanken UNESCO Global Geopark (ARGE GK) Heritage-led regeneration plan

6.1 Background information

In November 2015 Karavanke/Karawanken was established as an UNESCO Global Geopark. The Geopark was established through a bottom-up process involving all relevant local and regional stakeholders and authorities in the area: landowners, community groups, tourism providers, and local organizations. The purpose of an UNESCO Global Geopark is to explore, develop and celebrate the links between geological heritage and all other aspects of the area's natural, cultural and intangible heritages. By raising awareness of the importance of the area's geological heritage in history and society today, UNESCO Global Geoparks give local people a sense of pride in their region and strengthen their identification with the area. UNESCO Global Geoparks empower local communities and give them the opportunity to develop cohesive partnerships with the common goal of promoting the area's significant geological processes, features, periods of time, historical themes linked to geology, or outstanding geological beauty as well as other capitals present in the area. When we talk about geoparks, we not talk just about the geographical areas, rich in geological, other natural and cultural heritage, but also about people, living in the geopark, local communities, in the case of the Karavanke/Karawanken UNESCO Global Geopark, local inhabitants of 14 municipalities.

The Rural Heritage Hub of Karavanke/Karawanken is situated within the the Karavanke/Karawanken UNESCO Global Geopark in the in the village of Tichoja (Tihoja), Austria. The Geopark Karavanke/Karawanken is cross-border geopark which includes 14 municipalities altogether. Nine of these are Austrian (Zell/Sele, Gallizien (Galicija), Bad Eisenkappel-Vellach/Železna Kapla-Bela, Sittersdorf (Žitara vas), Globasnitz/Globasnica, Feistritz ob Bleiburg/Bistrica nad Pliberkom, Bleiburg/Pliberk, Neuhaus (Suha), Lavamünd (Labot)) and five are situated on the slovenian side (Črna na Koroškem, Mežica, Prevalje, Ravne na Koroškem, Dravograd). The two regions hosting the Geopark are the Koroška region, which is the Slovenian part of the geopark, and the Völkermarkt/Velikovec region, situated in the Austrian territory.

Figure 17: Geopark Karavanke/Karawanken Rural Heritage Hub - main entrance

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It extends over an area of 1,067 km² with a population of 53,000 residents. It is located between two Alpine mountains that exceed 2,000 metres: the Petzen/Peca and the Koschuta/Košuta. The area is recognised for its rich geological variety between the Alps and Dinarides.

The hub itself is a former primary school, built in 1880, and called St. Philippen ob Sonnegg/Šentlipš. A renovation of the school took place in 1996. In 2011 school formally closed its doors, when 11 children had to join to the main school in the Municipality of Sittersdorf (Žitara vas). It was given new life almost 20 years later with RURITAGE. The official opening event of the RURITAGE Rural Heritage Hub took place on the 12th of April 2019. The infrastructure of the building provides us two offices and a lot of space for various events (meetings, roundtables, workshops, exhibitions, etc.) in the meeting room, sports hall and the lobby.

Figure 18: Rural Heritage Hub

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Figure 19: Area and location of the RHH

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6.1.1 The Reference SIA

PILGRIMAGE FOR RURAL REGENERATION

As a Replicator of Role models' actions, Karavanke/Karawanken UNESCO Global Geopark is working mainly within the SIA Pilgrimage, due of the rich pilgrimage heritage of the area. During the Migration Period around 400 AD, the Roman and Celtic population around Globasnitz/Globasnica settled on the Hemmaberg (St. Hema Mountain) because of the safety the mountain provided. The mountain settlement was surrounded by a fortification wall, and the first church of the Christian community was built on the edge of the summit plateau around 400 AD. Around 510 AD, a double church of the Catholic Romans was built, and later, another double church was built by the Ostrogoths who were Arian Christians. The Hemmaberg (St. Hema Mountain) gradually developed into an important place of pilgrimage. The Catholic church had a rich interior with mosaic floors, which are partially visible at the Archaeological-Pilgrim Museum in the Municipality of Globasnitz/Globasnica. The Arian double church only had a mosaic floor in the chancel area. Under the former altar, archaeologists discovered remains of a martyr from the eastern Mediterranean. This was the first early Christian pilgrimage site discovered in Central Europe. With the settlement of pagan Slavs around 600 AD, the pilgrimage site was destroyed by fire.

One of the most important pilgrimage sites on Hemmaberg (St. Hemma Mountain) is St. Rosalia cave - St. Rosalia has been the patron saint who is said to protect from plague. The local inhabitants of the Jauntal valley have always been describing the cave as intriguing and mysterious. There are many tales and stories about the small grotto and its spring. What is however sure is that for thousands of years, people have made pilgrimages to St. Rosalia Grotto to find their inner peace and take time for reflection. They drank the water from the spring to which "healing powers" are attributed.

Unfortunately, due to a rockfall, the St. Rosalia cave and spring are currently not accessible for the public. Within the frame of the RURITAGE project, we are planning to make this important heritage place accessible again. Through RURITAGE, Karavanke/Karawanken UNESCO Global Geopark will give more importance to the pilgrimage heritage of the area. The aim is to use the heritage of pilgrimage as a powerful tool to boost economy through the promotion of the sustainable tourism. We want to show that our geopark is not only about natural and geological heritage, but also cultural heritage and people.

Figure 20: St. Rosalien cave is one of the most important pilgrimage place on St. Hema mountain

© photo: Daniel Zupanc

6.1.2 Other relevant SIAs

FOOD FOR RURAL REGENERATION

Rural food production in territories included in the Geopark Karavanke/Karawanken area is based on cross-border cuisine and traditional mountain food based on the products of the Jauntaler Had'n (buckwheat) region, which is part of the geographical area Jauntal. They represent the raw material of various specialities like "Hadnsterz" and "Hadn Nudeln" (buckwheat noodles), the Jauntaler salami, produced by using special seasoning and curing with subsequent smoking over beech wood in the geographical area Jauntal, Sittersdorfer wine, homemade apple cider, noodles with dried pear filling »Kvočevi nudlni«, various types of homemade schnapps. Within the frame of the RURITAGE project, Geopark Karavanke/Karawanken will valorise these local products, agricultural and culinary traditions through the establishment of a "Geopark partners" community, a new partnership of the local food producers acting in the area of the geopark.

Figure 21: Geopark Karavanke/Karawanken local food - buckwheat products and landscape

© Geopark Karavanke/Karawanken Archive

© photo: Daniel Zupanc

LANDSCAPE FOR RURAL REGENERATION

Karavanke/Karawanken UNESCO Global Geopark is recognised for its rich geological variety between the Alps and Dinarides. Already 48 geosites and 14 Geopark localities are equipped with information or interpretation boards which demonstrate the great geodiversity of the area. Many elements are exceptional and unique given a global level. Some of Geopark Karavanke/Karawanken highlights are: one of the three richest deposits of carnian crinoids in Europe (Helena creek valley); the Mežica mine, former mine of lead and zinc ore, today Tourist Mine and Museum - Podzemlje Pece, place for unique underground adventures like underground biking and kayaking; Wulfenite deposits in Mežica - the richest in Europe and one of the most famous in the world; the Topla Regional Park; Dobrova pri Dravogradu - a typical deposit (*locus typicus*) of Dravite mineral; the Periadriatic fault system - form as a consequence of the collision between the Adriatic microplate and Eurasian plate; Obir dripstone caves, which have been considered as the most beautiful stalactite cave in Austria, Wildensteiner waterfall, that is one of the highest free-fall waterfalls in Europe; the Korte/Trögerer Klamm - a natural reserve with the famous Tarviser breccia deposits; slopes of dark grey pillow lava in the Obir gorge - an evidence of former volcanic activity; the Smrekovec Mountain Range - deposits of igneous and pyroclastic rocks; Dravograd lake; several mineral water sources between Jezersko and Bad Eisenkappel/Železna Kapla; Leše coalmine - once one of the biggest and most modern coalmines in Slovenia. Last but not least is the 1,500 years-old pilgrimage site of St. Hema Mountain/Hemmaberg, developed precisely because of special geological situation with good accessibility.

Furthermore, these unique geological characteristics and the favourable climatic conditions influenced the cultivation of buckwheat on the gravel soils south of the Drau in the Municipality of the Neuhaus (Suha). The soils in the entire Jauntal offer the ideal conditions also for the cultivation of maize and soy, which is designed for pig fattening. The famous Jauntaler salami is produced from these pigs.

Providing information about the landscape and natural heritage is one of the main tasks and an integrated part of various events and educational programmes of the Karavanke/Karawanken UNESCO Global Geopark. Through the H2020 RURITAGE project, Geopark Karavanke/Karawanken will add new contents to the activities currently in place dedicated to exploring and visit the local landscape. Discovering the Geopark Karavanke/Karawanken through various experiences in the nature and landscape can increase the interest in visiting the Geopark and then the knowledge of the natural and cultural heritage of the area.

6.1.3 The Replicator baseline

According to the Layman’s report proposed by CARTIF, Geopark Karavanke/Karawanken has a 38% level of accomplishment. This gives us room for improvement.

Cultural Capital (CC) reflects the way people “know the world” and how they act within it, as well as their traditions and language. Although the number of cultural events at local level is high enough (CC-06), there is still room for improvement in the use of social media (CC-02 to CC-05), crowdfunding campaigns (CC-07) and training in traditional skills (CC-08).

Natural Capital (NC) connected with biodiversity and landscape is one of the key assets that rural destinations are traditionally taking advantage of. More development is needed in areas related to the type of ecosystem services (NC-01), companies with sustainability certifications (NC-05) and green tourism packages (NC-07) (CARTIF, 2019).

Historic built heritage can play a key role in the heritage-led process if it is reused and maintained from a sustainability point of view. Overall performance in Built Capital (BC) is high, but there is still room for improvement by using RURITAGE digital tools (BC-01 to BC-03) and fostering public & shared transport services (BC-08 and BC-09).

Social capital (SC) reflects the connections among people and organizations or the social “glue” to make things, positive or negative, happen. Although the projects involving people with disabilities is high (SC-06) there is still room for improvement involving more local associations (SC-03) and projects addressing migrants (SC-05) .

In RURITAGE, Human Capital (HC) is improved through practices that contribute to the health, training & education of the population. Overall performance is high, but some improvements could be done in training for migrants (HC-03 & HC-04) and internships for students (HC-06) .

Financial Capital (FC) refers to the financial resources available to invest in community capacity-building. In RURITAGE, the financial capital is understood as a mean to achieve the growing of the other capitals. Main improvement areas are related to the number of start-ups and spin-offs (FC-05) and companies with new business models and innovative processes (FC-06) .

Figure 22: R1 performance (baseline calculation)

© RURITAGE monitoring platform, using Grafana

6.1.4 The main challenges

My main challenges	
C1	High rate of depopulation and unemployment
Due to depopulation (outward migration, high death rate) and remoteness, the entire Geopark area is among the most scarcely populated areas. The population of the Geopark Karavanke/Karawanken is approximately	

53,000 – with a population density of 61.1/km². In villages and towns in the valley, the concentration of the population is higher, while the mountainous areas are scarcely populated.

The two regions hosting the Geopark Karavanke/Karawanken show different the economic figures: in the Koroška region (which is the slovenian part of the geopark) the unemployment rate was 7,3 % in the year 2019 (Slovenian average: 4,3 %), while in the area of Völkermarkt/Velikovec (the Austrian part of the geopark), the unemployment rate was 11,4 % in the year 2019 (Austrian average is 4 ,6 %). Globally, in both regions the unemployment rate in the area of the Geopark Karavanke/Karawanken is higher than the national average.

C2 Lack of resources dedicated to maintaining the heritage

Lack of interest in CNH and its maintenance characterises the whole area. The maintenance of the CN heritage is not high in the agendas of the regions, which constitute a barrier to the restoration of the important cultural and natural heritage of the Geopark Karavanke/Karawanken area due lack of the economic support, private investments and governance support concerning CNH.

C3 Lack of visibility of and sense of belonging for the area

The cultural and natural heritage already present in the Geopark Karavanke/Karawanken is not enough known locally and beyond the area of the Geopark Karavanke/Karawanken. Indeed, the CN heritage of the Geopark Karavanke/Karawanken is not enough valorized among the inhabitants and not recognized enough by visitors from outside.

C4 Lack of cross border cooperation between inhabitants

There is still a great amount of people in the area of the Geopark Karavanke/Karawanken who are taking the crossborder region more as an obstacle than a chance to get in touch with the other Country's activities. There is a lack of cooperation among the two Countries' institutions, which aggravates the possibilities of development and Karavanke/Karawanken UNESCO Global Geopark as a unified trademark.

C5 Lack of overview of what the area has to offer

Currently, the touristic offers in the area of Geopark Karavanke/Karawanken are not very well integrated to each other and they do not touch all the different possibilities that the area can offer. At the moment, a common platform or information point where to find an overview of what the area offers is missing.

6.2 Overall objectives of the plan

The main aim of the action plan is to support the rediscovering of our area in all its aspects, through the development of our natural and cultural heritage resources, taking into account the holistic Geopark characteristics thought RURITAGE innovative approach. Our geological, natural and cultural heritage is an essential element of our territory, that should be more valorised. In the frame of the RURITAGE project, we selected 5 Actions that have been developed and will be implemented together with our partners and relevant local stakeholders, aiming at generating positive effects thus fostering a sustainable development of our cross-border region. The following specific objectives (O1-O4) identified in the frame of the RURITAGE project adhere also with what is written in our statute as UNESCO Global Geopark, thus ensuring a strong commitment among our members.

Specific objectives

O1 Better conservation of geological and natural resources and the cultural and natural heritage

Protecting the cultural and natural heritage and ensuring its accessibility to the public is relevant for preserving the traditional landscape in all its elements. As UNESCO Global Geopark, we have the responsibility to ensure to achieve this objective.

Linked with challenges

C2 Lack of resources dedicated to maintaining the heritage

O2 Raising awareness, information and education about the geological, other natural and cultural heritage of the Geopark Karavanke/Karawanken

Providing visitors and local inhabitants with new and more targeted experiences of the local cultural and natural heritage and to raise awareness of the importance of preserving and enjoying the local landscape will ensure to achieve a sustainable and more conscious development in the area.	
Linked with challenges	
C3	Lack of visibility of and sense of belonging for the area
C4	Lack of cross border cooperation between inhabitants
C5	Lack of overview of what the area has to offer
O3	Fostering new economic opportunities for the region based on geo tourism
The promotion of sustainable local economic development through sustainable (geo)tourism is one of the key pillars of the UNESCO Global Geoparks. RURITAGE approach, through the promotion of natural heritage in conjunction with local culture and products for visitors and tourists, will create job opportunities for the local communities.	
Linked with challenges	
C1	High rate of depopulation and unemployment
C2	Lack of resources dedicated to maintaining the heritage
C3	Lack of visibility of and sense of belonging for the area
O4	General cross-border cooperation
The Geopark Karavanke/Karawanken, established in 2011 is managed by a cross-border partnership network, therefore one of its main objectives is the cross-border cooperation. Until 1918 the entire geopark area was united under the Habsburg regime. The Slovenian language was the most striking symbol of the common region. The events during WW2 and afterwards created deep gaps between the countries of Austria and Yugoslavia. One of the Geopark's tasks is also to set cultural accents and, if possible, to help bring the two formerly united countries closer together, and to establish a well-functioning cross-national cooperation among our stakeholders for a unified approach based on the enforcement of local cultural and natural heritage values. This will increase the cooperation and harmony within the community.	
Linked with challenges	
C3	Lack of visibility of and sense of belonging for the area
C4	Lack of cross border cooperation between inhabitants

6.3 Operational programme for the implementation of the plan

No	Action	SIA	Challenge(s)	Objective(s)
R1.1	Design a set of new touristic and cross border packs, integrating different cultural experiences	Local Food, Landscape	C3, C4, C5	O2, O4
R1.2	The digital use of the Karavanke/Karawanken Geopark	Pilgrimage, Landscape	C3, C4, C5	O2, O4
R1.3	Safeguarding and making the site of St. Hema mountain - St. Rosalia cave accessible again	Pilgrimage, Landscape	C1, C2, C3, C4, C5	O1
R1.4	Selection of "Geopark partners" sharing RURITAGE vision of local food as part of local heritage	Local food	C1, C2, C3	O3
R1.5	Boost local pride by making the heritage of area more accesible	Pilgrimage, Local Food, Landscape	C1, C2, C3, C4, C5	O2, O3

6.3.1 The actions in detail

Code of the action	
R1.1	
Title the action	Design a set of new touristic and cross border packs, integrating different cultural experiences
Relevant SIA or SIAs	Local food, Landscape, Pilgrimage
Relevant Heritage	Tangible- Natural Heritage; Intangible - Knowledge and Practices
Reference RM Action/s (code and name)	RM 8-1, Creation of a set of tourist packs, composed by FOOD related activities (i.e. he "Middle Age Menus"), ART (i.e. Middle Age poetry performance), NATURALISTIC Activities, etc.
Useful lesson/s Learned (code and name)	<p>LL20. Innovative revenue models for CNH facilities, to maximise income and minimise costs, including efficient use of technology for income generation</p> <p>LL08. Create synergies and foster a collaborative approach with other organizations, programmes or local activities (i.e. festivals, arts, food, etc.) and attractors of the territory to increase impact of the actions</p> <p>LL04. Build sense of belonging, individual and community self-confidence and increased autonomy for promotion, safeguarding, management and well-being</p> <p>LL07. Create 'tourist pack and experiences' based on the different clusters (culture, food & wine, nature, religion, etc.) and sell combined packages, including transport</p> <p>LL25. Take advantage from traditional events and make the typical characteristics of the area (food & wine, handcraft, traditions) a tourist attraction</p> <p>LL28. Promote access to all ages and abilities and ensure fruition of cultural resources to all, including transport and online information provision</p> <p>LL11. Develop and improve transportation to make places accessible and to facilitate the launch of new touristic destinations</p> <p>LL16. Foster and promote sustainable tourism</p> <p>LL13. Ensure, at least, standard quality internet connection and mobile coverage</p>
Responsible person	ARGE Geopark Karawanken (Mag. Antonia Weissenbacher, Mag. Gerald Hartmann)
Relevant RM/KFP involved	RM 8-1, The Living Village of the Middle Age Visegrad (Hungary)
Brief description of the action	Currently, the touristic offers in the area of Geopark Karavanke/Karawanken are not very well integrated to each other and they do not touch all the different possibilities that the area can offer. In the frame of this Action, we will connect various local attractions on the both side of the border and create different touristic packages composed by local food, local cross-border history/culture and new activities in nature, like wood rafting. Within this Action, tourists and local people get the chance to experience the multifaceted nature of our cultural and natural heritage as well as its crossborder character.
Objective and target of the action (by the end of the project)	<p>The main objective of this Action is to create an added value for the local tourist offer. In the frame of this Action we will foster and promote sustainable tourism through informing and "organized tourism". The main target group of this action are visitors/pilgrims of our territory. In the long run however, the target group is our local communities' private business owners.</p> <p>The target audiences of the action are the follow:</p> <p>Pilgrims/Tourists visiting the Geopark. Quantitative target: 50 people. Qualitative target: awareness about the cultural factors of the Geopark.</p> <p>First year 1 touristic package will be created. In the autumn this year we will evaluate the package, and then make adaptations and work on additional packages. In total 3 different packages will be created (one per year, from 2020 to 2022).</p>
Specific activities	<p>Preparatory activities (activities done during the co-development phase, before M19):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Design with partners already involved their specific participation and contact other possible partners to be engaged; • to define different options included in the packages (food-nature combination, etc.) <p>Activities implementation:</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • round table with key stakeholders; • designing and finalising the packages (content and visual identity for the integrated tourist packages); • implementation, promotion and communication of the 1st package through various channels (national and international fairs, Facebook page, Web page, Flyers, Brochures, etc.), including press-releases to inform journalists, public and stakeholders about the action; • Evaluation of the 1st package and creation of the new package; • implementation, promotion and communication of the 2nd package; • Evaluation of the 2nd package and creation of the new package; • implementation, promotion and communication of the 3rd package.
Monitoring plan and indicators	CC-05 Number of posts mentioning RURITAGE at local level CC-11 Total number of arrivals of tourist in the last year
Capital involved	Cultural, Natural, Social, Human capitals
Main stakeholders involved and their roles and contribution	Uroš Grabner , photographer and graphic designer, role in the action: design and final visual identity of created packages Franz Logar , contribution of ideas for developing and implementation of the packages Tourism agency Lavamünd/Labot , managing and implementation of the packages
Beneficiaries	Local restaurants, local shops, local craftsmen, local SMEs, accommodation providers, museum, nature experience providers that will benefit from the tourists' arrival, since they could spend all-day in the area. Foreign tourists and visitors will get the opportunity to experience the cross-border area, its cultural and natural heritage. Local inhabitants, who could have more occasions to exchange with other communities living beyond the border.
Formal partnership established (PPP, voluntary agreement, etc.)	Voluntary agreement with stakeholders involved during the action implementation for defining the packages.
Timeframe	January 2020 - May 2022
Indicative costs	1,000 €
Indicative funding sources	Geopark Karavanke/Karawanken
Sustainability of the action	Geopark Karavanke/Karawanken is fully committed to promote and manage the touristic packages also beyond the project.

Code of the action	R1.2
Title the action	The digital use of the Karavanke/Karawanken Geopark
Relevant SIA or SIAs	Pilgrimage, Landscape
Relevant Heritage	Tangible - Natural Heritage; Digital Heritage
Reference RM Action/s (code and name)	RM 1-6, Digitalization of the pilgrimage - through websites, GIS maps, apps
Useful lesson/s Learned (code and name)	LL02. Apply IT technologies for natural and cultural heritage promotion and safeguarding LL28. Promote access to all ages and abilities and ensure fruition of cultural resources to all, including transport and online information provision LL07. Create 'tourist pack and experiences' based on the different clusters (culture, food & wine, nature, religion, etc.) and sell combined packages, including transport LL11. Develop and improve transportation to make places accessible and to facilitate the launch of new touristic destinations
Responsible person	ARGE Geopark Karavanke/Karawanken (Mag. Gerald Hartmann)
Relevant RM/KFP involved	RM 1-6, Camino de Santiago (Spain) Dr. John Martin, University of Plymouth

	Nils Brunet, Acir compostelle
Brief description of the action	In the frame of the action we will create a digital solution (mobile application), presenting the pilgrimage route and the entire Geopark and informing users about events, accommodation possibilities, touristic attractions, restaurants, etc. so it will be used by tourists visiting our Geopark for different reasons and interests. The digital solution will also be useful for local inhabitants to better know what is going on in the area and to generate contents thus making the digital solution a living tool.
Objective and target of the action (by the end of the project)	<p>The objective of this action is to make the area more accessible for tourists/pilgrims and for local people, by gathering all the events and happenings from the municipalities in the cross-border region. Local offers and products, such as food and restaurants as well as all the various tourist sites will become more accessible.</p> <p>The target audiences of the action are the follow:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pilgrims/tourists. Quantitative target: 150 people. Qualitative target: better accessibility to local products such as food and to local sites will be more approachable. • Local people. Quantitative target: 500 people. Qualitative target: better accessibility to local products such as food and to local sites will be more approachable.
Specific activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Co-creation with the stakeholder Uroš Grabner of the first draft of mobile application (content) • invitation to submit offers for the creation of the Geopark Karavanke/Karawanken mobile application; • obtaining offers; • evaluation of the received offers; • choice of the appropriate company - and signing of the contract with the company for the creation of the Geopark Karavanke/Karawanken mobile application; • developing the mobile application together with the chosen company; • presentation and promotion of the mobile application (FB, web-page, press-release with the presentation of the mobile application).
Monitoring plan and indicators	CC-07 Number of people reached by actions and cultural events produced by citizens at local level
Capital involved	Cultural, Natural, Social, Human capitals
Main stakeholders involved and their roles and contribution	<p>Tourism agency Tourism Region Klopeinersee-Südkärnten, responsible stakeholder Robert Karlhofer - support with data collection concerning events, touristic offers, accommodation providers, restaurants, ...;</p> <p>Development agency for Koroška (RRA Koroška), responsible person Primož Vodovnik - support with data collection concerning events, touristic offers, accommodation providers, restaurants;</p> <p>Uroš Grabner, creation of first draft and content of the mobile application, co-working with external expert, maintaining a mobile application.</p>
Beneficiaries	Municipalities, tourists, local inhabitants, local SMEs (restaurants, hotels), all cultural active groups
Formal partnership established (PPP, voluntary agreement, etc.)	Voluntary agreement with Uroš Grabner, tourism agency and development agency
Timeframe	January 2020-August 2021
Indicative costs	20.000 €
Indicative funding sources	RURITAGE Project
Sustainability of the action	Geopark Karavanke/Karawanken will use, promote and maintain the digital solution also after the project duration.

Code of the action	
R1.3	
Title the action	Safeguarding and making the site of St. Hema mountain - St. Rosalia cave accessible again
Relevant SIA or SIAs	Pilgrimage, Landscape
Relevant Heritage	Tangible - Natural, Built Heritage; Intangible - Social Practices, Rituals and Festive Events
Reference RM Action/s (code and name)	/
Useful lesson/s Learned (code and name)	LL16. Foster and promote sustainable tourism LL15. Identify heritage resources (formal and informal), foster a better understanding of the tangible and intangible values of natural and cultural heritage and create a recognized value as a driver for local development LL04. Build sense of belonging, individual and community self-confidence and increased autonomy for promotion, safeguarding, management and well-being LL19. Increased Health and Wellbeing services LL27. Official protection of cultural/natural/intangible good by national/international Authority
Responsible person	ARGE Geopark Karavanke/Karawanken (manager Mag. Gerald Hartmann) and Municipality of Globasnitz/Globasnica (Mayor Mr. Bernhard Sadovnik)
Relevant RM/KFP involved	/
Brief description of the action	Background information: The most important pilgrimage site on St. Hemma mountain is the so-called St. Rosalia grotto or „St. Rosalia cave“. St. Rosalia has been the patron saint who is said to protect from the plague. Every year thousands of visitors and residents used to come to the cave and drink the healing water of the spring which is said to give the visitor eternal health and to heal eye-diseases. Unfortunately, in the last 5 years, because of a dangerous rockfall, the cave and the spring are closed and not accessible at all. Action: Protection and renovation of cultural and natural points - St. Rosalia cave on the St. Hemma mountain, to recover the cave and make it possible to visit it again.
Objective and target of the action (by the end of the project)	The objective of this action is to make the site of St. Rosalia cave accessible to visitors again. Restore the heritage, make it possible for people to go there. The target groups are: visitors/tourists/pilgrims as well as local inhabitants.
Specific activities	Preparatory activities (activities done during the co-development phase, before M19): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • co-development of the Project for the restoration and protection of the cave with the Municipality of Globasnitz/Globasnica • Invitation to submit offers for the Protection and renovation of cultural and natural points - St. Rosalia cave on the St. Hemma mountain (Municipality of Globasnitz/Globasnica, ARGE Geopark Karavanke/Karawanken) • obtaining of offers (Municipality of Globasnitz/Globasnica, ARGE Geopark Karavanke/Karawanken); • evaluation of the received offers (Municipality of Globasnitz/Globasnica, ARGE Geopark Karavanke/Karawanken); • choice of the appropriate company (Municipality of Globasnitz/Globasnica, ARGE Geopark Karavanke/Karawanken); • signing of the contract with the company for the renovation and protection (Municipality of Globasnitz/Globasnica, ARGE Geopark Karavanke/Karawanken); Implementation activities: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • working on the renovation and protection of the cave (this activity started before M19. The reason is that we and our stakeholders were ready to start the works before the implementation phase official start to ensure the good running of the restoration). • official opening of the “St. Rosalia cave” (Municipality of Globasnitz/Globasnica, ARGE Geopark Karavanke/Karawanken).

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> opening event with press conference; diverse stakeholders, including journalists (regional and national journalists), local government, touristic association will be invited.
Monitoring plan and indicators	BC-11 Number of “buildings” (cave) restored/retrofitted CC-05 Number of posts mentioning RURITAGE at local level CC-11 Total number of arrivals of tourist in the last year
Capital involved	Cultural, Natural, Human, Built, Social capitals
Main stakeholders involved and their roles and contribution	Municipality of Globasnitz/Globasnica is in charge to look after the historical and cultural heritage of St. Hema mountain, because the mountain and St. Rosalien cave are located in their area. The Municipality also found additional funding for the renovation and protection of the St. Rosalia cave.
Beneficiaries	Tourists, local inhabitants, Tourism agency
Formal partnership established (PPP, voluntary agreement, etc.)	Official contract with the Municipality of Globasnitz/Globasnica
Timeframe	October 2019 - October 2020.
Indicative costs	€ 176.976,26
Indicative funding sources	70.000,00 € in the frame of the RURITAGE project. 71.500,00 € provided by the Municipality of Globasnitz/Globasnica in the framework of the National LE 14-20 (Entwicklung für den Ländlichen Raum) project „Rosalienpforte Hemmaberg Gemeinde Globasnitz“, supported by Federal Ministry Republic of Austria for Sustainability and Tourism, Land and European Union (LEADER PROGRAMME). Difference covered by the Municipality of Globasnitz/Globasnica with own resources.
Sustainability of the action	The Municipality of Globasnitz/Globasnica is meant to care for the maintenance of the object after the renovation and protection.

Code of the action	R1.4
Title the action	Selection of “Geopark partners” sharing RURITAGE vision of local food as part of local heritage
Relevant SIA or SIAs	Local food
Relevant Heritage	Tangible – Natural; Intangible - Social Practices, Rituals and Festive Events
Reference RM Action/s (code and name)	RM 3-3, Definition of marketing and communication strategies for the products
Useful lesson/s Learned (code and name)	LL06. Create a ‘brand’ based on one of the cultural and natural resources and the added valued created LL25. Take advantage from traditional events and make the typical characteristics of the area (food & wine, handcraft, traditions) a tourist attraction
Responsible person	ARGE Geopark Karavanke/Karawanken (Dr. Darja Komar, Danijela Modrej)
Relevant RM/KFP involved	D.A.Re., Distretto Agroalimentare Regionale scrl, Puglia ICLEI (Community event) BITN
Brief description of the action	In the frame of this Action we will engage with local food producers/farmers and sellers sharing RURITAGE principles based on local food as part of local heritage and as a mean to sustain economic growth of the territories. Selected and compliant partners will be awarded as “Geopark partners”. This will ensure that these partners are producing and selling traditional and sustainable products and will guarantee the establishment of a strong cooperation between them, binding them together through the Geopark identity. The possibility to join the RURITASTE brand will be explored.

Objective and target of the action (by the end of the project)	<p>The overall objective of this action is to enhance local food as a part of local heritage; this consequently will give more visibility and will strengthen the quality of local products by selecting local business and producers who share the same approach for producing and selling local food products with specific requirements of sustainability and quality. At the same time it valorises the local territory and heritage. The selection of these “Geopark partners” will certify that they share RURITAGE values and approach in enhancing CNH and will strengthen their partnership with the Geopark. During the implementation of the action, the possibility to join RURITASTE brand will be explored. The target groups are local business and also tourists.</p> <p>Quantitative target: 5 local food producers involved. Qualitative target: better and joint promotion of the Geopark Karavanke/Karawanken local food.</p>
Specific activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Open event with key stakeholders, with the local food producers/sellers and farmers that could be involved in the action to explain the objective of the action and its steps; • Open call to the local food producers/sellers and farmers for collecting their interest in the action; • selection process in cooperation with Jauntaler Salami and Jauntaler Hadn association to choose the partners to be involved actively in the action as “Geopark partners”; • learning visit in Apulia (Italy) - where we will get ideas on how to engage producers and farmers and implement marketing and the promotion of the local food; • all local farmers and food producers who have been selected present their own products in the frame of Fine tuning workshop (WP2) hosted in the Geopark Hub, where we will officially present the RURITAGE approach especially on food to the local community (community event foreseen in task 3.5); • workshop where “Geopark partners” get familiar with best practices in the production and promotion of sustainable local food all over the Europe, developed together with Magma UGG and Dare; • developing a strategy for marketing and promotion of the “Geopark partners” and the products the members produce, also taking into consideration the branding approach developed by RURITAGE and the possible adoption of the RURITASTE brand; • on-line training courses for support of the local food producers; • Geopark Karavanke/Karawanken will promote “Geopark Partners” network at different international fairs (Vienna, Klagenfurt, Ljubljana)
Monitoring plan and indicators	SC-04 Number of local associations involved
Capital involved	Cultural, Natural, Social capitals
Main stakeholders involved and their roles and contribution	<p>The Genusregion Jauntaler Had’n Association – Buckwheat Association – Mr. Josef Hirm Sittersdorfer Wein – wine producer Association in Sittersdorf – Mr. Karoline Schippel Jauntaler Salamibauern – Association of home – made Salami producing farmers Many local producers are already a part of an above-mentioned association.</p>
Beneficiaries	Local food producers, local farmers, local stores, local customers, tourists
Formal partnership established (PPP, voluntary agreement, etc.)	<p>Until now we do not have a formal partnership – this would be the result of the process. The plan is to develop partnership (agreement) with the Geopark partners (local food producers, sellers, etc.) and persons who will share the objective of the action.</p>
Timeframe	January 2020 – April 2021
Indicative costs	20.000,00 €
Indicative funding sources	<p>10.000 € In the frame of the RURITAGE Project for selecting the “Geopark partners” sharing the RURITAGE approach to local food 10.000 € In the frame of the RURITAGE Project for activities related with SIA Food (organization of events related with local food production, development of online training courses for local producers)</p>

Sustainability of the action	Geopark partners network will be promoted by Geopark Karavanke/Karawanken also after the project duration.
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Code of the action	
Code and Title the action	R1.5 Boosting local identity and sense of belonging by experiencing the local heritage
Relevant SIA or SIAs	Pilgrimage, Local Food, Landscape
Relevant Heritage	Tangible - Natural Heritage; Intangible - Knowledge and Practices
Reference RM Action/s (code and name)	RM 2-3, Create a set of guided tours or organized travels tailored for different target groups
Useful lesson/s Learned (code and name)	LL07. Create 'tourist pack and experiences' based on the different clusters (culture, food & wine, nature, religion, etc.) and sell combined packages, including transport LL11. Develop and improve transportation to make places accessible and to facilitate the launch of new touristic destinations LL25. Take advantage from traditional events and make the typical characteristics of the area (food & wine, handcraft, traditions) a tourist attraction LL16. Foster and promote sustainable tourism
Responsible person	ARGE Geopark Karavanke/Karawanken (Mag. Antonia Weissenbacher)
Relevant RM/KFP involved	RM 2 Mária Út Nils Brunet, Acir compostelle John Martin (geocaching for groups, schools)
Brief description of the action	Background information: Geopark Karavanke/Karawanken already implements some guided tours regularly (April-October), like: Hike "Sunrise in the Geopark", „Full Moon hiking“, Petzen panoramic circular hike, Family adventure hike, Culturally historical cross-border hike, Two wheels – two countries – a borderless cycle experience, "On the Border" hike Action: Because the area of the cross-border Geopark Karavanke/Karawanken has very rich pilgrimage history and important pilgrimage points, we will add new guided tours with additional topics more targeted to local people including schools, elderly people and families. In the year 2020 we will offer guided hiking tours for different target groups with special focus on elderly people. These tours include mainly the topic of the cultural heritage on St. Hema mountain.
Objective and target of the action (by the end of the project)	The objective of this action is to make the heritage of the Karavanke/Karawanken geopark more accessible for the whole community firstly, and then for visitors. This action focused on strengthening the awareness of our landscape and its cultural functions. Karavanke/Karawanken geopark will try to implement a broad understanding of landscape evolution to increase this knowledge among residents and visitors/pilgrims. We thus hope to encourage more people to participate and enjoy the cultural and natural heritage of the area. Number of participants per year: 120 Number of tours run per year: each week there will be around one tour offer (in May, June, September and October), but if there will be no participants, the tour does not take place. Therefore the predicted number of tours per year is 8. Number of vulnerable people involved: 30 elderly people
Specific activities	Preparatory activities: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The first step was reflecting the needs of different target groups in the community first and then of the visitors together with the representatives of different target groups (schools, officials in the municipalities dealing with different social groups) and the tourism agency. This actually happened in September/October 2019. Together we decided to start off with one new tour in summer 2020. The tour will be related to pilgrimage and will be run differently according with the different target groups hosted. That is why different approaches will be fulfilled, depending on the participants (school children, families, elderly people).

	<p>Implementation activities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Actual definition of the different contents of the tours. Initial ideas are that the new tour will last up to 6 hours, depending on the type of participants and could include the visit of the local archaeological Pilgrimage – museum and the excavations and a lunch at a local restaurant. • meeting with Mrs Enze from Hemmastüberl (restaurant on Hemmaberg) and clarifying all ideas and expectations; meeting with Mr. Glaser and Mrs Rutter concerning the visits of the museum; • promotional material design, printing and distribution. • start with the new tours to Hemma Mountain during summer 2020; • evaluation of the past season and developing a new tour for 2021 • start with the new tours during summer 2021; • evaluation of the past season and developing a new tour for 2022 • start with the new tours during summer 2022;
Monitoring plan and indicators	<p>CC-11 Total number of arrivals of tourist in the last year SC-07 Number of disadvantaged people engaged (elderly, migrants, unemployed)</p>
Capital involved	Cultural, Natural, Built, Social, Human capitals
Main stakeholders involved and their roles and contribution	<p>Geopark Karavanke/Karawanken will provide guides running the tour Tourismusregion Klopeinersee – Robert Karlhofer (Tourism agency). They will promote all tours throughout the region.</p> <p>Archaeological Pilgrimage Museum of Globasnitz/Globasnica: Mr. Franz Glaser and Mr. Sandra Rutter. They will provide spaces and information about the museum Hemmastüberl – restaurant on St. Hemma Mountain: Victoria Enze – owner of the restaurant. They will be involved for providing food and refreshments for the visitors Municipality of Globasnitz/Globasnica: Mayor: Mr. Bernhard Sadovnik. They will be in charge of defining specific needs and promote the tour</p>
Beneficiaries	<p>Elderly people, children, families are the main beneficiaries of the tour, who will gain new experiences and knowledge of the local territory and heritage. Restaurants and local businesses that will also have the possibility to get more recognized within the community.</p>
Formal partnership established (PPP, voluntary agreement, etc.)	<p>Partnership with the (Tourism agency) Tourismusregion Klopeinersee – they have been promoting our products in the last 2 years. In 2020 this partnership will be continued., Archaeological Pilgrimage Museum of Globasnitz/Globasnica and Hemmastüberl – restaurant on St. Hemma Mountain.</p>
Timeframe	March 2020 – May 2022
Indicative costs	Promotion costs are up to Tourism agency (Tourismusregion Klopeinersee Südkärnten) - at the moment we do not have the precise number
Indicative funding sources	For the year 2020 the Tourismusregion Klopeinersee (Tourism agency) – takes over all promotional costs (printing of the brochure)
Sustainability of the action	The Geopark Karavanke/Karawanken will ensure the run and the promotion of the tour also beyond the project, to continue engaging the community and spreading knowledge and understanding to establish a common pride.

6.3.2 Timeline for the implementation

Action No:	Action Name:	19	2020												2021												2022				
		December	January	February	March	April	May	June	July	August	September	October	November	December	January	February	March	April	May	June	July	August	September	October	November	December	January	February	March	April	May
		19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	41	42	43	44	45	46	47	48
1	Design a set of new touristic and cross border packs, integrating different cultural experiences																														
2	The digital use of the Karavanke/Karawanken Geopark																														
3	Safeguarding and making the site of St. Hema mountain - St. Rosalia cave accessible again																														
4	Selection of "Geopark partners" sharing RURITAGE vision of local food as part of local heritage																														
5	Boost local pride by making the heritage of area more accessible																														

Action 3 started before M19, when the implementation phase formally should start. The reason is that ARGE GEOPARK and its stakeholders were ready to start the works before M19 so they decided not wait to ensure the good running of the restoration.

6.4 Risks for the implementation of the plan

Risk No.	Action/s involved	Description of the risk	Mitigation action proposed
1	R1.1 R1.2 R1.4 R1.5	Low interest by targeted audiences	Additional promotion of the actions at different fairs, using social media channels more efficiently
2	R1.2	Low availability of the data, a lack of data	Alternative sources of information, as official statistics, could be used
3	R1.2	Too much information, data	Focusing the information on the needs of the application
4	R1.2	Low budget	Find additional financial resources; own Geopark resources; directly approach to possible investors
5	R1.2	People will not aware of the resource	Additional promotion in the frame of various events, and among schools, kindergartens. Targeted marketing actions
6	R1.1 R1.2 R1.3 R1.4 R1.5	It is difficult to get inhabitants interested in CNH aspects in the landscape	Additional promotion in the frame of various events, and among schools, kindergartens
7	R1.1 R1.2 R1.4 R1.5	Limited commitment of some stakeholders	Use social medias and local newspapers to disseminate the “Geopark partners”; organisation of the event for engagement of stakeholders; adaption of feature events and programmes

7. Magma UNESCO Global Geopark (Magma UGG) Heritage-led regeneration plan

7.1 Background information

Since Magma UNESCO Global Geopark (UGG) was established as a geopark in 2008, it has been actively working in the field of community engagement and valorisation of cultural and natural heritage through tourism activities and educational programmes. In particular, we aim to strengthen the awareness of local people about the potential of the geo-heritage in their own area, to make them proud of living in it and to support them in developing new initiatives in the frame of sustainable development. More specifically, from 2015 Magma UGG has been working with local food and craft producers in order to develop specific actions for the promotion of the uniqueness of our heritage, tradition and culture. There is a visible link between the peculiar landscape and the human activities, especially agriculture, that have taken place since the Stone Age. In fact, in Magma UGG, landscape and agricultural activities, have always been interrelated: throughout history the ice age landscape has been shaped by human who has gained new land for cultivation by moving huge quantity of rocks creating piles and rock walls which are clearly visible today.

The Magma UNESCO Global Geopark Hub is located in the city centre of Egersund in Eigersund municipality in South West Norway. There are about 15 000 people living in Egersund, and about 32 000 people living in the geopark which consists of 5 municipalities; Eigersund, Sokndal, Bjerkreim, Lund (Rogaland County) and Flekkefjord (Agder County). The Hub is also the Magma office and is situated in an old historical building. This used to be the town dairy. The building dates back to 1850 and is found in the city centre of Egersund. With its 26 meters high chimney, the protected building is a well-known and important figure in the townscape of Egersund. Because of limited space at the Hub, Magma has an agreement with the adult education centre close to the HUB providing us space for larger events.

Figure 23: Magma UNESCO Global Geopark Rural Heritage Hub

© Magma UGG

7.1.1 The Reference SIA

FOOD FOR RURAL REGENERATION

The landscape in Magma Geopark is a peneplane surface which gently slopes towards the coast, interrupted by hundreds of small valleys and more than 6,000 lakes. The area is dominated by barren and infertile soils and large areas with bare rocks completely lacking vegetation. As a result, agriculture in the area traditionally has consisted of fishing, sheep and cattle farming. Agriculture and the fish industry have throughout history been closely linked in Magma. Locals have traditionally worked part time as fishermen and part time as farmers, which has led to the local name ‘fish-farmers’. Today Flekkefjord and Egersund harbours are very important in the so-called “Blue industry”, and Egersund harbour is still one of the largest fish harbours in Norway.

Magma UGG, since 2015, has engaged local farmers, beekeepers, meat producers and fishermen in an international project called: GEOfood, together with UGGs in Iceland, Finland, Denmark. The project goal has been to exchange best practices linked with local food productions and its valorisation, to create common criteria for defining “local food” within Geoparks and to set up tailored tourist offers focused on local food experiences. The result was the GEOfood criteria and brand which is, from 2017 in use for defining local food productions and restaurants in Magma Geopark and other Geoparks in the world, becoming the official brand for local food within the European Geoparks Network in 2016. The brand aims to valorise the connection between geological heritage, local tradition and to support local entrepreneurs toward new economic activities, encouraging sustainable agriculture and local communities to implement km-zero food in their daily life. However, Magma Geopark has struggled to involve local producers in the process of becoming GEOfood members, despite all our effort the participants in the project locally were not more than three companies. Thus, the need to focus on the Food SIA to boost local food as a driver for rural regeneration.

7.1.2 Other relevant SIAs

LANDSCAPE FOR RURAL REGENERATION

Local food and local landscape are closely connected. The local food is a direct result of the local landscape, and therefore reflects the agricultural possibilities provided by our geology and climate. In the RURITAGE process it became clear to us that in addition to SIA Local Food we will have to focus on Landscape in order to provide a more holistic approach to the development of our area.

One of our Role Models, the Wild Atlantic Way in Ireland, has already implemented a lot of the actions that we consider necessary in Magma Geopark, including branding, promotion, marketing, making trails etc. From their lessons learned we have gathered thoughts and ideas on how to implement the selected actions in our area. The tasks connected to infrastructure is also directly linked to the knowledge shared by our Role Models in Ireland.

PILGRIMAGE FOR RURAL REGENERATION

During spring 2020 Magma will work on co-developing a new action. The main objective will be to promote the Saint Olav Pilgrimage Route as a tourist attraction, which supports and strengthens the local identity within the geopark. We will be part of establishing a center for the pilgrimage starting point and we will invest about 20.000 euros from the RURITAGE budget in this center. Other investors and funding will also be part of the establishment of this pilgrimage center, therefore this RURITAGE activity will have a positive impact and leverage additional co-funding sources.

7.1.3 The Replicator baseline

According to the Deliverable D1.4 and the Layman's report by CARTIF, Magma Geopark has a 38% level of accomplishment. This gives us room for improvement.

Cultural Capital is defined as “the way people know the world and how they act within it, as well as their traditions and language” (CARTIF, 2019). Our area does have a lot of cultural events at local level (CC-06) and also crowdfunding campaigns (CC-07), but we need to improve the use of social media (CC-02 to CC-05) and enhance training in traditional skills (CC-08).

Our **Natural Capital** is one of the key assets in our area. This includes both biodiversity and landscape. The report from CARTIF shows that more development is needed in areas related to the type of ecosystem services (NC-01) and green tourism packages (NC-07). According to the report we are doing well with sustainable companies (NC-05) and shops selling local products (NC-06). We would still like to improve the number of local products and also shops selling local products.

According to the baseline, our area has a medium score on reusing and maintaining historical buildings. Our **Built Capital** can still improve by using RURITAGE digital tools (BC-02 and BC-03), fostering shared transport services (BC-09) and retrofitting/reusing buildings (BC-11 and BC-12). Traditionally a lot of old houses and buildings in Magma Geopark are already being reused and retrofitted. Both main cities in the geopark consist of old wooden historic houses and are being protected and lived in by local inhabitants. Industrial areas are developed in already existing infrastructure and provides sustainable reuse. The Built Capital is probably the capital we will target less in our Action Plan but is still something we will keep in mind if the need for new production areas will arise in this process.

Social Capital scores really low in the report from CARTIF. This capital “reflects the connections among people and organizations or the social “glue to make things, positive or negative, happen” (CARTIF 2019). The score connected to involving people with disabilities is high (SC-06), but we need to improve just about all other aspects connected to our Social Capital. During our work with implementing the action plan we will aim towards engaging the local communities (SC-01 and SC-02) and include local organizations (SC-03). This is reflected in all three actions selected and hopefully we will see a change in our area during this process.

Several of our selected tasks in our Action Plan aim towards educating local inhabitants (HC-01). By increasing their digital competence in workshops connected to the calendar, offer guide courses and ambassador courses we aim at improving our **Human Capital**. By creating new offers for tourists and promoting it through social medias and digital platforms (HC-07 and HC-08), we hope to improve the digital competence for local self-employees and small businesses.

The main driver for all tasks in our Action Plan is the **Financial Capital**. As described in the CARTIF report we have challenges connected to population ageing and depopulation, but our main concern is that the oil business is changing. Since the 70s' the main employment facilitator in the geopark area has been oil related businesses. Climate change, low oil prices and other factors have forced us to look for other business possibilities. Tourism is one of the possibilities emerging from this local financial change. We can already see an increasing number of local producers and local activity providers (FC-05 and FC-06), but we see the lack of a system and a joint promotion and overall plan. Through our activities chosen in our Action Plan we aim at fulfilling that need. We offer a brand, an umbrella, for the area for promotion of our uniqueness. Not just the landscape, but above all our local food and our natural- and cultural heritage. All growing from local pride, knowledge and identity.

Figure 24: R2 performance (baseline calculation)

© RURITAGE monitoring platform, using Grafana

7.1.4 The main challenges

In addition to these capitals the Baseline states that we have other challenges to be faced. The main additional challenge is Coastline and climate change issue. Three out of five municipalities have a long, and shared coastline facing the North Sea. Even though this presents a stunning and unique landscape, it also provides vulnerability to pollution in the sea. Accidents at sea, often causing massing oil pollution, have huge effects on our coastal landscape and our marine biosphere. This will also directly affect fishing and harvesting for a lot of our local producers and fishermen and cause less income.

Living close to the North Sea has always been a tough life, but this has shaped our landscape and our personality into strong, fierce, stubborn people for thousands of years. Even though we are proud of our heritage and our resilience, we are now facing new challenges from the elements. Climate change is causing an increasing number of storms, stretching the storm season throughout the year and even though we did not think it would be possible the storms are often tougher, stronger and more damaging than before. Our area is experiencing more storms, floods and dry periods. This has impact on income and production for our farmers and fish farmers and is making this kind of living harder and more expensive.

Change in the Golf Stream is also a challenge we might encounter in the future. This will have serious impact on a lot of biotic factors. We can already see a change in species in sea, getting an increasing amount of more tropical species along our coastline.

Main challenges	
C1	Local divisions and lack of involvement
	Our 5 municipalities are struggling with working together, and due to some not so successful events in the past some of them are reluctant to try again.
C2	Visibility
	Our 5 municipalities are too small to offer enough events and festivals to attract visitors from outside the geopark separately.

C3	Overview of offers
There is no overview of the offers provided to guests in our area related to restaurants, hotels, activities and local food producers. This makes it hard to present the variety, diversity and possibilities to guests.	

7.2 Overall objectives of the plan

To enhance growth through our rural heritage, our stakeholders have chosen three main actions during the co-development phase. Taking into consideration the lessons learned from our Role Models, we firmly believe that these three actions will generate positive and sustainable change in our five municipalities. These actions target our need for making all our local assets more visible. They also rely on close collaboration between all five municipalities, which has not proven very successful in the past.

The overall objectives of the stakeholders were focus on increasing the visitors in the area, enhancing local enterprises which valorize local traditions in food and craft and to make local inhabitants proud to live in a UNESCO Global Geopark.

Specific objectives	
O1	Gather all Festivals and Events
To gather all festivals and events in the five municipalities in one shared calendar to present ourselves as one unified area with a variety of experiences to get more guests to visit us.	
Linked with challenges:	
C2	Visibility
O2	Digital Overview of the area
To be able to present all that the area has to offer in one digital overview, and to enlighten tourist providers, destination company and municipalities so that they can advise guests in the best way possible when they visit Magma Geopark.	
Linked with challenges:	
C3	Overview of offers
O3	Fostering Local Identity
To get our 5 municipalities to see the advantage of being part of a UNESCO Global Geopark, and to take the possibilities provided by the local identity, strengthening the “sense of the place” and growth based on natural and cultural heritage.	
Linked with challenges:	
C1	Local divisions and lack of involvement
C2	Economic
C3	Lack of visibility
C6	Environmental

7.3 Operational programme for the implementation of the plan

No	Action	SIA	Challenge(s)	Objective(s)
R2.1	Create a common calendar for all 5 municipalities presenting festivals and other events in the geopark	Local Food, Landscape	C2	O1
R2.2	Promote the tourist offer in all 5 municipalities through the design of a tourist route that specifies restaurants, hotels, activity providers and producers	Local Food, Landscape	C3	O2

R2.3	Promote joint actions to strengthen the local identity and to enhance heritage resources, in order to turn MAGMA Geopark into an internationally recognized concept	Landscape	C1	O3
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7.3.1 The actions in detail

Code of the action		R2.1
Title of the action	Create a common calendar for all 5 municipalities presenting festivals and other events in the geopark	
Relevant SIA or SIAs	Local Food, Landscape	
Relevant Heritage	Intangible – Social practices, Rituals and Festive Events Intangible – Performing arts Intangible – Knowledge and Practices	
Reference RM Action/s (code and name)	RM4-10 Design a calendar of each fair of folk heritage and festivals to promote tourism	
Useful lesson/s Learned (code and name)	LL25. Take advantage from traditional events and make the typical characteristics of the area (food & wine, handcraft, traditions) a tourist attraction. LL16. Foster and promote sustainable tourism. LL04, Build sense of belonging, individual and community self-confidence and increased autonomy through CNH	
Responsible person	Juste Druskiniene (Magma Geopark)	
Relevant RM/KFP involved	RM4 the Colombian Federation of Municipalities (FCM)	
Brief description of the action	This action is aimed at integrating the events that occur in Magma Geopark within one calendar which is jointly agreed and updated in collaboration with the 5 municipalities of the Magma Geopark. The starting point for this activity is the Region Stavanger calendar, that will be also available on the Magma website. Contact persons will be identified in all the municipalities, and supported by Magma, they will develop new skills to ensure the calendar is always updated. In this way, the calendar will be disseminated to make both local people and visitors aware of it.	
Objective and target of the action (by the end of the project)	The main goal of this activity is to make people, both locals and guests, aware of the diversity and quantity of festivals and cultural offers in our region – leading to participation and “reason to come – reason to stay”. Hence this will lead to more activity locally, increasing economic growth and above all build local pride and identity.	
Specific activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Define which digital platform to use. • Define in which section of the Magma website the calendar should be published and how the contents should be organised. • Define a contact person in each municipality. • Define what kind of content is relevant for this calendar. • Buy access to digital platform from Region Stavanger. • Workshop for contact persons, with responsible person Juste Druskiniene (MAGMA geopark staff), to make sure all 5 contact persons know how to access the calendar and how to publish in it. Agree on a common template and common criteria for selecting which events should be published. • Launch calendar: contact local media and present the calendar with all stakeholders/representatives from all 5 involved municipalities present. 	
Monitoring plan and indicators	Reporting every 6 th month in the CARTIF digital template/survey Digital tracking of activities on all digital platforms; calendar on Magma webpage, but also social medias. List of KPI: CC2 Increment the number of mentions of CNH in social media, media and press. CC3 Number of users registered in the Digital Hub or following the social networks CC4 Number of posts in the digital hub	

	<p>CC5 Number of posts mentioning RURITAGE at local level CC8 Number of people trained in traditional skills CC 10 Distribution of arrivals along the year SC1 Number of citizens engagement activities and participants SC3 Number of local Association involved SC 4 Number of participants in formal or informal voluntary activities or active citizenship in the last 12 months HC1 Level of education HC7 Number of people trained in IT and tourism</p>
Capital involved	Cultural, Social, Human capitals
Main stakeholders involved and their roles and contribution	<p>Bjerkreim municipality represented by Gerd; contact person for the calendar in Bjerkreim municipality, will attend workshop and is co-responsible for posting in the calendar. Lund municipality, represented by Olav; contact person for the calendar in Lund municipality, will attend workshop and is co-responsible for posting in the calendar. Sokndal municipality, represented by Nils; contact person for the calendar in Sokndal municipality, will attend workshop and is co-responsible for posting in the calendar. Flekkefjord municipality, represented by Aleksander; contact person for the calendar in Flekkefjord municipality, will attend workshop and is co-responsible for posting in the calendar. Eigersund municipality, represented by Juste; contact person for the calendar in Eigersund municipality, will prepare the workshop and is main-responsible for posting in the calendar. Region Stavanger, will deliver the digital calendar and also provide assistance and digital support in the implementation process.</p>
Beneficiaries	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All 5 municipalities • 2 counties; Rogaland county and Vest-Agder county • Local festivals and markets • Local producers (food & art) • Local communities/cities
Formal partnership established (PPP, voluntary agreement, etc.)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All 5 municipalities, and both counties, have signed a contract saying they support the RURITAGE project. • All participants in this “Round Table” have signed contracts agreeing on their participation in this project and this task.
Timeframe	January - March 2020.
Indicative costs	€ 3,200
Indicative funding sources	RURITAGE budget and Municipalities budget
Sustainability of the action	<p>Magma Geopark is committed to make this action sustainable also after the end of the project lifetime by assigning one staff to its implementation and maintenance. Since there will be designated people in each municipality that will be responsible for adding their content into the calendar, we believe that this will ensure sustainability for this action.</p> <p>As long as this calendar is “kept alive” with new updates and inputs, tourists and locals will find it useful and appreciate the overview and variety it presents.</p>

Code of the action	R2.2
Title of the action	Promote the tourist offer in all 5 municipalities through the design of a tourist route that specifies restaurants, hotels, activity providers and producers
Relevant SIA or SIAs	Local Food, Landscape
Relevant Heritage	Intangible – Social practices, Rituals and Festive Events
Reference RM Action/s (code and name)	RM4-9 Promote the tourist offer of both municipalities through the design of a tourist route that specifies restaurants, hotels and shops

<p>Useful lesson/s Learned (code and name)</p>	<p>LL23. Involvement of private and third sector in cultural heritage in order to optimize business model, answer to social needs and effectively manage heritage. LL07. Create 'tourist pack and experiences' based on the different clusters (culture, food & wine, nature, religion, etc.) and sell combined packages, including transport. LL16. Foster and promote sustainable tourism. LL06. Create a 'brand' based on one of the cultural and natural resources and the added value created. LL03. Bottom-up initiatives can be turned from informal and random experiences to well established ones. LL04. Build sense of belonging, individual and community self-confidence and increased autonomy through CNH. LL06. Create a "brand" based on one of the cultural and natural resources and the added value created. LL12. Discover economic values of traditional food (e.g traditional fish processing, historical orchards and fruit production) and use it as a way to protect historical landscapes. LL17. Boost effective leadership, including through agencies, to promote and drive the actions, with strategic vision, enthusiasm and network of contracts. LL18. Implementation of participatory approach and involvement of local people, including private owners, from early stage. LL25. Take advantage from traditional events and make the typical characteristics of the area (a site, food & wine, handcraft, traditions) a tourist attraction.</p>
<p>Responsible person</p>	<p>Cathrine Johannessen Skogen (Magma Geopark)</p>
<p>Relevant RM/KFP involved</p>	<p>RM13 the Wild Atlantic Way might provide assistance and guidance concerning:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • establishing a route • contracts/agreements with stakeholders/partners • signs/visibility • content • digital promotion of the route <p>RM4 the Colombian Federation of Municipalities (FCM) ACIR</p>
<p>Brief description of the action</p>	<p>The action consists of the design of a tourist route connecting local resources within the geopark area, including restaurants, accommodations, activity providers, producers. The idea is to disseminate as much as possible the tourist opportunities of the Magma geopark by building a network of different providers and producers identified as "Active Partners" (i.e. producers and service and tourist providers that are committed in strengthen the local identity and to enhance heritage resources). By working jointly in collaboration with each other and with the Magma geopark, the providers and producers will allow a multiplier effect. The tourist route will increase the visibility of the tourist offer, at the same time valorizing the local values and heritage.</p>
<p>Objective and target of the action (by the end of the project)</p>	<p>The main objective of this action is to increase the collaboration within the geopark between providers targeting tourists, like restaurants, hotels, activity providers and producers. Magma will like to take advantage of our cultural- and natural heritage and increase value from it.</p>
<p>Specific activities</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gather all potential partners in all 5 municipalities. • Define a tourist route including accommodation, restaurants, activity providers and local producers. • Sign contracts with all partners/stakeholders involved in our tourist route. • Distribute and promote the tourist route (social medias, webpages etc.). • Create a designated page on the Magma webpage to present the tourist route, and maybe add the possibility to book. • To design a way to make all the partners (i.e. Active Partners) easy to identify as partners of the tourist route through Active Partner signs • Testing tourist route. • Accessibility in the route: testing the trail with people with disability to make sure it is accessible for all visitors in the geopark.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Launch tourist route: event inviting press, stakeholders and local inhabitants to test parts of the route.
Monitoring plan and indicators	<p>Reporting every 6th month in the CARTIF digital template/survey. Get numbers from local Active Partners on visitors and enquires. List of KPI: CC2 Increment the number of mentions of CNH in social media, media and press. CC3 Number of users registered in the Digital Hub or following the social networks CC 10 Distribution of arrivals along the year NC1 Value of ecosystem services NC5 Number of companies and organisations with sustainability certification and labelling NC6 number of shops restaurants and tourism facilities selling local products NC7 Number of green tourism packages BC1 Number of hotspots provided BC 3 Number of CNH objects mapped through Atlas BC9 Number of shared transport services BC12 Number of re used buildings SC1 Number of citizens engagement activities and participants SC2 Number par type of stakeholder involved SC3 Number of local Association involved SC4 Number of participants in formal or informal voluntary activities or active citizenship in the last 12 months HC02 Number of recreational facilities HC07 Number of people trained in IT and tourism HC9 Number of publications as recommendations and guidelines provided FC03 Number of PPPs set and sign FC05 Number of start-up and spin off created FC06 Number of companies supported in defining new business models and innovative processes of production</p>
Capital involved	Cultural, Natural, Built, Social, Human, Financial capitals
Main stakeholders involved and their roles and contribution	<p>Bjerkreim municipality, represented by Gerd; will gather information on all accommodations, restaurants, activity providers and local producers in Bjerkreim municipality.</p> <p>Lund municipality, represented by Kjell Andreas and Anders; will gather information on all accommodations, restaurants, activity providers and local producers in Lund municipality.</p> <p>Sokndal municipality, represented by Nils; will gather information on all accommodations, restaurants, activity providers and local producers in Sokndal municipality.</p> <p>Flekkefjord municipality, represented by Frode; will gather information on all accommodations, restaurants, activity providers and local producers in Flekkefjord municipality.</p> <p>Eigersund municipality, represented by Juste; will gather information on all accommodations, restaurants, activity providers and local producers in Eigersund municipality.</p>
Beneficiaries	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> All 5 municipalities 2 counties; Rogaland county and Vest-Agder county Local accommodation providers Local restaurants Local activity providers Local producers The inhabitants of Magma Geopark
Formal partnership established (PPP, voluntary agreement, etc.)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> All 5 municipalities, and both counties, have signed a contract saying they support the RURITAGE project. All participants in this “Round Table” have signed contracts agreeing on their participation in this project and this task.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> We will sign contracts with all partners in the tourist route (Active Partner), but we will have to wait until the route is defined and partners are involved.
Timeframe	November 2019 - June 2021
Indicative costs	€ 10,500
Indicative funding sources	RURITAGE budget Magma Geopark yearly budget
Sustainability of the action	<p>This tourist route will be part of the Magma Geopark general action plan and strategy. The tourist route will be a way for us to continue working towards the goals set by UNESCO and GGN for us as a geopark, giving us the possibility to enhance focus on local natural- and cultural heritage. Making all the partners (i.e. Active Partners) easy to identify as partners of the tourist route through signs will give Magma Geopark more visibility locally and increase the awareness and local identity connected to our heritage. It will also provide possibilities for sustainable economic growth for our partners and our area.</p> <p>Due to all these aspects we are confident that this action will make a much-needed impact in our area and will be sustainable and contribute to growth locally.</p>

Code of the action	R2.3
Title of the action	Promote joint actions to strengthen the local identity and to enhance heritage resources, in order to turn MAGMA Geopark into an internationally recognized concept
Relevant SIA or SIAs	Landscape
Relevant Heritage	Tangible – Natural Intangible – Knowledge and Practices Intangible – Social practices, Rituals and Festive Events Digital
Reference RM Action/s (code and name)	RM12-1 Promote joint actions (also through PPP) to enhance heritage resources and create an internationally recognized brand
Useful lesson/s Learned (code and name)	<p>LL08. Create synergies and foster a collaborative approach with other organizations, programmes or local activities (i.e. festivals, arts, food, etc.) and attractors of the territory to increase impact of the actions.</p> <p>LL23. Involvement of private and third sector in cultural heritage in order to optimize business model, answer to social needs and effectively manage heritage.</p> <p>LL18. Implementation of participatory approach and involvement of local people, including private owners, from early stage.</p> <p>LL24. Long-term vision to build confidence among stakeholders and continuous communication to create long-lasting relationships.</p> <p>LL34. To define an action plan.</p> <p>LL15. Identify heritage resources (formal and informal), foster a better understanding of the tangible and intangible values of natural and cultural heritage and create a recognized value as a driver for local development.</p> <p>LL06. Create a 'brand' based on one of the cultural and natural resources and the added value created.</p> <p>LL17. Boost effective leadership, including through agencies, to promote and drive the actions, with strategic vision, enthusiasm and network of contacts.</p> <p>LL05. Collaborative approaches to achieve innovative financing solutions and access to funding.</p> <p>LL25. Take advantage from traditional events and make the typical characteristics of the area (a site, food & wine, handcraft, traditions) a tourist attraction.</p>
Responsible person	Cathrine Johannessen Skogen (Magma Geopark)
Relevant RM/KFP involved	<p>RM11, Austrått and Ørland landscape, might provide valuable input on</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> how to approach the locals (bottom-up) how to make our hub functional for local networking

	<p>RM13, the Wild Atlantic Way, might provide assistance and guidance concerning</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • how to strengthen the local networks and valorise the heritage resources • how to promote the Magma Geopark as a concept • how to make locals see the value of participating in exploiting the Magma Geopark as a concept • how to do the “ambassador courses” with locals
<p>Brief description of the action</p>	<p>The aim of this action is to enhance the local identity of the area belonging to the geopark thus reinforcing the international recognition of this concept. The activities within this action regard, first of all, getting an overview of all potential partners in the geopark area and then sign agreements with all “Active Partners” (i.e. producers and service and tourist providers that are committed in strengthen the local identity and to enhance heritage resources) and give them information to enhance their awareness of belonging to an UNESCO Global Geopark area. Local GEOfood producers will also be included into the agreement, together with other local producers which are not. The action will also consist of a dissemination part, to increase the local involvement through Magma Facebook and Instagram, and through partners social medias. The resulting hub will be used as a driver for growth and collaboration creating various networks.</p> <p>As part of building local identity, Magma geopark will also add content to geoVR which is our virtual reality system. We will present the area better, make places that are not so accessible possible to experience for all and add GEOfood experiences. We will use a portable system that can be placed in different municipalities for inhabitants to use and learn from.</p> <p>Through a shared digitalization process, Magma geopark will reach more potential visitors, but also build local pride. This is also done through our Instagram takeover were a lot of locals follow Magma Geopark and the posts done by our guest publishers. This action is strongly linked with R2.2. The idea is to reinforce the recognition of the geopark concept by mainly working on the sustainable local food SIA at first, but then to broaden the activities to all the types of heritage that are embedded in the geopark.</p> <p>Finally, training more local guides will be part of building local identity, but also part of providing an offer for tourists and guests. In the long run this can generate economic value for our area. We expect the same results from the ambassador courses which are aimed at training and engaging tourism providers in order to allow them to positively represent and disseminate the Magma geopark values and identity.</p>
<p>Objective and target of the action (by the end of the project)</p>	<p>Magma Geopark consists of 5 municipalities spread across 2 counties. Traditionally there has not been much successful collaboration between these municipalities and counties. Magma Geopark is the first, and only, “umbrella” gathering this area under one unique concept, which is the Magma UNESCO Global Geopark. The objective of this action is to enhance the local identity of the area belonging to the geopark thus reinforcing the international recognition of this concept.</p>
<p>Specific activities</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Promote and use Magma Geopark logo on all partners webpages and social medias. • Create food trails linking with activities and results of action R2.2. • “Active Partner” signs at all our partners/stakeholders. • Ambassador courses in all 5 municipalities. • Two training courses for local guides in at least two municipalities involving people with disability and disadvantages groups. • Continuously work on digitalization to improve the booking system, the way the feedback from visitors are handled, digital media for better communication • Continue with our Instagram takeover to create local enthusiasm and identity. • Welcome signs to Magma Geopark in all the entry points, improving the recognition of the area and its boundaries. • Update and upgrade our geoVR; new oculus rifts, technical support and develop more content (photos, films, information).
<p>Monitoring plan and indicators</p>	<p>Reporting every 6th month in the CARTIF digital template/survey. Get numbers from Active Partners on activity and enquiries. Gather number from counters at our most known localities. List of KPI:</p>

	<p>CC2 Increment the number of mentions of CNH in social media, media and press. CC3 Number of users registered in the Digital Hub or following the social networks CC4 Number of posts in the digital hub CC10 Distribution of arrivals along the year NC5 Number of companies and organisations with sustainability certification and labelling NC6 number of shops restaurants and tourism facilities selling local products NC7 Number of green tourism packages SC1 Number of citizens engagement activities and participants SC2 Number par type of stakeholder involved SC3 Number of local Association involved HC1 Level of education HC07 Number of people trained in IT and tourism FC03 Number of PPPs set and sign FC05 Number of start-up and spin off created FC06 Number of companies supported in defining new business models and innovative processes of production We will monitor the counters at our main localities, and study numbers from statistics related to sleepovers at accommodations to measure impact from this action in our geopark. We will also provide ways to ask guests in the area directly to evaluate their visit here.</p>
Capital involved	Cultural, Natural, Social, Human, Financial capitals
Main stakeholders involved and their roles and contribution	<p>Bjerkreim municipality, represented by Gerd; will actively represent the work involved with the brand in Bjerkreim municipality, and will be the Magma contact person. Will participate in our Round Table of Stakeholder meetings and work towards implementing relevant projects related to this action in her municipality.</p> <p>Lund municipality, represented by Kjell Andreas and Anders; will actively represent the work involved with the brand in Lund municipality, and will be the Magma contact persons. Will participate in our Round Table of Stakeholder meetings and work towards implementing relevant projects related to this action in their municipality.</p> <p>Sokndal municipality, represented by Nils; will actively represent the work involved with the brand in Sokndal municipality, and will be the Magma contact person. Will participate in our Round Table of Stakeholder meetings and work towards implementing relevant projects related to this action in his municipality.</p> <p>Flekkefjord municipality, represented by Frode; will actively represent the work involved with the brand in Flekkefjord municipality, and will be the Magma contact person. Will participate in our Round Table of Stakeholder meetings and work towards implementing relevant projects related to this action in his municipality.</p> <p>Eigersund municipality, represented by Juste; will actively represent the work involved with the brand in Eigersund municipality, and will be the Magma contact person. Will participate in our Round Table of Stakeholder meetings and work towards implementing relevant projects related to this action in her municipality.</p> <p>A variety of stakeholders/active partners in the geopark. This is work in process, but there is an overview of our active partners here.</p> <p>Region Stavanger is the regional destination company and will have a role promoting the brand and the area through their channels.</p>
Beneficiaries	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All 5 municipalities • Both counties • Local producers • Local shops (as Active partners) • Local hotels (as Active partners) • Inhabitants in Magma Geopark • Museums (as Active partners) • Activity providers (as Active partners) • Local restaurants

<p>Formal partnership established (PPP, voluntary agreement, etc.)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All 5 municipalities, and both counties, have signed a contract saying they support the RURITAGE project. • All participants in this “Round Table” have signed contracts agreeing on their participation in this project and this task. • All “Active Partners” • Region Stavanger has signed contract supporting the RURITAGE project, and both Magma and 4 out of 5 municipalities pay a yearly fee to them for promoting our area. We will sign contracts with new partners related to the promotion of the Magma UNESCO Geopark concept.
<p>Timeframe</p>	<p>January 2020 – end of 2022 (beyond RURITAGE lifespan).</p>
<p>Indicative costs</p>	<p>€ 49,500</p>
<p>Indicative funding sources</p>	<p>RURITAGE budget</p>
<p>Sustainability of the action</p>	<p>Through the RURITAGE project we have been given the possibility to work locally in our area. Through the tools provided in this project we’ve engaged the locals and the five municipalities at a new level. The Round Table of Stakeholders events have been very fruitful, and we can now see that we are filling a void; the entire area is working together to achieve change and growth.</p> <p>To turn the Geopark into an internationally recognized concept takes time, but our goal is that this project is just the start of this process. The collaboration that we have now started will go on because all parties can benefit from it and see the value of it.</p> <p>By implementing the signs of the MAGMA Geopark all over the geopark and at the, Active Partners’ premises, its recognition will be strengthened, and people will understand that they belong to an area with unique features, rich in natural and cultural heritage.</p> <p>We believe that all of these tasks will be part of a sustainable and continuing growth in our area.</p>

7.3.2 Timeline for the implementation

Action No:	Action Name:	19	2020												2021												2022				
		December	January	February	March	April	May	June	July	August	September	October	November	December	January	February	March	April	May	June	July	August	September	October	November	December	January	February	March	April	May
		19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	41	42	43	44	45	46	47	48
1	Create a common calendar for all 5 municipalities presenting festivals and other events in the geop				W/E																										
2	Promote the tourist offer in all 5 municipalities through the design of a tourist route that specifies restaurants, hotels, activity providers and producers																														
3	Promote joint actions to strengthen the local identity and to enhance heritage resources, in order to turn the geopark into an internationally recognized concept																														

W = workshop run E = event run

7.4 Risks for the implementation of the plan

Risk No.	Action/s involved	Description of the risk	Mitigation action proposed
1	R2.1 R2.2 R2.3	The collaboration with one or more municipalities struggles to exist.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Close follow up on all tasks. • Support from the geopark staff. • Involve the counties.
2	R2.1	We do not get enough local restaurants, accommodations, activity providers and/or local producers to work with us to establish a sufficient tourist route.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use our local partners/stakeholders as motivators and recruiters and promote the benefits of joining our network/route.
3	R2.1	We do not have/get sufficient funding to print or develop new signs for Active Partners.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • We must directly approach our owners and the five municipalities in the geopark to make them aware of the importance of these signs for strengthening the local identity and sense of belonging.
4	R2.2	The digital platform provided for the calendar from Region Stavanger is not compatible with the existing Magma Geopark digital platform.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use the digital competence in Magma Geopark and our 5 municipalities to ensure the compatibility of the different platforms.
5	R2.2	There will not be any events or festivals published from one or several municipalities.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Responsible person in Magma will have to support the relevant contact person closely, and also consider the need for providing additional training or a repetitive workshop.
6	R2.2	No one will use the calendar.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All 5 municipalities and Magma will have to promote it harder and disseminate it through more channels.
7	R2.3	Our 5 municipalities will not commit to adopt the Magma Geopark visual identity and integrate the Magma Geopark logo on all relevant publications, webpage, social medias etc.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Visit all municipality boards and explain the benefits of using one common concept for the area. • Show them how our RM13 Wild Atlantic Way has succeeded in the branding of their area.
8	R2.3	We do not get enough active partners to make the Magma Geopark identity visible and consistent in the area.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use our local partners as ambassadors to promote the Geopark • Magma responsible person attending gatherings where potential Geopark partners are participating to inform and recruit. • Use social medias and local newspapers to disseminate the concept.
9	R2.3	No participants for our guide courses.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Promote the guide course through more channels; newspapers, social medias, leaflets, posters etc. • Get our contact persons in the 5 municipality to headhunt local heroes and other interesting persons.
10	R2.3	Our Active Partners will not put up the designated sign at their venue.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Show them how it's done at our Role Models in Ireland. • Arrange a gathering for all Active Partners to give them an overview of the benefits of consistent branding of the area.

11	R2.3	No one will attend our Ambassador courses.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Promote the course through more channels; newspapers, social medias, leaflets, posters etc. • Targeting the people who “should” attend this meeting and approach them directly.
12	R2.3	The collaboration across all 5 municipalities connected to communication and digitalization will collapse.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Get the government in all 5 municipalities to see the importance of this collaboration, and to designate competent people to work on it. • Use all accessible funding and apply for additional funding taking advantage of the possibilities provided through our collaboration across municipality boarders and county boarders.
13	R2.3	No locals want to do our Instagram takeover.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Target people directly and present the possibility to show their area to a wide range of followers on the Magma Instagram account. • Ask businesses and Active Partners, directly to participate. • Give a price to the photo that will get most “likes” during a year.
14	R2.3	We will not be allowed by the government to put up welcome signs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Add pressure by involving the other two UNESCO Global Geoparks in Norway. • Use political force by involving local and national politicians.

8. Geo-Naturpark Bergstraße-Odenwald UNESCO Global Geopark (GEO-N) Heritage-led regeneration plan

8.1 Background information

The Geo-Naturpark Bergstraße-Odenwald (Geo-N) is located in southwest Germany, covering the states of Hesse, Bavaria and Baden-Württemberg which includes 102 municipalities. Within Bergstraße-Odenwald you find representation of various geological, natural and human history, this includes three UNESCO World Heritage Sites. The Geo-N offers a more than 500 million years old history of our planet, a diverse landscape, from agricultural land to deep forests, and a rich cultural history.

Being as central situated makes Bergstraße-Odenwald recreation accessible for millions of people. For now, the geopark offers a wider range of education, tours and fieldtrips in cooperation with various stakeholder. By taking part in RURITAGE, Geo-Naturpark Bergstraße-Odenwald will use heritage as sustainable tool to boost migrant's integration in the area.

In the Geo-N, inhabitants and newcomers can learn about the geological, natural and cultural heritage of our landscape in a predominantly rural territory. We intend to learn from Earth history for the future, we explain, why biodiversity and culture is essential for our life, we demonstrate, how education for sustainable development can gather benefit for future generations. We assume, that our CNH can be a driving force for the mutual understanding and fruitful development of our region. Together with our partners, we offer a broad variety of activities and guided tours for target groups of all ages. Following our holistic approach, we connect not only topics and a regional partner network, but also methods of getting into contact with nature by hands-on activities and learning to know each other by educational and training settings. People understand, why natural and cultural diversity is important for all of us, and experience the healing function of forest, meadow, water and movement.

The Geo-N Rural Heritage Hub is located in the headquarters of the Geo-N in Lorsch, Germany. It is equipped with 12 offices and one large meeting room. Address: Geo-Naturpark Bergstrasse-Odenwald, Nibelungenstrasse 44, 64653 Lorsch, Germany. It is situated in the city centre of Lorsch, close to UNESCO World heritage Site Abbey Lorsch. The RHH is suitable for meetings up to 20 individuals, like e.g. the serious game, the business model workshop, the stakeholder roundtables. About 50 meters close by, we have the option to use a big conference hall, suitable for 170 participants, which has been used for the Launch event of the RHH. Depending on the topic or the locality of a project element, meetings can be held at other places, e.g. information centres within the Geo-Naturpark's territory or cooperation partners' halls or offices like the Citizens hall in Bensheim, which has been used for the participatory planning workshop.

Figure 25: Geo-N Rural Heritage Hub and the larger meeting room of the Hub

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8.1.1 The Reference SIA

MIGRATION FOR RURAL REGENERATION

As UNESCO Global Geopark, the objectives of the United Nations regarding peacebuilding and understanding between the nations as well as the Global Goals 2030 are a guidelines and leading motivations underlining our actions and activities. Besides the close cooperation with a total of 147 UNESCO Global Geoparks worldwide, this also includes the active participation in international funding projects, which match the potentials and topics of the Geo-N. The RURITAGE project with its overall objective to support the sustainable development of rural areas by their natural and cultural heritage fits perfectly into the principles and holistic approach of the UNESCO Global Geoparks. The 6 SIAs highlight some of the core activities, which Geoparks can offer to the inhabitants of their territories and also for newcomers from all-over the world: Learning about Earth history, nature and landscape, experiencing that the CNH can create resilience, using the intangible heritage for creating awareness (e.g. pilgrimage routes), celebrating local food as part of the regional identity, integrating arts as driving force to experiencing nature, and building strong connections between people to protect and promote our territories in a sustainable and holistic way for future generations.

Geo-N offers an ideal setting for the integration of migrants. Vice versa, the participation of migrants in our activities can lead to a better understanding of each other and reduce possible fears and prejudices. Especially the Geo-N's philosophy, potentials and tools, which we have developed as an UNESCO Global Geopark, make us a multi-experienced partner in developing and implementing new approaches to experiencing nature, culture and landscape tailored to migrants, which enable a higher grade of integration by training of skills, learning to know each other and building capacity. The positive impact relates to anyone, newcomers as well as since-long inhabitants, can benefit from the RURITAGE approach by building awareness in local communities and sharpen the profile of our natural and cultural values and by offering migrants multiple options to becoming vivid parts of our society. We want to provide the opportunity for migrants to learn more about the protection of environment, about local habits and traditions, practise language in a welcoming setting, improve sports skills, and develop own potentials.

We understand this international context connected with our regional Geopark philosophy as core task and benefit for our territory and at the same time as capacity and awareness building process for inhabitants as well as for migrants for a better understanding and living together. This positive and constructive seed of RURITAGE will also grow for our future generations, when the world is facing the increase of the climate crisis, when we need even more places for life and tools for integration. Capacity building, knowledge transfer and the development of ethic potentials for inhabitants and as well as for migrants is social, human, natural and cultural capital – fostered and triggered in a sustainable way by RURITAGE.

8.1.2 Other relevant SIAs

Despite Geo-N regeneration activities within RURITAGE are primarily linked with the «Migration for Rural Regeneration» Systemic and Innovation Action (SIA), Geo-N can also benefit and learn from the following SIAs, thanks to the knowledge exchange and codification of Role Model actions and Lessons Learned coming from a variety of other Role Models other than the one from the Migration SIA:

ART & FESTIVAL FOR RURAL REGENERATION

In the context of arts and festivals, we have developed a long-lasting partnership with the International Forest Art Association. Up until now, more than 140 artists from all-over the world are part of this nature-based art symposium. Based on cooperation and experience, we add new developed art workshops and programmes which enable migrants to get in contact with the CNH, with artists from Germany and other nations and to experience, that they have competences and abilities. The nature art setting also creates an ideal environment for short and mid-term internships for migrants including multi-faceted tasks in a natural environment combined with world-open colleagues. RURITAGE has enhanced the Forest Art Association to develop new programmes, to include migrants temporary into their team, and to build relationships to migrant contact groups, which they have never mentioned before RURITAGE. This combination of new offers and integration tools for migrants, initiated by RURITAGE, create an intense added value to our SIA Migration. Especially nature art is a communicator and driver for the mutual understanding and for knowing each other in a natural and relaxing environment.

LANDSCAPE FOR RURAL REGENERATION

Landscape for rural regeneration is one of our major tasks and an integral part of various programmes of Geo-N. In this relation, we have developed several partnerships and can rely on numerous stakeholders. Many of them are meanwhile involved into our RURITAGE-related activities for the integration of migrants into our society. RURITAGE has widened our view towards the potentials of our CNH for integration, exchange and development.

8.1.3 The Replicator baseline

Geo-N offers a high number of actions and cultural events (CC-06, social impact/inclusion) - we have developed together with our touristic partners a range of sustainable tourism packages (NC-07, economic impact/growth). We are present at several touristic fairs to promote our territory (BC-14, economic impact/growth), which offers a high number of beds for overnight stay and restaurants for experiencing local traditions and regional food (BC-04, BC-05, economic impact/growth). Visitors as well as inhabitants are able to use also public transport (BC-08, environmental impact/balance) to enjoy the landscape by hiking and cycling along the Geopark trails, which are equipped with explanation panels and uniform signage for information and orientation (BC-15, economic impact/growth).

Based on our community participation approach, we engage a high number of stakeholders, volunteers and citizens, who are integrated and contribute to our common projects (SC-01, SC-02, social impact/inclusion). This can build a link to the integration of immigrants and migrants to become an active part of RURITAGE and its connected capacity building processes (SC-05, social impact/inclusion).

Related to education, we have a long-term experience in vocational trainings, educational materials and published information, which we offer to the public via Ranger programmes and Geopark on site activities (HC-08, HC-09, organizational impacts).

Our member communities contribute annually to our budget and are regularly involved in a broad variety of projects. We are also involved in the regional development strategies and promotional activities of the German Naturepark Association and the UNESCO Global Geoparks. The unemployment rate in our territory is comparable low, due to the geographical position between the two metropolitan areas Rhein-Main and Rhein-Neckar (FC-02, FC-03, FC-04, economic, social impact/inclusion, growth).

Summarizing this description, the strength of our territory is a combination of the strategic position in-between the two metropolitan areas “Rhein-Main” (Frankfurt) and “Rhein-Neckar” (Mannheim, Heidelberg) with a high economic prosperity, combined with the above mentioned Geo-N potentials, which can support the integration of migrants in many ways: infrastructure, employment, education, prosperity and therefore willing to contribute to the integration of migrants.

On the other hand, we experience, that various integration barriers, like language and community participation still exist in many ways, that migrants often do not dare to participate in common regional events, and that the offers for them to learn and to experience our territory, are not specific enough to fit their needs. Especially nature and landscape, which offers a high integration potential, are undiscovered, the knowledge is low. Here, we have identified a series of challenges (see 5.1.4).

Figure 26: R3 performance (baseline calculation)

© RURITAGE monitoring platform, using Grafana

8.1.4 The main challenges

Currently, the general integration stage of migrants developed to an already advanced situation compared to the migration crisis of 2015 and the following year, when hundreds of thousands of migrants arrived in Germany within a short time period. Meanwhile, in 2019, lots of migrants are following more or less successful governmental integration programmes, some of them go to school or to work. Others live separated from the society in border areas of the communities. It therefore will be essential to build bridges and create opportunities for migrants to join our offers and also to create an environment which fit into their needs for advanced integration.

Related to this situation, we do not put a flashlight on huge separated migrant groups. The situation has changed and the migrants are in an integration phase, which requires a more tailored support, which we consider related to our challenges, objectives and actions. As a consequence, we focus on the invitation of migrants and inhabitants to newly developed approaches in cooperation with partners and stakeholders, based on our experiences and capacities as UNESCO Global Geopark. We support the process of integration by offering a range of actions, where migrants and inhabitants learn more about our CNH, our regional identity, our activities in nature and our language - and where they can meet each other in an open and welcoming atmosphere. This is also in line with our Role Models Lesvos UNESCO Global Geopark, Greece, which follows the same approach, and Asti Province (PIAM), Italy.

My main challenges

C1 There is a clear shortage of migrants in outdoor activities due to segregation.

Migrants often do not live in the centre of the communities, but in the border or suburbia units. They do not naturally take part in everyday life and common activities like e.g. sports. In addition, they do not dare to

participate in outdoor activities, which can be suitable platforms for learning to know each other and to overcome fears and barriers.

C2 Language skills of migrants are not sufficient to engage in events expressing and communicating the CNH

The process of language learning requires practise and multiple experiences in the new environment. Independent of language training courses (which are first mandatory in the stage of acceptance), migrants do not have enough options to practice their language skills in the natural environment. Therefore, their knowledge about the natural and cultural heritage connected with the respective vocabulary is poor.

C3 Our Geo-N landscape is vulnerable and needs intense care from all groups of society including migrants to increase awareness of the value of our CNH

Our cultural landscape is the product of natural development in interaction with the modifying influence of human beings. During the last centuries, our cultural landscape became more and more precious due to the land loss related to industrial and economical use. The remaining cultural and natural heritage needs protection and preservation by all groups the civil society including migrants, who are part of our community.

C4 Lack of opportunities for integrating migrants through creative and artistic projects in nature that contribute also to mental and physical health

The creation of art in nature can be a chance and door opener for vulnerable groups like migrants and other minorities of our society to take part in common activities and to express creative potentials. Their opportunities to experience nature are often limited due to psychological and real barriers as well as the lack of adequate artistic projects and options. Thus, they miss the chance to exchange experiences with inhabitants and to discover their creative abilities in natural environment by hands-on activities.

8.2 Overall objectives of the plan

This Action Plan is intended to support the regeneration of our area through the development of our natural and cultural heritage resources and taking into account our holistic Geopark approach.

As UNESCO Global Geopark, our natural and cultural heritage is an essential tool for the development of our territory. Working according the bottom-up approach, we integrate the local communities with participatory processes, a wide range of options to get into contact with our heritage and also to strengthen the mutual understanding between people of different nations. It is obvious, that this setting is also suitable to build a fruitful and successful platform for the integration of migrants. In addition, the integration of vulnerable groups like migrants or other minorities is a task, which can support the social, economic and ecological development of our territory.

RURITAGE offers a range of tools, practises and experiences for the capacity building of migrants as well as inhabitants and for awareness building of all groups of society. RURITAGE also enables exchange and learning from each other by interacting with our RURITAGE partners as a whole and our Role Model partners in detail. Geo-N benefits from this connection, exchange and mentoring each other.

We have developed together with partners and stakeholders from the territory our common RURITAGE philosophy by implementing the programme **“Warmly welcome to the Geo-Naturepark – being a part of our community, experiencing nature, being creative and discovering our natural and cultural heritage”**.

Here, we follow basic principles:

- *Only what you know lets you feel home*
- *Only what you understand you will appreciate*
- *Only what you enjoy together will connect you with others*
- *Only if you learn to know each other you lose fears*

Figure 27: Heritage Cycle

© RURITAGE – elaborated from Simon Thurley (2005)

Our intentions to reach these principles include the cooperation with partners and stakeholders and the common **development of new actions:**

- which act as platform, where inhabitants and migrants can meet and learn to know each other
- which support the building of capacities
- which are suitable for all ages
- which enable migrants by hands-on activities to reduce fears and barriers
- which strengthen the creativity and awareness
- which offer opportunities to be part of public events
- which offer tools and practises to support integration

These principles are based on our daily experiences and supported also by the Heritage Cycle (Thurley 2005). Starting from our overall Objective and Challenges (C1 – C4) and integrating our principles and intentions, the following **specific Objectives** (O1 – O9) have been defined and have been connected with the implementation of Actions (R3.1 – R3.9):

Specific objectives	
O1	Improve and increase the participation of migrants in outdoor events
Sports and activities in nature are door-openers for migrants to feel involved and to learn to know each other. Common activities can break the barrier and support mutual understanding. At the same time, special sports activities like mountain biking can offer new skills and requirements for experiencing the landscape and learning about the CNH or the territory.	
Linked with challenges	
C1	There is a clear shortage of migrants in outdoor activities due to segregation
O2	Increasing the participation of newcomers and local inhabitants in community and Geopark events as platform for exchange of our rural heritage
Regular Geo-N and community events and festivals include various information and activities about our CNH. The integration of specific welcoming booths including information material and educational activities could increase the participation of migrants.	
Linked with challenges	

C1	There is a clear shortage of migrants in outdoor activities due to segregation
O3	Increase the potentials of local community and newcomers to get familiar with local natural heritage and provide new perspectives on our heritage and its vulnerability via GIS-tools
Digital media are a part of our daily life and a tool for communication as well as for learning and experience. In this context, geographical information systems (GIS) can offer a series of options to document experiences combined with geographical data and information of the CNH to create mental maps regarding our environment as well as integrating specific topics considering the “citizen science” approach.	
Linked with challenges	
C1	There is a clear shortage of migrants in outdoor activities due to segregation
O4	Support the improvement of migrants’ language skills and connected with their awareness as part of the natural and cultural heritage of the community
Language is a key capacity for integration. Therefore, the ability of understanding and speaking the language of the new home country needs to be developed and strengthened. Besides the governmental and common language courses, migrants need educative and informative materials as well as events to work out their language skills in a welcoming and relaxed atmosphere of meeting and learning to know each other. Language learning by using words and phrases of our CNH can increase the capacity and the integration – and finally social sustainability by creating a social exchange platform.	
Linked with challenges	
C2	Language skills of migrants are not sufficient to engage in events expressing and communicating the CNH
O5	Create events, social platforms and options for interacting within local community
Traditions, fairy tales and intangible heritage are invaluable parts of our CNH. Getting in contact with this resource supports the understanding of the new home for migrants. Vice versa, the integration of tales and traditions of the migrants, widens the views of the inhabitants. Events and platforms, which enable the presentation of this heritage and the interaction between the local communities and migrants, can contribute to integration.	
Linked with challenges	
C2	Language skills of migrants are not sufficient to engage in events expressing and communicating the CNH
O6	Increase the integration of inhabitants and migrants, who are involved in cultural landscape and awareness actions
Our cultural landscape is a result of thousands of years of development and a precious capacity which needs our protection. Usually, people are not aware of this aspect. Integrating them – migrants together with inhabitants – into landscape awareness actions will lead to an increased understanding of our CH and also a mutual exchange. Following the heritage cycle as driving force (Thurley 2005), this approach will guarantee the sustainability of the respective actions (understanding – valuing – caring – enjoying).	
Linked with challenges	
C3	Our Geo-N landscape is vulnerable and needs intense care from all groups of society including migrants to increase awareness of the value of our CNH
O7	Offer options for locals and new inhabitants to be an active part of nature conservation measures
The support of biodiversity and nature protection measures are essential tasks for the sustainable development of a landscape and for the conservation of our CNH. Making people aware of these requirements by integrating them into common actions and protection activities can contribute to awareness building in combination with integration processes.	
Linked with challenges	
C3	Our Geo-N landscape is vulnerable and needs intense care from all groups of society including migrants to increase awareness of the value of our CNH
O8	Creation of opportunities for local inhabitants and migrants to express creative work in a natural environment
Creative work in natural environment can support psychological healing processes and health in a holistic way. Nature art can build a platform of expressing own thoughts and feelings and of being part of a big international	

movement. The contact to the local inhabitants as well as to international artists can support the understanding between each other and also between the nations. We have a long-term experience with nature arts and its connection with local communities and a variety of different target groups. For migrants, the development of new creative expression opportunities can support their self-confidence, their experience with different target groups and their integration. Our approaches are also part of exchange with RM Lesvos UNESCO Global Geopark.

Linked with challenges

C2	Language skills of migrants are not sufficient to engage in events expressing and communicating the CNH
C3	Our Geo-N landscape is vulnerable and needs intense care from all groups of society including migrants to increase awareness of the value of our CNH
C4	Lack of opportunities for integrating migrants through creative and artistic projects in nature that contribute also to mental and physical health

O9 Offer migrants temporal work with artists and artist organizations

It is a unique experience to be a continuous part of an art project – to work with the artist in nature, to support the development and creation of the art works and to get an insight into all organizational procedures related with the nature art approach. Creating an own art piece with the support of an artist is an additional option and the advanced stage of this approach, which can support integration of migrants in many ways.

Linked with challenges

C4	Lack of opportunities for integrating migrants through creative and artistic projects in nature that contribute also to mental and physical health
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8.3 Operational programme for the implementation of the plan

The above described objectives are developed taking into account the Geo-N baseline, the philosophy, skills and experiences as UNESCO Global Geopark, intense discussion processes with partners and stakeholders and the feedback from our activities related to the co-development phase (learning on the spot). They are also chosen according to the Strategic Actions of our SIA Role Models Lesvos UNESCO Global Geopark and Asti Province (PIAM) and include mentoring visits, exchange activities and common projects in the respective territories.

Based on our principles and intentions, our baseline, challenges and objectives and considering the Strategic Actions of our Role Models Lesvos UNESCO Global Geopark (Greece) and Asti Province (PIAM, Italy), as well as the experiences of additional Role Models and Replicators, we have selected **9 Actions (R3.1 to R3.9)**. We take into account the discussion and exchange process together with our key partners and stakeholders during the implementation phase and the experiences and results of the respective participation tools (serious game, participatory planning workshop, business model workshop, stakeholder roundtables).

All linked actions will be accompanied by intense public relations activities like regular pre-event press releases, invitation of the media to the respective events, website, reports in our Geopark magazine, social media, official welcome events of the local communities, information booths at local fairs and photo documentation. This is in line also with Task 7.4.

No	Action	SIA	Challenge(s)	Objective(s)
R3.1	Organizing a Mountainbiking Event with tech-courses and forest-teaching by rangers for migrants	Migration, Landscape	C1	O1
R3.2	Welcoming booths at Geopark-events	Migration, Landscape	C1	O2
R3.3	Utilizing GIS-Tools to map citizen’s opinion and interaction with the natural and cultural	Migration, Landscape	C1	O3

	heritage on a personal level and in regard to climate change induced vulnerability			
R3.4	Educational material for language skills supporting migrants' understanding of natural and cultural heritage	Migration, Landscape	C2	O4
R3.5	Author reading and family events at visitor centre of UNESCO World Heritage Site Messel Pit	Migration, Landscape, Art & Festivals	C2	O5
R3.6	Increasing the awareness of cultural and natural heritage by cultural landscape interpretation	Migration, Landscape	C3	O6
R3.7	Local and new inhabitants are an active part in preserving Orchard meadows and old Fruit varieties.	Migration, Landscape	C3	O7
R3.8	Strengthening the bonds between migrants and residents through creative land art and forest art work	Migration, Landscape, Art & Festivals	C2, C3, C4	O8
R3.9	Migrant internships with International Forest Art Centre and international artists	Migration, Landscape, Art & Festivals	C4	O9

8.3.1 The actions in detail

Code of the action	R3.1
Title of the action	Organizing a Mountainbiking Event with tech-courses and forest-teaching by rangers for migrants
Relevant SIA or SIAs	Migration; Landscape
Relevant Heritage	Tangible – Nature Intangible – Social Practices, Rituals and Festive Events
Reference RM Action/s (code and name)	RM6-2; Educational programs and guided tours, specifically tailored for migrants to make them aware of the CNH of the territory RM19-3; Initiatives for the enhancement and protection of the historical, cultural, natural and local heritage
Useful lesson/s Learned (code and name)	LL04; Build sense of belonging, individual and community self-confidence and increased autonomy through CNH LL15; Identify heritage resources (formal and informal), foster a better understanding of the tangible and intangible values of natural and cultural heritage and create a recognized value as a driver for local development
Responsible persons	Dr. Jutta Weber (Geo-N), Marcus Seuser (Geo-N)
Relevant RM/KFP involved	RM6; Boosting migrant integration with nature and outdoor sports like Mountainbiking in Lesvos Island (Greece) additional RM19; Ecomuseum (Alpi Apuane, Italy)
Brief description of the action	The aim of this action is to offer migrants the chance to explore our natural heritage by bike in cooperation with local mountainbike clubs, thus promoting integration through the valorisation of natural heritage. In the process, migrants shall overcome shyness and increase confidence to participate in public events via physical education in bike tech courses. This will enable them to increase their options for experiencing the geopark, combining sport activities with awareness activities. They get to know the possibilities of activities in our forests and how to protect them (teaching by forest ranger). In general, the heritage should be more accessible to everyone. Exchange visit by project coordinator Marcus Seuser with role model Lesvos for their annual mountainbike festival and exchanging best practice knowledge.

Objective and target of the action (by the end of the project)	Improve and increase the participation of migrants in sports events. Migrants feel confident enough to join local mountainbike clubs. They finally have the knowledge and resources to organize themselves for outdoor activities in our natural heritage. The target group includes migrants with a general interest in outdoor sports and local bikers who have an interest in working and meeting with new residents and teaching.
Specific activities (Annex I)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • event planning meeting I • MTB-Event in Lesvos, Marcus Seuser is going there to exchange knowledge and best practice examples • event planning meeting II • meeting with logistic partner for food and beverages • meeting with the city of Michelstadt for event location • final meeting and organization of logistics (tables, chairs, etc....) • technique Training at the event by guides from Muemlingtalradler • rental bikes for migrants from local bike shops for the event itself • inform and invite media • guiding event by guides from Muemlingtalradler • logistics of the event (food, beverages, table, chairs)
Monitoring plan and indicators	SC-3; Number of local associations involved SC-5; Number of immigrants actively engaged in the project SC-1; Number of citizens engagement activities and participants
Capital involved	Cultural, Natural and Social capitals
Main stakeholders involved and their roles and contribution	Muemlingtalradler (Local MTB-Club): Training and Guiding Courses for migrants HessenForst (Forest Ranger): Lecture on natural heritage forest and behavior rules
Beneficiaries	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • migrants who are not aware of the sport opportunities in the local natural heritage and not sure how to participate in outdoor events. • bikers
Formal partnership established (PPP, voluntary agreement, etc.)	support agreement with the mountainbike-club Muemlingtalradler signed already on the 10.12.2019
Timeframe	April 2020 – September 2020
Indicative costs (Annex I)	€ 3,540
Indicative funding sources (Annex I)	RURITAGE Geo-N yearly budget additional co-financing supplementary logistic facilities by sponsors (transport, logistics)
Sustainability of the action	In case of a successful event we would like to encourage more local MTB-Clubs in our territory (around 30 exist), to host such welcoming and training events for migrants on their own in cooperation with the local municipality. These costs will then be covered by the Geo-N, partners and sponsors.

Code of the action	R3.2
Title of the action	Welcoming booths at Geopark-events
Relevant SIA or SIAs	Migration; Landscape
Relevant Heritage	Tangible – Nature Intangible – Social Practices, Rituals and Festive Events Intangible – Knowledge and Practices
Reference RM Action/s (code and name)	RM6-1; Developing integration and information programmes for migrants and citizens. RM9-2; Develop interactive exhibitions to attract a broader audience. RM19-2; Promote the awareness of the value of territorial heritage and its potential as a driver of local development.

Useful lesson/s Learned (code and name)	<p>LL08; Create synergies and foster a collaborative approach with other organizations, programmes or local activities and attractors of the territory to increase impact of the actions.</p> <p>LL21; Integration of vulnerable groups in local value chain.</p> <p>LL25; Take advantage from traditional events and make the typical characteristics of the area (a site, food & wine, handcraft, traditions) a tourist attraction.</p> <p>LL28; Promote access to all ages and abilities and ensure fruition of cultural resources to all, including transport and online information provision.</p>
Responsible persons	Dr. Jutta Weber (Geo-N), Manuel Bruckdorfer (Geo-N)
Relevant RM/KFP involved	<p>RM6; Boosting migrant integration with nature in Lesvos Island (Greece)</p> <p>RM9; Teaching culture for learning resilience in Crete (Greece)</p> <p>additional RM19; Ecomuseum (Alpe Apuane, Italy)</p>
Brief description of the action	Choose and/or develop adequate Geopark-events, local markets and festival events in the area with respect to the migrant target group. Contact local communities to organize tailored, multi-lingual information material about the cultural and natural heritage, which are combined with suitable activities to facilitate contact between migrants and residents at the booth.
Objective and target of the action (by the end of the project)	The main objective of this action is to increase the integration of inhabitants and migrants in community by talking about the surrounding landscape, its history and cultural and ecological function. Thus, on the one hand, the booth provides a communication base (cultural and natural heritage as a topic), on the other hand conversation between migrants and residents can lead to common outdoor activities.
Specific activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • contact and invite media, local communities, counties and migrant aid associations to choose local events with expected migrant participation probability • define time schedule preparing four welcoming booths per year • develop and produce multi-lingual invitation and information material • organizational meeting to define position and structure of the booth for each event and discuss presentation of specified local aspects. • plan of personnel resources for each event • realization • debriefing following each event – which aspects could be improved?
Monitoring plan and indicators	<p>CC-6; Number of actions and cultural events produced by citizens at local level (n. and n. of people reached)</p> <p>SC-1; Number of citizens engagement activities and participants</p> <p>SC-3; Number of local associations involved</p> <p>SC-5; Number of immigrants actively engaged in the project and participating to the hub</p> <p>SC-6; Number of projects addressing people with disabilities (n. of projects, and n. of people involved)</p>
Capital involved	Cultural and Social capitals
Main stakeholders involved and their roles and contribution	<p>Geopark on site-guides: On site-guide teams help to staff the individual booths and to circulate local, authentic information about landscape, history and natural phenomena.</p> <p>UNESCO WHS Messel Pit, UBZ Kühkopf & Felsenmeer Information Centre</p> <p>All of the three information facilities are located in the western part of the region, which is densely populated and therefore predestined for integration processes of migrants within the Geopark area. Furthermore, they provide rooms and regular program formats, which are already well-reputed and visited. Establishing welcoming booths for migrants promises successful implementation especially at these locations.</p>
Beneficiaries	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Residents and migrants in participating municipalities • Local festivals and markets • Supporting information facilities
Formal partnership established (PPP, voluntary agreement, etc.)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Executive board and member communities have basically agreed to RURITAGE during annual general assembly (March 2019). • Voluntary agreement of Geopark-on-site-guides (e.g. Fischbachtal team) • support agreement of UNESCO World Heritage Site Messel Pit, UBZ Kühkopf and Felsenmeer Information Centre.

Timeframe	First welcoming booths will be planned until and realized from April 2020 until M48
Indicative costs	€ 12,500
Indicative funding sources	RURITAGE Supplementary logistic facilities (transport, booth material) Additional co-financing by Geopark budget.
Sustainability of the action	Since the new concept of welcoming booths can easily be integrated in the existing Geo-N regional network, it provides a powerful tool to use Geopark-events as a platform to initiate a communication and integration process between migrants and residents. The common development of multi-lingual information material amplifies contacts and cooperation between engaged citizens, official stakeholders in municipalities and Geo-N. Once established, the new concept will be continued by the staff of the Geo-N and the volunteers associated with the Geoparks' philosophy. The internal evaluation (debriefing following each event) ensures quality and improvement of the concept during the duration of the project action. We also hope to generate volunteers out of the migrant target group, after they got integrated in the local communities and got familiar with the Geopark concept – in this case, integrated immigrant people could help to integrate recently arrived migrants.

Code of the action	R3.3
Title of the action	Utilizing GIS-Tools to map citizen's opinion and interaction with the natural and cultural heritage on a personal level and in regard to climate change induced vulnerability
Relevant SIA or SIAs	Migration; Landscape
Relevant Heritage	Tangible – Nature Intangible – Social Practices, Rituals and Festive Events Digital
Reference RM Action/s (code and name)	RM6-2; Educational programmes and guided tours, specifically tailored for migrants to make them aware of the CNH of the territory RM19-3; Initiatives for the enhancement and protection of the historical, cultural, natural and local heritage RM9-4; Participative mapping of the Heritage Features at risk RM11-1; Develop a participative process for the recognition and the evaluation of the tangible and intangible cultural and natural heritage features
Useful lesson/s Learned (code and name)	LL31; Improve resilience of natural and cultural environments against natural hazards LL35; Training on digital technologies LL15; Identify heritage resources (formal and informal), foster a better understanding of the tangible and intangible values of natural and cultural heritage and create a recognized value as a driver for local development
Responsible persons	Dr. Jutta Weber (Geo-N), Marcus Seuser (Geo-N)
Relevant RM/KFP involved	RM6; Boosting migrant integration with nature in Lesvos Island (Greece) RM9; Teaching culture for learning resilience in Crete (Greece) RM11; A CNH-led approach in Austrått manorial landscape (Norway) additional RM19; Ecomuseum (Alpi Apuane, Italy) RM 9 and RM10; Mapping techniques for natural hazards and climate change issues combined with mapping the opportunities for climate change resilience (Crete and Iceland) University of Plymouth
Brief description of the action	Give citizens (including migrants) the digital resources (our data collection app "Survey123" by Esri) and the application knowledge to collect visual data on place specific sympathy (places they like/dislike, where they spent most of the time) and vulnerable places due to climate change, that need protection measures. Especially in the rural context it is often hard to organize people for action taking and analyzing the status quo situation in widespread areas. This is why the bottom-up approach by local

	citizens is most appropriate for the analyzing part. In applying the mapping process, citizens will more actively observe their surroundings and identify more with it, increasing the feeling of responsibility in citizens to protect it.
Objective and target of the action (by the end of the project)	Learning new perspectives on our natural and cultural heritage from the eye of citizens and migrants and making them aware of the vulnerability of their local natural heritage. This is achieved by engaging people in local field work with the app and creating a visual representation and maps exhibition from the data. Our first target group are migrants who lack the language skills to express their feelings towards our local natural and cultural heritage. Our second target group are citizens who are interested in mapping the vulnerabilities of their local natural and cultural heritage and want to make it more resilient towards climate change.
Specific activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • develop the collection app Survey123 from Esri for migrants and citizens and/or to use Rate my View App from WP5 • workshop I: introduction local citizens to the project and collecting feedback on the app and beyond • improving the app and adding necessary collection features according to the results from Workshop I • distributing the app to migrants and citizens via e-mail with download link and start the collection period • reminder to add data and Workshop II in the middle of collection period to keep motivation high • final collection round and feedback on collection process at the end of collection period • production of touring exhibition • several presentations of results in exhibition and in front of the media, majors and planners
Monitoring plan and indicators	SC-3; Number of local associations involved SC-5; Number of immigrants actively engaged in the project SC-1; Number of citizens engagement activities and participants HC-7; Number of people trained in IT
Capital involved	Social, Human, Natural capitals
Main stakeholders involved and their roles and contribution	Municipalities, stakeholders: municipalities and other stakeholder help to contact interested residents and migrants Agency for refugee issues
Beneficiaries	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Migrants who were not able to communicate their experiences with their local natural and cultural heritage due to language barriers or lack of confidence • Citizens who want to get active in the fight against climate change and don't know where to get started in their local territory • participating municipalities
Formal partnership established (PPP, voluntary agreement, etc.)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Executive board and member communities have basically agreed to RURITAGE during annual general assembly (March 2019)
Timeframe	June 2020 – November 2020
Indicative costs	€ 4,000
Indicative funding sources	RURITAGE Geo-N additional co-financing
Sustainability of the action	In case of a successful event, we would like to encourage more municipalities in our territory to find volunteers, which repeat the mapping process in the future. We could still provide the digital resources, but the leadership would be transferred to the municipalities.

Code of the action	R3.4
Title of the action	Educational material for language skills supporting migrants' understanding of natural and cultural heritage

Relevant SIA or SIAs	Migration; Landscape
Relevant Heritage	Tangible – Nature Intangible – Social Practices, Rituals and Festive Events Intangible – Knowledge and Practices
Reference RM Action/s (code and name)	RM6-1; Developing integration and information programs for migrants and citizens. RM3-6; Social innovation ideas RM5-2; Capacity building activities: Training to migrants and residents related with organic farming, arts, built heritage restoration, traditional crafts and trades, etc. RM19-2; Promote the awareness of the value of territorial heritage and its potential as a driver of local development. RM19-3; Initiatives for the enhancement and protection of the historical, cultural, natural and local heritage
Useful lesson/s Learned (code and name)	LL04; Build sense of belonging, individual and community self-confidence and increased autonomy through CNH. LL15; Identify heritage resources (formal and informal), foster a better understanding of the tangible and intangible values of natural and cultural heritage and create a recognized value as a driver for local development. LL08; Create synergies and foster a collaborative approach with other organizations, programs or local activities and attractors of the territory to increase impact of the actions.
Responsible persons	Dr. Jutta Weber (Geo-N), Dr. Marie-Luise Frey (UNESCO WHS Messel Pit),
Relevant RM/KFP involved	RM3; Agro-food production in Apulia (Italy) RM5; Migrants hospitality and integration in Asti Province (Italy) RM6; Boosting migrant integration with nature in Lesvos Island (Greece) RM9; Teaching culture for learning resilience in Crete (Greece)
Brief description of the action	Creation of didactic materials (ABC-card games, posters, flyers) for all ages. Making these materials available for our municipalities and rangers for integration work as well as for cooperation with partners like UNESCO WHS Messel Pit.
Objective and target of the action (by the end of the project)	Improvement of language skills through the application of the developed education material. Getting to know the geological, cultural, natural and historical heritage of the Geo-N to support the identification with the region. Getting in contact with inhabitants and typical places of the Geo-N.
Specific activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • concept of ABC Card game • layout of ABC Card game • production of Card game • editorial creation of information material to the subject “forest, meadow, water” • layout of CNH information posters • production of CNH information posters • development and production of additional education material • media presentation during special event
Monitoring plan and indicators	SC-1; Number of citizens engagement activities and participants CC-6; Number of actions and cultural events produced by citizens at local level (n. and n. of people reached) SC-3; Number of local associations involved
Capital involved	Cultural and Social capitals
Main stakeholders involved and their roles and contribution	UNESCO WHS Messel Pit: co-development of educational material and training facilities. Municipalities of Geo-N: support contact with local migration associations. Local migrant aid associations: establish contact with migrants and advise on what needs exist.
Beneficiaries	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Residents and migrants • Participating municipalities • UNESCO World Heritage Site Messel Pit
Formal partnership established (PPP, voluntary agreement, etc.)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Executive board and member communities have basically agreed to RURITAGE during annual general assembly (March 2019). • Support agreement of UNESCO WHS Messel Pit has been already signed

Timeframe	Production of ABC Card Game 2020/2021. Creating and production of information material and posters starting from 2020.
Indicative costs	€ 19,500
Indicative funding sources	RURITAGE UNESCO WHS Messel Pit Geo-N: additional co-financing. supplementary logistic facilities by sponsors (transport, logistics)
Sustainability of the action	We develop educational material which gives rise to communicate about the cultural and natural heritage in the Geo-N region. The special form of a face-to-face card game dealing with CNH aspects provides possibilities to train general language skills as well as phonetics. The card game gives reason to talk and is designed for a multi-generational approach. Both card games and additional posters will be used by Geo-N rangers, Geopark-on-site guides and interested municipalities or their migrant aid associations, respectively. We therefore plan special short trainings to apply the material for these groups of multipliers.

Code of the action	R3.5
Title of the action	Author reading and family events at visitor centre of UNESCO World Heritage Site Messel Pit
Relevant SIA or SIAs	Migration; Landscape; Arts & Festival
Intangible – Knowledge and Practices	Tangible – Nature Intangible – Oral traditions Intangible – Knowledge and Practices
Reference RM Action/s (code and name)	RM6-1; Developing integration and information programs for migrants and citizens. RM6-2; Educational programmes and guided tours, specifically tailored for migrants to make them aware of the CNH of the territory. RM3-6; Social innovation ideas.
Useful lesson/s Learned (code and name)	LL04; Build sense of belonging, individual and community self-confidence and increased autonomy through CNH. LL08; Create synergies and foster a collaborative approach with other organizations, programs or local activities and attractors of the territory to increase impact of the actions. LL15; Identify heritage resources (formal and informal), foster a better understanding of the tangible and intangible values of natural and cultural heritage and create a recognized value as a driver for local development. LL18; Implementation of participatory approach and involvement of local people, including private owners, from early stage.
Responsible person	Dr. Jutta Weber (Geo-N), Dr. Marie-Luise Frey (UNESCO WHS Messel Pit)
Relevant RM/KFP involved	RM6; Boosting migrant integration with nature in Lesbos Island (Greece) RM3; Agro-food production in Apulia (Italy)
Brief description of the action	UNESCO WHS Messel Pit and Geo-N will organize author lectures for migrant families, who have found a new home in Hesse, Germany, to bring them in contact with local families. Local, regional, national as well as international authors present their books and read stories from different cultural environments all over the world. The programme also involves local literature concerning legends, myths and fairy tales. This facilitates understanding foreign people, other ways of life and enhances tolerance. At the same time this action gives the opportunity for residents to exchange ideas with migrants. The event also includes a guided tour to the UNESCO WHS Messel Pit.
Objective and target of the action (by the end of the project)	The main objective is to use literature as a medium to bring people from all over the world into contact. The event rises arouses interest for local cultural and natural heritage and the German language. By participating in a guided tour, the guests become familiar with the geological heritage of the Geo-N.
Specific activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • concept development • scheduling

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • define and invite authors • public relation work • event planning • addressing the target groups • organize catering • invite and inform media • event realization • debriefing
Monitoring plan and indicators	<p>SC-1; Number of citizens engagement activities and participants</p> <p>SC-5; Number of immigrants actively engaged in the project and participating to the hub</p> <p>CC-6; Number of actions and cultural events produced by citizens at local level (n. and n. of people reached)</p>
Capital involved	Cultural, Social, Human capitals
Main stakeholders involved and their roles and contribution	<p>UNESCO WHS Messel Pit: the WHS provides the location for the author reading events and supports public relation work for the events which will be part of the WHS programme.</p> <p>Authors</p>
Beneficiaries	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • resident and migrant families • UNESCO WHS Messel Pit • authors get possibility to present new literature
Formal partnership established (PPP, voluntary agreement, etc.)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • support agreement of UNESCO World Heritage Site Messel Pit • each invited author will get a contract
Timeframe	First author readings in autumn 2020, afterwards five reading and family events per year, 2022 three events planned.
Indicative costs	€ 14,500
Indicative funding sources	<p>RURITAGE</p> <p>UNESCO WHS Messel Pit</p> <p>Geo-N: additional co-financing.</p> <p>supplementary logistic facilities (transport, logistics)</p>
Sustainability of the action	This action combines integrating literature arts with local CNH knowledge and also anchors the world heritage site as meeting and exchange place of different global cultures within the Geo-N region. We tested the concept in 2019 with success, so WHS Messel Pit and Geo-N naturally agreed to further development during RURITAGE and continuation of the action after termination the project.

Code of the action	R3.6
Title of the action	Increasing the awareness of cultural and natural heritage by cultural landscape interpretation
Relevant SIA or SIAs	Landscape; Migration
Relevant Heritage	<p>Tangible – Nature</p> <p>Intangible – Knowledge and Practices</p>
Reference RM Action/s (code and name)	<p>RM11-1; Develop a participative process for the recognition and the evaluation of the cultural and natural heritage features, both tangible and intangible. features</p> <p>RM2-3; Create a set of guided tours or organized travels, tailored for different targets .</p> <p>RM8-4; Enhance the narrative of the place and promote the discovering of the territory through history: guided tours, thematic excursions, games, re-enactment.</p> <p>RM 19-2; Promote the awareness of the value of territorial heritage and its potential as a driver of local development.</p>
Useful lesson/s Learned (code and name)	<p>LL04; Build sense of belonging, individual and community self-confidence and increased autonomy through CNH.</p> <p>LL15; Identify heritage resources (formal and informal), foster a better</p>

	<p>understanding of the tangible and intangible values of natural and cultural heritage and create a recognized value as a driver for local development.</p> <p>LL18; Implementation of participatory approach and involvement of local people, including private owners, from early stage.</p> <p>LL08; Create synergies and foster a collaborative approach with other organizations, programmes or local activities and attractors of the territory to increase impact of the actions.</p> <p>LL25; Take advantage from traditional events and make the typical characteristics of the area (a site, food & wine, handcraft, traditions) a tourist attraction.</p>
Responsible persons	Dr. Jutta Weber (Geo-N), Manuel Bruckdorfer (Geo-N), Jochen Babist (Geo-N)
Relevant RM/KFP involved	RM2; Maria Ut-Mary's way (Romania) RM8; The Living Village of the Middle Age, Visegrad (Hungary) RM11; A CNH-led approach in Austrått manorial landscape (Norway) additional RM19; Ecomuseum (Alpi Apuane, Italy)
Brief description of the action	Besides the ranger programmes, the Geo-N network comprises many voluntary groups engaged with documentation, preservation and teaching cultural and natural heritage at the local base. All these groups already "live" the heritage cycle in the sense of Thurley 2005 (understanding – valuing – caring – enjoying). The described action therefore involves advanced trainings for rangers, the geopark-on-site teams, volunteers as well as the development of local guided tours for visitors, residents and migrants based on the concept of cultural landscape interpretation. These activities will be complemented by "hands-on" workshops dealing with special aspects of the historical/cultural landscape as beekeeping, a photographic landscape expedition and experimental historical mining (e. g. charcoal burning and building a historic smeltery).
Objective and target of the action (by the end of the project)	This action focuses on strengthening the awareness that our landscape is vulnerable in its cultural functions. Besides the touristic efforts, Geo-N now tries to implement a broader understanding of landscape evolution to increase this knowledge about the direct living environment for both residents and new inhabitants. We thus hope to encourage more people to take care and enjoy the cultural and natural heritage of the region at the local base according the motto "Only what you know let you feel home, only what you understand you will appreciate, only what you enjoy together will connect you with others and only if you learn to know each other, you lose fears."
Specific activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Discuss almost unknown but specific phenomena and themes of landscape environment (which are particularly threatened and what should be done to minimize the threat?) with geopark-on-site teams Felsenmeer, Fischbachtal, the municipality of Fürth and the Historical Mining Association Odenwald. • Detailed planning of guided ranger tours and hands-on actions for each threatened CNH element, bringing together Geo-N, rangers, the abovementioned geopark-on-site guides and volunteers • Public relation work advertising the events • Realize the heritage cycle events: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Photographic landscape expedition (Fischbachtal), ○ Charcoal burning at Wegscheide (Fürth), ○ Building and driving a historical bloomery furnace (iron smeltery) in Michelstadt-Rehbach, ○ beekeeping-workshops at Felsenmeer Information Centre). • Plan & realize additional and further heritage cycle events based on the existing activities and specific hands-on activities of the Rangers • Plan and realize a post-event advanced training for rangers, Geopark-on-site teams and other multipliers on methods, realization and results of the projects.
Monitoring plan and indicators	CC-6; Number of actions and cultural events produced by citizens at local level (n. and n. of people reached). SC-1; Number of citizens engagement activities and participants. SC-3; Number of local associations involved.
Capital involved	Cultural, Social capitals

<p>Main stakeholders involved and their roles and contribution</p>	<p>Rangers: Rangers get involved in the action as regional experts of cultural and natural heritage of the area. This will facilitate the choice of abovementioned specific landscape phenomena to be interpreted.</p> <p>Geopark on site-guides Felsenmeer and Fischbachtal: These two on site-guide teams provide voluntary support organizing the specific guided tours and “hands-on” workshops. Additionally, the Felsenmeer geopark-on-site team involves beekeepers, who will carry out the beekeeping-workshop with their own expertise.</p> <p>AG Altbergbau Odenwald (Historical Mining Association): This voluntary group carries out historical mining research and cultural landscape mapping in cooperation with the Hesse Department of Archeological Monument Conservation and therefore will act as multiplier especially for cultural heritage (e. g. planned activities at visitor mine “Marie” in Weinheim, building an historical bloomery furnace in Michelstadt-Rehbach etc.).</p> <p>Felsenmeer Information Centre (“Ocean of Rocks”): This information centre will provide environment and logistic support and knowledge for the planned beekeeping-workshop.</p> <p>Municipality of Fürth: The municipality of Fürth supports the experimental charcoal burning near Wegscheide, which will be performed by the voluntary group “NaturAgendten”.</p>
<p>Beneficiaries</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Residents and migrants in participating municipalities • Supporting information facilities and voluntary groups – public relation work will communicate their commitment to CNH to a broader public • Generating members for voluntary and organized preservation projects will enhance engagement for caring the CNH in the whole area of Geo-N.
<p>Formal partnership established (PPP, voluntary agreement, etc.)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rangers are linked to the Geopark by formal partnerships as freelancers. • Support agreement of Felsenmeer Information Centre • Support agreement of Felsenmeer Geopark-on-site team concerning the beekeeping-workshop (business model workshop, 18.11.2019). • Support agreement of Geopark-on-site team Fischbachtal (business model workshop, 18.11.2019). • The municipality of Fürth is member of the Geopark association. Executive board and member communities have basically agreed to RURITAGE during annual general assemblage (13.3.2019). • Support agreement of the historical mining association to engage in CNH-related events.
<p>Timeframe</p>	<p>The first four actions will be carried out already in 2020: Beekeeping-Workshop (April-October 2020), Photographic landscape expedition Fischbachtal (June 2020), Charcoal burning (July or August, depends on weather and soil humidity in the forest) and Bloomery Furnace (August 2020). In during 2020, continued CNH events for the next two years (2021/22) will be planned in detail.</p>
<p>Indicative costs</p>	<p>€ 17,000</p>
<p>Indicative funding sources</p>	<p>RURITAGE Supplementary logistic facilities (transport, booth material) Charcoal burning, financial support geopark budget Additional co-financing by geopark budget, financial capacities of the stakeholders.</p>
<p>Sustainability of the action</p>	<p>The precious cultural and natural heritage of the Geo-N area is manifested in a particular diversified landscape. This cultural landscape is threatened by modern land-use as, for example, growth of settlements or forestry with heavy machines. The action should make both residents and migrants aware of the vulnerability of the CNH and engage them to develop methods to keep and care for the specific elements of the landscape. Whereas until now, Geo-N has focused on touristic aspect in guided tours predominantly, this action should especially integrate the idea of the heritage cycle by landscape interpretation and experimental features / working projects. Once established, we think this idea will (supported by the Geo-N staff) be continued by all participating groups, institutions and municipalities, because it combines individual knowledge acquisition, knowledge transfer and visible effects and results in the landscape.</p>

Code of the action	R3.7
Title of the action	Local and new inhabitants are an active part in preserving Orchard meadows and old Fruit varieties.
Relevant SIA or SIAs	Migration; Landscape
Relevant Heritage	Tangible – Nature Intangible – Knowledge and Practices
Reference RM Action/s (code and name)	RM6-1; Developing integration and information programmes for migrants and citizens RM6-2; Educational programmes and guided tours, specifically tailored for migrants to make them aware of the CNH of the territory. RM19-2; Promote the awareness of the value of territorial heritage and its potential as a driver of local development. RM19-3; Initiatives for the enhancement and protection of the historical, cultural, natural and local heritage
Useful lesson/s Learned (code and name)	LL08; Create synergies and foster a collaborative approach with other organizations, programmes or local activities and attractors of the territory to increase impact of the actions. LL29; Recover and put in value the traditional skills and agricultural and farming methods LL31; Improve resilience of natural and cultural environments against natural hazards
Responsible person	Dr. Jutta Weber (Geo-N), Roland Mayer (Geo-N)
Relevant RM/KFP involved	RM6; Boosting migrant integration with nature in Lesvos Island (Greece) additional RM19; Ecomuseum (Alpi Apuane, Italy) Contact and exchange with the additional Replicator Styrian Eisenwurzen UNESCO Global Geopark (this additional Replicator is specialized within fruit trees)
Brief description of the action	Orchard meadows are a historical landscape type of the Geo-N. Their protection is an important contribution to the preservation of the cultural landscape. The aim of the project is the protection, retrieval and planting of historical varieties. Many of the existing orchards require extensive maintenance measures in order to maintain them. Based on this experience, we implement new trainings for volunteers and migrants to carry out tree care measures for communities. The measures also take place within the framework of public events in which both local inhabitants and migrants and their families can participate both in the preparation and the event.
Objective and target of the action (by the end of the project)	The objective of this action is twofold: to increase the integration of migrants, and to increase the awareness of local community and newcomers on the importance of preserving this type of landscape and its biodiversity. Through this activity, inhibitions are reduced and participants come into contact with each other. They get to know the local nature and the use of the regional fruit products. These activities will also contribute to the protection of the CNH.
Specific activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • conception phase: scientific and picture research concerning old fruit varieties • contact cooperation partners and migrant groups • meeting with local representatives and municipalities • contact tree nurseries for specific Fruit tree species – grafting of scions will be done by them • design, layout and print of flyers and information panel • implementation phase: writing invitation document for the representatives of the municipalities • coordinate event date and press • organize inauguration • buy trees for event and planting season in autumn, respectively • organizing planting equipment • realizing “Fruit of the Year” event • preparing tree trimming courses • contact cooperation partners, trainers and migrant groups • information meeting for interested persons and media • realization trimming course

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • final event and handover of certificates • debriefing
Monitoring plan and indicators	<p>SC-1; Number of citizens engagement activities and participants</p> <p>SC-3; Number of local associations involved</p> <p>SC-5; Number of immigrants actively engaged in the project and participating to the hub</p> <p>CC-8; Number of people trained in traditional skills</p>
Capital involved	Cultural, Social capitals
Main stakeholders involved and their roles and contribution	<p>Municipalities: The communities provide contact to local migrant aid associations.</p> <p>Streuobstwiesenretter: advice on the selection of fruit varieties. They carry out training courses on tree planting and trimming.</p> <p>Local migrant aid associations: Establish contact with the families of the migrants and advise on what needs exist.</p>
Beneficiaries	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • residents and migrants • participating municipalities • Geo-N • tourists
Formal partnership established (PPP, voluntary agreement, etc.)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Executive board and member communities have basically agreed to RURITAGE during annual general assembly (March 2019). • support agreement of Streuobstwiesenretter association
Timeframe	Presentation “Fruit variety of the year” each April 2020-2022. Tree trimming course November 2020
Indicative costs	€ 14,250
Indicative funding sources	<p>RURITAGE</p> <p>Geo-N: additional co-financing. supplementary logistic facilities by sponsors (transport, logistics)</p> <p>Streuobstwiesenretter: personal capacity of experts in tree maintenance</p>
Sustainability of the action	<p>Orchard meadows are a characteristic, but highly threatened feature of the cultural landscape in the Geo-N region. They involve an important bio-ecological function between forest and open landscape and represent an archive for the biodiversity of fruit trees. The action enables both residents and migrants to value orchards as an element of cultural landscape (CNH) as well as a source of healthy regional products. Tree trimming and planting of new trees is essential for the preservation of orchards. Training the practical skills also means a benefit to the municipalities and their touristic efforts. We intend to increase the regeneration and usage of untended orchard meadows by initiating local projects with the municipalities, which will continue the idea. Participating migrants and their families can acquire further skills in active landscape conservation. This offers the possibility to bring their competences into the communities and to advance their integration.</p>

Code of the action	R3.8
Title of the action	Strengthening the bonds between migrants and residents through creative land art and forest artwork
Relevant SIA or SIAs	Migration; Arts & Festival; Landscape
Relevant Heritage	<p>Tangible – Nature</p> <p>Intangible – Social Practices, Rituals and Festive Events</p> <p>Intangible – Performing Arts</p> <p>Intangible – Knowledge and Practices</p>
Reference RM Action/s (code and name)	<p>RM5-2; Capacity building activities: training to migrants and residents related with arts.</p> <p>RM6-1; Developing integration and information programs for migrants and citizens.</p> <p>RM6-2; Educational programmes and guided tours, specifically tailored for migrants to make them aware of the CNH of the territory.</p> <p>RM7-2; Provide opportunities for all ages and abilities to experience, participate and</p>

	work in the arts within a predominantly rural context. RM8-3; Networking with other Festivals on the same topic: possibility of joint actions.
Useful lesson/s Learned (code and name)	LL15; Identify heritage resources (formal and informal), foster a better understanding of the tangible and intangible values of natural and cultural heritage and create a recognized value as a driver for local development. LL04; Build sense of belonging, individual and community self-confidence and increased autonomy through CNH. LL08; Create synergies and foster a collaborative approach with other organizations, programmes or local activities and attractors of the territory to increase impact of the actions.
Responsible persons	Ute Ritschel (International Forest Art Association), Dr. Jutta Weber (Geo-N)
Relevant RM/KFP involved	RM5; Migrants hospitality and integration in Asti Province (Italy) RM6; Boosting migrant integration with nature in Lesvos Island (Greece) RM7; Take Art: Sustainable Rural Arts Development (UK) RM8; The Living Village of the Middle Age, Visegrad (Hungary)
Brief description of the action	Both migrants and residents get involved in the concept of land art and forest art, respectively. We organize common events for migrant families and inhabitants to experience artistic work together with international land art/forest art experts (regularly and in the context of the International Forest Art Trail). We provide a mobile art caravan for activities especially developed for children and young people. It is also planned to have an exchange land art training and festival with RM6 (Lesvos).
Objective and target of the action (by the end of the project)	The possibility to express creative skills and to work together with international artists will create an open atmosphere to communicate beyond prejudices and to find commonalities. Experiencing that landart and forest art does not depend on derivation nor social standing will strengthen the bonds between local and migrant groups. Additionally, the medium forest art will enhance the awareness of cultural and natural heritage, since the experience of art is emotionally and philosophically connected with reflecting the surrounding landscape.
Specific activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Plan a public workshop program associated with the Forest Art Trail performance and (as a second) accompanying Landart activities (e.g. Global Nomadic Art Project 2021) • Develop a time schedule and prepare the landart exchange festival with RM6 • Define personnel resources for each event (International Forest Art Association / Geo-N) • Invite migrant and resident groups separately (to overcome language barriers) and also together (to promote inclusion and collaboration) to workshops and events • Invite and inform media to all events • Realize workshops in 2020/2021 • Realize exchange festival Lesvos – Geo-N • Prepare event documentation, publish a brochure/catalogue about the activities • Workshop on continuation of the public forest art actions with migrants and residents by cooperation of International Forest Art Association and Geo-N, financed by both partners and sponsors.
Monitoring plan and indicators	CC-1; Number of enterprises in the cultural sector SC-1; Number of citizens engagement activities and participants SC-5; Number of immigrants actively engaged in the project and participating to the hub SC-6; Number of projects addressing people with disabilities (n. of projects, and n. of people involved)
Capital involved	Cultural and Social capitals
Main stakeholders involved and their roles and contribution	International Forest Art Association: The International Forest Art Association, located in Darmstadt, is the main stakeholder of the action and provides the artist network and the aforementioned art caravan.
Beneficiaries	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Residents and migrants attending the workshops • International Forest Artists • Local inhabitants in general

Formal partnership established (PPP, voluntary agreement, etc.)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Formal partnerships with International Art Association
Timeframe	Landart and Forest Art Workshops will be planned for 2020/2021, the Lesvos exchange art festival will be scheduled in 2020.
Indicative costs	€ 20,500
Indicative funding sources	RURITAGE Geo-N : Supplementary logistic facilities Additional co-financing by Geo-N budget and partner (International Forest Art Association) as well as sponsors
Sustainability of the action	The frame of the presented concept consists of regular events as the “Forest Art Trail” in Darmstadt and the biannual “Global Nomadic Art Project”. The Forest Art Association and Geo-N have met several times to develop a new format of participation especially for migrant families coming together with local inhabitants (e.g. workshops, internships, art caravan). These offers will be accompanied by the regular, well-attended events, and therefore provide a maximum feeling of integration for the migrants as well as for the inhabitants. The action involves a planning workshop to ensure the continuity of the newly designed format for migrants after the termination of the RURITAGE Project.

Code of the action	R3.9
Title of the action	Migrant internships with International Forest Art Centre and international artists
Relevant SIA or SIAs	Migration; Arts & Festival; Landscape
Relevant Heritage	Intangible – Social Practices, Rituals and Festive Events Intangible – Knowledge and Practices Intangible – Performing Arts
Reference RM Action/s (code and name)	RM1-7; Foster training and employment: school workshops and internships. RM3-6; Social innovation ideas. RM5-2; Capacity building activities: training to migrants and residents related with arts. RM5-5; Internship for migrants in local businesses, farms, tourism related activities. RM7-1; To increase social capital and resilience by developing informal education resources.
Useful lesson/s Learned (code and name)	LL18; Implementation of participatory approach and involvement of local people, including private owners, from early stage. LL15; Identify heritage resources (formal and informal), foster a better understanding of the tangible and intangible values of natural and cultural heritage and create a recognized value as a driver for local development. LL21; Integration of vulnerable groups in local value chain. LL04; Build sense of belonging, individual and community self-confidence and increased autonomy through CNH. LL08; Create synergies and foster a collaborative approach with other organizations, programmes or local activities and attractors of the territory to increase impact of the actions. LL24: Long-term vision to build confidence among stakeholders and continuous communication to create long-lasting relationships.
Responsible person	Ute Ritschel (International Forest Art Association), Dr. Jutta Weber (Geo-N)
Relevant RM/KFP involved	RM1; Way of Saint James (Spain) RM3; Agro-food production in Apulia (Italy) RM5; Migrants hospitality and integration in Asti Province (Italy) RM7; Take Art: Sustainable Rural Arts Development (UK)
Brief description of the action	Offer regular internships to migrants who will create their own art piece in collaboration with international artists in residency.

Objective and target of the action (by the end of the project)	Creating an own art piece to refugees means reflecting their experiences of escape, their feelings about the country they now live in. On the other hand, working with international artists provides the possibility to get integrated in the artists' community in an equal way. Communicating with each other during the creative process gives rise to new ideas in land art and forest art. For migrants, the internship could present a social and economic perspective for further life.
Specific activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Contact local migrant organization for cooperation • Invite migrants and artists for the land art internship • Develop a time schedule, prepare and conduct administrative processes, if necessary • Realize the internships in 2020/2021/2022 (see also timeframe) • Documentation work during the creation process of art pieces • Organize art exhibitions at the Centre for Forest Art in Darmstadt • Invite and inform media and organize opening event • Find sponsors to continue the internship program after termination of RURITAGE
Monitoring plan and indicators	CC-1; Number of enterprises in the cultural sector SC-5; Number of immigrants actively engaged in the project and participating to the hub HC-3; Number of immigrants involved in educational-training programs HC-4; Number of internship for immigrants activated
Capital involved	Cultural, Social, Human capitals
Main stakeholders involved and their roles and contribution	International Forest Art Association: The International Forest Art Association, located in Darmstadt, is the main stakeholder of the action and provides the artist network and supervision as well as locality (International Forest Art Centre) for the migrant internships.
Beneficiaries	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • migrants attending the internship • International Artists • City inhabitants, migrants become part of the society
Formal partnership established (PPP, voluntary agreement, etc.)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Formal partnership with International Forest Art Association
Timeframe	Land art and Forest Art internships will be planned for 2020/2021 and 2022. One internship will be provided during the Forest Art Trail event 2020, another will be offered during the Global Nomadic Art Project 2021. Further possibilities will be proposed independent of these events throughout the years 2020, 2021 and spring 2022.
Indicative costs	€16,500
Indicative funding sources	RURITAGE Geo-N: Supplementary logistic facilities Additional co-financing by Geo-N budget and partner (International Forest Art Association) as well as sponsors.
Sustainability of the action	The common idea of migrant internships is a new developed action by the International Forest Art Association and Geo-N and has already been tested this year with success. The Association and Geo-N at this stage work on a co-financing concept by sponsors which will ensure the continuation of the internship programme after termination of funding by RURITAGE. The International Forest Art Association highly appreciates the new type of activities and the new target group.

8.3.2 Timeline for the implementation

Action No:	Action Name:	19	2020												2021												2022				
		December	January	February	March	April	May	June	July	August	September	October	November	December	January	February	March	April	May	June	July	August	September	October	November	December	January	February	March	April	May
		19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	41	42	43	44	45	46	47	48
1	Organizing a Mountainbiking Event with tech-courses and forest-teaching by rangers for migrants										E																				
2	Welcoming booths at Geopark-events																														
3	Utilizing GIS-Tools to map citizen's opinion and interaction with the natural and cultural heritage on a personal level and in regard to climate change induced vulnerability							W					E																		
4	Educational material for language skills supporting their understanding of natural and cultural heritage																														
5	Author reading and family events at visitor center of UNESCO World Heritage Site Messel Pit																														
6	Increasing the awareness of cultural and natural heritage by cultural landscape interpretation				W	W	W	W	W	W	W	W																			
7	Local and new inhabitants are an active part in preserving Orchard meadows and old Fruit varieties.				E							W	W	E			E													E	
8	Strengthening the bonds between migrants and residents through creative land art and forest art work									W/E													W			W					
9	Migrant internships with International Forest Art Centre and international artists												E											E							

W = workshop run E = event run

8.4 Risks for the implementation of the plan

Risk No.	Action/s involved	Description of the risk	Mitigation action proposed
RI1	R3.1, R3.2, R3.3, R3.8	Participation of migrants in the action is very low	Communication with multipliers such as Flüchtlingshilfe e.V. ("Help for refugees") well in advance and use local partners in the municipality to reach out for migrant groups that could not be reached with classical advertisement
RI2	R3.3	Availability is not given and technological knowledge about digital tools is very low, participants are not skilled enough to use them	Prepare very specific and detailed guidelines in printed forms and present example cases to participants. Use several meetings in between the active phase of the action to make sure everyone is on board with the tools and knows how to use them
RI3	R3.1	Participants struggle to ride bicycles and are very fearful when riding first time on a natural trail in the forest	Design a very easy practice parcours on a flat territory, where balance skills can be improved. Choose a natural trail with no mandatory objects to cross, so participants can always stop and walk.
RI4	R3.3, R3.8	Citizens get unmotivated during the process, hence they are not using the app often enough	Send them a weekly reminder with some interesting infographics of the progress itself. Give them a weekly task to accomplish while collecting data.
RI5	R3.1	The collaboration with our stakeholder Muemlingtalradler is not reliable and support for the event organization is very low	Make sure they understand what we ask them to deliver for the success of the action and put it down in a formal agreement. Do not overestimate the capacities and look for other partners that can also support the action
RI6	R3.2, R3.6	Provided information material is insufficient with respect to multi-lingual requests, it is not possible to communicate about aspects of CNH with migrants	Use debriefing meetings with booths' personnel after each event to define requirements and react by production of adequate material and conversation strategies (e. g. acquire translators)
RI7	R3.2	Selected events are not appropriate for welcoming booths due to less migrants visiting the presentation	Interviews with exhibitors, organizers etc. of regular local events to get information about the number of migrants visiting the event. Develop defined advertising material.
RI8	R3.2, R3.8	Migrants do not attend the offer	Use debriefing meetings with personnel after each event to train inclusive communication strategies
RI9	R3.6	Charcoal burning must not be realized because of extreme dryness	Find a new event date, use situation for guided tours about climate change and forestry
RI10	R3.6	Too many threatened CNH aspects/objects to deal with	Select specific items correlating with SDGs, build up thematic teams dealing with different themes (e. g. historic landscape, natural heritage etc.)
RI11	R3.6	Hands-on protective activities are too difficult to realize	Involve more stakeholders as HessenForst, the Department of monument protection, universities to get further expertise and training
RI12	R3.6	It is difficult to get residents interested in CNH aspects in the landscape	Besides the described activities, also use action 2 (welcoming booths) to promote the hands-on activities

RI13	R3.8, R3.9	Lack of exchange and communication due to language problems	Intensify collaboration with migrant aid associations, invite additional translators
RI14	R3.8, R3.9	Financing problems during contraction of artists	Provide additional financial support by generating sponsorships, crowdfunding etc. in cooperation with the involved stakeholder(s)
RI15	R3.8, R3.9	Too many people interested in workshops and internships	Create opportunities to offer regular internships and public workshops after termination of RURITAGE, find alternative concepts in other parts of the Geo-N region
RI16	R3.6, R3.8, R3.9	Migrants are not mobile	Organize public transport in collaboration with participating Geo-N municipalities
RI17	R3.9	Internship not completed	Discuss reasons, find individual solution with participant.
RI18	R3.9	Not able to find a time schedule for land art exchange event and training with RM6	Shift time of event to 2021

9. Negova Castle (KIBLA, KULTPROTUR) Heritage-led regeneration plan

9.1 Background information

Within RURITAGE project the Castle of Negova has been chosen to be the replicator in the SIA of Art & Festival. The castle is located in the village of Negova in the north eastern part of Slovenia. More precisely it is situated in the west part of the municipality of Gornja Radgona, in the Ščavnica valley and at the wine-growing area of the Radgona hills. It borders neighbouring Austria along the Mura River. The municipality measures around 75 km² and is part of the Pomurje statistical region. The municipality of Gornja Radgona covers 30 settlements, where approximately a total of 8,500 people live. The average age of people in Gornja Radgona is 44 years, which is slightly higher than the national average (42.6). Commonly, the municipality is known for its fairs, traditional viticulture and the sparkling wines. However, in the fair mala masa takes place each year in Negova but the numbers are not that high.

The Negova Castle and surrounding area is declared as a cultural monument of national importance. The castle has supposedly developed from the wooden shooting manor which was set here as early as the 11th or 12th century. It was first mentioned in 1425 as Vest Egaw. Negova Castle consists of three parts. The old castle originates from the 2nd half of the 14th century. The new castle, built in 1615 is the second part, and Pristava, which was used as an outbuilding, the third part. The total net floor area of all buildings is 4840 m². With its impressive size and given its history, the Negova Castle encompasses a complex of buildings representing a suitable site for visitors interested in local history, architecture and so on. Beyond that the buildings are well suited for business meetings, educational activities, events and organisation of celebrations and weddings. Since 2014, the Negova Castle has been the residence of the Photographic Federation of Slovenia which organises exhibitions of well-established Slovenian and foreign photographers within the project “Fotograd Negova”. The complex of buildings also includes a rich herbal park. The Manor House hosts a Tourist Information Centre.

The Rural Heritage Hub is located at the Negova Castle. At its location, inside the Castle and its buildings as outside in its courtyard several events are taking place throughout whole year, e.g. festivals, exhibitions, concerts, performances, workshops, literature readings, projections presentations, meetings, gatherings. There is also an herbs and spices garden and many gardens are set around the Negova Castle walls, where ecological farming brings local community together in offering organic domestic food and genuine traditional products.

Figure 28: Negova castel Rural Heritage Hub

9.1.1 The Reference SIA

ART & FESTIVAL FOR RURAL REGENERATION

In Gornja Radgona, both residents and visitors are offered various opportunities of cultural experiences. Recurring events run throughout the year and attract visitors from near and far: Fašenk (Carnival), Tradicionalno kresovanje z baklado (Traditional bonfire with torchlight parade, local and international fairs (Leopold's fair, Peter's fair, International fair of agriculture and food...), RAP – Radgona's summer nights, Jazzliebe - border-free Southeast Styrian Jazz Days, St. Martins day, and Medieval afternoons involving children.

The Negova Castle features exhibitions of internationally recognized photographers (in collaboration with FIAP - International Federation of Photographic Art) and art exhibitions. Concerts, workshops, performances and film screenings are also occasionally held at the castle, but not linked under the auspices of a joint event. Among the most important events at the Negova castle we highlight Prangerjada, organized every few years in collaboration with the tourism association Negova – Spodnji Ivanjci. This event is an important part of the cultural scene in the area. But the most promising event held in the Castel is the Festival of Love, that have already taken place at the Negova Castle between 2010 and 2012. Festival of Love was conceived as a travelling literary event, which includes performance, music, visual and other creative surpluses that literature is giving us with a special attention to children's program and interregional collaborations. For five years (2008-2012) it took place during a spring weekend, for the last three years only at Negova Castle. Visual and performance art, literature, music, theatre and dance, video and film screenings, on site installations, customised light set-ups were the most relevant experiences proposed.

In the framework of RURITAGE project we would to re-establish it and upgrade it, combining art with cultural and natural heritage of the area, promoting cooperation and local culture by capitalizing the past experiences of the Festival of Love and thus making Negova Castle the cultural node of the Gornja Radgona region. The outcome is for Negova Castle to become a social meeting place for locals which creates a sense of belonging and pride within the rural community, where arts and culture can be the binder and the trigger.

9.1.2 Other relevant SIAs

FOOD FOR RURAL REGENERATION

The hills around in Gornja Radgona are scattered with various fruit trees, e.g. apples, pears, peaches, apricots, cherries, fields and vineyards, on which some of most famous world class wines are produced. Gornja Radgona cellar is on the top with its production of sparkling wines through standard champagne and charmat procedures and also with its standard wines, where numerous winemakers compete on the European and world level getting most prestigious awards. The woods of Gornja Radgona on the other hand, are welcoming with richness of mushrooms and other fruits, while fields are covered with wheat, corn, oats, rye, potatoes and various vegetables, cabbage, buckwheat (Slovenian traditional plant), pepper, tomato etc. The location and its area offer many most delicious characteristic specialities, from food to drinks.

Herbalism is not only becoming more and more popular in Slovenia and Austria, it is also an important part of the local heritage of Negova. There is an herbs and spices garden just in front of the Negova Castle and many gardens are set around its walls. Its own herb garden is one of the most important 'spices' of the Negova Castle tradition.

To safeguard and acknowledge the knowledge of herbs, a specific event, called Herb Day was organised in 2019 as a one-day event to stimulate the interest in these traditional plants and in local food. Within the framework of RURITAGE project, domestic food and traditional products and knowledge will be promoted and better acknowledged by local community and visitors.

PILGRIMAGE FOR RURAL REGENERATION

Right next to the Negova Castle, once part of the castle itself, a church of St. Mary is located. The church is part of the Mary's pilgrimage route. As pilgrimage tourism is becoming increasingly important and popular in Gornja Radgona, especially in relation to sustainable tourism, this is an important heritage to safeguard. This not only means working on the connection of the site with other relevant attractions, but also to increase the accessibility of the territory. Actually, the Negova Castle and the entire area are not served by any means of sustainable transport and visitors (both residents and tourists) cannot access the castle without their own means of transport. Within the frame of the RURITAGE project, we aim at introducing and promoting new and more sustainable means of transport, thus stimulating also new ways of experiencing and travelling around our territory.

LANDSCAPE FOR RURAL REGENERATION

The landscape around Negova has been shaped by the communities for thousands of years. We want to enhance the local pride of the landscape within the community as well as promote it to visitors.

According to us, there are few places that can take pride with such beauty, especially coming from the natural springs around the river Mura. From the middle of a valley of Negova, the rivers Ščavnica and Pesnica flow the most of natural springs of mineral water are found. Natural mineral water springs have always been a constant and healthy source of refreshing drinking water for people who lived in the area. Natural mineral water was used in the household, for example in baking as a substitute for yeast.

The Negova Regional Park and the Negova Lake are protected as a regional park, and its surroundings are well known for their natural and cultural values. The Negova Lake is an important habitat for endangered species of animals and plants, such as water lily *Trapa natans*. The alga of the lake has traditionally been used as natural remedy.

As of today, there are some agro-tourism guesthouses around offering special lodging and delicious home food and drinks products and several activities, for example trekking, cycling, riding, rowing, swimming and forests discovery experiences.

9.1.3 The Replicator baseline

According to the Layman's report proposed by CARTIF we have a 48 % level of accomplishment, which gives us enough room for improvement.

Cultural Capital (CC) reflects the way people "know the world" and how they act within it, as well as their traditions and language. Although the number of cultural events at local level (CC-06) and the number of places in the tourist offer (CC-09) is high enough, there is still some room for improvement in using social media (CC-02 to CC-05) and training in traditional skills (CC-08)

Natural Capital (NC) connected with biodiversity and landscape is one of the key assets that rural destinations are traditionally taking advantage of. Figures show a good overall performance, but more development is needed in areas related to the type of ecosystem services (NC-01), area of designations (NC-02b) and share of renewable energy (NC-04).

Historic built heritage can play a key role in the heritage-led process if it is reused and maintained from a sustainability point of view. Overall performance in **Built Capital (BC)** is high, but there is still room for improvement by using RURITAGE digital tools (BC-02 & BC-03) and fostering public & shared transport services (BC-08 and BC-09).

Social capital (SC) reflects the connections among people and organizations or the social “glue” to make things, positive or negative, happen. Although the projects involving disadvantaged people, i.e. migrants, disabled, elderly, etc. is high (SC-05 to SC-07) there is still room for improvement involving more local associations and stakeholders (SC-02 and SC-03).

In RURITAGE, **Human Capital (HC)** is improved through practices that contribute to the health, training & education of the population. Overall performance is mid-low, so some improvements could be done in training for migrants (HC-03) and internships for students, training in IT and tourism and professional management (HC-06 to HC-08).

Financial Capital (FC) refers to the financial resources available to invest in community capacity-building. In RURITAGE, the financial capital is understood as a mean to achieve the growing of the other capitals. Main improvement area is related to year revenues per sector (FC-02), while other indicators show a good performance for the baseline stage.

At present, Negova Castle tourist offer is limited and it needs to be enhanced, even if the tourist offer currently foresees outdoor activities and thematic offers related to cultural heritage, history, natural landscape and local craft and arts. This is in line with the Kultprotur and Negova Castle’s goal concerning the promotion of local territory through history deeply connected with the cultural heritage. Kultprotur is already active in local craft productions involving at least 15 SMEs and is cooperating with local SMEs for promoting and selling their products.

Figure 29: R4 performance (baseline calculation)

© RURITAGE monitoring platform, using Grafana

9.1.4 The main challenges

Main challenges	
C1	Lack of access for rural communities
The Negova Castle and its surrounding areas are currently more or less inaccessible for visitors without their own means of transport. Public transport is very limited already in the town of Gornja Radgona, to Negova is taken only from Gornja Radgona, only 2 times per day on weekdays and is primarily intended for schoolchildren.	

This influences the attractiveness of the Castle and the entire area as well as the possibility for people to have access to cultural and art related events at the Castel.

C2 Poor role of the Negova Castle as a cultural hub

Despite the activities currently in place at the Negova Castle, its role as cultural hub and catalyst of different art related events within the area is not well structured yet. Making the Castle a real point of attraction and meeting place for artists and venue for art and culture related activities in the area could ease the access to art and local traditions for local people and visitors, having also direct impact on tourism sector that is now not enough developed.

C3 Lack of connectivity

At present, visitors of the Negova Castle don't have the access to a broadband communication system. This prevents further development and use of the Castle as venue for conferences and workshops, more modern IT-based exhibitions and a wide range of other activities and services based on the use of this technology.

C4 Lack of entrepreneurial skills

Actually, local producers and businesses are oriented to local markets and new skills need to be created for promoting better local products and traditions. Tourism sector is not well developed despite the richness of the area in terms of natural heritage, food and local traditions.

9.2 Overall objectives of the plan

The overall of objective is to promote the Negova Castle and its community as a regional node of culture reinforcing its identity as artistic hub at local level and within the artistic and cultural networks operating in the region and abroad.

Proposing various programmes, events and festivals at the castle could provide the opportunity to rediscover and promote local history and traditions and the landscape, stimulating local creativity. Making the Castle a stable cultural centre in the area can strengthen collaborations at local, regional, national and even international levels in the field of art, as well as between the and urban contexts.

Specific objectives

O1 Establish Negova Castle as a permanent site of culture

Improving artistic programmes for making the Negova Castle a permanent set for artistic and culture-related performances and events, thus making art more accessible to everybody.

Stimulating new collaborations and connection between the rural dimension of the arts and experiences in urban contexts, such as the nearest city of Maribor, with its reference sights and highly artistic programmes and festivals, cultural institutions, galleries, concert halls, theatre, opera and ballet could help including the Negova Castle and its territory in broader networks (especially in art & festival, local food, landscape). This will increase interest knowledge and pride of the area within the local community and outside recognition.

Linked with challenges

C2 Poor role of the Negova Castle as a cultural hub

C3 Lack of connectivity

O2 Improved accessibility and connectivity

Since one of the main barriers is the isolation of the Castle in terms of transport and IT accessibility, in the frame of the RURITAGE project we are searching for new, alternative solutions for making the castle more accessible in terms of sustainable transports and IT connections. This allows to connect better the Castle with other important places in the surroundings and to enable visitors, guests and residents to be easily connected to the internet and most relevant IT networks to organise their work and life in a smarter way.

Linked with challenges

C1 Lack of access for rural communities

C2 Poor role of the Negova Castle as a cultural hub

C3 Lack of connectivity

O3 Improving skills and knowledge for boosting an experiential tourism in the area

The aim is to improve entrepreneurial skills in the community of the Negova Castle. Through workshops, and learning events, we would support businesses and producers to better define and emphasize their business which is related to local CN Heritage and can benefit from cooperation with art and culture-related activities. We will foster collaborations in sharing knowledge and experiences to show new job opportunities related with promotion of local products and skills.

Linked with challenges

C2 Poor role of the Negova Castle as a cultural hub

C4 Lack of entrepreneurial skills

O4 Increase the access of local community to art and local traditions

The aim is to give also to local people new possibilities to enjoy and to use art, to appreciate local crafts and promote their activities, to share the knowledge about local food production and get new knowledge in preparing it, in order to stimulate the sense of belonging and to find new leisure opportunities

Linked with challenges

C2 Poor role of the Negova Castle as a cultural hub

9.3 Operational programme for the implementation of the plan

No	Action	SIA	Challenge(s)	Objective(s)
R4.1	Making Negova Castle accessible and connectable	Pilgrimage, Landscape	C1, C2, C3	O1, O2, O4
R4.2	Festival of Love: Days of Summer	Art&Festival, Local food	C2, C3	O1, O4
R4.3	Festival of Love: Spring and Autumn Day / The Herb Day	Art&Festival, Local food	C2, C3	O1, O3, O4
R4.4	Festival of Love: Autumn day / Medieval day	Art&Festival, Local food	C2, C3	O1, O4
R4.5	Building new skills and knowledge about rural creativity	Art&festival, Local food, Pilgrimage, Landscape	C2, C4	O3, O4

9.3.1 The actions in detail

Code of the action	R4.1
Title of the action	Making Negova Castle accessible and connectable
Relevant SIA or SIAs	Landscape, Pilgrimage
Relevant Heritage	Tangible – Built, Intangible – Knowledge and Practices Digital
Reference RM Action/s (code and name)	RM2.1 improve services: eco-mobility, WI-Fi connection, tourism services, signals, maps, radio
Useful lesson/s Learned (code and name)	LL07. Create 'tourist pack and experiences' based on the different clusters (culture, food & wine, nature, religion, etc.) and sell combined packages, including transport LL08. Create synergies and foster a collaborative approach with other organizations, programmes or local activities (i.e. festivals, arts, food, etc.) and attractors of the territory to increase impact of the actions LL11. Develop and improve transportation to make places accessible and to facilitate the launch of new touristic destinations LL13. Ensure, at least, standard quality internet connection and mobile coverage LL16. Foster and promote sustainable tourism LL23. Involvement of private and third sector in cultural heritage in order to optimize

	<p>business model, answer to social needs and effectively manage heritageLL28. Promote access to all ages and abilities and ensure fruition of cultural resources to all, including transport and online information provision</p> <p>LL23. Involvement of private and third sector in cultural heritage in order to optimize business model, answer to social needs and effectively manage heritage</p>
Responsible person	Tatjana Kotnik Karba (Kultprotur)
Relevant RM/KFP involved	RM2 - Maria Ut-Mary's way
Brief description of the action	<p>With this action we will encourage other means of transport trying to make the castle more accessible to visitors, who are tourists but also local inhabitants. In the frame of the RURITAGE project we are introducing 2, new, more sustainable means of transport: recycled bicycle sharing system, with 1 renting station at the Negova castle (16 bicycles provided by RECIKEL, the first sustainable, green and responsible bike-sharing service in Pomurje region), and electric bike sharing system with 1 of the charging station at the castle and setting up a broadband communication system in the Negova Castle.</p> <p>The two systems can easily connect the castle with the stations in Gornja Radgona (Youth centre Gornja Radgona, Gornja Radgona Tourist information centre, Dom penine) and the one in Cogetinci (Firbas Holiday Farm, where one renting and charging station is already established). This will make it easier for residents, visitors and tourists to move between points of interest in the area.</p> <p>We are still discussing with the stakeholders about the possibility to prepare a tourist pack (renting bike, lunch and sightseeing), joint brochures, maps, promotional film and general promotion, which is the secondary aim of this activity.</p> <p>At present, at the Negova Castle visitors do not have access to a broadband communication system. In the frame of the RURITAGE project we are also setting up a broadband communication system in the Negova Castle, thus ensuring guests, visitors, residents, artists and local community to freely access and to organise their work also through the ICT. This will also open the doors to the conference tourism, as well as more modern exhibitions and performances.</p>
Objective and target of the action (by the end of the project)	<p>With this action we would like to make the castle more accessible for the community and for its visitors. Moreover, we want to promote reduction of waste, reuse, sustainable mobility and green tourism.</p> <p>Beyond that, we want to connect the castle to other networks and straighten the ties with other relevant partners in the field of art and tourism in the neighbourhood. This also takes the form of a joint promotion and of a new tourist package that will include both sightseeing, local food and bike rentals.</p> <p>Target:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> No. of rented bicycles per week: 10 in the first year (in good weather conditions).
Specific activities	<p>RECIKEL bike-sharing service:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> To prepare all the needed documentation for renting bikes (Kultprotur have to prepare the documents in line with GDPR, that customers will fulfil and sign by renting) Event planning meeting for the official launch of the new service (part of a Launch event of the implementation phase) Meeting with logistic partners for food and beverages, choosing and hiring the caterer Preparation and printing of invitations, press releases and other informational material Inviting media representatives, stakeholder and general public Final meeting and organisation of logistic Venue preparation (The Negova Castle) Realisation <p>E-bike sharing service:</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Meeting with Radgonske gorice d.d. to finalise the agreement (to determinate who of the two partners is responsible for maintaining e-bikes and who will cover the cost of their maintenance if the rental income will not be sufficient) • Obtaining offers from different bidders for electric bikes and charging stations • Meeting with Radgonske gorice d.d. and Farm Holliday Firbas to further discuss about the possibility of preparation of a tourist pack (renting bike, lunch and sightseeing), joint brochures, maps, promotional film, etc., final selection of advertising methods and dividing the tasks, responsibilities • Meeting with Radgonske gorice d.d. and Farm Holliday Firbas for fine-tuning the last details about tourist pack, advertisement, defining the location and other frames of the public presentation of a new product • Preparation of a new tourist pack with designing and producing invitations, posters, brochures, maps and other materials, agreed on previous meetings with Radgonske gorice d.d. and Holiday Farm Firbas • Meeting with Radgonske gorice - selecting the bidder for e-bikes and charging stations, final defining the prices for renting • Purchase of the electrical bikes and charging station • Inviting media representatives, stakeholders and general public • Final meeting and organisation of logistic • Venue preparations • Realisation <p>Broadband communication system in the castle:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Obtaining offers from different bidders • Selecting the bidder and signing the contract • Implementation
Monitoring plan and indicators	BC-9 Number of shared transport services (bike sharing, car sharing, etc.) BC-1 Number of hotspots provided
Capital involved	Human capital, Built capital, Social capital, Natural Capital
Main stakeholders involved and their roles and contribution	<p>Rastišče (NGO) contributed the initial concept for Recikel. Responsible for promotion and dissemination together with Kultprotur.</p> <p>Radgonske gorice d.d.: main donator for purchasing the electrical bicycles and charging stations.</p> <p>Holiday Farm Firbas – they already have their own electrical bicycles and a charging station, together with Radgonske gorice and Kultprotur, they will be involved in preparing a new tourist pack (renting bike, lunch and sightseeing), joint brochures, maps, promotional film and general promotion.</p> <p>Radgonske gorice d.d. will guarantee the funds for purchasing the electrical bikes.</p> <p>Municipality of Gornja Radgona will provide the missing funds for the implementation of this action and support the promotion.</p> <p>Municipality of Gornja Radgona will also cover all the cost regarding realisation of setting up a broadband communication system at the Negova Castle.</p>
Beneficiaries	Local population, tourists, artists, students, etc
Formal partnership established (PPP, voluntary agreement, etc.)	Voluntary agreement with NGO Rastišče, Radgonske gorice d.d., Holiday Farm Firbas, Municipality of Gornja Radgona
Timeframe	February 2020 - May 2021
Indicative costs	26.800,00 EUR
Indicative funding sources	600,00 EUR (RURITAGE – Launch event of the implementation phase - Kultprotur) 5000,00 EUR (Kultprotur) 14700,00 EUR (Radgonske gorice) 5000,00 EUR (Municipality of Gornja Radgona) 1500,00 EUR (Holiday Farm Firbas)
Sustainability of the action	If the action is successful, visitors will explore the surrounding area of Negova. Hopefully, locals will choose to use a bike instead of taking the car to the castle. The bikes are

	supposed to be maintained out of rental income, if those will not be enough at first, Kultprotur will cover the difference with its own resources. Wi-Fi access will be maintained by Kultprotur.
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Code of the action	R4.2
Title of the action	Festival of Love: Days of Summer
Relevant SIA or SIAs	Art & Festival, Local food
Relevant Heritage	Tangible – Natural, Tangible – Artefacts, Intangible – Social Practices Rituals and Festive Events, Intangible – Knowledge and Practices, Intangible – Oral traditions, Intangible – Performing arts, Intangible – Traditional craftsmanship, Digital
Reference RM Action/s (code and name)	Our own action
Useful lesson/s Learned (code and name)	LL05 Collaborative approaches to achieve innovative financing solutions and access to funding LL06 Create a ‘brand’ based on one of the cultural and natural resources and the added value created LL08. Create synergies and foster a collaborative approach with other organizations, programmes or local activities (i.e. festivals, arts, food, etc.) and attractors of the territory to increase impact of the actions LL24 Long-term vision to build confidence among stakeholders and continuous communication to create long-lasting relationships LL25. Take advantage from traditional events and make the typical characteristics of the area (food&wine, handcraft, traditions) a tourist attraction
Responsible person	Tatjana Kotnik Karba (Kultprotur), Aleksandra Kostič (Kibla)
Relevant RM/KFP involved	RM7 - Take Art
Brief description of the action	<p>Festival of Love is conceived as a series of events will be held throughout the year at the Negova Castle and its surrounding, indoor and outdoor, with connection with events held in Maribor (not on RURITAGE budget). Moreover, there will be a yearly Festival of Love week during the first week of June (5-7 in 2020 and 4-6 in 2021) leading and influencing all the other events. Specific theme days throughout the year within the Festival of Love are found under Actions R4.3, R4.4. Notably the first edition of the Medieval day will be hosted in the first edition of the Festival of love (see action R.4).</p> <p>The Festival’s program covers all generations and it strategically merges different art forms into the unique Castle experience to attract various audiences. The Festivals will start with an opening of the visual arts exhibition and continues with a concert. Within this opening day organizers will introduce RURITAGE approach to local community as local dissemination event foreseen in Task 3.5.</p> <p>Each evening ends with enlightened façade and projections on the Castle. Mornings are reserved for workshops and afternoons for discussions, performances and concerts. In parallel Food Events (food and beverages tastings and Sensory dinners) will be organized. They will be both innovative culinary events as well as promotional events of local products (e.g. Sensory dinner: Food will be presented in innovative way with use of sensory dishes and cutlery, with use of different multimedia tools like sound, video, performance; Penina fejest event: tasting of sparkling wines with a masterclass workshop led by the sommelier Jože Rozman gathering producers from all Slovenia).</p> <p>Special attention is being paid to the children’s program, with an aim of developing and encouraging their cultural and creative and artistic sensibility of young generations and their families.</p>

	For the year 2020 edition of the Festival we're discussing with our Role Model Take Art to host one of their programs as an international input and we'll continue our collaboration in 2021 and 2022.
Objective and target of the action (by the end of the project)	<p>Through the Festival of Love the castle will be better recognized as the cultural and creative and art & festival centre on local, regional, national and international level. Moreover, our objective is to make art and creativity more accessible to the local community, and to increase the interest of the population about art, and to get new people entrusted in art, and to give locals and visitors of all ages new opportunities to participate in art events or just to enjoy them, and to make art more accessible to the communities of Negova and its area. With the Festival also the visibility of the Negova Castle will rise, and the area will be more known and attractive for visitors.</p> <p>We are enriching the programme with food events promoting local food production and preparation and local producers and chefs collaborating with artists.</p> <p>Targets:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No. of visitors per year: at least 8000 visitors on the Festival of Love. • No. of events organized in the frame of the Festival of Love in each edition: at least 10 (concerts (3-4), performances (2-3), discussions (1-2), literature readings (1-2), projections (2), art & food events (1-2)). • No. of editions organized in the framework of the RURITAGE project: at least 2 yearly editions
Specific activities	<p>Each edition will foresee the following activities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • to set a plan (preparatory activity for the 1st edition) • to get in contact with stakeholders and local, national and international artist, producers, art centres, organizers (preparatory activity for the 1st edition) • defining the program framework (preparatory activity for the 1st edition) • selecting the program participants • preparation of promotional and advertising material • program realisation, dividing tasks and responsibilities • concluding agreements with performers and other providers • preparations of all the required legal documentation • to set artist-in-residence • organisation • preparation of the venue • implementation • analysing the results and the search for improvements for the next edition
Monitoring plan and indicators	<p>CC2 Increment in number of mentions of CNH in social media, media, press etc.</p> <p>CC5 Number of posts mentioning RURITAGE at the local level</p> <p>SC-1 Number of citizens engagement activities and participants</p> <p>SC-2 Number per type of stakeholders involved (according to the ones defined in D.3.1)</p> <p>SC-3 Number of local associations involved</p>
Capital involved	Cultural capital, Built capital, Social capital, Human capital, Financial capital
Main stakeholders involved and their roles and contribution	<p>Artists Saša Bezjak, Robert Jurak, Bojana Križanec: co-development of programme festival and art performances</p> <p>Tourism association Negova – Spodnji Ivanjci, Tourism association Majolka, Art association Gornja Radgona: direct involvement in the programme definition</p> <p>College of Hospitality and Tourism Maribor, High Culinary School Maribor: direct involvement in the programme definition of the food related events</p>
Beneficiaries	local citizens and artists, local restaurants, local SME's, visitors, tourists, children, families, wider audience
Formal partnership established (PPP, voluntary agreement, etc.)	There have been already discussions and round table with stakeholders. The exact type of agreement will be set during the implementation phase
Timeframe	<p>January 2019 – June 2020: first edition</p> <p>September 2020 – June 2021: second edition</p>

Indicative costs	33.500,00 EUR (for 2 editions)
Indicative funding sources	32.000,00 EUR (RURITAGE – Kibla) 1.500,00 EUR (RURITAGE – Kultprotur)
Sustainability of the action	Festivals can act as a magnet, attracting visitors. We are planning to carry out this festival also after the project duration in 2022 and beyond – we will try to find other ways of financing it, e.g. national and international and local funds, sponsors and donors, self-financing

Code of the action	R4.3
Title of the action	Festival of Love: Spring and Autumn Day / The Herb Day
Relevant SIA or SIAs	Art & Festival, Local Food
Relevant Heritage	Tangible – Natural, Intangible – Social Practices Rituals and Festive Events Intangible – Knowledge and Practices, Intangible – Oral traditions
Reference RM Action/s (code and name)	Our own action
Useful lesson/s Learned (code and name)	LL04 Build sense of belonging, individual and community self-confidence and increased autonomy through CNH LL 05 Collaborative approaches to achieve innovative financing solutions and access to funding LL17 Identify heritage resources (formal and informal), foster a better understanding of the tangible and intangible values of natural and cultural heritage and create a recognized value as a driver for local development LL18 Implementation of participatory approach and involvement of local people, including private owners, from early stage LL25 Take advantage from traditional events and make the typical characteristics of the area (a site, food & wine, handcraft, traditions) a tourist attraction
Responsible person	Tatjana Kotnik Karba (Kultprotur), Aleksandra Kostič (Kibla)
Relevant RM/KFP involved	RM3 - Dare Puglia
Brief description of the action	<p>The Herb day was already organised in 2019 as a one-day event. We engaged mainly local stakeholders, but some of them also were coming from different parts of Slovenia. Majority didn't get any financial stimulation for their involvement, but they could sell their products on The Herb day and, on the other hand, Kultprotur also offered them the possibility to sign the contract to sell their product in the tourist office in the castle throughout the year. Within this action we want to further increase the participation of producers and local people by introducing new activities and themes, thus stimulating interest and knowledge about traditions mainly related with food and herb production and use. Vulnerable groups are also involved in this action. A workshop for care receivers (people with disabilities) from VDC Gornja Radgona is planned, on which they will get to know more about the Herbs, their practical use and prepare signboards for herbs on the Herb garden on the castle's Herb garden. This workshop is one of the activities foreseen in Task 3.5.</p> <p>Local population, living in the Negova and its area will also be actively engaged in the programme with presentations of their products, workshops (on herbs, food products and cooking) and a concert.</p> <p>Workshops about foraging and using wild plants and herbs for culinary and healing, foraging in the area around the Negova Castle, preparing and tasting the food will be organised at each Herb Day. Also, a workshop will be set at the castle for preparing the traditional Prlekija cake (Prleška gibanica) and local food by local and invited chefs preparing the old recipes in a new way. Participants will be directly invited and also welcomed through the public call to reach more providers and herbal products makers. Stakeholders and media representatives will also be directly invited to each event.</p>

	The programme will be focused on showing traditional herbs and their usage for different occasions (as food, beverages, cosmetics, medicine, plant) as well as traditional food and cuisine
Objective and target of the action (by the end of the project)	<p>Our objective is to promote herbs and their usage to stimulate new opportunities in terms of knowledge and promotion of local resources and at the same time to enhance the local economy based on herbs production and selling and on the use of herbs for various purposes. We want to raise awareness about healthy food, inform about herbs and show several possibilities of their usage and treatment, increase herbal usage on daily basis, increase the overall interest in herbs, attract herb products makers and visitors, give locals and visitors of all ages new opportunities to get new knowledge about herbs and participate in organised events and workshops or just to enjoy the offer and the atmosphere. The Herb Day also promotes the activities at the Negova Castle, and it emphasises the visibility of the Castle and the area, which will be more known and attractive to visitors.</p> <p>Targets:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No of editions per year: 2 Herb Days per year (Spring and Autumn editions) • No. of editions within RURITAGE: 5. • No of visitors per each edition: at least 500 visitors at every Herb Day. • No. of visitors per year: 1.000 • Increased knowledge: good level of information about herbs and their usage and herbal products.
Specific activities	<p>Each edition will foresee the following activities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • set the plan (preparatory activity for the 1st edition) • contacting providers and engage them (preparatory activity for the 1st edition) • prepare the programme (preparatory activity for the 1st edition) • selection and hiring of lecturers and other contractors for workshops • preparation of advertising material and all the required documentation • promotion and dissemination • preparation of the venue • implementation • debriefing and search for potentially better solutions for the next edition
Monitoring plan and indicators	<p>CC-2 Increment in number of mentions of CNH in social media, media, press etc. BC-14 Number of fairs and tourism events per year related to the promotion of the area and related products SC-1 Number of citizens engagement activities and participants SC-3 Number of local associations involved SC-7 Number of disadvantaged people engaged</p>
Capital involved	Cultural capital, Natural capital, Social capital, Human capital
Main stakeholders involved and their roles and contribution	<p>Tourism Association Negova – Spodnji Ivanjci: direct involvement in event organisation and implementation (workshop) Tourism association Majolka: direct involvement in event organisation and implementation (workshop) VDC Gornja Radgona: direct involvement in the workshop for vulnerable groups</p>
Beneficiaries	local citizens, local food producers and restaurants, local SME's, visitors, tourists
Formal partnership established (PPP, voluntary agreement, etc.)	There have been already discussions and round table with stakeholders. The exact type of agreement will be set during the implementation phase.
Timeframe	January 2020 – April 2022
Indicative costs	26.000,00 EUR
Indicative funding sources	10.000,00 EUR (RURITAGE - Training related with the interested SIA (food) – Kibla) 16.000,00 EUR (RURITAGE - Kultprotur)
Sustainability of the action	The Herb day has been already run once in the past and the results were encouraging. We are planning to carry out this event also after the project duration in 2022 and beyond

	– we will try to find other ways of financing it, e.g. national and international and local funds, sponsors and donors, self-financing.
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Code of the action	R4.4
Title of the action	Festival of Love: Autumn day / Medieval day
Relevant SIA or SIAs	Art & Festival, Local food
Relevant Heritage	Tangible – Artefacts, Intangible – Social Practices Rituals and Festive Events, Intangible – Oral traditions, Intangible – Performing arts, Intangible – Traditional craftsmanship
Reference RM Action/s (code and name)	our own action
Useful lesson/s Learned (code and name)	LL04. Build sense of belonging, individual and community self-confidence and increased autonomy for promotion, safeguarding, management and well-being LL07. Create 'tourist pack and experiences' based on the different clusters (culture, food & wine, nature, religion, etc.) and sell combined packages, including transport LL08. Create synergies and foster a collaborative approach with other organizations, programmes or local activities (i.e. festivals, arts, food, etc.) and attractors of the territory to increase impact of the actions LL25. Take advantage from traditional events and make the typical characteristics of the area (food & wine, handcraft, traditions) a tourist attraction
Responsible person	Tatjana Kotnik Karba (Kultprotur), Aleksandra Kostič (Kibla)
Relevant RM/KFP involved	RM8 - Višegrad
Brief description of the action	<p>Medieval stories are already present on the Negova Castle - in cooperation with Tourism association Negova – Spodnji Ivanjci we organise annually The Castle Camp (Grajski tabor) for children, which traditionally ends with a Medieval afternoon. However, it is a micro-event with a very limited program that addresses a small number of target audiences. In the frame of the RURITAGE project we are upgrading and evolving this story, also on the basis of the know how/ experiences and networks of the Role Model from our main SIA, Art&festival, Višegrad. Indeed, we're discussing with RM8 to host one of their programs as an international input. An enriched and expanded program will address a wider target audience, raised the visibility of the castle and further contributed to the positioning of the castle as an international cultural center.</p> <p>The foreseen program consists of workshops, representations of medieval life, medieval dances, concerts of medieval music. Stakeholders and media representatives will also be directly invited to each event.</p> <p>The first edition of Medieval day (in 2020) will be held within the festival of Love: Days of summer, on the third day, but already in 2021 we are planning to organise a separate event, therefore we foresaw a separate action.</p>
Objective and target of the action (by the end of the project)	<p>Medieval day is one of the events, with which we are trying to make the castle recognized as the international cultural centre on local, regional, national and international level.</p> <p>Targets:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No. of visitors per event: 900. • No. of editions per year: 1 • No. of edition in the lifespan of the project: 2
Specific activities	<p>Each edition will foresee the following activities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • contacting providers and engage them (preparatory activity for the 1st edition) • to prepare the programme • selection and hiring of lecturers and other contractors (our Role Model Višegrad will participate with their program and overseeing and advising about its execution) • preparation of advertising material

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • promotion and dissemination (in conjunction with other Festival of Love related events) • preparation of the venue • implementation • debriefing and search for potentially better solutions
Monitoring plan and indicators	SC-1 Number of citizens engagement activities and participants SC-2 Number per type of stakeholder involved (according to the ones defined in D.3.1)
Capital involved	Cultural capital, Built capital, Social capital
Main stakeholders involved and their roles and contribution	Tourism Association Negova – Spodnji Ivanjci: direct involvement in the program
Beneficiaries	Municipality, local citizens, local restaurants, local SME's
Formal partnership established (PPP, voluntary agreement, etc.)	Tourism association Negova Spodnji Ivanjci: voluntary agreement.
Timeframe	January 2020 – September 2021
Indicative costs	10.000,00 EUR (4.000 in 2020 in conjunction with the budget for the Festival of Love: Days of summer; 6.000 in 2021 as an independent event)
Indicative funding sources	10.000,00 EUR (RURITAGE – Kultprotur)
Sustainability of the action	Festivals and events can act as magnets attracting visitors. As in the case of the other festivals and with the help from RM8 (Višegrad – their networks and experiences) we would like to make this event reoccurring.

Code of the action	R4.5
Title of the action	Building new skills and knowledge about rural creativity
Relevant SIA or SIAs	Art & Festival, Local food, Pilgrimage, Landscape
Relevant Heritage	Tangible – Natural, Tangible – Artefacts, Intangible – Social Practices Rituals and Festive Events, Intangible – Knowledge and Practices, Intangible – Performing arts, Intangible – Traditional craftsmanship, Digital
Reference RM Action/s (code and name)	Our own action
Useful lesson/s Learned (code and name)	LL04. Build sense of belonging, individual and community self-confidence and increased autonomy for promotion, safeguarding, management and well-being LL15. Identify heritage resources (formal and informal), foster a better understanding of the tangible and intangible values of natural and cultural heritage and create a recognized value as a driver for local development LL24. Long-term vision to build confidence among stakeholders and continuous communication to create long-lasting relationships LL15 Identify heritage resources (formal and informal), foster a better understanding of the tangible and intangible values of natural and cultural heritage and create a recognized value as a driver for local development LL29. Recover and put in value the traditional skills and agricultural and farming methods LL39. Get the trust of all land tenures and develop the common agreement that give benefits to all partners
Responsible person	Tatjana Kotnik Karba (Kultprotur), Aleksandra Kostič (Kibla)
Relevant RM/KFP involved	University of Plymouth

Brief description of the action	At the Negova Castle we are now running some workshops on different topics for children and adults, but we would like to make this range broader, offering new workshops for actual target groups but also for businesses, entrepreneurs, producers and artists that aspire to increase their knowledge and business. The aim is to involve broader spectre of moderators and speakers (individuals, institutions etc.) also by involving some RMs and KFPs (so far we identified UoP as main contributor). In 2020 we are planning to carry out 2 new workshops in cooperation with University of Maribor and Local development agency of Gornja Radgona, PORA on the topics of art-related tourism and to present local providers the opportunities to improve, upgrade and expand their core business.
Objective and target of the action (by the end of the project)	To increase knowledge and participation on art and culture related topics of local people and to increase skills of local entrepreneurs Target: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No. of participants attending the workshops per year: at least 40 participants attending the 2 workshops in 2020 on the Negova castle. • No. of workshops organized per year: at least 2. • No. of editions: 4. • Level of knowledge achieved on the topics touched by the workshops: good
Specific activities	Each edition will foresee the following activities: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • to analyse specific learning needs of the different target groups (preparatory activity for the 1st edition) • finding experts for the topics and engage them • preparation of the advertisement material and promotion • purchase and preparation of small catering (water, coffee, snacks) • preparation of the venue • implementation • debriefing
Monitoring plan and indicators	SC-1 Number of citizens engagement activities and participants SC-3 Number of local associations involved HC-7 Number of people trained in IT and tourism (in specific SIA)
Capital involved	Social capital, Financial capital, Human capital, Natural capital, Built capital
Main stakeholders involved and their roles and contribution	Local development agency PORA: direct participation in the organization and implementation of workshops. University of Maribor: direct participation in the organization and implementation of workshops.
Beneficiaries	Municipality, local citizens of different ages, local entrepreneurs, local artists, vulnerable groups
Formal partnership established (PPP, voluntary agreement, etc.)	There have been already discussions and round table with stakeholders. The exact type of agreement will be set during the implementation phase.
Timeframe	December 2020 – November 2021
Indicative costs	200,00 EUR
Indicative funding sources	100,00 EUR (Kultprotur) 100,00 EUR (Kibla)
Sustainability of the action	Investments in human and social capital are the crucial elements for further developments of the region. We foresee these workshops will be very popular therefore new editions will be foreseen.

9.3.2 Timeline for the implementation

Action No:	Action Name:	19	2020												2021												2022					
		December	January	February	March	April	May	June	July	August	September	October	November	December	January	February	March	April	May	June	July	August	September	October	November	December	January	February	March	April	May	
		19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	41	42	43	44	45	46	47	48	
1	Making Negova Castle accessible and connectable																															
	Recikel bike sharing service																															
	E-bike sharing service																															
	broadband communication system																															
2	Festival of Love: Days of Summer							E																								
3	Festival of Love: Spring and Autumn Day / The Herb Day																															
4	Festival of Love: Autumn day / Medieval day																															
5	Building new skills and knowledge about rural creativity																															

W = workshop run E = event run

9.4 Risks for the implementation of the plan

Risk No.	Action/s involved	Description of the risk	Mitigation action proposed
1	R4.1	Bicycle rental revenues does not cover the costs for their maintenance.	Kultprotur will provide funding for their maintenance.
2	R4.1 R4.2	The collaborations with our main stakeholders is not reliable	Try to motivate them again or in the worst-case scenario start searching for new/additional stakeholders
3	R4.2	Lack of human resources	Seek to involve stakeholders themselves.
4	R4.1 R4.2	Lack of funds – financial problems	Provide additional financial support by generating sponsorships, crowd-funding etc. in cooperation with the involved stakeholder(s)
5	R4.2 R4.3 R4.4 R4.5	Lack of interest and participation in workshops	Use social medias and local newspapers more efficiently to disseminate the information and promotion of the workshops through more channels. Targeting the people, that could be interested in the topic, invite them directly.
6	R4.2 R4.3 R4.4	Low number of visitors to the events	Use social medias and newspapers more efficiently to disseminate the information and promotion of the workshops through more channels

10. Appignano del Tronto (CoApp) Heritage-led regeneration plan

10.1 Background information

Appignano del Tronto is a village with 1728 inhabitants located in the south of Marche Region, in the Tronto River basin, at an altitude of about 194 m a.s.l. The territory is hilly, with several rivers and springs meeting in the Tronto river. The village is situated at about 20 km from the Adriatic Sea coast (west side) and about 35 km from the Sibillini Mountains. The vegetation is characterized by the prevalence of deciduous trees (oak, poplars in the most humid areas) while the most frequent crops are the vineyards and the olive trees.

The social and economic context of the area presents 7 fundamental characteristics: a) a trend towards depopulation that have been intensified due to earthquakes in 2016 and 2017; b) a trend towards deindustrialization that have been intensified due to European economic crisis from 2008 to 2013; c) an economic tissue of SME and Micro-companies (especially farms) that are mostly family businesses; d) an ageing population; e) a high unemployment rate that is 15% at Appignano del Tronto [Marche region 10,6% and Europe 7% in 2018]; f) a high poverty rate that is 10% of the local population [Marche region 8,8% and Europe 6,2% in 2018]; g) a lack of entrepreneurial skills. With regard to municipality, Appignano del Tronto has been governed by female mayors for the last 15 years. In Italy this is surely something very rare. For many years has been the only town in the province of Ascoli Piceno, and one of a few in our region, to be governed by a female mayor.

Concerning Natural and Cultural heritage the area is rich of tangible and intangible elements. Appignano del Tronto has a Medieval old town, six churches, three ruins of churches, traditional local foods, an active organic oil and cheese production, cultural events and festivals. About Natural Heritage the typical hilly landscape of Marche region and Grey-blue Badlands (Calanchi grigio-azzurri).

Appignano del Tronto Rural Heritage Hub (RHH) is located in a building that once was a nursery school. In the last few years, a part was renovated and used as an auditorium. This year, thanks to RURITAGE funds, we restored the other side that became our RHH. We have designed an open space, without barriers or chairs, to facilitate the exchange of opinions and to make it accessible to all.

There is a main room of about 50 square meters, equipped with video projector and sound system. There are no architectural barriers, every space is accessible for disabled people. Tables can be composed in different shapes to facilitate workshop, training, internal meetings, etc.

Figure 30: Appignano del Tronto Rural Heritage Hub

10.1.1 The Reference SIA

RESILIENCE FOR RURAL REGENERATION

Appignano del Tronto is a territory at high risk of earthquakes. In the last centuries the area has been seriously damaged after earthquakes in 1943, 1972, 1997 and 2009. A seismic crisis of central Italy started on 24th August 2016 (with an earthquake with a magnitude of 6.5 on 30th October 2016) caused several damages to the public and private heritage and to the viability. In Appignano del Tronto 200 buildings were condemned, two churches were closed, the town hall was damaged, and a big landslide caused by the earthquake blocked the main entrance to historic centre.

Perhaps even more importantly, the earthquake caused a psychological destabilization of the local people, children as well as adults. The feeling of uncertainty has come from a seismic sequence of four main shocks in a few months (magnitude 6.0 on 24th August 2016, magnitudes 5.4 and 5.9, 26th October 2016, magnitude 6.5 on 30th October 2016, 4 shocks of magnitude 5.4 on 18th January 2017). Moreover, on 18th of January 2017, an extraordinary snowfall and a week-long electrical blackout occurred.

After these unluckily events, inhabitants needed to recreate – not only tangible factors - but feelings. The psychological wellbeing of all people who experienced the tremendous earthquake is requiring and will require the use of essential resources. Community and individual resilience must be improved. Increasing the resilience of a territory means taking action to increase its ability to resist and react to natural disasters. Leveraging resilience in the case of social phenomena such as unemployment or poverty implies helping individual and collective subjects to better face life's adversities. In this perspective, the resilience approach adopted by Appignano del Tronto in the suit of the RURITAGE project wants to be inclusive and capable of working on strengthening the capacity of the territory and its community by acting on several fronts.

Figure 31: Appignano's church damaged by earthquake and private building damaged by earthquake

Through a holistic approach made of interventions through technological infrastructures, support to sustainable development and farmers through data monitoring, training activities aimed at citizens and professionals, actions are intended not only to strengthen the absorption capacity and to “restart” the community of Appignano del Tronto but also to transform a problem - the seismicity of the territory and the traumatic experience of the earthquake - into an opportunity to regenerate the territory.

The actions foreseen aim to increase resilience, directly or indirectly, in different meanings (R5.1, R5.2, R5.4, R5.5, R5.6, R5.10, R5.12).

10.1.2 Other relevant SIAs

LANDSCAPE FOR RURAL REGENERATION

The territory of Appignano is well known from the Middle Age for its hydrogeological vulnerability. Numerous landslides reshaped the historical centre during the years.

The Prickly “calanchi” (badlands) mark out the territory and threaten viability and buildings. These natural landscapes are recognised for their beauty, as they offer different in shapes and colours, depending on seasons. These generated from the action of weather conditions: sun, ice, rain and wind. The rainfall is currently changing. So, it is necessary to monitor the site in order to establish dangerous situations and save lives and buildings. The unique landscape needs to be valued and promoted because its beauty is incomparable. There is a centre of documentation of landslides and badlands whose activities need to be improved and increased. (R5.3, R5.4, R5.5, R5.6, R5.8, R5.9, R5.10, R5.12)

Figure 32: Appignano's badlands

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MIGRATION FOR RURAL REGENERATION

Figure 33: Appignano's monument for emigrates

Several migrants and refugees passed through Appignano del Tronto and the town is a big centre of emigration itself; lot of people left the cities because of the economic crisis in the last years. Several foreigners still lived in the town and so far, they are not included in any kind of integration programme, which could help them to better know the local territory and to establish relationships with the local community, the labour market and the overall social and economic life of the territory. Nevertheless, this can be considered as a powerful resource and through the RURITAGE action plan, they will be involved in different activities (specifically R5.3, R5.11).

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ART & FESTIVAL FOR RURAL REGENERATION

In Appignano del Tronto there are several cultural associations active on the territory: “Pro loco Appignano Del Tronto”, “Corpo Bandistico Città di Appignano Del Tronto”, “Centro studi Francesco D’Appignano”, the oratory “I discepoli di Emmaus” and the cultural association “Frammenti”. Most of them work in cooperation with the Municipality of Appignano del Tronto to organize social, cultural and artistic events, such as: the international festival of short movies, international conference “Francesco D’Appignano”, theatre courses for adults and children, the annual dinner “Riappignano” to gather people from Appignano who live somewhere else, popular games between quarters, rock, folk and symphonic music concerts.

A famous event is the “Processione dell’anno vecchio” which takes place on 31st December. It is a typical event in Appignano dating back to the end of the XVII century to celebrate the end of the last year and the beginning of the new one. Sacred and profane join in a singular and goliardic funeral procession composed of freakish characters in grotesque costumes which represents the months of the year.

Each event needs to be innovated, to be promoted and to improve in the contents in order to attract tourists and visitors and contribute to support the territory. Through the action plan the aim is to internationalize Appignano Rural Festival and to network cultural events with others local and neighbours’ activities (R5.7, R5.8).

Figure 34: Rural Art Festival of Appignano and Funeral of the old year

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FOOD FOR RURAL REGENERATION

The village is rich of agricultural products of high quality such as olive oil, wine, saffron, DOP olive “Ascolana Tenera”, stuffed olive from Ascoli Piceno, cheeses, sweet and salted typical baked products such as “piconi” and “pizza al formaggio”, which are special cheese breads, “maritozzi”, which are sweet buns, Eastern anise donuts, “frsting”, a typical Christmas cake and cured meat products.

Figure 35: Exhibition of typical local products

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However, a connection between producers and consumers does not exist and these food products are not promoted. Innovations, sustainability of the supply and demand mechanism, partnership with local event organizations are missing at the moment. Also, there are no educational programs (for example food education) for children at school. Different actions are foreseen to boost innovation, networking, entrepreneurial skills and more (R5.2, R5.3, R5.6, R5.8, R5.9, R5.11).

PILGRIMAGE FOR RURAL REGENERATION

Figure 36: The path of the BLUE-GREY Badlands

Il Cammino dei Calanchi Grigio Azzurri
The Path of the Blue-Grey Badlands

Since the two main city's Churches of San Giovanni Battista and San Michele Arcangelo have been seriously damaged during the 2016 earthquake and need a deep restoration before their re-opening, pilgrims coming to Appignano del Tronto can only visit the Church of the Madonna del Piano Santo. The religious building complex was made up by Mother Maria Giacobetti and the private Church of San Vincenzo Ferreri. Despite of the rich cultural and religious heritage, there are no hostels for pilgrims in the territory. A place would be useful for pilgrims to be hosted, even for just one night. Pilgrims need to visit and know local producers, farmers and artisans. For this reason, it is important to create new paths (The path of the Blue-Grey Badlands) and networks supported by ICT making trips and visits more interactive. The private Church of San Vincenzo is not open every day and it is not part of any programme. It would be nice

to include it in a programme of daily trips and tours since it stands in a scenic perspective at the basis of Ascensione Mount allowing a beautiful view over the Badlands. (R5.9).

10.1.3 The Replicator baseline

The Baseline is the starting situation against which to evaluate the obtained results that, in the case of Appignano del Tronto, is 36% as the level of development.

This result represents an average outcome value of the evaluation of 6 different types of capital (Social, Cultural, Built, Financial, Human and Natural). In this context, while the values relating to Cultural, Social and Human Capital are all above the average (36%) placing themselves in a fork ranging from 39% (Social) to 53% (Capital) passing through 45% (Human), the other three are all below: Buily Capital (28%), Financial Capital (30%) and Natural Capital (19%). A comparative approach with other RURITAGE replicators offers further reading elements:

Going more in deep into the six different types of capitals:

Cultural Capital (CC): Considering its small dimension and Earthquake damages (CC6), Appignano del Tronto has a relevant number of action and cultural events produced by citizens at local level (CC1) and people reached by it (CC2). Even the level of accessibility of sites by people with disabilities is higher (CC5). The weaknesses related to the Cultural Capital is the lack of local public transport services (CC3, CC4) and policies to promote it (CC9, CC10).

Natural Capital (NC): The Natural Capital of Appignano del Tronto has a great potential thanks to a combination of a typical landscape of Marche region («rolling hills in hall shades of green, medioeval hilltop towns, tiny villages») and the local calanchi grigio-azzurri (blue-gray Badlands). Despite this, there are not area designed or covered as “protected areas” with high environmental value (NC2). There are not companies with sustainability certification or green tourism packages (NC3, NC4).

Built Capital (BC): With Natural Capital, Built capital is the other weakness for Appignano. In the last years, the number of local restaurants (BC3) and beds (BC2) decreased because the economic crises and 2016/2017 earthquake but these number are not so bad for a small community. On the other site, there is only one hotspot (BC1) and a completely lack of cycle and pedestrian paths (BC4, BC5).

Social Capital (SC): Social Capital is a point of strength for Appignano del Tronto that is in a regional context where, historically, social capital is one of the highest in Italy. This explain why there are a god level of number of citizens' engagement activities and participation (SC1, SC2), formal and informal voluntary activities or active citizenship (SC4). Nevertheless, some of field of activity need to be boost such us for example projects addressing migrants (SC8) and disadvantages people (SC5).

Human Capital (HC): In terms of Human Capital, the baseline data shows a kind of polarization because the baseline shows a good number of recreational facilities/events (HC1), people trained in specific SIA (HC6) or involved in professional management training course (SC7) but there are not students involved in internship (HC4), or migrants who attends educational-training courses (HC2).

Financial Capital (FC): the financial capital represents another point of weakness of Appignano. Weakness especially in terms of lack of start-up companies (FC5), lack of innovation processes in business (FC6), low level of partnership with public and private sector (FC3) and a higher level of unemployment rate, also considering the Italian and the regional context (FC4).

Figure 37: R5 performance (baseline calculation)

© RURITAGE monitoring platform, using Grafana

10.1.4 The main challenges

The 2016/2017 Earthquake in Central-Italy damaged 300 buildings and forced to move more than 150 inhabitants. Thanks to local public policies such as a detailed emergency management and a process of renovation of public buildings such as the local school, the municipality of Appignano del Tronto could manage effectively the post-Earthquake emergency phase. Despite this, the municipality is still facing a series of challenges, mainly identified in the table here below.

Main challenges	
C1	Resilience challenge: lack of knowledge; data and capacity building activity to convert a problem into an opportunity
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - the lack of scientific data of monitoring seismic activity; - the management of the psychological impact of the earthquake; - the lack of training in resilience in the Appignano population; - the lack of resilience and climate change especially for farmers.
C2	Societal challenge: ageing of population, depopulation, unemployment, poverty, to foster social cohesion
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - almost 30% of the population of the region is over 65 years old; - in the last 15 years Appignano del Tronto lost about 12% of the population; - 15% of the population is unemployed;

	- 10% of the population is in poverty condition.
C3	Economic challenge: lack of innovation, entrepreneurial skills, competitiveness, investments
	- lack of start-up companies; - low level of innovation projects in local companies; - lack of managerial and entrepreneurial skills in local companies; - no private investments.
C4	Cultural and Environmental challenge: to protect and promote Cultural and Natural Tangible and Intangible Heritage
	- lack of natural parks; - lack of Cultural and Natural Heritage promotion; - lack of Cultural and Natural Heritage networking; - lack of Cultural and Natural Intangible Heritage identification.
C5	Communication and branding challenge: To boost tourism and attractivity
	- no distinctive element has been found for tourist's attraction; - no local expertise to develop destination management; - no communication strategies for Cultural and Natural Heritage; - no storytelling strategies.

10.2 Overall objectives of the plan

The overall objective is to boost resilience through Cultural and Natural Heritage with a holistic approach. The general objective of Appignano del Tronto is to become safer and more competitive community through the leverage of Cultural and Natural Heritage related with the SIA identified by RURITAGE. Through this holistic approach, and providing technological infrastructures, scientific data monitoring, awareness about natural hazard, training activities, innovation and knowledge transfer to local companies and more, Appignano wants to become a more resilient community. This has to be intended not only in terms of strengthening its capacity to recovery and rebound after disasters or economic crisis but, more generally, to build a community able to transform a problem - the seismicity of the territory and the traumatic experience of the earthquake - into an opportunity to regenerate the territory.

The action plan – with its 12 actions focusing on the six different SIA and Cultural and Natural heritage distinctive elements of Appignano del Tronto – is the instrument to achieve the general objective. If the general objective describes what is the Appignano del Tronto expectation in general terms, the specific objectives listed below identify in details, with the specific reference to challenges and actions foreseen, the multiple aims of the Action Plan.

Specific objectives	
O1	To boost resilience and transform natural hazards into an opportunity of development.
The objective is to provide tools, training and capacity building activities to increase local resilience and to make it an opportunity for rural regeneration.	
Linked with challenges	
C1	Resilience challenge: lack of knowledge; data and capacity building activity to convert a problem into an opportunity
C2	Societal challenge: ageing of population, depopulation, unemployment, poverty, to foster social cohesion
C3	Economic challenge: lack of innovation, entrepreneurial skills, competitiveness, investments.
C4	Cultural and Environmental challenge: to protect and promote Cultural and Natural Tangible and Intangible Heritage
O2	To strengthen resilience for environmental sustainability
The objective is to increase resilience. i.e. to strength the capacity of the whole community and of farmers to face natural risks and hazards as a consequence of climate change.	
Linked with challenges	

C1	Resilience challenge: lack of knowledge; data and capacity building activity to convert a problem into an opportunity
C5	Communication and branding challenge: To boost tourism and attractivity
O3	To communicate more effectively Cultural and Natural Heritage
Cultural and Natural tangible and intangible heritage of Appignano del Tronto needs to be communicated in more effective ways, creating a narrative of the local CNH.	
Linked with challenges	
C4	Cultural and Environmental challenge: to protect and promote Cultural and Natural Tangible and Intangible Heritage
C5	Communication and branding challenge: To boost tourism and attractivity
O4	To increase the touristic attractivity of Appignano del Tronto
The objective is to foster skills, knowledge and synergies of local stakeholders involved in tourism sector in order to increase the quality and quantity of the touristic offers.	
Linked with challenges	
C3	Economic challenge: lack of innovation, entrepreneurial skills, competitiveness, investments.
C4	Cultural and Environmental challenge: to protect and promote Cultural and Natural Tangible and Intangible Heritage
C5	Communication and branding challenge: To boost tourism and attractivity
O5	To foster economic competitiveness of local companies
The objective is to foster economic competitiveness of local companies through training in different fields such as business administration, English language, service design etc.	
Linked with challenges	
C3	Economic challenge: lack of innovation, entrepreneurial skills, competitiveness, investments.
C4	Cultural and Environmental challenge: to protect and promote Cultural and Natural Tangible and Intangible Heritage
C5	Communication and branding challenge: To boost tourism and attractivity
O6	To foster social cohesion
The objective is to increase social cohesion through activities able to involve migrants, people with disabilities and, more generally, disadvantaged people.	
Linked with challenges	
C2	Societal challenge: ageing of population, depopulation, unemployment, poverty, to foster social cohesion

10.3 Operational programme for the implementation of the plan

This section is dedicated to draft the operational programme for the implementation of the actions of the heritage-led regeneration strategies. The operational programme contains one detailed factsheet for each action. RURITAGE methodology provided participatory approaches and tools for building a co-creation processes towards the enhancement of CNH. After a series of workshops, building upon the lessons learnt from RURITAGE Role Models, and also the organizations of round-table meetings with local stakeholders, the actions of the heritage-led regeneration plan have been identified, aiming to foster rural development, enhance its CNH and empower the rural community.

No	Action	SIA	Challenge(s)	Objective(s)
R5.1	Natural Heritage: awareness raising, Capacity building and training activities for resilience	Resilience	C1	O1

R5.2	Natural Heritage: awareness raising, capacity building and training activities for sustainable local food production	Resilience, Local food	C1, C4	O2, O1
R5.3	Capacity building and training activities for local companies through enchantment of cultural and natural heritage	Landscape, Migrants, Local Food	C3	O6, O1
R5.4	Development of toolkit for resilient citizens	Resilience	C1	O1
R5.5	Appignano HUB for Community Resilience, Training and Education	Resilience, landscape	C1, C2, C3, C4	O1, O4, O5
R5.6	RURITAGE Stories	Landscape, Resilience, Local food	C4, C5	O3
R5.7	RURITAGE Art festival	Art & Festival	C5	O4, O5, O6
R5.8	Creation of an integrated green pack based on Nature and Cultural Heritage products, paths and sites	Landscape, Local food, Art & Festival	C3, C5	O5, O6
R5.9	Natural Heritage: pact of the Grey-Blue Badlands	Landscape, local food, Pilgrimage	C3, C4, C5	O4, O5
R5.10	Definition of measures to increase private investments at Appignano del Tronto related with resilience and Cultural and Natural Heritage	Resilience, Landscape	C3	O1, O5
R5.11	Preserving old tradition integrating migrants	Migrants, Local food	C2	O6

10.3.1 The actions in detail

Code of the action	R5.1
Title of the action	Natural Heritage: awareness raising, capacity building and training activities for resilience
Relevant SIA or SIAs	Resilience
Relevant Heritage	Tangible - Natural, Intangible - Knowledge and Practices
Reference RM Action/s (code and name)	RM 9-1 Organizing training, also using informal education methodology, to improve the resilience of local people
Useful lesson/s Learned (code and name)	LL04 Build sense of belonging, individual and community self-confidence and increased autonomy for promotion, safeguarding, management and well-being LL35 Training on digital technologies LL18 Implementation of participatory approach and involvement of local people, including private owners, from early stage
Responsible person	Antonella D'Angelo
Relevant RM/KFP involved	RM9-RM10-UNESCO
Brief description of the action	The aim of the action is to improve community resilience through training activities addressed to different targets. This action will allow to increase the resilience of the community through the development of a renewed knowledge of the territory, its peculiar landscapes and geology.
Objective and target of the action (by the end of the project)	In the general context of strengthening resilience at Appignano Del Tronto (citizens toolkit, innovative technologies etc), this action will focus on Knowledge transfer through training activities. The target audiences of the action are the following: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Local school students. Quantitative target: 150 people. Qualitative target: awareness about emergency procedures and base knowledge about natural risks and hazards and connect it to their reality – the area of COAPP.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Elderly people. Quantitative target: 80 people. Qualitative target: awareness about emergency procedures and prevention of psychological impacts of natural hazards Citizens. Quantitative target: 100 people. Qualitative target: awareness about emergency procedures and natural hazards and risks and connect it to their reality – the area of COAPP. Professionals (engineers, geologists): 150 people
Specific activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Press release at the beginning of each training activity (2020, 2021); Preparation of training exercises for various group that will take place during training activities; Training for local school students <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Two courses (one per school year) for kindergarten children- duration of the course: 2 meetings of 1h and half each-at the end a final certificate of “resilient child” will be given to each participant. Two courses (one per school year) for primary school students- duration of the course: 3 meetings 2 hours each- at the end a final certificate of “resilient student” will be given to each participant. Two courses (one per school year) for secondary school students- duration of the course: 3 meeting 2 hours each- at the end a final certificate of resilient student” will be given to each participant. Training exercises according to developed plans. Awareness Training activities for elderly people <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Four events organized in collaboration with the local elderly club. Each event will be divided into two parts - first part: vision of a film, documentary etc. about natural risks and hazards; -second part: discussion with an expert Drills according to developed plans Capacity building activities for adults about knowledge of the territory and civil protection plans <ul style="list-style-type: none"> two events to increase the knowledge of the territory (the first about history of the landscape and geology, the second about the RURITAGE resilience stories and about earthquake experience); two events to explain the technical sites of civil protection plans (one about hydro geological risks, one about seismic risks); Training exercises according to developed plans Small recap once a year to refresh people mind about the use of the Toolkit for Resilient Citizens (action n. 4) Training for engineers and geologists: engineers, geologists with professional training credits <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Two events; the first dedicated to local seismic response, using measurements recorded by local seismograph- the second dedicated to hydro geological risks, using local weather stations.
Monitoring plan and indicators	<p>CC-02 Increment in number of mentions of CNH in social media, media, press, etc. CC-05 Number of posts mentioning RURITAGE at local level CC-07 Number of people reached by actions and cultural events produced by citizens at local level SC-01 Number of citizens engagement activities SC-02 Number of participants in citizens engagement activities SC-03 Number per type of stakeholder involved (according to the ones defined in D.3.1) SC-04 Number of local associations involved SC-10 Number of disadvantaged people engaged (elderly, migrants, unemployed)</p> <p>New indicator: Number of people trained Monitoring timeline: every six months</p>
Capital involved	Social capital, Cultural capital, Human capital
Main stakeholders involved and their roles and contribution	INGV- human capital Unicam-geology division-School of science and technology- human capital Regione Marche-Ufficio speciale per la ricostruzione- human capital Federazione regionale ordine ingegneri Marche

	Ordine regionale geologi Marche Circolo una nuova primavera
Beneficiaries	The whole community of Appignano del Tronto, including vulnerable groups.
Formal partnership established (PPP, voluntary agreement, etc.)	Six formal partnership agreement (The agreement will refer to all the actions in which the stakeholders are involved)
Timeframe	Start of the action: April 2020 – end of the action April 2022
Indicative costs	€ 10.000,00
Indicative funding sources	RURITAGE budget
Sustainability of the action	If the training courses will be effective, local stakeholders and municipality will make the experience permanent.

Code of the action	R5.2
Title of the action	Natural Heritage: awareness raising, capacity building and training activities for sustainable local food production
Relevant SIA or SIAs	Resilience
Relevant Heritage	Tangible - Natural, Intangible - Knowledge and Practices
Reference RM Action/s (code and name)	RM3-1 Support local farmers and producers in innovation projects RM15-8 Development of multifunctional farms
Useful lesson/s Learned (code and name)	LL01 Adapt agricultural techniques to climate change LL37. Engage knowledge partners (universities, research center, etc.) in the process
Responsible person	Antonella D'Angelo- Massimiliano Fazzini
Relevant RM/KFP involved	RM3-RM15-Unesco
Brief description of the action	The aim of the action is to improve community resilience through training activities and capacity building related to climate change adaptation, particularly in agriculture. This action will support sustainable local food production through the knowledge of the territory, in its particular environmental conditions.
Objective and target of the action (by the end of the project)	In the general context of strengthening resilience at Appignano Del Tronto (citizens toolkit, innovative technologies etc.), this action will focus on citizens and farmers capacity building about climate change. The target audiences of the action are the following: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Local school students (from 10 to 14 years old): 40 people. Qualitative target: awareness about base knowledge and correct behaviors about climate change and consequently hydrogeological hazards and risks through local meteo-climatic database. • Elderly: 30 people. Qualitative target: awareness about correct behaviors relative to climate change and prevention of psychological impacts of natural hazards through local meteo-climatic database. • Adults: 100 people. Qualitative target: awareness about correct behaviors about climate change and consequently hydrogeological hazards and risks through local meteo-climatic database. • Farmers: 20 people. Qualitative target: awareness about correct behaviors about climate extreme and soil erosion through local meteo-climatic database applied to sustainable food cultivation. • Professionals (engineers, geologists, agronomists): 100 people. Qualitative target: application of local data in environmental planning.
Specific activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Automatic control about activities of local weather station network; • Implementation of a digital platform to collect data from different sources available in the field of climate change (seismograph, weather stations...); • Implementation of a specific web application to show the dataset; • Organization of one field trip for local school students from 10 to 14 years old;

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Training for engineers, geologists and agronomists: organization of one public event open to professionals to explain the application of local data in environmental planning; • Drafting of a monthly report that analyzes the local weather climate conditions, published on the municipality's website, RURITAGE section; • Drafting of an annual report that assesses the effects of climate change in the area and publication on the institution's website, RURITAGE section; • Special issue of probabilistic weather forecast before and during severe weather addressed to all population (heatwaves, strong thunderstorm, downburst, heavy snowfall...). During severe weather, every 24 hours a special bulletin that contains weather forecast and includes guidance on appropriate behavior of the population will be drawn up and published on the website of the Municipality-RURITAGE section and on the Facebook page; • Dedicated issue of probabilistic weather forecast linked to local cultivation needs (dry timespan, late frost, hailstorms, heatwaves, strong thunderstorm, downburst, heavy snowfall)-During severe weather for cultivation needs, every 24 hours a special bulletin that contains weather forecast and includes guidance for cultivations will be drawn up. The municipality has the list of local farmers that are involved in another project about climate change adaptation in agriculture. The bulletin will be widespread by WhatsApp to all farmers and published using common channels. • Proper communication and dissemination activities.
Monitoring plan and indicators	<p>CC-02 Increment in number of mentions of CNH in social media, media, press, etc. CC-05 Number of posts mentioning RURITAGE at local level CC-07 Number of people reached by actions and cultural events produced by citizens at local level SC-01 Number of citizens engagement activities SC-02 Number of participants in citizens engagement activities SC-03 Number per type of stakeholder involved (according to the ones defined in D.3.1) SC-04 Number of local associations involved SC-10 Number of disadvantaged people engaged (elderly, migrants, unemployed) HC-09 Number of publication as recommendation and guidelines provided</p> <p>New indicator: Number of people trained Number of people reached by dedicated issue of probabilistic forecast Monitoring timeline: every six months</p>
Capital involved	Social capital, Cultural capital
Main stakeholders involved and their roles and contribution	<p>Unicam-geology division-School of science and technology- human capital Regione Marche Federazione regionale ordine ingegneri Marche Ordine regionale geologi Marche Circolo una nuova primavera</p>
Beneficiaries	The whole community of Appignano del Tronto, including vulnerable groups.
Formal partnership established (PPP, voluntary agreement, etc.)	Five formal partnership agreement (The agreement will refer to all the actions in which the stakeholders are involved)
Timeframe	Start of the action: February 2020 – end of the action April 2022
Indicative costs	€ 5.000,00
Indicative funding sources	RURITAGE budget
Sustainability of the action	If the training courses will be effective, local stakeholders and municipality will make the experience permanent.

Code of the action	
R5.3	
Title of the action	Capacity building and training activities for local companies through enchantment of cultural and natural heritage
Relevant SIA or SIAs	Local food, Landscape
Relevant Heritage	Tangible - Natural
Reference RM Action/s (code and name)	RM 3-1 Support local farmers and producers in innovation projects RM 3-6 Social Innovation ideas RM 3-5 Promote the environmental sustainability of the agro-food production, packaging and selling RM 5-2 Capacity building activities: Training to migrants and residents related with organic farming, arts, built heritage restoration, traditional crafts and trades, etc.
Useful lesson/s Learned (code and name)	LL15 identify heritage resources (formal and informal), foster a better understanding of the tangible and intangible values of natural and cultural heritage and create a recognized value as a driver for local development LL17 Booster effective leadership, including through agencies, to promote and drive the actions, with strategic vision, enthusiasm and network of contacts
Responsible person	Gianluca Vagnarelli
Relevant RM/KFP involved	Savonia University, APRE, CARTIF
Brief description of the action	The action consists in providing 2 guidelines/learning material and 9 training activities for stakeholders, especially local companies, in order to boost their capacities, abilities and skills in 5 different fields: a) Entrepreneurial skills; b) English skills; c) Social media and e-commerce skills; d) EU funds opportunities for SME; e) Service Design skills.
Objective and target of the action (by the end of the project)	The main objective of the action is to boost the human and financial capital of Appignano del Tronto. As RURITAGE baseline data shows, local companies need to be supported in in defining new business models and innovative processes of production and, more generally, creation of a more favourable pro-business environment. The targets of the actions are: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Companies: 10 people. Qualitative target: awareness, knowledge and skills about entrepreneurship, business budget, e-commerce, English language, Service Design. • Associations: 5 people. Qualitative target: awareness, knowledge and skills about entrepreneurship, English language. • Citizens: 50 people. Qualitative target: awareness, knowledge and skills about English language. • Migrants or other vulnerable groups: 5 people. Qualitative target: awareness, knowledge and skills about English language.
Specific activities	<p>a) Call for training. Before starting each training activity (2020, 2021) the municipality of Appignano del Tronto will publish a “Call for training” to find participating companies from Appignano and Marche region.</p> <p>b) pre-training activity (2020, 2021) with the online-training course developed by INNO-4-AGRIFOOD (Horizon2020 project) and supported by APRE focusing on small and medium companies in the food sector.</p> <p>c) training course for developing entrepreneurial skills: 8h training course on “An Introduction on How to manage companies and business budget” in 2020 and 8h training course on “An Introduction on How to manage companies and business budget” in 2021.</p> <p>d) training course to foster English skills: 25 hours of English Language Course (Beginner Level) in 2020 and 25 hours of English Language Course (Beginner Level) in 2021.</p> <p>e) training course on Social media and e-commerce skills: 4 hours training course on “Introduction to e-commerce opportunities for micro-companies” + 4 hours training course on “An introduction to Social media platforms” in 2020 and 4 hours training course on “Introduction to e-commerce opportunities for micro-companies” + 4 hours training course on “An introduction to Social media platforms” in 2021.</p> <p>f) training course on Service Design skills. 30 hours training course on “Build-up a Service Design team for Appignano del Tronto” in 2020.</p>

	g) 1 guideline/learning material provided by Savonia University on “Innovation for SME”. h) 1 guideline/learning material and 1 skype call with APRE on “EU funds opportunities for SME”.
Monitoring plan and indicators	<p>Quantitative indicators: HC-07 Number of people trained (in specific SIA) [Human Capital]: HC-03 Number of migrants involved in educational-training programs, over the total amount of migrants (tra 0 e 100) [Human Capital]: HC-08 Number of people involved in professional management training course (e.g. summer school and master) [Human Capital]: HC-09 Number of publications as recommendation and guidelines provided [Human Capital]: FC-06 Number of companies supported in defining new business models and innovative processes of production [Financial Capital]: Number of people reached by Training material/Guidelines:</p> <p>Qualitative indicators: Evaluation questionnaire Focus group with local companies</p> <p>Modality to monitor activity: Appignano del Tronto detailed plan for monitoring RURITAGE Activity</p> <p>Timeline of the monitoring: Every six months (starting from January 2020) + At the end of each single activity (questionnaire at the end of each training course etc.)</p>
Capital involved	Financial Capital, Human Capital, Social capital
Main stakeholders involved and their roles and contribution	Stakeholders involved within RURIATGE will mainly be beneficiaries, RURITAGE partners will be actively involved in this action (SAVONIA UAS, APRE)
Beneficiaries	The direct beneficiaries of the action are local companies, associations and, more generally, citizens of Appignano del Tronto. A special attention will be paid in order to involve in the activity migrants and vulnerable groups.
Timeframe	Start of the action: March 2020. End of the action: October 2021
Indicative costs	Euro 10.000
Indicative funding sources	RURITAGE project
Sustainability of the action	The empowerment of the financial and human capital through training course and learning material will increase the level of sustainability of the action. Thanks to the knowledge, abilities and skills acquired during the activity, local stakeholders will improve their capacities permanently and for a long-term period that overcome RURITAGE project.

Code of the action	R5.4
Title of the action	Development of toolkit for resilient citizens
Relevant SIA or SIAs	Resilience
Relevant Heritage	Intangible - Knowledge and Practices
Reference RM Action/s (code and name)	RM 9-3 Development of toolkit for resilient citizens
Useful lesson/s Learned (code and name)	LL31. Improve resilience of natural and cultural environments against natural hazards LL02. Apply IT technologies for natural and cultural heritage promotion and safeguarding
Responsible person	Antonella D’Angelo
Relevant RM/KFP involved	RM9-RM10-UNESCO
Brief description of the action	The aim of the action is to increase personal resilience of citizens in a small community providing a kit for each family

Objective and target of the action (by the end of the project)	In the context of strengthening resilience at Appignano Del Tronto (citizens toolkit, innovative technologies etc), this action will focus on personal resilience of citizens and families, than can be increased providing an emergency toolkit and explaining how to use it. Target of the action: each Appignano family (700 families). A special toolkit will be developed for disabled people. One report will be produced after the delivery of the toolkit.
Specific activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Standard Toolkit design by a scientific group of experts; • Toolkit for disabled people design together with associations of disabled people; • Purchase and delivery of the kit to each family (one-to-one delivery through municipal employees); • Toolkit explanation through public events.
Monitoring plan and indicators	SC-01 Number of citizens engagement activities SC-02 Number of participants in citizens engagement activities One report after the toolkit delivery
Capital involved	Human capital, Cultural capital
Main stakeholders involved and their roles and contribution	INGV- human capital Unicam-geology division-School of science and technology- human capital Regione Marche-Ufficio speciale per la ricostruzione- human capital Federazione regionale ordine ingegneri Marche Ordine regionale geologi Marche
Beneficiaries	Each Appignano family, including vulnerable groups.
Formal partnership established (PPP, voluntary agreement, etc.)	Five formal partnership agreement (The agreement will refer to all the actions in which the stakeholders are involved)
Timeframe	Start of the action: February 2020 – end of the action April 2021
Indicative costs	€ 3.500,00/€ 5.000,00
Indicative funding sources	RURITAGE budget – private sponsors for Euro 1.500 [local companies]
Sustainability of the action	The action presents a low sustainability in terms of long-term duration because it is a unique event.

Code of the action	R5.5
Title of the action	Appignano HUB for Community Resilience, Training and Education
Relevant SIA or SIAs	Resilience
Relevant Heritage	Tangible – Built, intangible - Knowledge and Practices
Reference RM Action/s (code and name)	RM9-2 Develop interactive exhibitions to attract a broader audience RM9-4 Participative mapping of the Heritage Features at risk RM20-1 Designating the Sanriku Fukko National Park
Useful lesson/s Learned (code and name)	LL36. Transform prevention against natural calamity and integration process into local development opportunities (creation of a geologic museum, companies, integration of migrants in the agro-food and tourism sector) LL31. Improve resilience of natural and cultural environments against natural hazards
Responsible person	Antonella D’Angelo
Relevant RM/KFP involved	RM9-RM10-UNESCO- BITN-UNIBO
Brief description of the action	The aim of the action is to design an innovative centre with scientific attractions, media tools and training activities based on resilience and prevention against natural calamities, including climate crisis.
Objective and target of the action (by the end of the project)	This action will investigate the feasibility of making Appignano del Tronto a Resilience Hub, able to attract special groups (scientist and researchers, schools, families, travellers

	<p>etc.) for learning and capacity building activities, scientific congresses and cultural related activities.</p> <p>This action together with Action 1, 2, 3 and 4 aims at increasing local community resilience and at transforming natural risks into local regeneration opportunities.</p> <p>Potential target of the action: local community and schools – tourists – researchers. The precise target of the action will be defined in the preliminary draft phase.</p>
Specific activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Establish the study and design team (the team will include one representative for each stakeholder, the earthquake office staff of Appignano del Tronto municipality and other members that will be selected through a public notice) • Preliminary draft. It will analyse other stakeholders to involve, the possible target audiences, other scientific centres to visit and learn from, other best practices, the possible location and the size of a building to host a Resilience Hub/knowledge centre, how to equip it, the management mode. The design time will last for 9 months, at the end the preliminary draft study will be first submitted to CoApp RURITAGE team, and then to the RM and KFP involved. • Visit to scientific centres in order to study other good experiences (i.e. Trento Science Museum to visit the “Science on a sphere”, Earthquake simulator in Italy...) • Project final study- The project team, following all the suggestions received and the good practices studied, will draw the project final study that will include urban context, architectural study, study of the target and the functionality, equipment, management mode, budgets. • Based on the results of the previous activity, development of a preliminary business plan for the Resilience Hub/Knowledge centre. • Study of different funding channels, possible public funds to apply for, or private investors identification to realize the innovation hub
Monitoring plan and indicators	<p>SC-03 Number per type of stakeholder involved</p> <p>SC-01 Number of citizens engagement activities</p> <p>SC-02 Number of participants in citizens engagement activities</p>
Capital involved	Human capital, Cultural capital, Natural capital
Main stakeholders involved and their roles and contribution	<p>INGV- human capital</p> <p>UNICAM-geology division-School of science and technology- human capital</p> <p>Regione Marche-Ufficio speciale per la ricostruzione- human capital</p> <p>Federazione regionale ordine ingegneri Marche</p> <p>Ordine regionale geologi Marche</p>
Beneficiaries	Appignano community
Formal partnership established (PPP, voluntary agreement, etc.)	Five formal partnership agreement (The agreement will refer to all the actions in which the stakeholders are involved)
Timeframe	Start of the action: February 2020 – end of the action February 2022
Indicative costs	€ 5.000,00
Indicative funding sources	RURITAGE budget
Sustainability of the action	The action, once carried out, will give to Appignano Municipality- in short and medium term- a good chance to develop an innovative and international center for preventing natural risks and hazards

Code of the action	R5.6
Title of the action	RURITAGE Stories
Relevant SIA or SIAs	Local food, Pilgrimage, Resilience, Landscape, Art&Festival
Relevant Heritage	Intangible - Oral traditions

Reference RM Action/s (code and name)	<p>RM 3.3 Definition of marketing and communication strategies for the products</p> <p>RM 8.4 Enhance the narrative of the place and promote the discovering of the territory through history</p> <p>RM 10.1 Discover and diffuse the traditional Storytelling and superstitions as means to understand the natural environment and to promote the place ownership</p> <p>RM 19-2 Promote the awareness of the value of territorial heritage and its potential as a driver of local development</p>
Useful lesson/s Learned (code and name)	<p>LL-04 Build sense of belonging, individual and community self-confidence and increased autonomy through CNH</p> <p>LL-06 Create a “brand” based on one of the cultural and natural resources and the added valued created.</p> <p>LL08 Create synergies and foster a collaborative approach with other organizations, programmes or local activities and attractors of the territory to increase impact of the actors.</p> <p>LL15 Identify heritage resources (formal and informal), foster a better understanding of the tangible and intangible values of natural and cultural heritage and create a recognized value as a driver for I.d.</p> <p>LL25 Take advantage from traditional events and make the typical characteristics of the area (a site, food & wine, handcraft, traditional) a tourist attraction</p>
Responsible person	Gianluca Vagnarelli
Relevant RM/KFP involved	<p>ICLEI</p> <p>KATLA Geopark local hero LCP</p>
Brief description of the action	<p>The action consists in a collection – through a participatory approach – of 10 local stories related to resilience, local identity and tradition of Appignano del Tronto. The stories will be collected mainly by local young people who will interview elderly people of their community (grandparents, relatives etc.). The most interesting stories will be selected as “RURITAGE Stories” and published Facebook page, municipality website, multilingual pdf file free downloadable etc.</p>
Objective and target of the action (by the end of the project)	<p>The objectives of the action are essentially three:</p> <p>a) Community building. To generate awareness, sense of belonging in the Appignano community, also abroad, through stories related to its resilience, identity and tradition. In short, storytelling not only as emotional communication but as a strategy of community building; this is in line also with Task 7.4</p> <p>b) To stimulate participation by young people. The protagonists of the stories collection will be the group of 40 young people of the Appignano del Tronto local Oratorio. Thanks to this activity they will have an active role in the RURITAGE project rediscovering their local identity through a human exchange with the elderly people of their community.</p> <p>c) To make Appignano del Tronto more attractive for people – especially tourists – using local stories as distinctive element.</p> <p>d) To widespread and promote local identity coherent with RURITAGE values.</p> <p>Main aim of this action is to create a local RURITAGE storytelling, enhancing local values, traditions and identities, also looking at most vulnerable groups.</p>
Specific activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Training activity: “How to collect a good story” • Define the main objectives of the stories to be collected, the tools, the minimum quality and prepare the call for stories • Launch of a Call for Stories: Participatory approach in collecting local stories • Selection of the most interesting stories with a potential narrative capital • Develop the overall plot of the storytelling • Selection of the best platform for sharing stories (youtube, facebook, Instagram etc.) • Publish he stories • Storytelling event: gather the selected storyteller and launch the overall RURITAGE story with local journalists
Monitoring plan and indicators	<p>Quantitative indicators:</p> <p>Number of actions and cultural events produced by citizens at local level: [Cultural Capital]:</p>

	<p>Number of people reached by actions and cultural events produced by citizens at local [Cultural Capital]:</p> <p>Number of citizens engagement activities [Social Capital]:</p> <p>Number of citizens engagement activities participants [Social Capital]:</p> <p>Number of participants in formal or informal voluntary activities or active citizenship in the last 12 months [Social Capital]:</p> <p>Number of disadvantaged people engaged (elderly, unemployed, etc.) over the total people addressed [Social Capital]:</p> <p>Number of like on Facebook page “RURITAGE – Appignano del Tronto” sharing “RURITAGE Stories” posts sharing “RURITAGE Stories”.</p> <p>Number of visualizations on Facebook page “RURITAGE – Appignano del Tronto” sharing “RURITAGE Stories” video sharing “RURITAGE Stories”.</p> <p>New local indicators: number of people “called” after the Call for Stories, number of people involved in the storytelling event</p> <p>Qualitative indicators:</p> <p>Evaluation questionnaire</p> <p>Focus group with young people involved in the stories collection</p> <p>Timeline of the monitoring:</p> <p>Every six months</p>
Capital involved	Cultural capital, Social Capital
Main stakeholders involved and their roles and contribution	<p>Associazione Culturale 7/8 chili: Cultural Capital.</p> <p>Centro Studi Francesco d’Appignano: Cultural Capital.</p> <p>Pro Loco: Cultural Capital.</p> <p>Oratorio: Social Capital.</p>
Beneficiaries	The direct beneficiaries of the action are young and elderly people of Appignano del Tronto, cultural associations, tourists and citizens. A special attention will be paid in order to promote social inclusion for migrants and vulnerable groups through storytelling.
Timeframe	Start of the action: February 2020. End of the action: December 2021
Indicative costs	Euro 1000
Indicative funding sources	RURITAGE project
Sustainability of the action	The action presents a high level of sustainability in terms of long-term duration. Once local stories are collected, the community of Appignano del Tronto will build an Intangible Cultural Heritage that can be exploited in different way: scientific research, creativity, local history etc.

Code of the action	R5.7
Title of the action	RURITAGE Art Festival
Relevant SIA or SIAs	Art&Festival, Local food
Relevant Heritage	Intangible - Social Practices, Rituals and Festive Events, Performing arts
Reference RM Action/s (code and name)	<p>RM 4-9 Promote the tourist offer of both municipalities through the design of a tourist route that specifies the restaurants, hotels and shops.</p> <p>RM7:5 Promote rural touring opportunities to artists and companies</p> <p>RM7:2 Provide opportunities for all ages and abilities to experience, participate and work in the arts within a predominantly rural context</p> <p>RM 8-1 Creation of a set of tourist’s packs, composed by FOOD related activities, ART, NATURALISTIC activities</p> <p>RM 8-3 Networking with other Festivals on the same topic: possibility of joint actions (i.e. Festival passport)</p> <p>RM 8-4 Enhance the narrative of the place and promote the discovering of the territory through history: guided tours, thematic excursion, games, re-enactments</p> <p>RM 14-2 Develop resources and expand tourism</p>
Useful lesson/s Learned	LL-02 Apply IT technologies for natural and cultural heritage promotion

(code and name)	<p>LL-04 Build sense of belonging, individual and community self-confidence and increased autonomy through CNH</p> <p>LL-08 Create synergies and foster a collaborative approach with other organizations, programmes or local activities and attractors of the territory to increase impact of the actors.</p> <p>LL-16 Foster and promote sustainable tourism</p> <p>LL-25 Take advantage from traditional events and make the typical characteristics of the area (a site, food & wine, handcraft, traditional) a tourist attraction</p>
Responsible person	Gianluca Vagnarelli
Relevant RM/KFP involved	Take Art Visegrad
Brief description of the action	The RURITAGE Art Festival at Appignano del Tronto is a 2 days International Summer Festival (end of September) through which performing arts, taste local food and communicating RURITAGE values. The action refers to two Festival editions: 2020 and 2021.
Objective and target of the action (by the end of the project)	<p>The objective of the action is to launch a 2 days International Summer Festival (end of September) called “RURITAGE Art Festival” at Appignano del Tronto through which performing arts, taste local food and communicating RURITAGE values. Appignano del Tronto already experienced a first edition of the Festival in 2019 and through this action the event will be implemented and fostered.</p> <p>The targets of the action are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tourists: 150 tourists involved in the Festival. Qualitative target: to internationalize the cultural offer of Appignano del Tronto and to foster the number of foreign tourists at Appignano. • International artists: 6 international artists involved in each Festival, 12 in total. Qualitative target: to give them the possibility to visit Marche region offering them a hosting experience in one of the Appignano’s family. • Local stakeholders involved in cultural/tourism sector: 10 Local stakeholders from cultural/tourism sector involved. Qualitative target: having an active contribution from each stakeholder in order to co-create the Festival. • Appignano del Tronto community: 50 citizens of Appignano del Tronto involved in the Festival. Qualitative target: active participation from local community in organization/promotion/management of the Festival. This is in line also with Task 7.4
Specific activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • An International “Call for Artists” • Selection of International + local artists (from centre of Italy) • Selection of Appignano del Tronto Hosting families for international artists • Develop the Programme of the Festival • Communication campaign through different communication channels: a) press release to online and off-line local newspapers, radio and regional tv; b) posts and promotional video (sponsored) through Facebook Page “RURITAGE – Appignano del Tronto”; c) putting-up posters in Appignano del Tronto and in the in nearby cultural sites (public library, bookshops etc.) • Implementation of the 2 days Festival (2 days in 2020, 2 days in 2021) • Video of the Festival
Monitoring plan and indicators	<p>Quantitative indicators:</p> <p>CC-06a Number of actions and cultural events produced by citizens at local level [Cultural Capital]:</p> <p>CC-06b Number of people reached by actions and cultural events produced by citizens at local [Cultural Capital]:</p> <p>CC-09 Number of places involved in the tourism offer (Places located in the Replicator area that are relevant as tourist destinations) [Cultural Capital]:</p> <p>CC-10 Total number of arrivals of tourist in the last year [Cultural Capital]:</p>

	<p>NC-07 Number of "green tourism packages" [Natural Capital]: BC-07 Pedestrian/hiking paths (km) [Built Capital]: BC-15 Number of sites provided with signals [Built Capital]: SC-01a Number of activities [Social Capital]: SC-01b Number of participants [Social Capital]: SC-04 Number of participants in formal or informal voluntary activities or active citizenship in the last 12 months Info [Social Capital]: FC-01 Nights spent at tourist accommodation establishments [Financial Capital]:</p> <p>Qualitative indicators: Evaluation questionnaire for International Artists Timeline of the monitoring: Every six months (starting from January 2020) + questionnaire after Festival</p>
Capital involved	Cultural Capital, Natural Capital, Built Capital, Social Capital, Financial Capital
Main stakeholders involved and their roles and contribution	Conca d'Oro. Oleificio Stipa. Pasticceria Oneiro. Azienda Agricola Valle San Martino. Azienda Agricola Biologica Mari Anna Maria. Pro-Loce. Ristorante Santa Lucia. Agriturismo "Il Gigante". Alessi Ceramica. Adesso Pasta di Cinzia Alessi Panificio Allevi Carolina. Associazione 7/8 Chili, Associazione Frammenti, Oratorio di Appignano del Tronto, Minimo Teatro, Compagnia dei Folli. All stakeholders will be involved in the organization and implementation of the festival activities
Beneficiaries	The direct beneficiaries of the action will be tourists and citizens of Appignano del Tronto. The indirect beneficiaries are International artists and local stakeholders of Appignano.
Timeframe	Start of the action: May 2020. End of the action: february 2022
Indicative costs	Euro 27.000
Indicative funding sources	RURITAGE
Sustainability of the action	The action presents a medium level of sustainability in terms of long-term duration. If the format "Call for International Artists" + "Family Accommodation" works it can be replied for the following editions of the Festival (2022, 2023...)

Code of the action	R5.8
Title of the action	Creation of an integrated green pack based on Natural and Cultural Heritage products, paths and sites
Relevant SIA or SIAs	Local food, Landscape
Relevant Heritage	Tangible – Built and Natural
Reference RM Action/s (code and name)	<p>RM 4-9 Promote the tourist offer of both municipalities through the design of a tourist route that specifies restaurants, hotels and shops</p> <p>RM 8-1 Creation of a set of tourist packs composed by food, art and naturalistic related activities</p> <p>RM 14-2 Develop resources and expand tourism</p>
Useful lesson/s Learned (code and name)	<p>LL16 Foster and promote sustainable tourism.</p> <p>LL25 Take advantage from traditional events and make the typical characteristics of the area (a site, food & wine, handcraft, traditional) a tourist attraction.</p>
Responsible person	Gianluca Vagnarelli
Relevant RM/KFP involved	Distretto Agroalimentare Regionale srl Borghi Italia Tour Network srl
Brief description of the action	At this stage, the tourist offer of Appignano del Tronto is split in different fields that are not linked each to another. Through the action "Creation of an integrated green pack based on Natural and Cultural Heritage products, paths and sites" we would like to put together any kind of local tourist "attraction" [landscape ("Path of the blue-grey Badlands"), architecture, folklore, food etc.] with the purpose to concentrate all local strengths point in only one "product". In this sense this action is linked with Action 9 on the new path of blue and grey Badlands and with Action 5 of Appignano Hub for resilience

	<p>since both of them can become important attractors for the area. The possibility of building on the RURITAGE brand and the specific SIAs brands developed in WP6 will be assessed. Specifically, RURITASTE and RURISCAPE brands' exploitation will be explored and the idea of building a RURibox will be considered.</p>
<p>Objective and target of the action (by the end of the project)</p>	<p>The main objective of the action is to create an added value for tourists through an integrated approach. An additional value in terms of: a) better quality and diversity of tourist offer, b) a better communication of local tourism offer, c) a tourism-experience approach, d) a better environmental sustainability of local tourism e) more job opportunities for local tourism sector.</p> <p>The targets of the actions are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Local stakeholder involved in tourism offer: 11 Local stakeholders involved in tourism offer (farms, restaurant, pro-loco, companies, agriturismo). Qualitative target: have an active contribution from each stakeholder in order to create an effective integrated tourist pack. • Tourists: 100 targeted by the tourist pack. Qualitative target: to experience Appignano through one of the activity/experience/products/event/sites presents in the tourist pack.
<p>Specific activities</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gathering information about activities and product local stakeholders can offer • select, from the information gathered, the best products/experiences/services to design an integrated tourist pack • include the attractors developed within this action plan in the kit – i.e the blue grey Path and, in the future, the Resilience Hub /knowledge centre. • define an innovative visual identity for the integrated tourist pack • explore the possible use of the RURITASTE and RURISCAPE brand and explore the possibility of launching the integrated tourist pack as the first RURibox for rural travel experience • publish the integrated green tourist pack • upload it in the municipality website, in the websites of each stakeholder involved, • develop and implement a crowdfunding campaign to increase the budget for the promotion • promotion and communication of the package through various channels: a) press release to online and off-line local newspapers, radio and regional tv; b) posts on Facebook Page "RURITAGE – Appignano del Tronto"; c) posters in Appignano del Tronto bad&breakfast; d) c) posters in every stakeholders shop involved; d) posters in tourism information points of Marche region; ;
<p>Monitoring plan and indicators</p>	<p>Quantitative indicators: NC-06 Number of shops, restaurants and tourism facilities selling local products (km0) [Natural Capital] NC-07 Number of "green tourism packages [Natural Capital] CC-09 Number of places involved in the tourism offer [Cultural Capital]: CC-10 Total number of arrivals of tourist in the last year [Cultural Capital]: FC-06 Number of companies supported in defining new business models and innovative processes of production [Financial Capital] FC-01 Nights spent at tourist accommodation establishments [Financial Capital] BC-07 Pedestrian/hiking paths (km) [Built Capital] BC-13 Number of brands and labels granted for local products and services: 5 (DOC, DOCG, BIO (ITBIO009/BB25), DOP, IGP) [Built Capital] BC-14 Number of fairs and tourism events per year related to the promotion of the area and related products [Built Capital]</p> <p>Qualitative indicators: Evaluation questionnaire</p> <p>Timeline of the monitoring:</p>

	Every six months (starting from January 2020) + questionnaire after having produced the Tourist pack
Capital involved	Natural Capital, Cultural Capital, Built Capital, Financial Capital
Main stakeholders involved and their roles and contribution	Conca d’Oro. Oleificio Stipa. Pasticceria Oneiroi. Azienda Agricola Valle San Martino. Azienda Agricola Biologica Mari Anna Maria. Pro-Loco. Ristorante Santa Lucia. Agriturismo “Il Gigante”. Alessi Ceramica. Adesso Pasta di Cinzia Alessi. Panificio Allevi Carolina. All the stakeholders will actively contribute to the co-creation of Tourist pack.
Beneficiaries	The direct beneficiaries of the action will be tourists who, through an integrated tourist pack, will have the possibility to experience Appignano del Tronto from different point of view: cultural activities, local food&wine, natural paths etc.
Formal partnership established (PPP, voluntary agreement, etc.)	
Timeframe	Start of the action: June 2020. End of the action: June 2021
Indicative costs	Euro 5.000
Indicative funding sources	Euro 2000 RURITAGE budget At least Euro 3.000 through a local crowdfunding campaign
Sustainability of the action	The action presents a high level of sustainability in terms of mid-term duration. Once the integrated green tourist pack has been realized, the local stakeholders will have an instrument to better promote Appignano del Tronto and its Cultural and Natural Heritage in tourism fields.

Code of the action	R5.9
Title of the action	Natural Heritage: The path of the Grey-Blue Badlands
Relevant SIA or SIAs	Pilgrimage, Landscape, Resilience
Relevant Heritage	Tangible – Natural, Digital
Reference RM Action/s (code and name)	RM2-1 Improve services: eco-mobility, Wi-Fi connection, tourism services (hostels, bar & restaurants), signals, maps, radio...
Useful lesson/s Learned (code and name)	LL11. Develop and improve transportation to make places accessible and to facilitate the launch of new touristic destinations LL08. Create synergies and foster a collaborative approach with other organizations, Programs or local activities (i.e. festivals, arts, food, etc.) and attractors of the territory to increase impact of the actions LL02. Apply IT technologies for natural and cultural heritage promotion and safeguarding LL09. Create companies and start-ups in cultural services and products (hotels, restaurants, museums, handcraft, etc.) LL28. Promote access to all ages and abilities and ensure fruition of cultural resources to all, including transport and online information provision LL07. Create 'tourist pack and experiences' based on the different clusters (culture, food & wine, nature, religion, etc.) and sell combined packages, including transport L16. Foster and promote sustainable tourism
Responsible person	Antonella D’Angelo
Relevant RM/KFP involved	RM1-RM2 – Agence des Chemins de Compostelle
Brief description of the action	“Path of the Grey-Blue Badlands” (“Cammino dei Calanchi Grigio-Azzurri”) will take tourists into a sensory trip that alternates the visit to sacred and culturally valuable places and the meetings with local producers of honey, cheese, cold cuts, beef, saffron, olive oil, wine, olives and typical products in a unique landscape. The path will be equipped with signals and QR-codes which will get the tourist to the description of each attraction.

Objective and target of the action (by the end of the project)	<p>Objective: Strengthening the tourism sector and enlarge the tourism offer (28 km of routes provided with signals and explanation panels). Promote local business for sustainable production (+15% increase of the number of shops, restaurants and tourism facilities selling local products)</p> <p>Quantitative target: 100 tourists targeted by the tourist pack (action 8) that will include this path. 28 km of route improved</p>
Specific activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Installation of tourist signs indicating the route: main signs (direction signs with km or journey times): about 2 per km; TOT: 54 secondary signs (continuity flag and path confirmation): about 10 per km; TOT: 144 Installation of tourist signs with indication of local producers (who have signed the partnership) main signs (road type signs): about 2 per local producers; TOT: 28 - Installation of explanatory and information signs indicating the architectural and landscape emergencies encountered along the Path punctual totems with description of the place of interest and QR code for interactive experience: 1 per point of interest; TOT: 24 - Implementation of an App or Another digital tool with interactive content for users (the digital tool will be implemented through an external contract) : augmented reality notions of history, geography, sciences map of places of interest, including local producers information of tourist interest (in ex. places of opening and contact details of local producers). - Promotion and communication of the new path, integration with existing paths in the region (done by RURITAGE staff) - Promotion of the new path together with the integrated green pack (action 8)
Monitoring plan and indicators	<p>CC-02 Increment in number of mentions of CNH in social media, media, press, etc. CC-11 Total number of arrivals of tourist in the last year NC-07 Number of shops, restaurants and tourism facilities selling local products (KM0) 10 NR NC-08 Number of "green tourism packages" BC-16 Number of km of routes provided with signals and explanation panels to help describing the sites and orienteering visitors SC-04 Number of local associations involved</p>
Capital involved	Cultural, Natural, Social
Main stakeholders involved and their roles and contribution	<p>Adesso Pasta di Alessi Cinzia, Alessi Events, Azienda Agricola Biologica Cantina Sesi, Azienda agricola biologica Conca D'oro, Confettificio Alessi snc, Azienda Agricola Valle San Martino ,Azienda Agricola Il Colle , Il Gigante, L'Arte di realizzare sogni, Gal Piceno, Linea Verde, Azienda Agricola Biologica Mari Anna Maria, Azienda Agricola Biologica Martelli Alessia, Natura Viva, Oleificio Stipa Felice, Panificio Allevi, Ristorante Santa Lucia, Zafferano de lu Repà, Oneiroi di, Chiara Vagnoni, Parrocchia San Giovanni Battista, Giovanni D'Ercole - Vescovo di Ascoli Piceno Comune di Castignano</p>
Beneficiaries	Pilgrims, excursionists, walkers, cyclists
Formal partnership established (PPP, voluntary agreement, etc.)	21 formal partnership agreement (The agreement will refer to all the actions in which the stakeholders are involved)
Timeframe	Start of the action: May 2021 – end of the action December 2021
Indicative costs	€ 18.000,00
Indicative funding sources	RURITAGE budget
Sustainability of the action	The growing interest in hiking and cycling routes suggests that “Path of the Blue-Grey Badlands” can live its own long life. It can have a continuous increase in visitors in the time.

Code of the action	R5.10
Title of the action	Definition of measures to increase private investments at Appignano del Tronto related with resilience and Cultural and Natural Heritage
Relevant SIA or SIAs	Local food, Landscape, Pilgrimage, Resilience, Art&Festival
Relevant Heritage	All
Reference RM Action/s (code and name)	RM 16-3 Promote the creation of new companies and jobs RM 19-1 Promote a new governance model with a network of public/private subjects processing an alternative development project for the territory
Useful lesson/s Learned (code and name)	LL-05 Collaborative approaches to achieves innovative financing solutions and access to funding LL-23 Involvement of private and third sector in cultural heritage in order to optimize business model, answer to social needs and effectively manage heritage LL-40 Use economic incentives (e.g. lower tax, lower renting fees if the use of building/land fits in the overall management goals) owners or tenants
Responsible person	Gianluca Vagnarelli
Relevant RM/KFP involved	Joe (Investors meeting Crete), DARE
Brief description of the action	The action consists in finding technical measures (tax exemption especially) to stimulate private investments (banks, foundations, business angels etc.) in the heritage-based rural regenerations model developed at Appignano del Tronto. In particular this action will be relevant in connection with Action R5.1 that will produced a business model to make Appignano a European resilience centre.
Objective and target of the action (by the end of the project)	The main objective of the action is to increase the possibility of gathering private investments at Appignano del Tronto after the ending of RURITAGE project. The challenge of the action is to find additional funds to boost and follow up the rural regeneration model experienced thanks to RURITAGE in order to guarantee its long term sustainability. The target of the actions are: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Banks contacts: 10 • Foundation contacts:10 • Private investors contacts: 20 people.
Specific activities	a) asking advisor expert in companies and bank taxation in order to identify practical measures to promote private investments b) data collecting of banks, foundations and private investors potentially interested in Cultural and Natural Heritage projects c) definition of an Appignano/RURITAGE investment plan, co-created with local stakeholders, for the period 2022-2025 d) video-presentation of Appignano del Tronto/RURITAGE investment plan e) contacts with investors to submit it them underlining the advantages from incentives
Monitoring plan and indicators	Quantitative indicators: FC-03 Number of PPPs set and signed [Financial Capital]: FC-04 Unemployment rate (tra 0 e 100) [Financial Capital]: FC-05 Number of start-ups and spin-off created / Birth of enterprises [Financial Capital]: FC-06 Number of companies supported in defining new business models and innovative processes of production [Financial Capital]: Qualitative indicators: Evaluation questionnaire Modality to monitor activity: Appignano del Tronto detailed plan for monitoring RURITAGE Activity Timeline of the monitoring: Every six months (starting from January 2021)
Capital involved	Financial Capital

Main stakeholders involved and their roles and contribution	Fondazione Cassa di risparmio GAL
Beneficiaries	The direct beneficiaries of the action are local companies, associations and, more generally, the citizens of Appignano del Tronto. Thanks to the action Appignano del Tronto will be able to continue in implementing the Rural Regeneration Model of RURITAGE even after the end of the project.
Timeframe	Start of the action: March 2021. End of the action: February 2022
Indicative costs	Euro 4.000
Indicative funding sources	RURITAGE project
Sustainability of the action	The action aims to guarantee the maximum long-term impact and follow-up of the project RURITAGE thanks to private investments able to support the further developing of the RURITAGE model.

Code of the action	R5.11
Title of the action	Preserving old traditions integrating local migrants
Relevant SIA or SIAs	Local Food, Migrants
Relevant Heritage	Intangible - Social Practices, Rituals and Festive Events
Reference RM Action/s (code and name)	RM3-1 Support local farmers and producers in innovation projects
Useful lesson/s Learned (code and name)	LL24. Long-term vision to build confidence among stakeholders and continuous communication to create long-lasting relationships LL17. Boost effective leadership, including through agencies, to promote and drive the actions, with strategic vision, enthusiasm and network of contacts LL29. Recover and put in value the traditional skills and agricultural and farming methods
Responsible person	Antonella D'Angelo
Relevant RM/KFP involved	RM3
Brief description of the action	The activity is based on a <u>social event/per year</u> (a dinner) with a combination of typical local food and foreign food. Senior farmers bring their products and tell their stories for others. Similarly, migrants present their own products and traditions. They become friends and start to stay in touch. The experience produces collaborations and cooperation projects.
Objective and target of the action (by the end of the project)	Objective: Include immigrants and outcasts by exploring similarities and differences. Deepen the knowledge on typical dishes and on foreign food. Handing down the uses and traditions of typical local cuisine. Target: Migrants (10), people from Appignano who lives in other villages (10), senior farmers and youth generation (10).
Specific activities	Organization of a dinner per year with the presence of: - senior farmers - young generations - immigrants from foreign countries - Appignano del Tronto emigrants currently residing in other countries - Anyone with historical memory of local customs and traditions. Exhibition of typical local products and foreign foods and explanation by testimonials. The immigrants from foreign countries will be involved through the Municipality Office for Social Service and through UNITALSI. The other people will be involved through local stakeholders as Pro Loco di Appignano del Tronto, Parrocchia San Giovanni Battista, Oratorio San Vincenzo Ferreri, Oratorio I Discepoli di Emmaus (Local non-profit associations that can reach lot of people)

Monitoring plan and indicators	CC-07 Number of people reached by actions and cultural events produced by citizens at local level CC-09 Number of people trained in traditional skills SC-02 Number of participants in citizens engagement activities SC-04 Number of local associations involved SC-06 Number of projects addressing migrants SC-07 Number of people involved in projects addressing migrants
Capital involved	Social and Human capitals
Main stakeholders involved and their roles and contribution	Adesso Pasta di Alessi Cinzia, Alessi Events, Azienda Agricola Biologica Cantina Sesi Azienda agricola biologica Conca D'oro, Confettificio Alessi snc, Azienda Agricola Valle San Martino, Azienda Agricola Il Colle , Il Gigante, L'Arte di realizzare sogni, Gal Piceno, Linea Verde Azienda Agricola Biologica Mari Anna Maria, Azienda Agricola Biologica Martelli Alessia, Natura Viva, Oleificio Stipa Felice, Panificio Allevi, Ristorante Santa Lucia, Zafferano de lu Repà , Oneiroi di Chiara Vagnoni, Pro Loco di Appignano del Tronto, Parrocchia San Giovanni Battista, Giovanni D'Ercole - Vescovo di Ascoli Piceno, Oratorio San Vincenzo Ferreri, Oratorio I Discepoli di Emmaus, U.N.I.T.A.L.S.I.
Beneficiaries	Migrants, outcasts, citizens.
Formal partnership established (PPP, voluntary agreement, etc.)	23 formal partnership agreement (The agreement will refer to all the actions in which the stakeholders are involved)
Timeframe	Start of the action: August 2020 – August 2021
Indicative costs	€ 1.500,00
Indicative funding sources	RURITAGE budget
Sustainability of the action	The event is sustainable over time, as it requires low costs. Dinner is easy to organize with the help of Pro Loco, local associations and farmers.

10.3.1 Timeline for the implementation

Action No:	Action Name:	2020												2021												2022				
		January	February	March	April	May	June	July	August	September	October	November	December	January	February	March	April	May	June	July	August	September	October	November	December	January	February	March	April	May
		20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	41	42	43	44	45	46	47	48
1	Natural Heritage: awareness raising, Capacity building and training activities for resilience																													
2	Natural Heritage: pact of the Grey-Blue Badlands																													
3	Capacity building and training activities for local companies' through enchantment of cultural and natural heritage																													
4	Development of toolkit for resilient citizens																													
5	Appignano HUB for Community Resilience, Training and Education																													
6	RURITAGE Stories																													
7	RURITAGE Art festival																													
8	Creation of an integrated green pack based on Nature and Cultural Heritage products, paths and sites																													
9	Natural Heritage: pact of the blue grey Badlands																													
11	Preserving old tradition integrating migrants																													

10.4 Risks for the implementation of the plan

Risk No.	Action/s involved	Description of the risk	Mitigation action proposed
1	R5.1 R5.2 R5.3	Lack of participation in training activities	New “Call for training”; more effective communication (sponsored posts) through Facebook Page; to differentiate target; new press release.
2	R5.7	Not enough answers in the call for artists	Mailing to foreign Fine Arts Academy to find young international networks of artists
3	R5.6	Not enough answers in call for stories	To enlarge the “Call for Stories” to neighbouring villages; to involve local archives; to ask to former Appignano citizens who lives abroad.
4	R5.8	Not enough collaboration from some stakeholders in the tourist pack creation	To enlarge the network of local stakeholders to the neighbouring villages, more effective communication (sponsored posts) through Facebook Page;
5	R5.4	Difficulties to understand the toolkit for resilience citizens	One-to-one delivery of the toolkit
6	R5.2	Difficulties to use the probabilistic weather forecast linked to local cultivation needs	Organizing dedicated meetings with local farmers
7	R5.5	Difficulties to find tailored solution to transform resilience in an opportunity to development	Additional meetings with Role Models and KFPs
8	All actions	Change in local political priorities after the election in 2020	Explanation of the relevance of RURITAGE project to the new local leaders
9	All actions	Turnover in the RURITAGE technical staff	New recruitment and new responsibility in the municipality staff
10	R5.10	Lack of private investments after having introduced incentives	To enlarge abroad the research of private investors, business angels, foundations etc. potentially interested in rural and cultural investments
11	R5.7	Lack of participation in RURITAGE Art Festival	Involving local cultural associations and local heroes and better communication through facebook page and one-to-one recall

11. Izmir in Gediz-Bakircay Basins (IZM, DEM, IZTECH) Heritage-led regeneration plan

11.1 Background information

Figure 38: Related Systemic Innovation Areas of Replicator 6

The area of the Izmir Replicator includes Bergama, Dikili and Kinik district municipalities. The area of influence of the Izmir Metropolitan Area has been gradually extended by laws of urbanism. The Metropolitan Municipality Law No. 6360 (2012) has affected the boundaries of the city making it 6 times bigger in the last years. According to different projections, in 2030 it is estimated that Izmir metropolitan area will be 6.2 million, and in 2050 the population will rise to 8 million and almost double in a 30 years period. Carrying capacity limits of the actual city will be exceeded. For the enlargement of the city limits İzmir Metropolitan Municipality has arranged various thematic and spatial planning strategies. Firstly, the municipality has established the Gediz-Bakircay River Basin Local Development Strategy (2015). The idea is to focus

on local sustainable development of the rural area of the municipality with particular emphasis on natural and cultural assets of the region which is called 'local asset-based development'. Secondly, based on Gediz-Bakircay River Basin Local Development Strategy, the Municipality approved its extension plan with the integration of newly added service boundaries towards a "blue and green growth". This spatial strategy emphasized the value of nature, green connectivity and ecological and ecosystem services. Ultimately, the extension plan of 2017 amended the existing plan while central city has remained untouched, peripheral areas (new service boundaries) has been integrated with new networks of agricultural corridors and newly proposed UNESCO protection sites such as a geopark in the north and a biosphere reserve area in the western part of the city. **The integration and the synergies of the RURITAGE heritage-led regeneration plan with already defined development objectives, strategies and existing plans represents a strong added value for the area and the project.** Indeed, valuable natural and cultural assets of the region touch upon many SIAs identified in RURITAGE and better defined in this section below. Therefore, working on integrated landscape management within RURITAGE is key for the sustainable local development of the area.

IZM is interested in other four SIAs, although the main SIA is Integrated Landscape Management. The main idea is to develop integrated landscape management through cultural and natural heritages including the different SIAs. The RURITAGE Izmir HUB is located in Yukarıbey Village. The village has been a sub-district with the Kozak Plateau villages with a high population and it is located at the geometric center of the plateau. The RHH, that will be the center of our project works and activities, is an old primary school building owned by the village cooperative that. It was extensively repaired during the first phase of the project. Since the official launch of HUB on 23th July 2019, the former school building has been used for meetings and courses within the scope of the RURITAGE project and beyond.

Figure 39: Gediz-Bakircay Basins Location of region and RHH

© IZM, DEM, IZTECH

Figure 40: the Rural Heritage Hub before and after restoration

© IZM, DEM, IZTECH

The hub consists of a meeting room (25 m²), a training room (28 m²), a computer room (26 m²), an office room (18 m²), a kitchen (25 m²), and a disabled toilet (5,6 m²) with the total area of 145 m². It is refunfctioned to serve for necessary facilities such as organizing courses, film screenings, meetings, trainings with furniture and internet connection.

Since the official launch of HUB on 23th July 2019, our RHH Izmir building is used for several meetings and courses within the scope of the RURITAGE. However, due to the high number of participants, we organize our workshops within the scope of the project.

11.1.1 The Reference SIA

LANDSCAPE FOR RURAL REGENERATION

The area of the Izmir Replicator offers a wide range of landscape types. The most important and productive areas of agriculture, focused on grapes and the pine nuts, are in the highlands of Kozak Plateau in Bergama. The northern part of Bergama is covered with forest which is located in the Kozak Plateau and the southern part of region is covered with plains. Besides the Bakircay River is rising north and east sides of region and flows into the Dikili (Candarli) Bay which is located in the southwest of district. Altogether it covers an area of 128 km².

Figure 41: An image of geological formations in the area

This landscape enhances and embrace very diverse cultural and natural heritage rich in archeological and geological features. In 2014, the site of Pergamon was listed in the UNESCO World Heritage List embedding exclusive universal values, which include tangible and intangible heritages. Close to Pergamon, the ancient healing center Asklepion is found. Already in the ancient world Asklepion offered natural treatments (thermal treatment), sport and theatre. In addition, within the regional master plan development report, the municipality is working to inscribe parts of the area to the World UNESCO Geoparks. The proposed Geopark site is located in the central western Anatolia, on Madra Mountain, at the northern end of Izmir. The Madra mountain is

an inactive volcano, today consisting of the accumulation of lavas of various structures, which emanate from the magma and erupt. Different types of geological units have been seen in this region. Basement rocks of Western Anatolia consist of Paleozoic metamorphic rocks and Mesozoic mélangé, comprising clastic and carbonate rocks. These basement rocks are cut by granitic and intrusive granodioritic and are covered mainly by calc-alkaline and minor alkaline volcanic rocks. The surrounding area includes ancient Pergamon gold mines. Moreover, with Kula Geopark (2013) in neighboring province Manisa and Lesvos Geopark in Greece (RM 6) IZM would like to explore the possibility of developing a unique cross-border geopark.

The highlands offer spectacular forest and mountain tourism opportunities. However, as for now economic wealth has been declining in the local villages. This is due to impacts of urban migration and loss of the young population, decreasing value for agricultural products and little or no subsidies to agriculture due to de-regulatory pressure of the government. Particularly challenging is the loss of income due to declining yields in pine nuts. Not sufficient economic alternatives have been created to maintain income levels in villages while in the local mid-size towns such as Bergama, Dikili and Kinik, tourism has been entrusted to possibly provide additional income. Several developments within tourism are particularly positive in this respect. First of all, Izmir has joined the ECF's Eurovelo cycling tourism network. Secondly, a newly planned sea line between Dikili and Lesvos in Greece has been planned. Both these developments will contribute to the enhancement of a tourism network. CNH assets of the region will generate touristic spots through this cycling network. The cycling network will be integrated with the pilgrimage route of Izmir to enhance value of territories by arranging direction signs, maps and promotional activities. In this

context, more tourist attraction will be created by connecting cultural and natural assets in the RURITAGE project area through cycle routes (R6.5).

Given all above factors, the IZMIR Replicator will focus on landscape, recognizing the huge potential of the area for the enhancement of the cultural and natural heritage features, also using citizen science approaches. Actions that are related to landscape aim to valorize its cultural and natural components, enhance accessibility and increase awareness about these assets to generate alternative economic sources for rural communities, which have been planned within the timeframe of the RURITAGE project. The creation of geo trails, enhancing the mobility options to CNH assets, will increase the capacity of both locals and foreigners for touristic attractions (R6.1, R6.5, R6.6).

11.1.2 Other relevant SIAs

As R6, our main aim is to conserve and enhance natural and cultural resources to maintain and foster economic activities in the region. Developing a participatory process to rediscover local cultural heritage and identity through our landscape art and food is among the main objectives of our action plan and we have already started to build this through the co-development phase and the establishment of the RHH.

As also mentioned in the introduction, our heritage-led regeneration plan will focus on landscape, but it will touch upon all the different SIAs to tackle local challenges and to make use of local strengths and opportunities.

ART & FESTIVAL FOR RURAL REGENERATION

Arts & Festivals are important drivers for promotion of localities both in a relation with the SIAs of Landscape and Local Food. Promotion and support of local traditional activities will be used to increase the visibility both in national and international markets. By increasing the length of stay and reveal the potential of touristic destinations, the main objective is to ensure economic vitality in the involved area. Arts & Festivals will enhance the narrative of the place to promote the discovery of the territory and will be associated with potential touristic destinations of the site. In this way, cultural, natural and geological heritage of the site can be used for rural regeneration. There has been a lack of effective strategies for branding and marketing for the historic, cultural, natural assets and local products. This can be considered the main obstacle on dissemination of existing festivals and congress and to reach wide audience, such as the International Theatre Festival of Pergamon, in which art enthusiasts from all over the world come together in the ancient theatres, plazas and streets of the thousand-year-old city of Bergama. The Festival provides a unique and unprecedented environment for both visitors and locals, in which a collective production, viewing, experimenting and discussion take place.

Apart from already existing festivals in the region, the organization of a cross-cultural musical festival will be the aim within the SIA of Arts and Festivals. It will allow to increase social inclusion and enrich cultural diversity of the region via using the unifying feature of music. The history of the music is back a long time ago in Bakircay Basin. Especially clarinet which is played by the Greek is very popular musical instrument since 1900's. In Bergama, in particular Atmaca neighborhood children showed a great interested in music, thanks to extensive tradition. Children in the area often start to play clarinet and trumpet as early as 5 or 6 years old. Their musical education starts with rhythm, and their purpose is to play their instrument in a very short time without learning or reading notes. This situation attracts many local and foreigner music researchers to research and workshop activities. (R6.4).

Figure 42: Cultural/traditional events, festivals in the area

Category	art	food	Historical/folkloristic	thematic	open-air
Number of existing festivals/events	2	1	1	3	2

Apart from traditional food and agricultural products, each craft of the region has narrative that has a bond to history. Visibility of all these assets need to be increased to strength tourism sector in the region and ensure sustainability of heritage. Basket weaving is a traditional activity in Bakircay Basin, in particular Bergama. The main materials of baskets are the willow trees in Bergama that are naturally growing along the Bakircay River and Kozak road. The basis of baskets is preparing to use pike, vitex and branches of withy. As it is now, only one family has continued the tradition of basket weaving. We intend to safeguard the intangible heritage of basket weaving through the development of a sales network. Moreover, we intend to educate people on the craft to keep the tradition alive. The municipality and the master of basket weaving are in collaboration to organize more courses and workshops (R6.7).

Given the richness of the cultural assets and the willingness to participate among locals on building a local brand, a holistic regeneration strategy in which natural, cultural and landscape dimensions are integrated is a need for preventing depopulation and the loss of economic and socio-cultural vitality of the region. Organizing training activities and workshops are targeted to sustain and gain value to region's arts and handicraft.

FOOD FOR RURAL REGENERATION

The region is rich in local food production; however, it is weak when it comes to geographical and quality certification of products and relative marketing. Important agricultural products are red-black grapes peculiar to the region, pine nuts, olives, tomatoes, corn, wheat and honey. The production is now also seriously threatened by mining interests. Upgrading gastronomical dimension of the region's tourism services are also needed rapidly.

Another issue has been the declining incomes from pine fruit in the last several years, a major source of income in the villages. Several attempts have been made to diversify this income via alternative agricultural production and the Metropolitan Municipality has supported the rural population to diversify by encouraging honey production. The Municipality has invested in honey production, this including a packaging atelier in Kiranlı, one of the villages in Kozak Plateau. This diversification will get a boost from planting of different species of locally known trees (licorice) and berry bushes suitable to beekeeping around Kozak villages. Besides increasing the visibility and integration to the market of local food, producing economic value-added products are another focal point for the area. In this regard, creating a better knowledge and awareness of spontaneous local herbs constitutes an important research topic useful for training activities on ethnobotanic for rural communities (R6.3). Also, a better understanding of the bioeconomic modelling of the Kozak Plateau is needed to know the real potential of the area regarding alternative value-added products to increase the income level of the local people (R6.2).

RESILIENCE FOR RURAL REGENERATION

Economic return of agricultural production is important for the livelihood of the locals as in most rural communities. The drop in the pine nuts productivity has affected areas where demographical, economical and landscape changes are already challenging local population. Therefore, the actions that are related with food are also related with resilience. For the next decades, due to the decreasing of pine nut yield, new source of income will be required. The territory is rich with agricultural and natural assets. We will supply to contribution to economic resilience through further research biodiversity and ethnobotanic features. Besides sustainability of agricultural production and environment, identifying heritage features that are under risk and ensuring resilient communities have to be targets of the actions. The feasibility and modelling studies for harvesting of different

value-added products or products of pine trees are directly related with the sustainability of the region (R6.2, R6.3, R6.10).

PILGRIMAGE FOR RURAL REGENERATION

Figure 43: Pilgrimage Route of Izmir

In Pergamon there is a church where the first Christians gathered secretly during early Christianity. There are two other churches in Efes (Ephesus) and Izmir (Smyrna) besides Pergamon. There are already biblical tours including the three counties. The pilgrimage suggestions of the project is complementary to the present situation. Right now, the train rail system from Izmir, IZBAN, is being extended to include Bergama and Selcuk (the site of Ephesus). This will help to attract tourists to the biblical tour and as well as the antique sites Pergamum and Ephesus. Promoting “connection routes” between the planes Pilgrimage Route (Pergamon-Smyrna-Ephesus historical corridor), Eurovelo cycling route in the north region and train line (IZBAN) is taken into account to establish the linkage between cultural and natural assets of the region as well as improving accessibility and inclusivity of rural communities (R6.5, R6.6).

11.1.3 The Replicator baseline

The replicator area, composed of three districts, represents northern territory of Izmir region, has key economic, socio-cultural and environmental assets for the Aegean region of Turkey. The most preserved and potent asset is the region’s cultural capital, that will be further boosted with of the integration of music and cultural festivals, trainings on local crafts and the involvement of local people in these cultural activities. The region has also essential capital with its human, built and natural capitals to be developed for creating added value. The financial resources and social frameworks are the weakest pint of the area and will require specific attention.

The graphs below show the results of the baseline presented in Deliverable 1.4. Data requested were not always available, creating some limitations in the results showed. Further details and explanations can be found in the deliverable 1.4.

Cultural Capital (CC) reflects the way people “know the world” and how they act within it, as well as their traditions and language. There are a lot of cultural heritage sites within the area that attracts many tourists. There are significant amounts of cultural events (CC-06). These events could reach higher number of local as well as people from neighboring cities (CC-07) and increase the offer of area for economic growth. RURITAGE project and the hub will enable us to reach to wider people through social media and networks. There is still room for improvement in the use of social media (CC-02 to CC-05).

Natural Capital (NC) connected with biodiversity and landscape is one of the key assets that rural destinations are traditionally taking advantage of. The natural capital is one of the most important assets of the area in terms of biodiversity and landscape. The report of CARTIF shows that there is a need to work on areas related to the ecosystem services and sustainable touristic offers. Although there are quite a lot of shops, restaurants and touristic facilities with local products, they are not very organized. There is a need to increase the number of places

with touristic services, train the locals to do business in a modern and more sustainable way (NC-01, NC-08). Branding the local products, services might be key to overcome this challenge.

Historic built heritage can play a key role in the heritage-led process if it is reused and maintained from a sustainability point of view. Overall performance in **Built Capital (BC)** allows for some improvements by using RURITAGE digital tools (BC-02 & BC-03). The area is not very close to the city center of İzmir but there is the train line and minibus service that connects İzmir with the area. Still it is not easy to reach every destination. Public transportation services can be improved (BC-08 & 09). With the help of recently joined Eurovelo route, cycle & hiking paths will be enhanced (BC-06 and BC-07). The signs and orienteering of the area need to be improved (BC15&BC16). The area is very rich with its local products or traditional foods / crafts and events organized to promote these products, but the branding and promotion activities are quite weak and need to be enhanced.

Social capital (SC) reflects the connections among people and organizations or the social “glue” to make things, positive or negative, happen and SC scores of the area is quite low. İzmir is quite a populated city with a lot of stakeholders. There are many volunteers, associations, NGOs that wants to do something for the territory some of whom have high resources like the Chamber of Bergama or just do volunteering work. And yet SC area is one of the weakest points of the area. The main problem is the lack of collaboration between different parties. RURITAGE project and the tools it offers can be the driving force to enhance the collaboration culture since the stakeholders came together quite often the last 18 months. Although participants in projects involving people with disabilities is high (SC-06a), there is still room for improvement in most of the other indicators.

In RURITAGE, **Human Capital (HC)** is improved through practices that contribute to the health, training & education of the population. Some of the actions that we have been planned in the area are related with increasing the capabilities of the local inhabitants to improve and create new offers for visitors or to use new developments, techniques and/or technologies in their production processes. It is important for them to learn how to promote their services and products. Hopefully, RURITAGE will enable the locals to increase their income by providing more value-added services.

Financial Capital (FC) refers to the financial resources available to invest in community capacity-building. In RURITAGE, the financial capital is understood as a mean to achieve the growing of the other capitals. As seen from the results there is a huge tourism income potential, but the business environments are not very promising for new businesses (FC05-FC06). One of the reasons is the aging and depopulation as indicated in the challenges. One of the main incomes (pine nuts) has decreased due to low harvest. Some of our actions will try to overcome this issue by finding other value-added products from pine trees or other business opportunities for locals (pensioning, etc.).

Figure 44: R6 performance (baseline calculation)

© RURITAGE monitoring platform, using Grafana

11.1.4 The main challenges

Five main challenges have been identified in the region. All the challenges proposed by the report are mainly connected to economy and livelihood of the citizens of the area. There is unemployment within the area due to the loss of harvest and agriculture in general not being very profitable in the country. Also, youth move to cities looking for employment opportunities. The impossibility of transmitting traditional crafts, arts, food to younger generations would lead to loss of cultural heritage. Since elderly population is higher in the region; access to innovation, emergence of new ideas or new ways of doing business is quite low. Also, there is no awareness about the distinctive heritage values of the region and the potential that can be used for economic development. There are some widely known cultural heritage sites but they lack of touristic attractions and offers and of marketing strategies; as a consequence, the overnight stay rates are quite low. The livelihood of the citizens could have been much higher if the area was widely recognized, promoted and the service providers for tourism were more organized. The lack of a comprehensive inventory on the cultural and natural assets of Bakircay Basin prevents to identify the potential areas/clusters to develop and to take the necessary actions to enhance the tourism potential of the area.

The actions planned in the heritage-led regeneration plan and further described in the operational programme will tackle all these challenges. The enhancement of the landscape and natural heritage combined with the powerful promotion of cultural heritage will enhance the feeling of identity, livelihood of the citizens living within the region. Specific challenges are described here below:

Main challenges	
C1	Depopulation and ageing of the local population
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Population ageing represents a challenge as the percentage of elderly population is continuously increasing. The most important causes of poverty in the county are under-employment, lack of jobs, low level of income, poor infrastructures, difficult access to specialized social and medical services; the aging tendency, etc. Decreasing harvest of many products and especially of pine nuts are affecting the livelihood of people in the area. This is also one of the reasons of depopulation. Depopulation is recognized as a challenge as a great percentage of the active population seeking employment opportunities abroad.
C2	Lack of recognition of distinctive cultural and natural heritage of the region
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Depopulation has been causing the loss of local traditions and cultural heritages like arts and crafts. Lack of a comprehensive inventory on cultural and natural assets of Bakircay Basin prevents to see potential areas/clusters to develop, and to take necessary actions Unawareness on heritage values causes loss on authentic rural identity. Lack of adequate infrastructures to make linkage between cultural and natural assets of the landscape
C3	Lack of efforts and motivation to explore alternatives potential income sources
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Lack of cooperation among stakeholders causes waste of time and resources. There is a need to engage experts, volunteers, NGO's and private sector with locals and to work for clusters constituting local power.
C4	No marketing and branding strategies for the products of the area (food, art, crafts)
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Low use and understanding of marketing and promotion activities. New ways of doing business need to be investigated. Social media, on-line marketing and selling strategies, etc. Number of local people educated/experienced touristic activities and services sector is insufficient. Lack of adequate infrastructure to make linkage between cultural and natural assets of the landscape.
C5	High risk on extinctions of cultural and natural heritage assets (arts & crafts, natural resources)
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> There is only one parchment master in Bergama district across the region.

- There are too many mining areas in the region which are close to natural resources.
- The pine trees are being cut by the owners because of decreasing productivity of pine nuts

11.2 Overall objectives of the plan

The overall objective of this heritage-led regeneration plan is to create an integrated landscape management model for the case study area based on local cultural and natural resources and crossing the different SIAs. The developed model will work as an effective showcase for rural regeneration. The action plan tries to achieve the main objective focusing on the local assets of landscape, arts, food and handicrafts revealing tangible and intangible heritage of the community. Economic objectives are more focused on local food and its relation with tourism activities.

Landscape consists of various CNH assets that will be taken into account as drivers for the rural regeneration of the area where social, cultural, economic, environmental, technic and technological aspects are considered. Micro and macro scale actions of RURITAGE will generate a ground for policy and investment decision to go further. This action plan is developed to fulfill the general objective of ensuring the sustainability of Bakircay Basin’s peculiar landscape qualities and improving the welfare and the quality of life of local people through natural and cultural heritage led strategies. The specific objectives linked to Bakircay Basin are listed as follows against our challenges:

Figure 45: Schematic representation of local cultural, natural and built environment heritage

Specific objectives	
O1	Create new sources of income through natural and cultural heritage development
Linked with challenges	
C1	De-population and elderly residents
C3	Lack of efforts and motivation to explore alternatives potential income sources
C4	No marketing and branding strategies for the products of the area and the region as a whole
O2	Improve partnership and collaboration among different stakeholders of the region for the integrated landscape management
Linked with challenges	
C1	Depopulation and elderly residents
C2	Lack of recognition of distinctive cultural and natural heritage of the region
C3	Lack of efforts and motivation to explore alternatives potential income sources
C4	No marketing and branding strategies for the products of the area and the region as a whole
C5	High risk on extinctions of cultural and natural heritage assets (arts & crafts, natural resources)
O3	Increase the strong sense of belonging by raising awareness of the importance and sustainability of the cultural and natural assets for the region
Linked with challenges	
C2	Lack of recognition of distinctive cultural and natural heritage of the region
C5	High risk on extinctions of cultural and natural heritage assets (arts & crafts, natural resources)
C3	Lack of visibility
O4	To foster the visibility and the value of local food production
Linked with challenges	
C1	Depopulation and elderly residents
C2	Lack of recognition of distinctive cultural and natural heritage of the region
C4	No marketing and branding strategies for the products of the area and the region as a whole
O5	Prevent the extinction of the natural heritages and use them as driver for creating economic values
Linked with challenges	
C1	Depopulation and elderly residents
C4	No marketing and branding strategies for the products of the area and the region as a whole
C5	High risk on extinctions of cultural and natural heritage assets (arts & crafts, natural resources)
O6	To foster the visibility and the value of local food production
Linked with challenges	
C1	Depopulation and elderly residents
C4	No marketing and branding strategies for the products of the area and the region as a whole
C5	High risk on extinctions of cultural and natural heritage assets (arts & crafts, natural resources)

11.3 Operational programme for the implementation of the plan

This section is dedicated to draft the operational programme for the implementation of the actions of the heritage-led regeneration strategies. The operational programme contains one detailed factsheet for each action.

CNH-led rural regeneration is adopted, locals and local actors are taken into account as main stakeholders while the action plan is being prepared. The Methodology of the RURITAGE project contains participatory approaches and tools for co-creation processes towards enhancing CNH. After a series of workshops, building upon the lessons learnt from Role Models of RURITAGE project, and round-table meetings with stakeholders, the actions of the heritage-led regeneration plan have been identified to foster rural development, enhance its CNH and empower rural communities.

No	Action	SIA	Challenge(s)	Objective(s)
R6.1	Building of a Geology road map through Citizen science	Landscape	C2, C5	O2, O3
R6.2	Researching on biodiversity in the villages to improve economic resilience	Resilience, Landscape	C1,C3,C5	O1,O2,O4,O6
R6.3	Developing ethnobotanic activities in Bergama region	Landscape, Resilience, Local Food	C2,C3,C5	O1,O2,O4,O6
R6.4	Celebrating cultural diversity of Bakircay Basin	Art & Festival	C1,C2,C5	O2, O3,O5
R6.5	Improve and promote the connection routes between cultural and natural assets in Bakircay Basin.	Pilgrimage, Landscape	C2,C5	O2, O3
R6.6	Increasing the capacity of locals for more touristic offers (accommodation, waitressing, hosting etc.)	Landscape, Resilience	C1,C2,C3,C4,C5	O1,O2,O3,O4,O6
R6.7	Promotion of basket weaving in Bakircay Basin	Art & Festival	C2,C5	O2,O3, O5
R6.8	Promote ownership of cultural and natural heritage of Bakircay Basin via Forest School	Landscape	C1,C2,C5	O2, O5, O6
R6.9	Enhancing the local food culture in Bakircay Basin	Local Food	C1,C3,C4,C5	O2,O4,O5

11.3.1 The actions in detail

Code of the action		R6.1
Title of the action		Building of a Geology road map through Citizen science
Relevant SIA or SIAs		Landscape
Relevant Heritage		Tangible – Natural, Intangible - Knowledge and Practices
Reference RM (code and name)	Action/s	<p>RM 8-4 Enhance the narrative of the place and promote the discovering of the territory through history</p> <p>RM 11-1 Develop a participative process for the recognition and the evaluation of the tangible and intangible cultural and natural heritage features</p> <p>RM12-1 Promote joint actions (also through PPP) to enhance heritage resources and create an internationally recognized brand</p>
Useful lesson/s Learned (code and name)		<p>LL15 Foster a better understanding of the tangible and intangible values of natural and cultural heritage and create a recognized value as a driver for local development</p> <p>LL37 Engage knowledge partners (universities, research centre, etc.) in the process</p> <p>LL15 Identifying your natural heritage resources</p>
Responsible person		Koray Velibeyoğlu (IZTECH), Alper Baba (IZTECH)
Relevant RM/KFP involved		<p>RM6 Boosting migrant integration with nature in Lesvos Island (Greece): Our territory is really close to Lesvos Island and has geographical similarities, RM6 will share experiences on their geopark management.</p> <p>UNESCO can help us to create “RURITAGE volunteer” certificate for non-official stakeholders/participants in the project.</p>
Brief description of the action		This action will create a participatory map of tangible heritage by using “citizen science” as a participation tool in which local volunteers will be involved in data collection and analysis. The initial study will be carried out by international students and academics who are interested in geological science as a summer workshop for the participatory mapping of geological heritage in Bergama and Dikili region. The results of this workshop will be

	discussed with local citizens to be tailored and adopted by them. This is also in line with task 7.4 'Community outreach'.
Objective and target of the action (by the end of the project)	<p>The main objective of this event is to create first draft of geological road map of Bergama and Dikili region that is an important first step to attract geo-tourists in the area. It also aims to initiate efforts becoming a geopark.</p> <p>1 summer school with around 15 international students in the field of geodesy and photogrammetry.</p> <p>2 workshops in the RHH with local citizens and stakeholders – at least 30 - to tailor and validate the summer workshop results.</p> <p>1 RURITAGE volunteering certificate to boost citizens participation and to make it certified and recognizable.</p>
Specific activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Development of the programme of the summer schools by Hacettepe University · Identification of the trainers, experts, teachers · Promotion and communication of the summer school/workshop through the university and the project communication channel · Implementation of the summer school: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Lecture sessions about the RURITAGE, project sites and the region Basic training on the scientific geological surveying methods Site survey of potential geo-trails Workshop sessions of making geology road maps in RURITAGE Izmir Coordination Centre <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Public discussion (with locals) of the results of the summer workshop and selection of geo-trails - Publication of material (maps, apps, to be decided) · Creating a "RURITAGE volunteering certificate" for the RURITAGE project
Monitoring plan and indicators	<p>SC-01 Number of citizens engagement activities</p> <p>SC-02 Number of participants in citizens engagement activities</p> <p>SC-05 Number of participants in formal or informal voluntary activities or active citizenship in the last 12 months</p> <p>HC-08 Number of people involved in professional management training course (summer school and master)</p>
Capital involved	Natural capital (geological assets), Human capital
Main stakeholders involved and their roles and contribution	<p>Izmir Institute of Technology, Izmir Metropolitan Municipality and Demir Energy (project partners) will provide basic training about the project, site and the scientific surveying methods in geology. Izmir Metropolitan Municipality will also provide domestic transfers to the site and nearby attractions.</p> <p>Hacettepe University Department of Geodesy and Photogrammetry (organizer of international student workshop) will provide international citizen science summer school organization.</p> <p>Yukarıbey Tourism Development Cooperative will provide basic logistics such as food, shelter (volunteer villagers in Kozak Plain) and local cultural activities.</p> <p>Chamber of Geology Engineers (Izmir Chapter) will provide technical assistance in site surveying.</p>
Beneficiaries	<p>The people in Kozak Plain where the RURITAGE Izmir Coordination Centre locates will largely benefit from this action.</p> <p>International students will benefit from learning basic scientific surveying methods.</p>
Formal partnership established (PPP, voluntary agreement, etc.)	<p>Voluntary participation of international students of Hacettepe University</p> <p>Joint event and scientific collaboration by universities in Izmir (Izmir Institute of Technology) and Ankara (Hacettepe University)</p> <p>Partnership between academia, Municipality and tourism cooperative</p>
Timeframe	April 2020 - May 2022
Indicative costs	€ 7,000
Indicative funding sources	<p>The main funding sources will be RURITAGE and Izmir Metropolitan Municipality. Hacettepe University will be funding their logistics, accommodation, courses)</p> <p>Bergama Chamber of Commerce, Bergama and Dikili Municipalities (district) also want to contribute to the studies. Some of the costs covered by the project might decrease.</p>

Sustainability of the action	After the project, the collaborative data obtained from citizen science activity will be refined by the experts involved in the process. The geology road map production process will be launched. It mainly contributes to attract geo-tourists to the region as well as a background material to Izmir Geopark application. This citizen science activity can also be repeated by other RURITAGE volunteers that would be mostly students of the IZTECH and other universities interested.
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Code of the action	R6.2
Title of the action	Researching on biodiversity in the villages to improve economic resilience
Relevant SIA or SIAs	Resilience, Landscape
Relevant Heritage	Tangible- Natural, Intangible - Knowledge and Practices
Reference RM (code and name)	RM3-3 Definition of marketing and communication strategies for the products RM13-2 External Monitoring Group to ensure robust systems in place to ensure that there are no adverse effects on the environment. RM13-4 Action Plan for Jobs developed for the region and the State RM11-1 Design a framework for integrated management RM3-6 Social innovation ideas
Useful lesson/s Learned (code and name)	LL05 Collaborative approaches to achieve innovative financing solutions and access to funding LL15 Identify heritage resources (formal and informal), foster a better understanding of the tangible and intangible values of natural and cultural heritage and create a recognized value as a driver for local development LL37 Engage knowledge partners (universities, research centre, etc.) in the process LL31 Improve resilience of natural and cultural environments against natural hazards LL18 Implementation of participatory approach and involvement of local people, including private owners, from early stage. LL01 Adapt agricultural techniques to climate change
Responsible person	Koray Velibeyoğlu (IZTECH), Zeynep Durmuş Arsan (IZTECH)
Relevant RM/KFP involved	RM13-Wild Atlantic Way (Ireland) RM9- Teaching culture for learning resilience in Crete museum from university (Greece) UOP – University of Plymouth
Brief description of the action	The drop in the harvesting of pine nut in Kozak Plateau has led to search for new income sources related to by-products of pine trees and other forest resources. This action proposes diversified sources of income for Kozak community by using natural assets of the region as a driver for new economic sources, understanding value of ethnobotanics and flora with high biodiversity in the region.
Objective and target of the action (by the end of the project)	Objectives of the action: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · To prevent the cutting of pine nut trees due to the decrease of pine nuts yield · To create alternative income instead of pine nut production · To define biodiversity of territory Quantifiable targets of the action can be listed as: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · One map of local biodiversity · One report on economic feasibility of the proposed alternative · At least 2 citizens will be trained to boost learning on alternative products · Rising income levels will reflect on the decrease of migration trend from rural to urban · Number of villager family that have additional sources of income instead of pine nut - at least two within the timeline of the project · Number of villager family, changed their main sources of income - at least two within the timeline of the project ·

Specific activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Organizing a meeting to provide a wider understanding of biodiversity to the RHHs stakeholders and citizens Collaborating with experts for field work to define biodiversity and to map it (possible link with Landscape connect app, developed in WP5) Preparing an economic feasibility report that is based on pine resin and other forest resources in Kozak Plateau to determine alternative income sources Ensuring the involvement of citizens by meetings/trainings to encourage in order to add other products to their income sources and create new businesses Knowledge transfer for the best production method for pine resin, trainings to locals about alternative products. Disseminate the results of this action at local level (including it in other planned dissemination and RHH activities)
Monitoring plan and indicators	<p>SC-01 Number of citizens engagement activities SC-02 Number of participants in citizens engagement activities SC-03 Number per type of stakeholder involved HC-05 Number of self-employees FC-03 Number of PPPs set and signed</p>
Capital involved	Social capital, human capital, financial capital
Main stakeholders involved and their roles and contribution	Izmir Metropolitan Municipality Izmir Institute of Technology Bioeconomy Cooperative
Beneficiaries	Local people Natural heritage Pine nut trees Regional economy RURITAGE volunteers
Formal partnership established (PPP, voluntary agreement, etc.)	Formal partnership with Bioeconomy Cooperative
Timeframe	May – December 2020
Indicative costs	€ 5,000
Indicative funding sources	RURITAGE budget 8000€ Co-funding by İzmir 1300€
Sustainability of the action	Through this action we will provide to economic resilience for local people offering alternatives to the harvesting of pine nut in Kozak Plateau. If the new income sources will result to be sustainable the action will be further boosted and sustained.

Code of the action	R6.3
Title of the action	Developing ethnobotanic activities in Bergama region
Relevant SIA or SIAs	Landscape, Resilience, Local Food
Relevant Heritage	Tangible - Natural
Reference RM Action/s (code and name)	<p>RM3-1 Support local farmers and producers in innovation projects RM12-1 Promote joint actions (also through PPP) to enhance heritage resources and create an internationally recognized brand RM3-6 Social innovation ideas RM4-5 Define an action plan for the communication of the biodiversity of the area.</p>
Useful lesson/s Learned (code and name)	<p>LL06 Create a 'brand' based on natural resources and added value created LL15 Identifying your natural heritage resources LL37 Engage knowledge partners (universities, research centre, etc.) in the process LL01 Adapt agricultural techniques to climate change</p>
Responsible person	Assoc. Prof. Dr. Zeynep Durmuş Arsan (IZTECH)

Relevant RM/KFP involved	RM12- Douro cultural landscape, driver for economic and social development (Spain) UOP – University of Plymouth
Brief description of the action	Planned activities under this action aims to build knowledge on ethnobotanical potential, train local people /producers and to have value-added products. Some of the villagers might start growing new herbs/products that can increase their income level. 17 villages of the plateau will be involved.
Objective and target of the action (by the end of the project)	This action aims to bring a new business area with a high economic return to local people basing on the enhancement of the natural resources of the landscape. Quantifiable targets can be listed as: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · List of ethnobotanical plants and products of the region – coming from Action R6_2 · At least 2 organized workshop activities on ethnobotanical herbs · At least 2 meeting organized with local stakeholders (with villages of Kozak Plateau – beginning and end of the action) · At least 20 trained citizens (locals) · At least 3 experimental study on ethnobotanical products Qualitative targets can be listed as: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Locals will reach knowledge about ethnobotanical presence
Specific activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Organize meeting with the leaders of Kozak villages in the Hub to inform about planned ethnobotanical activities in the Plateau, introduce the research team, explain the purposes, and announce the field study (related action 2) · Prepare the list of ethnobotanical herbs and products of the region, having cultural heritage value, based on the literature survey · Perform the field work within totally 30 days in the villages · Organize meeting with the leaders of Kozak villages in the Hub to present the results, underline specific ethnobotanical products with high economic added value and open discussion about encouraging for new entrepreneurship · Organize workshops and trainings in the Hub to carry out experimental study on particular ethnobotanical products and show the dynamic relations between plants and land-owners to have additional income (in parallel with action 2) · Local media and journalist can be invited to the workshop for a wider dissemination
Monitoring plan and indicators	SC-02 Number of participants in citizens engagement activities SC-03 Number per type of stakeholder involved (according to the ones defined in D.3.1) SC-04 Number of local associations involved SC-05 Number of participants in formal or informal voluntary activities or active citizenship in the last 12 months HC-02 Number of recreational facilities/events
Capital involved	Natural capital, social capital, human capital
Main stakeholders involved and their roles and contribution	Izmir Metropolitan Municipality Ege University, Department of Biology -human capital Ege University, Faculty of Agriculture - human capital
Beneficiaries	Local people, especially women Natural resources Academics Local producers RURITAGE volunteers
Formal partnership established (PPP, voluntary agreement, etc.)	Formal partnership with Ege University (Department of Biology, Faculty of Agriculture)
Timeframe	June 2021 – April 2022
Indicative funding sources	€ 8,500
Sustainability of the action	The region has substantial potential about ethnobotanic however there is need for R&D activities to obtain value-added products for expanding income sources and articulate. Participation of Agriculture Faculty of Ege University will ensure research sustainability.

Code of the action		R6.4
Title of the action	Celebrating cultural diversity of Bakircay Basin	
Relevant SIA or SIAs	Art & Festival	
Relevant Heritage	Intangible - Social Practices, Rituals and Festive Events - Performing arts	
Reference RM Action/s (code and name)	RM8-2 Promote and support local traditional activities RM8-4 Enhance the narrative of the place and promote the discovering of the territory through history	
Useful lesson/s Learned (code and name)	LL15 Identify heritage resources (formal and informal), foster a better understanding of the tangible and intangible values of natural and cultural heritage and create a recognized value as a driver for local development. LL08 Collaborative approach with other organizations or local activities to increase impact of the actions LL07 Create 'tourist pack and experiences' based on the different clusters (culture, food & wine, nature, religion, etc.) and sell combined packages, including transport	
Responsible person	Demet Burçin Gezgin (IZM), Duygu Türkmen (IZM), Hüseyin Çırak (IZM)	
Relevant RM/KFP involved	RM7 Take Art: Sustainable rural arts development (United Kingdom) RM8 The Living Village of the Middle Age, Visegrad (Hungary) UNESCO	
Brief description of the action	This action will provide opportunity to bring cultures together via organizing cross cultural events for exchange of music. It will also increase the recognition of the region and the ownership of local heritage by citizens. This is also in line with Task 7.4.	
Objective and target of the action (by the end of the project)	The main aim of this action is sustaining music culture of the region, building sense of identity by using unifying power of music. Quantifiable targets can be listed as: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · At least 10 local, 6 international musicians that are involved in the festival · At least 500 attendances to the festival Qualitative targets can be listed as: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Multi-cultural environment of the festival will support social engagement 	
Specific activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Organizing the music (trumpet) ateliers with local musicians · Organization of cross-cultural musical festival (Music of Roman-Lesvos, Music of Alevi) · Get in touch with local musicians · Develop a festival programme · Invite artists from different cultures · Arrange documentation of the festival (photos & recordings) · Promotion activities for the festival · Implementation of the festival 	
Monitoring plan and indicators	CC-05 Number of posts mentioning RURITAGE at local level CC-02 Increment in number of mentions of CNH in social media, media, press, etc. CC-03 Number of users registered in the digital hub or following the social networks (facebook, twitter) CC-04 Number of posts in the digital hub CC-05 Number of posts mentioning RURITAGE at local level CC-09 Number of people trained in traditional skills CC-11 Total number of arrivals of tourist in the last year SC-05 Number of participants in formal or informal voluntary activities or active citizenship in the last 12 months BC-14 Number of fairs and tourism events per year related to the promotion of the area and related products	
Capital involved	Cultural capital, social capital, built capital	
Main stakeholders involved and their roles and contribution	TEOS Culture Art Association (knowledge transfer, national and international relations, and management) RURITAGE volunteers (Complementary stakeholders)	

Beneficiaries	Local musicians Tourists International Cultural Associations RURITAGE volunteers Cultural heritage Music culture Trumpet tradition
Formal partnership established (PPP, voluntary agreement, etc.)	Formal partnership with TEOS Culture and Arts Association
Timeframe	Dec 2020 – July 2021
Indicative costs	€ 16,000
Indicative funding sources	RURITAGE budget 13,250€ Co-funding by Izmir 2,750€
Sustainability of the action	Izmir Metropolitan Municipality will create a calendar to sustain this cross-cultural festival to sustain diversity of music culture in the region which has strong relation with lifestyles and daily activities of the locals. This action will support both citizen engagement and sustainability of the music culture.

Code of the action	R6.5
Title of the action	Improve and promote the connection routes between cultural and natural assets in Bakircay Basin
Relevant SIA or SIAs	Landscape, Pilgrimage
Relevant Heritage	Tangible – Natural
Reference RM Action/s (code and name)	RM1-6 Digitalization of the pilgrimage - through websites, GIS maps, apps. RM2-2 Expand the offer, promoting eco-tourism: link the pilgrimage route to other activities
Useful lesson/s Learned (code and name)	LL02 Application of IT technologies LL16 Foster and promote sustainable tourism LL06 Create a ‘brand’ or ‘tourist pack and experiences’ based on the natural resources and the added valued created – synergies with other local activities
Responsible person	Demet Burçin Gezgin (IZM), Duygu Türkmen (IZM), Hüseyin Çırak (IZM)
Relevant RM/KFP involved	RM1- Camino de Santiago (Spain) RM2- Via Maria (Romania) BORGHI
Brief description of the action	In collaboration with the transportation department, the connection routes between Pergamon-Smyrna-Ephesus corridor will be improved adding new cycle lanes, increasing alternative ways of accessing to the replicator area through bike and pilgrimage routes. With the additional signs the hikers, bikers will be oriented much better. The routes will be promoted to attract more visitors to the area.
Objective and target of the action (by the end of the project)	This action aims to increase accessibility to rural areas where cultural and natural assets exist and have insufficient accessibility. Specifically, this action aims at promoting “connection routes” between Pilgrimage Route (Pergamon-Smyrna-Ephesus historical corridor), Eurovelo Route in the north region and IZBAN line. This action fits with the overall aim of promoting integrated landscape management within this replicators’ case in the RURITAGE project. Quantifiable targets can be listed as: - at least 1 sub-cycling route will be defined - at least 80 km cycling route will be defined - at least 3 historical landmarks will be defined to connect cycling route - 2 workshops organize to define new sub-cycling routes

	By the end of 2020, there will be further discussion on feasible quantitative target and timeline of this action that can be reviewed afterwards.
Specific activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Collaboration with transportation department of greater municipality and other district municipalities. Organizing coordination meetings and workshop · Organizing a participatory workshop in the RHHs to define the route through the region · Organizing a cycling tour to test the draft route · Making the necessary arrangements by driving on the Draft Bicycle Route and determining the final version of the route · Implementation of RURITAGE Izmir Cycle Route as a sub-route to the EUROVELO · Creating the necessary visuals (map video brochure, etc.) for promotion · Launch event of the new RURITAGE Izmir Cycle Route -maybe to be integrated with other foreseen communication activities
Monitoring plan and indicators	<p>BC-06 Cycle paths (Km) BC-07 Pedestrian/hiking paths (km) BC-08 Share of people served by public transport services BC-09 Number of shared transport services (bike sharing, car sharing, etc.) BC-15 Number of sites provided with signals and explanation panels to help describing the sites and orienteering visitors BC-16 Number of km of routes provided with signals and explanation panels to help describing the sites and orienteering visitors</p>
Capital involved	Cultural, built and social capital
Main stakeholders involved and their roles and contribution	Izmir Metropolitan Municipality Department of Transportation (IZM) IZBAN Other District Municipalities (Selcuk, Bergama)
Beneficiaries	Bike users Tourists Local people of Ephesus, Smyrna, Pergamon
Formal partnership established (PPP, voluntary agreement, etc.)	Most of the actions will be done by the Transportation Department of the Municipality. The local district Municipalities will support the Metropolitan Municipality within their jurisdiction areas. (already supports of RURITAGE project)
Timeframe	2020 - 2021 Promotion activities will be done afterwards and even beyond the timeframe of RURITAGE project
Indicative costs	€ 20,500
Indicative funding sources	RURITAGE budget 20,500€ Co-financing by Izmir 6000 € Support from other district municipalities
Sustainability of the action	The Transport Department of Izmir Municipality gets involved to this action that will bring a metropolitan scale accessibility approach. Accessibility network will be designed large scale and implementation will continue after also RURITAGE project.

Code of the action	R6.6
Title of the action	Increasing the capacity of locals for more touristic offers (accommodation, waitressing, hosting etc.)
Relevant SIA or SIAs	Landscape, Resilience
Relevant Heritage	Tangible – Built
Reference RM Action/s (code and name)	RM3-3 Definition of marketing and communication strategies for the products RM8-4 Enhance the narrative of the place and promote the discovering of the territory

	RM9-1 Organizing training - also using informal education methodology- to improve the resilience of local people (children, adults and elderly people, professionals, public authorities etc...)
Useful lesson/s Learned (code and name)	LL18 Implementation of participatory approach and involvement of local people, including private owners, from early stage. LL06 Create a 'brand' or 'tourist pack and experiences' based on the natural resources and the added valued created – synergies with other local activities (i.e. festival, food, etc.)
Responsible person	Demet Burçin Gezgin , Hüseyin Çırak, Duygu Türkmen (İzmir Metropolitan Municipality)
Relevant RM/KFP involved	RM3, RM8 RM9 BITN
Brief description of the action	This action is about increasing the capacity of the local people for touristic offers. The action is directly related with the sustainable development of the region. The strategy of the Izmir Metropolitan area is to enhance natural and cultural assets of the region which will eventually increase the tourist arrivals. After training local people about pensioning and other touristic offers a network of hotels will be established.
Objective and target of the action (by the end of the project)	The main objective of this action is to enhance the capabilities of the local people for touristic offers that shows the culture of the area as well as maintaining a certain standard to satisfy visitors and tourists. Quantifiable targets can be listed as: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · 20-25 people involved in the training · At least two trainings
Specific activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Define courses programs and trainers · A guideline will be prepared with relevant academicians, tourism experts · Define criteria for preselection of trainees and select the trainees to be involved in the program · Organizing "training courses" for pensioning and waitressing to increase capacity building for home boarding · Organizing meetings with local people to describe "distributed/diffused hotel network" · Define the villages and houses to be included in the hotel network · Creating "distributed/diffused hotel network (Albergo Diffuso)" in Kozak Plateau · Developing promotional materials (in synergy with action 9)
Monitoring plan and indicators	CC-05 Number of posts mentioning RURITAGE at local level CC-02 Increment in number of mentions of CNH in social media, media, press, etc. BC-04 Number of beds BC-05 Number of restaurants BC-11 Number of buildings restored/retrofitted BC-12 Number of reused buildings BC-13 Number of brands and labels granted for local products and services HC-05 Number of self-employees
Capital involved	Human capital, social capital, financial capital
Main stakeholders involved and their roles and contribution	Izmir Metropolitan Municipality Vocation Factory (IZM) Local Cooperatives Related Academics Local people attending to trainees
Beneficiaries	Unemployed people Hotels, bnb owners owners of underutilized building to introduce them to the possibility they have Other locals that will be affected indirectly (selling food, arts, crafts to tourists, job opportunities in pensions – local economy in general) RURITAGE volunteers
Formal partnership established (PPP,	Izmir Metropolitan Municipality already has a training program that will be used in the area and they are official RURITAGE partners

voluntary agreement, etc.)	
Timeframe	February 2020 – May 2022
Indicative costs	€ 8,750
Indicative funding sources	RURITAGE budget 7250€ Izmir Metropolitan Municipality – co financing – 1500€
Sustainability of the action	The training has already been developed and used in other areas. It will be adapted to other area conditions, in case is successful.

Code of the action	R6.7
Title of the action	Promotion of basket weaving in Bakircay Basin
Relevant SIA or SIAs	Art & Festival
Relevant Heritage	Intangible - Traditional craftsmanship
Reference RM Action/s (code and name)	RM8-2 Promote and support local traditional activities (branding, high quality standards, clustering, internationalization, etc.) RM8-4 Enhance the narrative of the place and promote the discovering of the territory through history
Useful lesson/s Learned (code and name)	LL08 Collaborative approach with other organizations or local activities to increase impact of the actions LL15 Identify heritage resources (formal and informal), foster a better understanding of the tangible and intangible values of natural and cultural heritage and create a recognized value as a driver for local development LL28 Promote access to all ages and abilities and ensure fruition of cultural resources to all, including transport and online information
Responsible person	Oya Tabanoğlu (DEM), Gonca Akgül (DEM), Esra Demir (DEM)
Relevant RM/KFP involved	BITN, UNESCO, RM8
Brief description of the action	To prevent the extinction of traditional crafts more people and especially young people need to learn about how to weave a basket.
Objective and target of the action (by the end of the project)	This action is about preventing the extinction of the traditional crafts, increasing awareness about the traditions of the local people to increase the feel of identity as well as increasing the recognition of the visitors of the area. Quantifiable targets can be listed as: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · At least 12 people to be trained for basket weaving · Organizing 2 workshops about basket weaving
Specific activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Organizing two workshops about basket weaving – local media will be also invited to further disseminate this action · Define new master candidates for basket weaving · Organizing training activities for new basket weaving masters · Promotion of the courses · Promotion of baskets
Monitoring plan and indicators	CC-09 Number of people trained in traditional skills CC-06 Number of actions and cultural events produced by citizens at local level CC-07 Number of people reached by actions and cultural events produced by citizens at local level CC-10 Number of places involved in the tourism offer CC-11 Total number of arrivals of tourist in the last year
Capital involved	Human capital, cultural capital

Main stakeholders involved and their roles and contribution	Demir Enerji Izmir Metropolitan Municipality (co-financing) Vocation Factory Public Education Center
Beneficiaries	Cultural heritage of parchment Cultural heritage (basket weaving) Izmir and Turkey New masters Masters' weaving Traditions RURITAGE volunteers
Formal partnership established (PPP, voluntary agreement, etc.)	N/A
Timeframe	May 2020 – September 2021
Indicative costs	€ 5,750
Indicative funding sources	RURITAGE project 5000€ Izmir Metropolitan Municipality (co-financing) 750€ Vocation Factory Public Education Center
Sustainability of the action	Sustainability of the action depends on the number of people that the knowledge will be transferred. There are people willing to learn basket weaving. After training of the people, they will be offered to teach to other people interested or even people from their own families.

Code of the action	R6.8
Title of the action	Promote ownership of Cultural and Natural Heritage of Bakircay Basin via Forest Schools
Relevant SIA or SIAs	Landscape
Relevant Heritage	Tangible – Natural, Intangible - Knowledge and Practices
Reference RM Action/s (code and name)	RM8-2 Promote and support local traditional activities RM8-4 Enhance the narrative of the place and promote the discovering of the territory through history: guided tours, thematic excursions, games, re-enactments.
Useful lesson/s Learned (code and name)	LL06 Create a 'brand' based on natural resources and added value created LL15 Identifying your natural heritage resources LL18 Implementation of participatory approach and involvement of local people from early stage LL21 Integration of vulnerable groups of value chain LL07 Create 'tourist pack and experiences' based on the different clusters (culture, food & wine, nature, religion, etc.) and sell combined packages, including transport LL08: Collaborative approach with other organizations or local activities to increase impact of the actions
Responsible person	Oya Tabanoğlu (DEM), Gonca Akgül (DEM), Esra Demir (DEM)
Relevant RM/KFP involved	RM10, UNESCO
Brief description of the action	This action focuses on building ownership of Natural and Cultural Heritage by the local community. Organizing training activities, storytelling occasions and playing games that are related with natural and cultural assets with children and young adults form the activities under this action. Collaboration with associations and schools will be established for this aim where consultations will be provided by story writers, game builders, psychologists, sociologists, historians, local contributors. This action is in line

	with the objective of Task 7.4 ‘Community Outreach’ and could make use of the co-monitoring tool developed in Task 5.2.
Objective and target of the action (by the end of the project)	<p>Main objectives: to transfer and sustain cultural identity, to prevent loss of cultural and natural heritage and to create sense of belonging among local people and especially younger generations. Forest school is an inspiring learning method applied in forest or wooded areas that provides an environment in which all students or young adults with active participation where they can develop self-esteem.</p> <p>Quantifiable targets can be listed as:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · 240 trainees (students between 12 and 28 for the years of 2020 and 2021) · 6 forest school will be done <p>Qualitative targets can be listed as:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · The interaction and sharing between local people will increase.
Specific activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Define forest school activities schedule · Organizing 6 forest school activities with children in the region to build awareness on natural heritage of the region
Monitoring plan and indicators	<p>CC-09 Number of people trained in traditional skills</p> <p>CC-06 Number of actions and cultural events produced by citizens at local level</p> <p>CC-07 Number of people reached by actions and cultural events produced by citizens at local level</p>
Capital involved	Cultural capital, natural capital, human capital
Main stakeholders involved and their roles and contribution	<p>Izmir Metropolitan Municipality (IZM)</p> <p>Good Works Association (GID) -human capital (knowledge share)</p>
Beneficiaries	<p>Local people</p> <p>Local associations</p> <p>Local children in elementary education: urban explorer kids</p> <p>Local students in high school education</p> <p>Students in elementary and high school institutions</p> <p>University students</p>
Formal partnership established (PPP, voluntary agreement, etc.)	Formal partnership with GID (an NGO)
Timeframe	April 2020 – April 2022
Indicative costs	€ 3,750
Indicative funding sources	RURITAGE budget 3000€ co-funding budget, the NGO will also fund the game activities with human resources 750€
Sustainability of the action	<p>Through RURITAGE project, we will have opportunity to connect children with nature, and raise awareness about their own natural and cultural heritage values. After the project, it is possible to expect that the same children will become the guardians of region, and will influence for younger generations.</p> <p>The forest school activities organized through the project will increase the number of young trainers and local practitioners working for new children-family related activities.</p>

Code of the action	R6.9
Title of the action	Enhancing the local food culture in Bakircay Basin
Relevant SIA or SIAs	Local Food
Relevant Heritage	Tangible – Natural, Intangible - Social Practices, Rituals and Festive Events

<p>Reference RM Action/s (code and name)</p>	<p>RM13-1 To set out a strategy and an implementation framework and programme for the sustainable implementation of the Wild Atlantic Way (food strategic plan) RM3-5 Promote the environmental sustainability of the food production, packaging and selling RM3-3 Definition of marketing and communication strategies for the products RM3-1 Support local farmers and producers in innovation projects RM4-10 Design a calendar of each fair of folk heritage and festivals to promote tourism RM3-6 Social innovation ideas</p>
<p>Useful lesson/s Learned (code and name)</p>	<p>LL04 Build sense of belonging, individual and community self-confidence and increased autonomy through CNH. LL08 Create synergies and foster a collaborative approach with other organizations, programs or local activities and attractors of the territory to increase impact of the actions. LL07 Create 'tourist pack and experiences' based on the different clusters (culture, food & wine, nature, religion, etc.) and sell combined packages, including transport LL37 Discover economic values of traditional food (e.g. traditional fish processing, historical orchards and fruit production) and use it as a way to protect historical landscape</p>
<p>Responsible person</p>	<p>Demet Burçin Gezgin (IZM), Duygu Türkmen (IZM), Hüseyin Çırak (IZM)</p>
<p>Relevant RM/KFP involved</p>	<p>RM3 Preserving old traditions for innovating agro-food production in Apulia (Italy) RM13 Wild Atlantic Way (Ireland) BORGHI</p>
<p>Brief description of the action</p>	<p>Lack of well-known food brands, absence of standardization, weak food security and insufficient organizational activities about gastronomical qualities of Kozak villages requires joint actions for the valorization of local food production and selling. This action tries to create incentive mechanisms for small and medium-sized enterprises and entrepreneurs working with innovative ideas for new local food-based products. In this action, necessary new contacts and branding processes will be carried out for the products in Kozak villages. The recognition of Kozak regional products will be ensured by creating a certain promoting quality assurance and relating it with an improved image of the territory for the target buyers with the joint brand. The possible exploitation of the RURITASTE brand will be explored.</p>
<p>Objective and target of the action (by the end of the project)</p>	<p>The objective of this action is to have raise the awareness on local food standard and the importance of being a network to create a comprehensive marketing strategy for the local products of the region. It will enable to add value to the products; services offered and raise the livelihood of locals. Quantifiable targets can be listed as: At least one new local food brands in Kozak villages- possible adoption of the RURITASTE brand will be explored 5 social media releases 2 culinary activities within local food festival 1 webpages created At least 15 villagers trained for local food standardization</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Marketing and communication strategy for at least one selected products · One logo design · One cloth bag design
<p>Specific activities</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Organize a roundtable meeting with all potential partners in the Bakircay about branding, benefits, · Meet with BERTO (Bergama Chamber of Trade) to formalize the procedures of branding, licensing, promotion and selling · Organize training courses about local food standardization · Organize a promotional meeting with all potential partners in all villages to inform possible local products related to medicinal herbs (connected with action 3 about ethnobotanics) · Development of the brand visual identity and communication strategy – uptake of the RURITASTE communication strategy and criteria to be verified

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Periodically contact with local producers to increase communication and motivation · Periodically contact with local restaurants in Bergama and Kozak Plateau to promote the new brand · Organizing additional culinary activities within local food festivals to disseminate and promote local brands
Monitoring plan and indicators	<p>NC-07 Number of shops, restaurants and tourism facilities selling local products (KMO) HC-07 Number of people trained in IT and tourism (in specific SIA) HC-02 Number of recreational facilities/events BC-14 Number of fairs and tourism events per year related to the promotion of the area and related products</p>
Capital involved	Natural capital, human capital, built capital, financial capital
Main stakeholders involved and their roles and contribution	<p>Izmir Metropolitan Municipality Bergama Chamber of Commerce (BERTO) Vocation Factory Yasar University</p>
Beneficiaries	<p>Local people Tourists Bakircay Basin Local producers Local restaurants</p>
Formal partnership established (PPP, voluntary agreement, etc.)	<p>Formal partnership with "Tarım 4.0" Formal partnership with Universities Voluntary Agreements Public Private Partnership</p>
Timeframe	November 2020 - May 22
	€ 15,500
Indicative funding sources	<p>RURITAGE budget İzmir Metropolitan Municipality (co-financing) RURITAGE volunteers (volunteer work)</p>
Sustainability of the action	<p>Once the strategy and prototypes are out with the cooperation of local producers the strategy and the designs will be in use. The branding process requires time and consistent work that will continue after the project. The attempts taken though the project will create a locomotive effect in 17 Kozak villages to develop more standardized local food brands. Increasing demands for food-based products will increase to cope with challenges of poverty and depopulation.</p>

11.3.2 Timeline for the implementation

Action No:	Action Name:	2020												2021												2022				
		January	February	March	April	May	June	July	August	September	October	November	December	January	February	March	April	May	June	July	August	September	October	November	December	January	February	March	April	May
		20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	41	42	43	44	45	46	47	48
1	Building of a Geology road map through Citizen science																													
2	Resarching on biodiversity in the villages to improve economic resilience																													
3	Developing ethnobotanic activities in Bergama region																													
4	Celebrating cultural diversity of Bakircay Basin																													
5	Enhancing mobility of Bakircay's cultural and natural assets																													
6	Increasing the capacity of locals for more touristic offers (accommodation, dining, etc.)																													
7	Promotion of craft making in Bakircay Basin																													
8	Promote ownership of cultural and natural heritage of Bakircay Basin via Forest Schools																													
9	Enhancing the local food culture in Bakırçay Basin																													

11.4 Risks for the implementation of the plan

Risk N.	Action/s involved	Description of the risk	Mitigation action proposed
R1	Actions 1	Work done on geological features of site in the area might not be as productive as planned	The work plan of Hacettepe University and the methodology for the geo-trails will be asked in advance to ensure high quality work.
R2	Action 1 Action 2 Action 8	The collaboration with the locals to gather information about natural and cultural heritage might not be as informative as expected	It is important to align what is being offered and what is expected from the locals. The communication between the parties should be clear to overcome such conflicts.
R3	Action 2 Action 3	The field work for local food might not be as promising as expected	The results of the field work are not known. The expected result is to have value added products that can raise the income of the locals. The feasibility might end up with low income products.
R4	Action 3	Alternative vegetation might not be as supporting the income of locals	The results of the studies need to be validated. The marketing should be supportive to increase the income.
R5	Action 3	The local people might not be interested in learning about different herbs	The local people might not want to leave their comfort zone and try to adapt to new products. Close and open communication can be the key for success. Maybe small trials can be done with volunteers to show as good practice.
R6	Action 4	Music festivals might not be as interesting as thought for locals and for the artists	The festivals would be a good opportunity to promote the area. The area is also known with the musicians. With the collaboration among musicians from different cultures local people will find the promote the area, their products have more people coming to spend time in the area.
R7	Action 4 Action 5 Action 9	The collaboration with other departments of the Municipality and other stakeholders might be weak	For most of the action close relation with different departments and stakeholders is key for success.
R8	Action 6	The locals might not be as interested with pensioning as before	The locals should feel the support of the Municipality and the promotion should be effective. The affects would be seen in the mid-term and it is important to keep the expectations realistic.
R9	Action 7	There might not be enough candidates for trainings for traditional crafts	Communication and promotion could be the key.
R10	Action 4 Action 5 Action 6	Negative effects of climate change might diminish the sustainability of livelihoods in this hinterland region, negatively impacting sub-agricultural sector and tourism, the main income resources	During the studies about agricultural products the affects of climate change will be taken under consideration. The locals will be guided accordingly.
R11	Action 6	There is no specific action, mechanism or strategy to make sure natural and	The local food and tourism sectors planned for the area could attract new businesses.

	Action 9	historical areas utilized for developing innovative ideas and creating new entrepreneurship	Although not planned in the actions digitalization of some services or other new business areas for marketing and promoting the products might emerge.
R12	Action 1 Action 3 Action 5 Action 6	Natural and cultural resources at risk due to environmental factors. In particular, Bakırçay Basin is being polluted mostly from agricultural activities and mining industry.	Attracting more tourists and increasing the income levels of locals with other means of products they would be more sensitive to the environment. Locals will struggle with the mining companies or maybe not sell their lands to them.
R13	Action 1 Action 6	Lack of understanding and awareness on touristic potentials of geological formations at Kozak Plateau.	The geo trails produced at the end of Action 1 and additional touristic services offered should be communicated effectively to increase awareness.
R14	Action 5 Action 6	Inequalities reaching social services in mountainous areas of Kınık region Capability to do collaborative organizations (except local festivals) is limited	Communication about the synergies of different areas in the region would increase the collaborative culture. The effective use of the hub would have an important role for bringing people together.

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Annex I: List of activities per action per Replicator

Karavanke/Karawanken Unesco Global Geopark (ARGE GK)

Action R1.1: Design a set of new touristic and cross border packs, integrating different cultural experiences

N. of activity	List of activities foreseen	Timeline	Main responsible of the activity	Foreseen cost	Funding sources
Preparatory activities	Gathering ideas what kind of packages create - define different options included in the packages (food-nature-culture combination)	Autumn/Winter 2019	Antonia Weissenbacher, Gerald Hartmann, Darja Komar	none	none
1	Round table with key stakeholders (Franz Logar, Tourism Agency Lavamünd/Labot) - design with them their specific participation and contact other possible partners to engage them	14. January 2020	Antonia Weissenbacher, Gerald Hartmann	none	none
2	Designing and finalising the packages (visual identity)	March/April 2020	Antonia Weissenbacher, Gerald Hartmann, Uroš Grabner	none	none
3	Implementing, promotion and communication of the packages through various channels (also at the national/international fairs, Social media, Web page, Flyers, Brochures), including press-release to inform journalists, public and stakeholders about the action	Summer 2020	Antonia Weissenbacher, Gerald Hartmann, Franz Logar, Tourism Agency Lavamünd, Uroš Grabner	330,00 €	Geopark Karavanke/Karawanken own resources
4	Evaluation of the package, creation and designing of new package	Autumn 2020	Antonia Weissenbacher, Gerald Hartmann	none	none
5	Implementing, promotion and communication of the packages through various channels (also at the national/international fairs, Social media, Web page, Flyers, Brochures), including press-release to inform journalists, public and stakeholders about the action	Summer 2021	Antonia Weissenbacher, Gerald Hartmann	330,00 €	Geopark Karavanke/Karawanken own resources
6	Evaluation of the package, creation and designing of new package	Autumn 2021	Antonia Weissenbacher, Gerald Hartmann	none	none
7	Implementing, promotion and communication of the packages through various channels (also at the national/international fairs, Social media, Web page, Flyers, Brochures), including press-release to inform journalists, public and stakeholders about the action	May 2022	Antonia Weissenbacher, Gerald Hartmann	330,00 €	Geopark Karavanke/Karawanken own resources

Beyond RURITAGE lifespan	Evaluation of the package, creation and designing of new package	Autumn 2022	Antonia Weissenbacher, Gerald Hartmann	none	none
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Action R1.2: The digital use of the Karavanke/Karawanken Geopark

N. of activity	List of activities foreseen	Timeline	Main responsible of the activity	Foreseen cost	Funding sources
Preparatory activities	Meeting with the responsible persons of the organisation ARGE Pilgern of Carinthia (in the frame of the one INTERREG project they were working on the digitalization of the Hemma - Pilgerweg)	01.07.2019	Darja Komar, Antonia Weissenbacher	none	none
	Discussion with Mr. César del Valle Barreda at the mentoring visit (he is developing mobile application for the Camino de Santiago)	12.11.2019	Darja Komar, Antonia Weissenbacher	none	none
	Discussion with Dr. John Martin (University of Plymouth) in Bologna concerning the best digital solution	26.11.2019 -	Darja Komar, Antonia Weissenbacher	none	none
1	Round table with key stakeholder (Uroš Grabner)	10.01.2020	Darja Komar, Antonia Weissenbacher, Gerald Hartmann, Uroš Grabner	none	none
2	Creation of a first draft of mobile application (content)	Until end of February 2020	Uroš Grabner	none	none
3	Meeting and redefining/discussing the first draft	End of February 2020	Darja Komar, Gerald Hartmann, Antonia Weissenbacher, Uroš Grabner	none	none
4	Revision of the first version	Until the end of May 2020	Darja Komar, Gerald Hartmann, Antonia Weissenbacher, Uroš Grabner	none	none
5	Meeting and discussing the final version	End of May 2020	Darja Komar, Gerald Hartmann, Antonia Weissenbacher, Uroš Grabner	none	none
6	Invitation to submit offers for the creation of the Geopark Karavanke/Karawanken mobile application	June 2020	Gerald Hartmann	none	none

7	Obtaining offers	June-July 2020	Gerald Hartmann	none	none
8	Evaluation of the received offers - choosing the most suitable offer, company and signing the contract	July-August 2020	Darja Komar, Gerald Hartmann, Antonia Weissenbacher, Uroš Grabner	none	none
9	Developing process of the mobile application	August 2020 - August 2021	The company who is going to do it	20.000,00 €	RURITAGE project
10	Presentation of the mobile application, its promotion and communication (Fb, Web-page), together with the press release	August 2021	Darja Komar, Gerald Hartmann, Antonia Weissenbacher, Uroš Grabner	not sure yet	if any - Geopark Karavanke/Karawanken own resources
11	Maintenance of the mobile application	August 2021 on	Darja Komar, Gerald Hartmann, Antonia Weissenbacher, Uroš Grabner	not sure yet	if any - Geopark Karavanke/Karawanken own resources

Action R1.3: Safeguarding and making the site of St. Hema mountain - St. Rosalia cave accessible again

N. of activity	List of activities foreseen	Timeline	Main responsible of the activity	Foreseen cost	Funding sources
Preparatory activities	Several meetings with the Municipality of Globasnitz/Globasnica	Summer/Autumn 2018 (12.7.2018, 25.10.2018)	mag. Gerald Hartmann - ARGE GEOPARK Karavanke/Karawanken Bernhard Sadovnik - Municipality of Globasnitz/Globasnica	none	none
	Invitation to submit offers for the Protection and renovation of cultural and natural points - St. Rosalia cave on the St. Hemma Mountain	Spring (May) 2019	mag. Gerald Hartmann - ARGE GEOPARK Karavanke/Karawanken Bernhard Sadovnik - Municipality of Globasnitz/Globasnica	none	none
	The obtaining of offers	Till 13.06.2019	Municipality of Globasnica	none	none
	Evaluation of the received offers, choice of the appropriate company	2019-06-13	mag. Gerald Hartmann - ARGE GEOPARK Karavanke/Karawanken Bernhard Sadovnik - Municipality of Globasnitz/Globasnica	none	none

	In the frame of the round table with key stakeholders official signing of the contract with the company	31.10.2019	mag. Gerald Hartmann, Gerhard Visotschnig - ARGE GEOPARK Karavanke/Karawanken Bernhard Sadovnik - Municipality of Globasnitz/Globasnica	none	none
1	Working on the renovation and protection	October 2020 (depending on the weather conditions)	Chosen company, Municipality of Globasnitz/Globasnica, ARGE Geopark Karavanke/Karawanken	€ 176.976,26	€ 70.000 (RURITAGE project), Leader project, Municipality of Globasnitz/Globasnica own resources
2	Official opening of the St. Rosalia cave, opening event with press conference	October 2020 (depending on the weather conditions)	mag. Gerald Hartmann - ARGE GEOPARK Karavanke/Karawanken Bernhard Sadovnik - Municipality of Globasnitz/Globasnica	Not sure yet	if any - Municipality of Globasnitz/Globasnica own resources

Activity 1 started before M19, when the implementation phase formally should start. The reason is that ARGE GEOPARK and its stakeholders were ready to start the works before M19 so they decided not wait to ensure the good running of the restoration.

Action R1.4: Selection of “Geopark partners” sharing RURITAGE vision of local food as part of local heritage

N. of activity	List of activities foreseen	Timeline	Main responsible of the activity	Foreseen cost	Funding sources
1	Open event with key stakeholders, with the local food producers/sellers and farmers that could be involved in the action to explain the objective of the action and its steps;	January 2020	Darja Komar, Antonia Weissenbacher	none	none
	Open call to the local food producers/sellers and farmers for collecting their interest in the action;	Spring 2020	Darja Komar, Antonia Weissenbacher	none	none
2	Selection process in cooperation with Jauntaler Salami and Jauntaler Hadn association to choose the partners to be involved actively in the action as “Geopark partners”;	Summer 2020	Darja Komar, Danijela Modrej, Antonia Weissenbacher, Hirm Josef, Manfred Hirn, Charly Plantz	none	none
3	Learning visit in Apulia (Italy) - where we will get ideas on how to engage producers and farmers and implement marketing and the promotion of the local food	September 2020	Antonia Weissenbacher, Danijela Modrej, Darja Komar	not planned yet (cca. 2500,00 €)	RURITAGE project - travel costs
4	All local farmers and food producers who have been selected present their own products in the frame of Fine tuning workshop (WP2) hosted in the Geopark Hub, where we will	October 2020	Antonia Weissenbacher, Danijela Modrej	4.000,00 €	RURITAGE project (organisation of events related with

	officially present the RURITAGE approach especially on food to the local community (community event foreseen in task 3.5);				local food production)
5	Workshop where “Geopark partners” get familiar with best practices in the production and promotion of sustainable local food all over the Europe, developed together with Magma UGG and Dare;	End of the year 2020	Antonia Weissenbacher, Danijela Modrej	1.000,00 €	RURITAGE project (organisation of events related with local food production)
6	Developing a strategy for marketing and promotion of the “Geopark partners” and the products the members produce, also taking into consideration the branding approach developed by RURITAGE and the possible adoption of the RURITASTE brand;	End of the year 2020/beginning 2021	Antonia Weissenbacher, Gerald Hartmann, Danijela Modrej	7.000,00 €	RURITAGE project (costs for food branding creation and marketing)
7	on-line training courses for support of the local food producers	Beginning 2021	Antonia Weissenbacher, Gerald Hartmann, Danijela Modrej	5.000,00 €	RURITAGE project (development of on-line training courses)
8	Geopark Karavanke/Karawanken will promote the local food of the Geopark Partners at different national and international fairs (Vienna, Klagenfurt, Ljubljana)	January - April 2021	Antonia Weissenbacher, Darja Komar, Danijela Modrej	3.000,00 €	RURITAGE project (costs for food branding creation and marketing)

Action R1.5: Boost local pride by making the heritage of the area more accessible

N. of activity	List of activities foreseen	Timeline	Main responsible of the activity	Foreseen cost	Funding sources
Preparatory activities	Developing ideas for different tours	September/October 2019	Antonia Weissenbacher, Gerald Hartmann	none	none
	Round table with key stakeholder - Tourism agency where we decided to start with new tour in summer 2020	31. October 2019	Antonia Weissenbacher, Gerald Hartmann, Robert Karlhofer	none	none
1	Meeting with Mrs. Enze from Hemmastüberl, Mr. Glaser and Mrs. Rutter (Archaeological Pilgrimage Museum Globasnitz)	March, April 2020	Antonia Weissenbacher	none	none

2	Promotion of the guided tour	Before summer 2020	Antonia Weissenbacher, Gerald Hartmann, Robert Karlhofer	We do not have precise number	Tourism agency
3	Guided tour implementation	May – October 2020	Antonia Weissenbacher	none	none
4	Guided tour evaluation	Autumn/Winter 2020	Antonia Weissenbacher, Gerald Hartmann, Robert Karlhofer	none	none
5	Developing ideas for new guided tours	Winter 2020/2021	Antonia Weissenbacher, Gerald Hartmann, Robert Karlhofer	none	none
6	Guided tour implementation	May – October 2021	Antonia Weissenbacher	none	none
7	Guided tour evaluation	Autumn/Winter 2021	Antonia Weissenbacher, Gerald Hartmann, Robert Karlhofer	none	none
8	Developing ideas for new guided tours	Winter 2021/2020	Antonia Weissenbacher, Gerald Hartmann, Robert Karlhofer	none	none
9	Guided tour implementation	May 2022	Antonia Weissenbacher	none	none
Beyond RURITAGE lifespan	Guided tour evaluation	Autumn/Winter 2022	Antonia Weissenbacher, Gerald Hartmann, Robert Karlhofer	none	none

Magma UNESCO Global Geopark (Magma UGG)

Action R2.1: Create a common calendar for all 5 municipalities presenting festivals and other events in the geopark

No. of activity	List of activities foreseen	Timeline	Main responsible of the activity	Foreseen cost	Funding sources
Preparatory activities	Define which digital platform to use	01/11/19	Juste Druskiniene, Magma Geopark	None	
	Define where the calendar should be published	01/11/19	Juste Druskiniene, Magma Geopark	None	
	Define a contact person in each municipality	01/11/19	Representatives from all 5 municipalities	None	
	Define what kind of content is relevant for the calendar	01/11/19	Juste Druskiniene, Magma Geopark	None	
6	Buy access to digital platform	31/01/20	Juste Druskiniene, Magma Geopark	€ 500 per year	RURITAGE
7	Annual fee digital calendar platform	31/01/20	Juste Druskiniene, Magma Geopark	€ 500 per year	RURITAGE
5	Workshop for contact persons	31/03/20	Juste Druskiniene, Magma Geopark	€ 200	RURITAGE
8	Launch calendar	31/03/20	Juste Druskiniene, Magma Geopark	€ 1,000	RURITAGE

Action R2.2: Promote the tourist offer in all 5 municipalities through the design of a tourist route that specifies restaurants, hotels, activity providers and producers

No. of activity	List of activities foreseen	Timeline	Main responsible of the activity	Foreseen cost	Funding sources
1	Gather all potential partners in all 5 municipalities	15/12/19	Representatives from all 5 municipalities	None	
2	Define a tourist route including accommodation, restaurants, activity providers and local producers	31/12/20	Cathrine Johannessen Skogen, Magma Geopark	None	
3	Sign contracts with all partners/ stakeholders involved in our tourist route	31/12/20	Cathrine Johannessen Skogen, Magma Geopark	None	
4	Distribute and promote the tourist route (social medias, webpages etc.)	On-going	Cathrine Johannessen Skogen, Magma Geopark	None	
5	Create a designated page on the Magma webpage to present the tourist route, and maybe add the possibility to book	30/09/20	Juste Druskiniene, Magma Geopark	€ 2,000 per year	RURITAGE

6	To find a way to make all the partners (i.e. Active Partners) easy to identify as partners of the tourist route	31/05/20	Cathrine Johannessen Skogen, Magma Geopark	€ 1,500	RURITAGE
7	Testing tourist route	31/12/20	Cathrine Johannessen Skogen, Magma Geopark	€ 2,000	RURITAGE
8	Testing tourist route with people with disability	31/12/20	Cathrine Johannessen Skogen, Magma Geopark	€ 1,000	RURITAGE
9	Launch tourist route	June 2021	Cathrine Johannessen Skogen, Magma Geopark	€ 2,000	RURITAGE

Action R2.3: Promote joint actions to strengthen the local identity and to enhance heritage resources, in order to turn MAGMA Geopark into an internationally recognized concept

No. of activity	List of activities foreseen	Timeline	Main responsible of the activity	Foreseen cost	Funding sources
1	Promote and use Magma UNESCO Global Geopark logo on all partners webpages and social medias	On-going	Magma and representatives from all 5 municipalities.	None	
2	Continuously work towards getting all local producers and restaurants to use the Active Partner sign	On-going	Cathrine Johannessen Skogen, Magma Geopark	None	
3	Active Partner signs at all our partners/stakeholders	On-going	Cathrine Johannessen Skogen, Magma Geopark	€ 1,500	RURITAGE
4	Integrate all GEOfood partners in our Magma Geopark application	On-going	Juste Druskiniene, Magma Geopark	None	
5	Continue with our Instagram takeover	On-going	Cathrine Johannessen Skogen, Magma Geopark	None	
6	Continuously work on digitalization to improve the booking system, the way the feedback from visitors are handled, digital media for better communication	On-going	Juste Druskiniene, Magma Geopark	tbd	Magma Geopark yearly budget

7	Create food trails (connected with action R2.2)	June 2021	Cathrine Johannessen Skogen, Magma Geopark	None	
8	Two training courses for local guides in at least two municipalities involving people with disability and disadvantages groups	31/03/21	Pål Thjømmøe, Magma Geopark	€ 8,000	RURITAGE
9	Ambassador courses in all 5 municipalities	31/12/21	Cathrine Johannessen Skogen, Magma Geopark	€ 5,000	RURITAGE
10	geoVR; oculus rift, technical support, develop new content	May 2022	Pål Thjømmøe, Magma Geopark	€ 23,000	RURITAGE
Beyond RURITAGE lifespan	Signs to welcome to Magma Geopark	31/12/22	Juste Druskiniene, Magma Geopark	€ 12,000	RURITAGE (within RURITAGE lifespan) and geopark and/ or municipalities budget

Geo-Naturpark Bergstraße-Odenwald UNESCO Global Geopark (GEO-N)

Action R3.1: Organizing a Mountainbiking Event with tech-courses and forest-teaching by rangers for migrants

No. of activity	List of activities foreseen	Timeline	Main responsible of the activity	Foreseen cost	Funding sources
1	event planing meeting I	April 2020	Geo-N, Muemlingtalradler	80 €	RURITAGE; Geo-N yearly budget and co-funding by stakeholders
2	MTB-Event in Lesvos, Marcus Seuser is going there to exchange knowledge and best practice examples	April 2020	Geo-N	600 €	RURITAGE; co-financing of activities with Geo-N budget and capacities of partners
3	event planing meeting II	June 2020	Geo-N, Muemlingtalradler	80 €	RURITAGE; co-financing of activities with Geo-N budget and capacities of partners
4	meeting with logistic partner for food and beverages	June 2020	Geo-N	0 €	
5	meeting with the city of Michelstadt for event location	June 2020	Geo-N, City of Michelstadt	0 €	
6	final meeting and organization of logistics (tables, chairs, etc...)	Aug. 2020	Geo-N, Muemlingtalradler	80 €	RURITAGE; co-financing of activities with Geo-N budget and capacities of partners
7	technique training at the event by guides from Muemlingtalradler	Sep. 2020	Muemlintalradler	400 €	RURITAGE; co-financing of activities with Geo-N budget and capacities of partners
8	rental bikes for migrants from local bike shops for the event itself	Sep. 2020	Geo-N	400 €	RURITAGE; co-financing of activities with Geo-N budget and capacities of partners
9	guiding event by guides from Muemlingtalradler	Sep. 2020	Muemlintalradler	400 €	RURITAGE; co-financing of activities with Geo-N budget and capacities of partners
10	logistics of the event (food, beverages, table, chairs)	Sep. 2020	Geo-N	1.500 €	RURITAGE; co-financing of activities with Geo-N budget and capacities of partners

Action R3.2: Welcoming booths at Geopark-events

No. of activity	List of activities foreseen	Timeline	Main responsible of the activity	Foreseen cost	Funding sources
1	Contact and invite local communities, counties and migrant aid associations to choose local events with expected migrant participation probability	Jan 2020 - M48	Geo-N	500 €	RURITAGE; co-financing of activities with Geo-N budget and capacities of partners
2	Develop and produce multilingual invitation and information material	Jan 2020 - M48	Geo-N, migrant aid associations	4.500 €	RURITAGE; co-financing of activities with Geo-N budget and capacities of partners

3	Define time schedule preparing 4 welcoming booths per year	Feb-March 2020 - M48	Geo-N, Geo-N information facilities, member municipalities, migrant aid associations	500 €	RURITAGE; co-financing of activities with Geo-N budget and capacities of partners
4	Organizational meeting to define position and structure of the booth for each event and discuss presentation of specified local aspects.	every time 2 month before realization	Geo-N, member municipalities, migrant aid associations, geopark-on-site teams	500 €	RURITAGE; co-financing of activities with Geo-N budget and capacities of partners
5	Plan of personnel resources for each event	every time 1 month before realization	Geo-N, migrant aid associations, geopark-on-site teams	0 €	
6	Realization	four times a year 2020, 2021 and 2022	Geo-N rangers, member municipalities, migrant aid associations, geopark-on-site teams	6.000 €	RURITAGE; co-financing of activities with Geo-N budget and capacities of partners
7	Debriefing following each event – which aspects could be improved?	every time not later than 1 month after realization	Geo-N, member municipalities, migrant aid associations, geopark-on-site teams	500 €	RURITAGE; co-financing of activities with Geo-N budget and capacities of partners

Action R3.3: Utilizing GIS-Tools to map citizen's opinion and interaction with the natural and cultural heritage on a personal level and in regard to climate change induced vulnerability

No. of activity	List of activities foreseen	Timeline	Main responsible of the activity	Foreseen cost	Funding sources
1	develop the collection app Survey123 from Esri for migrants and citizens	June 2020	Geo-N	0 €	
2	workshop I Introduction people to the project and collecting feedback on the app	July 2020	Geo-N	400 €	RURITAGE; co-financing of activities with Geo-N budget and capacities of partners
3	improving the app and adding necessary collection features according the results from Workshop I	July 2020	Geo-N	0 €	
4	distributing the app to migrants and citizens via e-mail with download link and start the collection period	Aug. 2020	Geo-N	0 €	
5	reminder to add data and Workshop II in the middle of collection period to keep motivation high	Sep. 2020	Geo-N	400 €	RURITAGE; co-financing of activities with Geo-N budget and capacities of partners
6	final collection round and feedback on collection process at the end of collection period	Oct. 2020	Geo-N	400 €	RURITAGE; co-financing of activities with Geo-N budget and capacities of partners
7	production of touring exhibition	Oct. 2020	Geo-N	2.000 €	RURITAGE; co-financing of activities with Geo-N budget and capacities of partners

8	several presentations of results in exhibition and in front of majors and city planners	Nov. 2020	Geo-N	800 €	RURITAGE; co-financing of activities with Geo-N budget and capacities of partners
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Action R3.4: Educational material for language skills supporting migrants' understanding of natural and cultural heritage

No. of activity	List of activities foreseen	Timeline	Main responsible of the activity	Foreseen cost	Funding sources
1	concept of ABC Card game	June 2020	Geo-N; UNESCO WHS Messel Pit	2.000 €	RURITAGE; co-financing of activities with Geo-N budget and capacities of partners
2	layout of ABC Card game	Dec. 2020	Geo-N; UNESCO WHS Messel Pit	3.000 €	RURITAGE; co-financing of activities with Geo-N budget and capacities of partners
3	production of ABC Card game	April 2021	Geo-N; UNESCO WHS Messel Pit	3.500 €	RURITAGE; co-financing of activities with Geo-N budget and capacities of partners
4	editorial creation of information material to the subject "forest, meadow, water"	June 2021	Geo-N	1.000 €	RURITAGE; co-financing of activities with Geo-N budget and capacities of partners
5	layout of CNH information posters	Dec. 2021	Geo-N	1.000 €	RURITAGE; co-financing of activities with Geo-N budget and capacities of partners
6	production of CNH information posters	April 2022	Geo-N	2.000 €	RURITAGE; co-financing of activities with Geo-N budget and capacities of partners
Beyond RURITAGE lifespan	development and production of additional education material	June 2022	Geo-N; UNESCO WHS Messel Pit	7.000 €	RURITAGE (within RURITAGE lifespan); Co-financing of activities with Geo-N budget and capacities of partners

Action R3.5: Author reading and family events at visitor centre of UNESCO World Heritage Site Messel Pit

No. of activity	List of activities foreseen	Timeline	Main responsible of the activity	Foreseen cost	Funding sources
1	concept development	January - March 2020	Geo-N; UNESCO WHS Messel Pit	500 €	RURITAGE; co-financing of activities with Geo-N budget and capacities of partners
2	scheduling events	February 2020 - M48	Geo-N; UNESCO WHS Messel Pit	500 €	RURITAGE; co-financing of activities with Geo-N budget and capacities of partners
3	define and invite authors	half a year before event	Geo-N; UNESCO WHS Messel Pit	5.200 €	RURITAGE; co-financing of activities with Geo-N budget and capacities of partners
4	public relation work	two months before event	Geo-N; UNESCO WHS Messel Pit	500 €	RURITAGE; co-financing of activities with Geo-N budget and capacities of partners
5	planning organization event	half a year before event	Geo-N; UNESCO WHS Messel Pit	0 €	

6	addressing the target groups	two months before event	Geo-N; UNESCO WHS Messel Pit	0 €	
7	organize catering	one month before event	Geo-N; UNESCO WHS Messel Pit	5.200 €	RURITAGE; co-financing of activities with Geo-N budget and capacities of partners
8	event realization (rent of room)	5 events 2020/21, 3 events 2022	Geo-N; UNESCO WHS Messel Pit	2.600 €	RURITAGE; co-financing of activities with Geo-N budget and capacities of partners
9	debriefing	one week after event	Geo-N; UNESCO WHS Messel Pit	0 €	

Action R3.6: Increasing the awareness of cultural and natural heritage by cultural landscape interpretation

No. of activity	List of activities foreseen	Timeline	Main responsible of the activity	Foreseen cost	Funding sources
1	Discuss almost unknown but specific phenomena and themes of landscape environment with geopark-on-site teams Felsenmeer, Fischbachtal, the municipality of Fürth and the Historical Mining Association Odenwald.	Jan. 2020	Geo-N, geopark-on-site teams Fischbachtal & Felsenmeer, municipality of Fürth, Hist. Mining Ass.	500 €	RURITAGE; co-financing of activities with Geo-N budget and capacities of partners
2	Detailed planning of guided ranger tours or hands-on actions for each threatened CNH element, bringing together Geo-N, rangers, the abovementioned geopark-on-site guides and volunteers	Feb-March 2020	Geo-N, geopark-on-site teams Fischbachtal & Felsenmeer, municipality of Fürth, Hist. Mining Ass.	500 €	RURITAGE; co-financing of activities with Geo-N budget and capacities of partners
3	Public relation work advertising the events	every time 2 month before realization	Geo-N	1.000 €	RURITAGE; co-financing of activities with Geo-N budget and capacities of partners
4	Photographic landscape expedition Fischbachtal	June 2020, June 2021, June 2022	Geopark-on-site team Fischbachtal, Geo-N	1.500 €	RURITAGE (within RURITAGE lifespan); Co-financing of activities with Geo-N budget and capacities of partners
5	Charcoal burning at Wegscheide (Fürth), single event	July 2020	Municipality of Fürth, Historical Mining Association, Geo-N	2.000 €	RURITAGE; co-financing of activities with Geo-N budget and capacities of partners
6	Building and driving a historical bloomery furnace (iron smeltery) in Michelstadt-Rehbach, single event	ago-20	Historical Mining Association, Geo-N	500 €	RURITAGE; co-financing of activities with Geo-N budget and capacities of partners
7	Beekeeping-workshop at Felsenmeer Information Centre, single event	March - Oct 2020, March-Oct 2021,	Felsenmeer Information Centre, Geopark-on-site team	3.000 €	RURITAGE (within RURITAGE lifespan); Co-financing of activities with Geo-N budget and capacities of partners

		March-Oct 2022	Felsenmeer, Geo-N		
8	Plan & realize additional heritage cycle events	Jan 2020 - M48	Geo-N, ranger, geopark-on-site teams, voluntary groups/associations	3.000 €	RURITAGE; co-financing of activities with Geo-N budget and capacities of partners
9	Training courses and materials for the mentioned programmes	Jan 2020 - M48	Geo-N	4.000 €	RURITAGE; co-financing of activities with Geo-N budget and capacities of partners
10	Plan and realize a post-event advanced training for rangers, Geopark-on-site teams and other multipliers on methods, realization and results of the projects.	up to half a year after the event	Geo-N together with groups which participated in a certain CNH event	1.000 €	RURITAGE; co-financing of activities with Geo-N budget and capacities of partners

Action R3.7: Local and new inhabitants are an active part in preserving Orchard meadows and old Fruit varieties

No. of activity	List of activities foreseen	Timeline	Main responsible of the activity	Foreseen cost (in Euro)	Funding sources
1	conception phase: scientific and picture research concerning old fruit varieties	six months before event	Streuobstwiesenretter, Geo-N	0 €	
2	contact cooperation partners and migrant groups	three months before event	Streuobstwiesenretter, Geo-N	0 €	
3	meeting with local representatives and municipalities	three months before event	Streuobstwiesenretter, Geo-N	500 €	RURITAGE; co-financing of activities with Geo-N budget and capacities of partners
4	contact nurseries for specific Fruit tree species	six months before event	Streuobstwiesenretter, Geo-N	0 €	
5	design, layout and print of flyers and information panel	four months before event	Streuobstwiesenretter, Geo-N	5.500 €	RURITAGE; co-financing of activities with Geo-N budget and capacities of partners
6	organize inauguration	Jan. 2020/2021/2022	Streuobstwiesenretter, Geo-N	0 €	
7	implementation phase: writing invitation document for the representatives of the municipalities	Feb. 2020/2021/2022	Streuobstwiesenretter, Geo-N	0 €	
8	coordinate event date and press	Feb. 2020/2021/2022	Streuobstwiesenretter, Geo-N	0 €	

9	buy trees for event and planting season in autumn, respectively	March 2020/2021/2022	Streuobstwiesenretter, Geo-N	3.750 €	RURITAGE; co-financing of activities with Geo-N budget and capacities of partners
10	organizing planting equipment	one week before event	Streuobstwiesenretter, Geo-N	0 €	
11	realizing “Fruit of the Year” event	each April 2020-2022	Streuobstwiesenretter, Geo-N	1.500 €	RURITAGE; co-financing of activities with Geo-N budget and capacities of partners
12	preparing tree trimming courses	April-August 2020	Streuobstwiesenretter, Geo-N	0 €	
13	contact cooperation partners, trainers and migrant groups	May 2020	Streuobstwiesenretter, Geo-N	0 €	
14	information meeting for interested persons	Sep. 2020	Streuobstwiesenretter, Geo-N	500 €	RURITAGE; co-financing of activities with Geo-N budget and capacities of partners
15	realization trimming course	Oct. -Nov. 2020	Streuobstwiesenretter, Geo-N	1.500 €	RURITAGE; co-financing of activities with Geo-N budget and capacities of partners
16	final event and handover of certificates	Dec. 2020	Streuobstwiesenretter, Geo-N	500 €	RURITAGE; co-financing of activities with Geo-N budget and capacities of partners
17	debriefing	Dec. 2020	Streuobstwiesenretter, Geo-N	500 €	RURITAGE; co-financing of activities with Geo-N budget and capacities of partners

Action R3.8: Strengthening the bonds between migrants and residents through creative land art and forest art work

No. of activity	List of activities foreseen	Timeline	Main responsible of the activity	Foreseen cost	Funding sources
1	Plan a public workshop program associated with the Forest Art Trail performance and (as a second) accompanying Landart activities (e.g. Global Nomadic Art Project 2021)	Jan. 2020 - M48	International Forest Art Association, Geo-N	500 €	RURITAGE; co-financing of activities with Geo-N budget and capacities of partners
2	Develop a time schedule and prepare the landart exchange festival with RM6	April 2020	International Forest Art Association, Geo-N	500 €	RURITAGE; co-financing of activities with Geo-N budget and capacities of partners
3	Define personnel resources for each event	every time 2 month before realization	International Forest Art Association, Geo-N	500 €	RURITAGE; co-financing of activities with Geo-N budget and capacities of partners
4	Invite migrant and resident groups to workshops and events	every time 2 month before realization	International Forest Art Association, Geo-N	1.000 €	RURITAGE; co-financing of activities with Geo-N budget and capacities of partners

			Association, Geo-N		
5	Realize workshops in 2020/2021 and contracting artists for creation of collective art pieces	Aug. 2020 / Sep. 2021	International Forest Art Association, Geo-N	10.000 €	RURITAGE; co-financing of activities with Geo-N budget and capacities of partners
6	Realize exchange festival Lesvos – Geo-N	Aug. 2020	International Forest Art Association, Geo-N, RM6 Lesvos	6.000 €	RURITAGE; co-financing of activities with Geo-N budget and capacities of partners
7	Prepare event documentation, publish a brochure about the activities	Sep. 2020 - M48	International Forest Art Association, Geo-N	1.500 €	RURITAGE; co-financing of activities with Geo-N budget and capacities of partners
8	Workshop on continuation of the public forest art actions with migrants and residents by cooperation of International Forest Art Association and Geo-N, financed by sponsors.	Jan. 2022	International Forest Art Association, Geo-N	500 €	RURITAGE; co-financing of activities with Geo-N budget and capacities of partners

Action R3.9: Migrant internships with International Forest Art Centre and international artists

No. of activity	List of activities foreseen	Timeline	Main responsible of the activity	Foreseen cost	Funding sources
1	Find sponsors to continue the internship program after termination of RURITAGE	Jan. 2020 - M48	International Forest Art Association, Geo-N	500 €	RURITAGE; co-financing of activities with Geo-N budget and capacities of partners
2	Contact local migrant organization for cooperation	every time half a year before realization	International Forest Art Association, Geo-N	500 €	RURITAGE; co-financing of activities with Geo-N budget and capacities of partners
3	invite migrants and artists for the land art internship	every time half a year before realization	International Forest Art Association, Geo-N	0 €	
4	Develop a time schedule, prepare and conduct administrative processes, if necessary	every time half a year before realization	International Forest Art Association, Geo-N	500 €	RURITAGE; co-financing of activities with Geo-N budget and capacities of partners
5	Realize the internships in 2020/2021/2022	July/Aug. 2020, July/Aug. 2021, May 2022,	International Forest Art Association, Geo-N	9.000 €	RURITAGE; co-financing of activities with Geo-N budget and capacities of partners
6	Documentation work during the creation process of art pieces	during realization	International Forest Art Association, Geo-N	1.000 €	RURITAGE; co-financing of activities with Geo-N budget and capacities of partners
7	Organize art exhibitions at the Centre for Forest Art in Darmstadt	Oct. 2020, Oct. 2021, Oct. 2022	International Forest Art Association, Geo-N	5.000 €	RURITAGE (within RURITAGE lifespan); Co-financing of activities with Geo-N budget and capacities of partners

Negova Castle (KIBLA, KULTPROTUR)

ACTION R4.1: Making Negova Castle accessible and connectable

SUB ACTION RECIKEL bike sharing service

No. of activity	List of activities foreseen	Timeline	Main responsible of the activity	Foreseen cost	Funding sources
1	Defining the prices and prepare all the needed documentation for renting the bikes	February 2020	Kultprotur		
2	Event planning meeting - for the official launch of the new service	February 2020	Kultprotur, Kibla	50,00 €	RURITAGE (Kultprotur)
3	Meeting with logistic partners for food and beverages, choosing and hiring the caterer	March 2020	Kultprotur		
4	Preparation and print of invitations, press releases and informational material	March 2020	Kultprotur, Kibla	500,00 €	RURITAGE (Kultprotur)
5	Inviting media representatives, stakeholders and general public	March 2020	Kultprotur, Kibla, NGO Rastišče		
6	Final meeting and organisation of logistic	March 2020	Kultprotur, Kibla	50,00 €	RURITAGE (Kultprotur)
7	Venue preparation	April 2020	Kultprotur		
8	Realisation	April 2020	Kultprotur, Kibla, NGO Rastišče		

SUB ACTION E-bike sharing service

No. of activity	List of activities foreseen	Timeline	Main responsible of the activity	Foreseen cost	Funding sources
1	Meeting with Radgonske gorice d.d. to finalise the agreement	February 2020	Kultprotur		
2	Obtaining offers from different bidders for electrical bikes and charging stations	February-December 2020	Kultprotur		
3	Meeting with Radgonske gorice d.d. and Farm Holliday Firbas to further discuss about the possibility of preparation of a tourist pack (renting bike, lunch and sightseeing), joint brochures, maps, promotional film, etc., final selection of advertising methods and dividing the tasks, responsibilities	June 2020	Kultprotur, Radgonske gorice d.d., Firbas Holiday Farm	60,00 €	Kultprotur
4	Meeting with Radgonske gorice d.d. and Farm Holliday Firbas for fine-tuning the last details about tourist pack, advertisement, defining the location and other frames of the public presentation of a new product	October 2020	Kultprotur, Radgonske gorice d.d., Firbas Holiday Farm	60,00 €	Kultprotur
5	Preparation of a new tourist pack with designing and producing invitations, posters, brochures, maps and other materials, agreed	October 2020 - April 2021	Kultprotur, Radgonske gorice d.d., Firbas Holiday Farm	6.000,00 €	Kultprotur, Radgonske gorice d.d.,

	on previous meetings with main stakeholders				Firbas Holiday Farm
6	Meeting with Radgonske gorice - selecting the bidder for e-bikes and charging stations, final defining the prices for renting	December 2020	Kultprotur, Radgonske gorice d.d.		
7	Purchase of the electrical bikes and charging station	February 2021	Kultprotur, Radgonske gorice d.d.	15.000,00 €	Kultprotur, Radgonske gorice d.d.
8	Inviting media representatives, stakeholders and general public	March - May 2021	Kultprotur, Radgonske gorice d.d., Firbas Holiday Farm		
9	Final meeting and organisation of logistic	April - May 2021	Kultprotur, Radgonske gorice d.d., Firbas Holiday Farm	80,00 €	Kultprotur
10	Venue preparations	April - May 2021	Kultprotur, Radgonske gorice d.d., Firbas Holiday Farm		
11	Realisation	April - May 2021	Kultprotur, Radgonske gorice d.d., Firbas Holiday Farm		

SUB ACTION Broadband communication system in the castle

No. of activity	List of activities foreseen	Timeline	Main responsible of the activity	Foreseen cost	Funding sources
1	Obtaining offers from different bidders	October - December 2020	Kultprotur		
2	Selecting the bidder and signing the contract	January 2021	Kultprotur, Municipality of Gornja Radgona		
3	Implementation	Until April 2021	Kultprotur, Municipality of Gornja Radgona	5.000,00 €	Municipality of Gornja Radgona

ACTION R4.2: Festival of love: Days of Summer

No. of activity	List of activities foreseen	Timeline	Main responsible of the activity	Foreseen cost	Funding sources
Preparatory activities for the first edition	Meeting of the two main partners in RURITAGE project (Kibla and Kultprotur) to set the plan	Sept 2019 and 2020 (at least 9 months before the first event for each year)	Kibla, Kultprotur	100,00 €	RURITAGE (KIBLA + Kultprotur)
	Inviting stakeholders and other interested in co-development of the programme and meetings with stakeholders to define their role in the event	November 2019 and 2020 (at least 8 months each year before the first event)	Kibla, Kultprotur	100,00 €	RURITAGE (KIBLA + Kultprotur)
	Second planning meeting for defining the programme framework and contributors	November 2019 and 2020 (at least 8 months each)	Kibla, Kultprotur	50,00 €	RURITAGE (KIBLA + Kultprotur)

		year before the first event)			
1	Selecting the programme's participants by collecting the offers from contractors and hiring them	January 2020 and 2021 (at least 6 months before each event)	Kibla, Kultprotur	19.600,00 €	RURITAGE (KIBLA + Kultprotur)
2	Preparing of all the advertising materials	May 2020 and 2021 (at least 4 weeks before the event until the event)	Kibla, Kultprotur	5.000,00 €	RURITAGE (KIBLA + Kultprotur)
3	Third planning meeting for dividing tasks and specific responsibilities	May 2020, May 2021 (at least one month before each event)	Kibla, Kultprotur	50,00 €	RURITAGE (KIBLA + Kultprotur)
4	Selecting and hiring a food and beverage provider -if needed	May 2020, May 2021 (at least 3 weeks before each event)	Kibla, Kultprotur	2.000,00 €	RURITAGE (KIBLA + Kultprotur)
5	Procurement of all the needed equipment and materials for implementation	May 2020, May 2021 (at least 2 weeks before each event)	Kibla, Kultprotur	3.600,00 €	RURITAGE (KIBLA + Kultprotur)
6	Arranging the residence for the international artists	May 2020, May 2021 (at least 2 weeks before each event)	Kibla, Kultprotur	3.000,00 €	RURITAGE (KIBLA + Kultprotur)
7	Final meeting and organisation of logistic	June 2020 June 2021 (at least one week before each event)	Kibla, Kultprotur		
8	Preparation of the venue	June 2020 June 2021 in the days before each event)	Kibla, Kultprotur		
9	Realisation of the Festival of love	June 2020 June 2021	Kibla, Kultprotur		
10	Debriefing after each event - evaluation of the past event and discussion about the possibilities of improvement	June 2020 June 2021 in a week after each event	Kibla, Kultprotur		

ACTION R4.3 Festival of Love: Spring and Autumn Day / The Herb Day

No. of activity	List of activities foreseen	Timeline	Main responsible of the activity	Foreseen cost	Funding sources
Preparatory activities for the first edition	Meeting of the two main partners in RURITAGE project (Kibla and Kultprotur) to define the topics, content, contributors of the event and its organization	Nov 2019/20/21 April 2020/21	Kultprotur, Kibla	250,00 €	RURITAGE (Kibla + Kultprotur)
	Contacting providers and engage them	November 2019/20/21 April 2020/21	Kultprotur, Kibla		
	prepare the programme	November 2019/20/21 February 2020/21	Kultprotur, Kibla		

	Selection and hiring of lecturers, workshops providers, chefs, artist, tutors, presenters and other contractors for workshops	December 2019/20/21 - January 20/21/22 June -July 20/21	Kultprotur, Kibla	23.250,00 €	RURITAGE (Kibla + Kultprotur)
	Preparation of advertising material and required documentation	January 2020/21/22 July 2020/21	Kultprotur, Kibla		
	Promotion and dissemination	February - March 2020/21/22 August-Sept 2020-21	Kultprotur, Kibla	2.500,00 €	RURITAGE (Kibla + Kultprotur)
	Preparation of the venue	April 2020/21/22 October 2020/21	Kultprotur, Kibla		
	Implementation	April 2020/21/22 October 2020/21	Kultprotur, Kibla		
	Debriefing and search for potentially better solutions for the next edition	April 2020/21/22 October 2020/21 (a week after each event)	Kultprotur, Kibla		

ACTION R4.4: Festival of Love: Autumn Day / Medieval day

No. of activity	List of activities foreseen	Timeline	Main responsible of the activity	Foreseen cost	Funding sources
Prep. activity for the 1st edition	Contacting providers and engage them	November 2019 - January 2020 March 2021-May 2021	Kultprotur, Kibla		
1	To prepare the programme	January 2019- February 2020 March 2021-May 2021	Kultprotur, Kibla		
2	Selection and hiring of lecturers and other contractors for workshops	December 2019 - March 2020 March 2021- June 2021	Kultprotur, Kibla	6.500,00 €	RURITAGE (Kultprotur)
3	Preparation of advertising material	March 2020 June 2021	Kultprotur, Kibla		
4	Promotion and dissemination)	March 2020-May 2020 June 2021-August 2021	Kultprotur, Kibla	3.500,00 €	RURITAGE (Kultprotur)
5	Preparation of the venue	June 2020 September 2021 (in the days before each event)	Kultprotur, Kibla		
6	Implementation	June 2020 September 2021 (on the day of each event)	Kultprotur, Kibla		

7	Debriefing and search for potentially better solutions for the next edition	June 2020 September 2021 (in a week after each event)	Kultprotur, Kibla		
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ACTION R4.5: Building new skills and knowledge about rural creativity

No. of activity	List of activities foreseen	Timeline	Main responsible of the activity	Foreseen cost	Funding sources
1	To analyse specific learning needs of the different target groups	December 2019/20 - February 2020/21	Kultprotur, Kibla		
	Finding experts for the topics and engage them	January – April 2020/21	Kultprotur, Kibla		
2	Preparation of the advertisement material and dissemination	April – May 2020/21 September - October 2020/21	Kultprotur, Kibla		
3	Purchase and preparation of a modest catering (water, coffee,...)	May 2020/21 October 2020/21	Kultprotur, Kibla	200,00 €	Kultprotur Kibla
4	Preparation of the venue	June 2020/21 November 2020/21 (in the days before each event)	Kultprotur, Kibla		
5	Implementation	June 2020/21 November 2020/21 (on the day of each event)	Kultprotur, Kibla		
6	Debriefing	June 2020/21 November 2020/21 (in a week after each event)	Kultprotur, Kibla		

Appignano del Tronto (CoApp)

Action R5.1: Natural Heritage: awareness raising, Capacity building and training activities for resilience

N. of activity	List of activities foreseen – name and short description	Timeline	Main responsible of the activity	Foreseen cost	Funding sources
1	Press release at the beginning of each training activity	A week before starting training activities	Francesca Luzi	--	--
2	Training for kindergarten children (two courses)	December 2020 December 2021	Antonella D'Angelo-	€ 1.500,00	RURITAGE funds
3	Training for primary school students	December 2020 December 2021	Antonella D'Angelo	€ 1.500,00	RURITAGE funds
4	Training for secondary school students	December 2020 December 2021	Antonella D'Angelo	€ 1.500,00	RURITAGE funds
5	Awareness activities for elderly people	1 st April 2020- 2 nd November 2020- 3 rd May 2021- 4 th November 2021	Fuschetto Palmina	€ 2.000,00	RURITAGE funds
6	Capacity building activities for adults	1 st April 2020- 2 nd November 2020- 3 rd May 2021- 4 th November 2021	Antonella D'Angelo	€ 1.500,00	RURITAGE funds
7	Capacity building activities for professionals	1 st January 2021- 2 nd April 2022	Ing. Massimo Conti (Fed Ing Marche)- Geol. Daniele Mercuri (Ord. Geol. Marche)	€ 2.000,00	RURITAGE funds

Action R5.2: Natural heritage: awareness raising, capacity building and training activities for sustainable local food production

N. of activity	List of activities foreseen – name and short description	Timeline	Main responsible of the activity	Foreseen cost	Funding sources
1	Automatic control about activities of local weather station network	February – March 2020	Antonella D'Angelo	€ 1.000,00	RURITAGE funds
2	Implementation of digital platform to collect data from different sources available in our field (seismograph, weather stations...)	April – May 2020	Antonella D'Angelo	€ 3.000,00	RURITAGE funds
3	Implementation of a specific web application to show the dataset	June- September 2020	Antonella D'Angelo	€ 1.000,00	RURITAGE funds
4	An Organization of one field trip for local school students from 10 to 14 years old	October 2020	Antonella D'Angelo- Massimiliano Fazzini	No costs	--
5	Training for engineers and geologists	May 2021	Massimiliano Fazzini	RURITAGE staff	--

6	Drafting of a monthly report	Each month, starting maximum in May 2020	Massimiliano Fazzini	RURITAGE staff	--
7	Drafting of an annual report	January 2021- January 2022	Massimiliano Fazzini	RURITAGE staff	--
8	Special issue of probabilistic weather forecast before and during severe weather addressed to all population (heatwaves, strong thunderstorm, downburst, heavy snowfall...)	From June 2020 to April 2022	Massimiliano Fazzini	RURITAGE staff	--
9	Dedicated issue of probabilistic weather forecast linked to local cultivation needs (dry timespan, late frost, hailstorms, heatwaves, strong thunderstorm, downburst, heavy snowfall)	From June 2020 to April 2022	Massimiliano Fazzini	RURITAGE staff	--

Action R5.3: Capacity building and training activities for local companies that work with cultural and natural heritage

N. of activity	List of activities foreseen – name and short description	Timeline	Main responsible of the activity	Foreseen cost	Funding sources
1	Pre-activity webinar on line	March 2020	Gianluca Vagnarelli	--	--
2	“Introduction to e-commerce opportunities for micro-companies”. Training course on e-commerce	March 2020	Marco Alessandrini (Conca d’Oro) Elisa Ballatori (Sesi)	300 Euro	RURITAGE
3	“An introduction to Social media platforms”. Training course on social media	March 2020	Marco Alessandrini (Conca d’Oro) Elisa Ballatori (Sesi)	300 Euro	RURITAGE
4	“English Language Course (Beginner Level)”. Training course to foster English skills	April 2020	M. Nazzarena Agostini	650 Euro	RURITAGE
5	“Build-up a Service Design team for Appignano del Tronto”. Training course on Service Design skills. 30 hours training course on	October 2020	Antonella D’Angelo Gianluca Vagnarelli	6.500 Euro	RURITAGE
6	“An Introduction on How to manage companies and business budget” Training course for developing entrepreneurial skills	November 2020	Marco Alessandrini (Conca d’Oro) Elisa Ballatori (Sesi)	500 Euro	RURITAGE
7	“Innovation for SME”. 1 guideline/learning material provided by Savonia University on	December 2020	APRE	no costs	/

8	“EU funds opportunities for SME”. 1 guideline/learning mater provided by APRE	January 2021	Savonia University	no costs	/
9	“Introduction to e-commerce opportunities for micro-companies”. Training course on e-commerce	March 2021	Elisa Ballatori (Sesi)	300 Euro	RURITAGE
10	“An introduction to Social media platforms”. Training course on social media	March 2021	Marco Alessandrini (Conca d’Oro) Elisa Ballatori (Sesi)	300 Euro	RURITAGE
11	“English Language Course (Beginner Level)”. Training course to foster English skills	April 2021	M. Nazzarena Agostini	650 Euro	RURITAGE
12	“An Introduction on How to manage companies and business budget” Training course for developing entrepreneurial skills	October 2021	Marco Alessandrini (Conca d’Oro) Elisa Ballatori (Sesi)	500 Euro	RURITAGE

Action R5.4: Development of toolkit for resilient citizens

N. of activity	List of activities foreseen – name and short description	Timeline	Main responsible of the activity	Foreseen cost	Funding sources
1	Standard Toolkit design by a scientific group of experts	February 2020- November 2020	Antonella D’Angelo-Carlo Casini (Regione Marche)	No costs	--
2	Toolkit for disabled people design together with associations of disabled people	February 2020- November 2020	Antonella D’Angelo	No costs	--
3	Kit Purchase	December 2020	Antonella D’Angelo	€ 3.500,00/€ 5.000,00	RURITAGE funds
4	Toolkit explanation through public events	January 2021	Antonella D’Angelo-Carlo Casini (Regione Marche)	No costs	--
5	delivery of the kit to each family (one-to-one delivery through municipal employees)	February 2021 April 2021	Sara Moreschini		

Action R5.5: Appignano HUB for Community Resilience, Training and Education

N. of activity	List of activities foreseen – name and short description	Timeline	Main responsible of the activity	Foreseen cost	Funding sources
1	Establish the study and design team	February 2020	Antonella D’Angelo-Sara Moreschini-Giuliano Milana (INGV)	No costs	--

			Emanuele Tondi Unicam		
2	Preliminary draft.	March 2020- November 2020	Antonella D'Angelo- Sara Moreschini- Giuliano Milana (INGV) Emanuele Tondi Unicam	No costs	--
3	Visit to scientific centers in order to study other good experiences	December 2020- January 2021	Antonella D'Angelo- Sara Moreschini- Giuliano Milana (INGV) Emanuele Tondi Unicam	€ 1.000,00	RURITAGE funds
4	Project final study-	February 2021- December 2021	Antonella D'Angelo- Sara Moreschini- Giuliano Milana (INGV) Emanuele Tondi Unicam	€ 4.000,00	RURITAGE funds
5	development of a preliminary business plan for the Resilience Hub/Knowledge center	December 2021	Antonella D'Angelo		
6	Study of different funding channels,	January February 2022	Antonella D'Angelo		

Action R5.6: RURITAGE stories

N. of activity	List of activities foreseen – name and short description	Timeline	Main responsible of the activity	Foreseen cost	Funding sources
1	Call for Stories	February 2020	Francesca Luzi	no costs	/
2	“How to collect a good story” Training activity	June 2020	Gianluca Vagnarelli and Chiara Stipa	no costs	/
3	Stories collection. A participatory approach in storytelling	July/September 2020	Oratorio of Appignano del Tronto	300 Euro	RURITAGE
4	Selection of the most interesting stories with a potential narrative capital	November 2020	Gianluca Vagnarelli, Chiara Stipa, Pro Loco Appignano del Tronto, Antonella D'Angelo, Sara Moreschini, M. Nazzarena Agostini	no costs	/
5	To create plots for emotional stories	December 2020	Gianluca Vagnarelli	no costs	/
6	To select the best platforms for sharing stories (youtube, facebook, Instagram etc.)	January 2021	Francesca Luzi	400 euro	RURITAGE
7	To publish stories	February 2021 to December 2021	Francesca Luzi	no costs	/
8	Storytelling event for presenting stories	February 2021	Oratorio of Appignano del Tronto	300 Euro	RURITAGE

Action R5.7: RURITAGE Art Festival

N. of activity	List of activities foreseen – name and short description	Timeline	Main responsible of the activity	Foreseen cost	Funding sources
1	International “Call for Artists”	May 2020	Minimo Teatro, 7/8 Chili, Compagnia dei Folli	Euro 500	RURITAGE
2	Selection of International + local artists	June 2020	Minimo Teatro, 7/8 Chili, Compagnia dei Folli	Euro 500	RURITAGE
3	Selection of Appignano del Tronto Hosting families for international artists	July 2020	Sara Moreschini	no costs	/
4	Finalizing the Programme of the Festival	July 2020	Minimo Teatro, 7/8 Chili, Compagnia dei Folli + Stakeholders	no costs	/
5	Communication campaign through Facebook Page	August/September 2020	Francesca Luzi	Euro 2.000	RURITAGE
6	2/3 days Festival	September/October 2020	Gianluca Vagnarelli	Euro 9.000	RURITAGE
7	To make video and pictures of the Festival	November 2020	Francesca Luzi/ Mauro Corinti	Euro 2.000	RURITAGE
8	An International “Call for Artists”	May 2021	Minimo Teatro, 7/8 Chili, Compagnia dei Folli	Euro 500	RURITAGE
9	Selection of International + local artists	June 2021	Minimo Teatro, 7/8 Chili, Compagnia dei Folli	Euro 500	RURITAGE
10	Selection of Appignano del Tronto Hosting families for international artists	July 2021	Sara Moreschini	no costs	/
11	Finalizing the Programme of the Festival	July 2021	Minimo Teatro, 7/8 Chili, Compagnia dei Folli + Stakeholders	no costs	/
12	Communication campaign through Facebook Page “RURITAGE – Appignano del Tronto”	August/September 2021	Francesca Luzi	Euro 2000	/
13	2/3 days Festival	September/October 2021	Gianluca Vagnarelli	Euro 9.000	RURITAGE
14	To make video and pictures of the Festival	February 2022	Francesca Luzi/ Mauro Corinti	Euro 1000	RURITAGE

Action R5.8: Creation of an integrated green pack based on Nature and Cultural Heritage products, paths and sites

N. of activity	List of activities foreseen – name and short description	Timeline	Main responsible of the activity	Foreseen cost	Funding sources
1	To deal out a form to local stakeholders involved in tourism offer	January 2020	Gianluca Vagnarelli, M.Nazzarena Agostini and Local stakeholders	no costs	RURITAGE

2	To gather (through a digital form) information from local stakeholders involved in tourism offer	March 2020	Gianluca Vagnarelli, M. Nazzarena Agostini and Local stakeholders	no costs	RURITAGE
3	to select from the information gathered the best products/experiences/services to design an integrated tourist pack	July 2020	RURITAGE Staff + Local Stakeholders + M. Nazzarena Agostini	no costs	RURITAGE
4	To define an innovative visual identity for the integrated tourist pack and explore the possible use of the RURITASTE and RURISCAPE brand	December 2021	Webeing.net	2.000 Euro	RURITAGE
5	To publish the integrated green tourist pack	January 2022	Webeing.net	no costs	
6	to upload it in the municipality website, in the websites of each stakeholder involved, to print it and disseminate it in the regional tourism point of information	March 2022	Sara Moreschini and Stakeholders	3.000 Euro	Local stakeholders

Action R5.9: Natural Heritage: Path of The Grey-Blue Badlands

N. of activity	List of activities foreseen – name and short description	Timeline	Main responsible of the activity	Foreseen cost	Funding sources
1	Installation of tourist signals	April/May 2021	Antonella D'Angelo Fabiola Pierantozzi	4.200,00 €	RURITAGE
2	Installation of explanatory and information signals	April/May 2021	Antonella D'Angelo Fabiola Pierantozzi	2.800,00 €	RURITAGE
3	Implementation of an App or digital tool	September 2021- November 2021	Antonella D'Angelo Fabiola Pierantozzi Maria Nazzarena Agostini	6.000,00 €	RURITAGE
4	Promotion and communication of the new path	November 2021	Gianluca Vagnarelli, M. Nazzarena Agostini	5.000,00 €	RURITAGE
5	Promotion and communication of the new path together with green path	December 2021	Gianluca Vagnarelli, M. Nazzarena Agostini		

Action R5.10: Definition of measures to increase private investments at Appignano del Tronto related with resilience and Cultural and Natural Heritage

N. of activity	List of activities foreseen – name and short description	Timeline	Main responsible of the activity	Foreseen cost	Funding sources
1	asking advisor expert in companies and bank taxation in order to identify practical measures to incentive private investments	March 2021	Antonella D'Angelo/Gianluca Vagnarelli	Euro 2.000	RURITAGE
2	data collecting of banks, foundations and private investors	April 2021/June 2021	Fabiola Pierantozzi	no costs	/

	potentially interested in Cultural and Natural Heritage projects				
3	definition of an Appignano/RURITAGE investment plan, co-created with local stakeholders, for the period 2022-2025	September October 2021	Antonella D'Angelo/Gianluca Vagnarelli	2.500,00 Euro	RURITAGE
4	video-presentation of Appignano del Tronto/RURITAGE investment plan	November 2021	Francesca Luzi	500 Euro	RURITAGE
5	contacts with investors to submit it them underlining the advantages from incentives	December 2021- February 2022	Antonella D'Angelo/Gianluca Vagnarelli/Sara Moreschini	1.000 Euro	RURITAGE

Action R5.11: c

N. of activity	List of activities foreseen – name and short description	Timeline	Main responsible of the activity	Foreseen cost	Funding sources
1	Organization of a dinner with senior farmers, young generations, immigrants, emigrants	August 2020- August 2021	Sara Moreschini, M. Nazzarena Agostini, Adriana Traini, Filippo Fabi Cannella, Giuliano Fares Pro Loco di Appignano del Tronto, Parrocchia San Giovanni Battista	1.500,00 €	RURITAGE
2	Exhibition of typical local products and foreign foods and explanation by testimonials	August 2020- August 2021	Marco Alessandrini (Conca d'Oro), Chiara Vagnoni (Oneiroi)	no costs	/

Izmir in Gediz-Bakircay Basins (IZM, DEM, IZTECH)

Action R6.1: Building of a Geology road map through Citizen science

Activity no.	List of activities foreseen	Timeline	Main responsible of the activity	Foreseen cost (without co-funding budget)	Foreseen cost co-funding budget	Funding sources
1	Development of the programme of the summer schools by Hacettepe University	April 2020	Hacettepe University, IZTECH	500 €	-	project budget
2	Identification of the trainers, experts, teachers	May 2020	Chamber of Geological Engineer, Turkish Association for the Conservation of Geological Heritage (Jemirko)	1,200 €	-	project budget
3	Promotion and communication of the summer school/workshop through the university and the project	June 2020	Hacettepe University		1,500 €	stakeholder budget
4	Implementation of the summer school	April - May 2020	Hacettepe University		250 €	stakeholder budget
5	Public discussion (with locals) of the results of the summer workshop and selection of geo-trails	April 2020 - January 2021	Hacettepe University, Local Cooperatives	600 €		project budget
6	Publication of material (maps, apps, to be decided)	May 2020- May 2022	IZM, IZTECH, DEM	2,500 €		project budget
7	Creating a "RURITAGE volunteering certificate" for the RURITAGE project	March 2020- May 2022	IZM, IZTECH, DEM		500€	co-funding budget

Action R6.2: Resarching on biodiversity in the villages to improve economic resilience

Activity no.	List of activities foreseen	Timeline	Main responsible of the activity	Foreseen cost (without co-funding budget)	foreseen cost co-funding budget	Funding sources
1	Organizing meeting on biodiversity of Bakircay Basin with local people	May-20	Bioeconomy Cooperative	750 €	-	project budget
2	Collaborating with experts for field survey to define biodiversity	Jun-20	Bioeconomy Cooperative	1,250 €	300 €	project budget & co-funding by izmir
3	Preparing economic feasibility report on pine trees and other forest resources in Kozak	June - September 2020	Bioeconomy Cooperative	2,000 €	500 €	project budget & co-funding by izmir

	Plateau to determine alternative income sources.					
4	Ensuring the involvement of citizens to encourage in order to create their new business	June - September 2020	Bioeconomy Cooperative	2,000 €	-	project budget
5	Knowledge transfer for the best production method for pine resin	September-December 2020	Bioeconomy Cooperative	2,000 €	500 €	project budget & co-funding by izmir

Action R6.3: Developing ethnobotanic activities in Bergama region

Activity no.	List of activities foreseen	Timeline	Main responsible of the activity	Foreseen cost (without co-funding budget)	foreseen cost co-funding budget	Funding sources
1	Organize meeting with the leaders of Kozak villages in the Hub to inform about planned ethnobotanical activities in the Plateau, introduce the research team, explain the purposes, and announce the field study for 2020	Jun-21	Ege university, department of biology	250 €	500 €	project budget & co-funding by izmir and ege university (stakeholder)
2	Prepare the list of ethnobotanical herbs and products of the region, having cultural heritage value, based on the literature survey	April - November 2021	Ege university, department of biology	1,500 €	-	project budget
3	Perform the field work within totally 30 days in the villages	April - November 2021	Ege university, department of biology	1,750 €	1,000 €	project budget & co-funding by izmir and ege university (stakeholder)
4	Organize meeting with the leaders of Kozak villages in the Hub to present the results, underline specific ethnobotanical products with high economic added value and open discussion about encouraging for new entrepreneurship	Mar-22	Vocation Factory, ege unv.	500 €	250 €	project budget & co-funding by izmir and ege university (stakeholder)
5	Organize workshops and trainings in the Hub to carry out experimental study on particular ethnobotanical products and show the dynamic relations between plants and people (in parallel with action 2)	November 2021 - April 2022	Vocation Factory, ege unv.	2,250 €	500 €	project budget & co-funding by izmir and ege university (stakeholder)

Action R6.4: Celebrating cultural diversity of Bakircay Basin

Activity no.	List of activities foreseen	Timeline	Main responsible of the activity	Foreseen cost (without co-funding budget)	foreseen cost co-funding budget	Funding sources
1	Organizing the music (trumpet) ateliers with local musicians	December 2020 - July 2021	TEOS Culture and Arts Association	3,000 €	500 €	project budget & co-funding by izmir
2	Get in touch with local musicians	December 2020 - July 2021	TEOS Culture and Arts Association	500 €	-	project budget
3	Develop a festival programme	December 2020 - July 2021	TEOS Culture and Arts Association	2,000 €	1,000 €	project budget & co-funding by izmir
4	Invite artists from different cultures	December 2020 - July 2021	TEOS Culture and Arts Association	2,500 €	-	project budget
5	Arrange documentation of the festival (photos & recordings)	December 2020 - July 2021	TEOS Culture and Arts Association	2,000 €	500 €	project budget & co-funding by izmir
6	Promotion activities for the festival.	December 2020 - July 2021	TEOS Culture and Arts Association	3,250 €	750 €	project budget & co-funding by izmir

Action R6.5: Improve and promote the connection routes between cultural and natural assets in Bakircay Basin

Activity no.	List of activities foreseen	Timeline	Main responsible of the activity	Foreseen cost (without co-funding budget)	foreseen cost co-funding budget	Funding sources
1	Promoting “connection routes” between Pilgrimage Route (Pergamon-Smyrna-Ephesus historical corridor), Eurovelo Route in the north region and IZBAN line	Sep-20	IZBAN, IZM,	-	1,000 €	co-funding by izmir
2	Collaboration with transportation department of greater municipality and other district municipalities. Organizing coordination meetings and workshop	September 2020 – september 2021	IZM, local municipalities	500 €	500 €	project budget & co-funding by izmir
3	Organizing a participatory workshop to define the route through the region	September 2020 – september 2021	IZM, local municipalities	-	500 €	co-funding by izmir

4	Organizing a cycling tour to test of the draft route	September 2020 – september 2021	IZM, local municipalities	1500€	500 €	project budget & co-funding by izmir
5	Making the necessary arrangements by driving on the Draft Bicycle Route and determining the final version of the route	September 2020 – september 2021	IZM, local municipalities	1,000 €	-	project budget
6	Implementation of RURITAGE Izmir Cycle Route as a sub-route to the EUROVELO	September 2020 – December 2021	IZM	14,000 €	2,000 €	project budget & co-funding by izmir
7	Creating the necessary visuals (map video brochure, etc.) for promotion	September 2020 – May 2022	IZM, local municipalities	3 500 €	500 €	project budget & co-funding by izmir

Action R6.6: Increasing the capacity of locals for more touristic offers (accommodation, waitressing, hosting etc.)

Activity no.	List of activities foreseen	Timeline	Main responsible of the activity	Foreseen cost (without co-funding budget)	foreseen cost co-funding budget	Funding sources
1	Define courses programs and trainers	February-April 2020	Vocation Factory, Public education center, cooperatives, IZM	1,000 €	-	project budget
2	A guideline will be prepared with relevant academicians, tourism experts	February-April 2020	Vocation Factory, Public education center, cooperatives, IZM	1,500 €	-	project budget
3	Define criteria for preselection of trainees and select the trainees to be involved in the program	April - June 2020	local cooperatives, Vocation Factory , IZM	-	250 €	co-funding by izmir
4	Organizing “training courses” for pensioning and waitressing to increase capacity building for home boarding	April - June 2020	local cooperatives, Vocation Factory , IZM	750 €	-	project budget
5	Organizing meetings with local people to describe "distributed/diffused hotel network (Albergo Diffuso)"	Oct-20	local cooperatives, IZM	-	500 €	co-funding by izmir
6	Define the villages and houses to be included in the hotel network	June 2020-May 2022	local cooperatives, IZM	-	250 €	co-funding by izmir
7	Creating "distributed/diffused hotel network (Albergo	June 2020-May 2022	local cooperatives, IZM	2,500 €	-	project budget

	Diffuso)" in Kozak Plateau					
	Developing promotional materials (in synergy with action 9)	June 2020-May 2022	IZM	1,500 €	500 €	project budget & co-funding by izmir

Action R6.7: Promotion of basket weaving in Bakircay Basin

Activity no.	List of activities foreseen	Timeline	Main responsible of the activity	Foreseen cost (without co-funding budget)	foreseen cost co-funding budget	Funding sources
1	Organizing two workshops about basket weaving	May 2020 – September 2021	Public education center, Vocation Factory, IZM, DEM	500 €	250 €	project budget & co-funding by izmir
2	Define new master candidates for basket weaving	May 2020 – September 2021	Public education center, Vocation Factory, IZM, DEM	500 €	-	project budget
3	Organizing training activities for new basket weaving masters	May 2020 – September 2021	Public education center, Vocation Factory, IZM, DEM	2,500 €	500 €	project budget & co-funding by izmir
4	Promotion of the courses	May 2020 – September 2021	Public education center, Vocation Factory, IZM	500 €	-	project budget
5	Promotion of baskets	May 2020 – September 2021	IZM, DEM	1,000 €	-	project budget

Action R6.8: Promote ownership of cultural and natural heritage of Bakircay Basin via Forest School

Activity no.	List of activities foreseen	Timeline	Main responsible of the activity	Foreseen cost (without co-funding budget)	foreseen cost co-funding budget	Funding sources
1	Define forest school activities schedule	May 2020 - April 2022	GID	500 €	-	project budget
2	Collaboration with forest school training / leader	May 2020 - April 2022	GID	500 €	-	project budget
3	Organizing 6 forest school activities with children in the region	May 2020 - April 2022	GID	2,000 €	750€	project budget & co-funding budget

Action R6.9: Enhancing the local food culture in Bakircay Basin

Activity no.	List of activities foreseen	Timeline	Main responsible of the activity	Foreseen cost (without co-funding budget)	foreseen cost co-funding budget	Funding sources
1	Organize a roundtable meeting with all potential partners in the Bakircay about branding, benefits,	Nov-20	IZM, BERTO	500 €	-	project budget
2	Meet with BERTO (Bergama Chamber of Trade) to formalize the procedures of branding, licensing, promotion and selling	June 2020 – September 2021	IZM, BERTO, Yasar University	1,500 €	1000€	project budget & co-funding by izmir
3	Organize training courses about local food standardization to create branding	Nov-20	IZM, BERTO, Vocation Factory, Yasar University	1,000 €	500 €	project budget & co-funding by izmir
4	Organize a promotional meeting with all potential partners in all villages to inform possible local products related to medicinal herbs (connected with action 3 about ethnobotanics)	August 2021 – May 2022	IZM, BERTO	1,000 €	500 €	project budget & co-funding by izmir
5	Periodically contact with local producers to increase communication and motivation	August 2021 – May 2022	IZM, BERTO	1,000 €	-	project budget
6	Periodically contact with local restaurants in Bergama and Kozak Plateau to promote the new brand	August 2021 – May 2022	IZM, BERTO	1,000 €	-	project budget & co-funding by izmir
7	Organizing additional culinary activities within local food festivals to disseminate and promote local brands	August 2021 – May 2022	IZM, BERTO	7,500 €	1,000 €	project budget & co-funding by izmir

Annex II: Guidelines for co-development phase workshops

RURITAGE

Heritage for Rural Regeneration

Guidelines for the launch event of the RHH

For RMs and Rs

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 776465

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Table 1: Abbreviations

RHH	Rural Heritage Hub
RM	Role Model
R	Replicator
SIA	Systemic Intervention Area

2. Objective

2.1 General objective

The primary objective of this activity is to officially launch Hub space and gather additional stakeholders to take part in the coming Hub activities. This event will also serve to raise awareness about the local area and community benefit from the involvement in the RHH and thus in the RURITAGE project.

Also, partners would emphasize overarching messages to stress on the benefits the promotion of cultural and natural heritage could generate in their areas (see communication messages developed by ICLEI), in particular:

1. Improve quality of life of the residents of rural areas;
2. Contribute to social inclusion, economic growth and environmental balance in rural areas;
3. Make rural areas more attractive for sustainable business development.

2.2 Specific objectives

- Launch the official Hub space;
- Present RURITAGE with focus on the role of the Role Model/Replicator area in the project;
- Make clear the expected benefits for the area's participation in RURITAGE project;
- Obtain support for the RHH;
- Build a good relationship with the 'local leaders' ('local heroes');
- Present the activity calendar of the Hub, key steps, meetings and deadlines;
- Involve local community and further disseminate the Hub space and activities at local level;
- Present specific challenges/objectives (for Replicators only).

3. Venue

The venue of the event is the local Rural Heritage Hub.

If the RHH has rather limited space, the organisers might host a part of the event in another location close-by or in an open space next to the Hub. Make the most of the space and program dynamic and creative activities for your stakeholders (see draft agenda proposed section for reference).

4. Target groups

Try to gather representatives from different type of your local stakeholders, among which the ones identified in D3.1 (regional and local governing bodies, local associations and actions groups, civil society organizations, education institutions, universities and research institutions, etc.) that are considered relevant into your regeneration strategies or territory.

Moreover, whenever possible, try to reach a gender balanced audience and include vulnerable groups (migrants, disable people, etc.)

5. When to engage stakeholders?

Apart from sending invitations to already engaged stakeholders well in advance (at least 15 days before the event), please refer to the section below on dissemination for further suggestions.

6. Duration

No fixed duration for the event (it could be one full day event or half a day according to the stakeholders to be involved and partners' preferences).

7. Draft agenda proposed

1. Institutional greetings
2. Presentation of RURITAGE project including presentation of the partner organization and their role in RURITAGE and at local level (great emphasis should be included on communicating the objective of the project at a local level)
3. Role of stakeholders and benefits in participating, plus interactive part when participants can meet the RHH stakeholders and interact with them directly. A presentation from regional/local authority could be planned too.
4. Hub foreseen activities
5. Creative workshop to collect insights on local challenges and potential improvements of SIA

Apart from the standard programme, **dynamic activities** related to the SIA of interest should be organized to attract as much people as possible into the event, such as:

- informative stands with tourism providers/offices
- mini-market with local food, tastings, etc
- art shows, concerts, traditional dances, theatre for both kids and adults
- workshops and traditional games for both kids and adults
- competitions / raffles
- video screenings

Local associations could also promote different activities not related to RURITAGE that will be organized in the Hub location, such as sewing lessons, language courses, etc. Stands or reserved spots for them must be provided considering the characteristics of the Hub space.

8. Expected results

- Updated list of participants in Hub activities
- Clear picture of the role of stakeholders in the Hub
- Dissemination of RURITAGE at local, regional and national level (please refer to your local Communication Plan)
- Wide visibility of the event (mass media, newspapers, social media, etc)

9. Costs

The budget estimated for the organization of this event is around **EUR 2.000 - 3.000 for Rs** and **EUR 1.500 - 2.000 for RMs**, including catering, facilitator, material for interaction with participants and feedback collection (i.e. flip board, post-its, pens, etc) and printing of dissemination material.

Possible partnerships and sponsorships: Accommodation providers, restaurants and local food producers (free small catering/snacks), farming companies, investors, non-profit organizations/associations, artists, handcrafters, universities and research centres, transport providers.

10. Useful materials

- Project Information Sheet (PIS) and Data protection Informed Consent Form (ICF) printed out, for those new stakeholders attending the workshop that are not in the database yet.
- Signature list
- Dissemination and communication material
- Projector for presentations
- Recorder and/or specific staff member in charge of collecting participant's suggestions/feedback

11. Dissemination

Partners shall refer Dissemination and Communication plan (ICLEI) for the dissemination of this activity. However, some **additional suggestions** are provided below:

- **Before the event:** distribute flyers, leaflets, make posters visible in key locations etc. in info points, local museums, cultural centers, public buildings. Disseminate the event through your own social media channels and website and also stakeholders' ones, if possible. Involvement of 'local heroes' will increase the reach-out effect. Send out press releases to relevant newspapers.
- **During the event:** place posters, roll-ups, flyers, leaflets and other communication material in visible spots. At the same time, it would be also good to have some 'live' dissemination of the event on the social media, posted on the accounts of the partner organisation and by tagging the project accounts and using hashtags, if relevant. Take short (1 to 3 min.) video/ audio interviews. Take a group picture with participants.
- **After the event:** publish pictures, videos and news about your event on the project's website and your own institutional website, on social media and other relevant channels. Send out press releases to relevant newspapers.

12. Monitoring of the activity

Please refer to the following documents available in the SharePoint folder and upload within 15 days:

- **FOR HUB COORDINATORS**
Launch event report – refer to the template in Annex I
- **FOR PARTICIPANTS**
Launch event evaluation questionnaire – refer to the template in Annex II

13. Annex I: Launch event report – Hub Coordinator

[Name of the organisation in charge of the event]

Venue	
Date	
Duration	
Type and number of stakeholders involved and role in the event	Please include the name of the different stakeholders involved and also the different SIAs they represent, if applicable I.e local government invited as speaker 3 local food company 2 univeristy etc
Total number of participants	
Number of female participants (indicative)	
Number of male participants (indicative)	
Number of disable people, if applicable	
Number of migrants, if applicable	

Agenda of the event

Please include the agenda of the event.

Photos of the event

Please provide some pictures from the event (making sure you comply with GDPR regulations)

Event assessment

Overall how would you rate the success of this specific event? *(mark only one option)*

- Very successful
- Fairly successful
- Not too successful
- Not successful at all

Please briefly describe the event including:

Main messages/lessons you take with you

Key results achieved and specific comments made by members of the Hub

Max. half page

Please briefly describe **main success and difficulties** related to this specific event, if any. Please provide suggestions for similar or future events (including improvements you would like to apply in the next events you will organize).

Max. half page

14. Annex II: Launch event evaluation questionnaire

Objective

As part of the monitoring procedures in terms of efficacy and efficiency of Hub activities, a qualitative assessment will be made after each event asking for stakeholders' feedback on several aspects.

Indications

1. Translate the following questionnaire into your **local language** (or in English if considered)
2. Distribute the questionnaire either in **paper format** and/or through an **online Google Form**, or both. In case of paper format, make sure that these are placed in a visible place (e.g. in a stand or table nearby the entrance, next to the registration list). If in Google Form, make sure you send out the link to all participants and that you specify the deadline to fill it out.
3. During the event, take a few minutes to explain **why** this data is being collected and **how** participants should fill out the questionnaire.
4. You should at least collect **10-15 answers**.
5. After the event, upload answers **in English** in the SharePoint within the following 15 days (PDF or Excel)

LAUNCH EVENT EVALUATION QUESTIONNAIRE				
<u>I. OVERALL EVALUATION</u>	<i>Please mark your answer</i>			
	VERY MUCH	MUCH	FAIR	INSUFFICIENT NOT AT ALL
How satisfied are you of the event organised?				
To what extent do you feel confident with the general aims of the project?				
To what extent do you consider this project relevant for your territory?				
To what extent do you consider relevant your involvement in the development or strengthening of the innovative strategies for promotion of cultural and natural heritage in your area?				
<u>II. DETAILED EVALUATION</u>	EXCELLENT	GOOD	FAIR	INSUFFICIENT
	VERY SATISFIED	SATISFIED	QUITE SATISFIED	NOT SATISFIED
1. PRE-EVENT ORGANISATION				
Did you receive the invitation in good time?				
Did the invitation offer a clear picture of what the event was about?				
<i>If not through invitation, how did you learn about the event? Please specify</i>				
2. OBJECTIVES				
Do you have a clear picture of your role in the Hub?				
How well did the event correspond to your expectations?				
3. HOW WOULD YOU RATE THE FOLLOWING?				
Quality of presentations - speakers				
Documentation & Visual aid				
Quality of moderation and of the Hub team				
Structure and overall design of the event				
Level of interaction among participants				

4. LOGISTICAL ASPECTS				
On-site organisation and support				
Venue's facility (Hub)				
Did the venue offer an environment that supports creativity?				
5. COMMENTS				
1. What did you most appreciate during the event?				
2. Do you have any recommendation for the improvement of the organization of the next Hub activities?				
3. After this event, are you interested in participating in future events?				

RURITAGE

Heritage for Rural Regeneration

Guidelines for the Serious Game event of the RHH

For Rs

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 776465

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Table 1: Abbreviations

RHH	Rural Heritage Hub
RM	Role Model
R	Replicator
SIA	Systemic Intervention Area

2. Objective

2.1 General objective

A workshop using the serious game will be an occasion to build connection and trust between stakeholders as well as illuminate the interconnections between different aspects of rural regeneration.

In particular, the general objectives of the serious game are to:

- Develop Systems Thinking: allow participants to experience and reflect on trade-off and synergies between various strategies of developing rural areas relevant to their situation.
- Nurture Collaboration: support stakeholders in developing a shared understanding of the major challenges and opportunities for their areas.

In the case of rural regeneration, there are many competing areas of potential investment: the chosen Strategic Investment Area (SIA) is only a launching point. Embedded in each SIA is income generation, workforce development, social inclusion / activation of local communities, and disaster preparedness. Focusing on only one to the detriment of others can have unintended consequences. The serious game helps participants understand the tradeoffs and synergies in achieving their goals.

2.2 Specific objectives

- Get participants acquainted with the key elements of the project methodology: Systemic Innovation Areas (SIAs), 6 Capitals, and Cross-cutting Themes.
- Provide participants with experiential opportunities to learn about model actions from the project.
- Create an opportunity for expressing diverse stakeholders' perspectives and foster mutual understanding.
- Create a safe space for brainstorming new innovative projects.

3. Venue

The venue of the event should be the Rural Heritage Hub. This helps connect stakeholders with the place of action. If the Hub has not been launched or there is not enough space, you may consider a space nearby, but make sure:

1. If it's in a public/outdoor place, do it in a tent or make sure to protect yourself from wind, rain and other unforeseen events
2. If it's in another building, make sure you have the room to set it up well

Please see Annex III - Game Setup Document for guidelines on how to set up the room. This is in a general form now, but we will provide a separate Game Setup document for each Replicator. If you have any questions, please let us know.

4. Target groups

All potential stakeholders, including:

- Policy: regional and local governing bodies, territorial development institutions, management of CNH sites, etc.
- Public: local residents, associations, schools, local action groups, civil society organizations, etc.
- Research: universities and research institutes, etc.

- Industry/services/investors: tourism industry representatives, representatives of key value chains, centres for territorial development, foundations, transport, health and leisure providers, media, press, etc.

5. When to engage stakeholders?

Apart from sending invitations to already engaged stakeholders well in advance (at least 15 days before the event), please refer to the section below on dissemination for further suggestions. Remember that you need at least 10 people to play the game, but you may have up to 30, depending on how big your room is.

6. Duration

Our advice is that the game should last at least 4 rounds so that players have time to be strategic. At the very minimum, 3 rounds. This requires a minimum of 2-2.5 hours for the game and the debriefing.

If players only play 2-3 rounds, they won't see the connections between actions and outcomes. They also won't see the need for cooperation.

The debriefing is also critical. If you don't discuss the game and its connection to the real world afterward, you make it "just a game" - and you lose the meaning of being able to build a bridge between what happened and what you want to see happen in your area.

7. Draft agenda proposed

Possible organization structure for longer games (approximate 3.5 hrs total) - this would be roughly what we did at Valladolid, this is ideal! :)

- 10 min - snacks and icebreaker (let me know if you need help with these!)
- 20 min - introduction to game world (something like what Piotr did before and after lunch but shorter - we will work on this together before your workshops)
- 40 min - Round 1
- 20 min - Round 2
- 10 min - Community Meeting
- 15 min - Round 3
- 15 min break - snacks & drinks
- 15 min - Round 4
- 10 min - Community meeting
- 15 min - Round 5
- 45-60 min - Debriefing

Possible organization structure for shorter games (approx. 2.5 hrs total)

- 15-20 min - snacks and introduction to game world (something like what Piotr did before and after lunch but shorter - we will work on this together before your workshops)
- 40 min - Round 1
- 20 min - Round 2
- 10 min - Community Meeting with snacks
- 15 min - Round 3
- 45 min for debriefing although participants can stay longer

8. Expected results

The debriefing should be a time for rich conversation about the main three sections: What happened? Why does it matter? What do we do now?

1. *Annex IV: Debriefing Outline* has specific questions for leading the debriefing. We have provided two versions, a short version, if you only have about 30 minutes, and a long version, if you have 1 hr. The general outline looks like this:
 - a. *What?* What happened on the board, what decisions did participants make, what did they not make? What happened?
 - b. *So what?* What did they notice with regards to: Goals, Challenges, Connections between Themes and Relationships.
 - c. *Now what?* Bridge to the “Real World” - What are the similarities you see between this world and the real world? What has inspired you? What lessons can you take from this in your further work? Does this change your approach to what you want to do, how you might work with each other?
2. In the third part, “Bridge to the Real World”, it offers you also a chance to further explain the RURITAGE project and your focus more specifically
 - a. SIAs
 - b. Capitals
 - c. Cross-Cutting Themes

Information from the debriefing can be gathered:

- (BEST) By taking notes as participants speak on a flipchart, whiteboard or notepad
 - Note: The best way to do this is having another person from your team make notes while the main facilitator runs the debriefing session
- By asking the participants to write down their answers on post-it notes and then put it on flipchart; you can later take a photo of this flipchart to archive it
- Consider using additional surveys with specific questions that you want answered at the end of the debriefing session
- Recording (audio or video) the debriefing session
 - Note: If you do this, due to GDPR you will need participants to agree to being recorded

Additional benefits of this game session may come to organizers:

1. Identify additional (unexpected) local leaders
2. Build closer relationships with leaders
3. Be able to ask hard questions of participants’ intentions and values that you wouldn’t ordinarily feel comfortable asking by framing it within the game - questions like:
 - a. “In the game you did this, is that the same as you plan to do?”
 - b. “Why did you choose to do this, what made it more important than that? Do we want to do the same in real life?”
4. Can help participants focus on individual impacts - what does this have to do with me? How could I be involved in real life?

9. Costs

Costs would be associated with providing catering to participants.

10. Useful materials

- RURITANIA game - an electronic version (PDF files with the game elements) will be provided 1 week

before; a hard copy will be provided the day before

- Whiteboard / Flipchart - for making notes of what was observed at the debriefing
- Signature sheet - for attendance
- Annex II – Serious game event evaluation questionnaire
- Annex III – Game Setup Document

11. Dissemination

Partners shall refer Dissemination and Communication plan (ICLEI) for the dissemination of this activity. However, some **additional suggestions** are provided below:

- **Before the event:** distribute flyers/invitations, leaflets, make posters visible in key locations etc. in info points, local museums, cultural centres, public buildings. Disseminate the event through your own social media channels and website and also stakeholders' ones, if possible. Involvement of 'local heroes' will increase the reach-out effect. Send out press releases to relevant newspapers. CRS will provide a video from the game in Valladolid.
- **During the event:** place posters, roll-ups, flyers, leaflets and other communication material in visible spots. At the same time, it would be also good to have some 'live' dissemination of the event on the social media, posted on the accounts of the partner organisation and by tagging the project accounts and using hashtags, if relevant. Take short (1 to 3 min.) video/ audio interviews. Take a group picture with participants.
- **After the event:** publish pictures, videos and news about your event on the project's website and your own institutional website, on social media and other relevant channels. Send out press releases to relevant newspapers.

Many of you expressed concerns about how to invite participants. Based on that, we put together some possible strategies to use:

- a. Networking opportunity - build your network at an innovative workshop
- b. Find common strategies for regenerating our area
- c. Don't mention the game? Mention the game? - This depends on your stakeholders
- d. Team-building opportunity - let's work together in an innovative way
- e. Get to know each other as we begin our RURITAGE journey - may or may not mention Serious Game
- f. Focus on the outcome - what will stakeholders leave knowing?
- g. "Create the future together"
- h. Traditionally unengaged people - consider designating someone from your hub as their "caretaker", actively get them involved in the game/activity
- i. Parents - have a kids room available with games and caretakers to help stakeholders with kids have a place to leave their kids and enable greater participation
- j. Try to reach out personally to local leaders: it may be time well spent to explain them what will happen during the workshop, why it's unique and why people should care
- k. Make sure that people know that in our workshop we think of them more as partners in the process than merely learners - they will get to use their knowledge and experience, which is extremely valuable to us

12. Monitoring of the activity

Please refer to the following documents available in the SharePoint folder and upload within 15 days:

- **FOR HUB COORDINATORS**
Serious game event report – refer to the template in Annex I

- **FOR PARTICIPANTS**

Serious game event evaluation questionnaire – refer to the template in Annex II

13. Annex I: Serious game event report – Hub Coordinator

[Name of the organisation in charge of the event]

Venue	
Date	
Duration	
Type and number of stakeholders involved and role in the event	Please include the name of the different stakeholders involved and also the different SIAs they represent, if applicable i.e. local government invited as speaker 3 local food company 2 university etc.
Total number of participants	
Number of female participants (indicative)	
Number of male participants (indicative)	
Number of disabled people, if applicable	
Number of migrants, if applicable	

Agenda of the event

Please include the agenda of the event.

Photos of the event

Please provide some pictures from the event (making sure you comply with GDPR regulations)

Event assessment

Overall how would you rate the success of this specific event? (*mark only one option*)

- Very successful
- Fairly successful

- Not too successful
- Not successful at all

Please briefly describe the event including:

Your key takeaways from the session (game + debriefing). You can also include specific comments made by members of the Hub regarding the game and their strategy, or any new projects you are considering for the Hub after the workshop.

Max. half page

Is there anything you would change about the workshop to get more engagement from stakeholders? If so, what?

Max. half page

14. Annex II: Serious game event evaluation questionnaire

Objective

As part of the monitoring procedures in terms of efficacy and efficiency of Hub activities, a qualitative assessment will be made after each event asking for stakeholders' feedback on several aspects.

Indications

1. Translate the following questionnaire into your **local language** (or in English if considered)
2. Distribute the questionnaire either in **paper format** and/or through an **online Google Form**, or both. In case of paper format, make sure that these are placed in a visible place (e.g. in a stand or table nearby the entrance, next to the registration list). If in Google Form, make sure you send out the link to all participants and that you specify the deadline to fill it out.
3. During the event, take a few minutes to explain **why** this data is being collected and **how** participants should fill out the questionnaire.
4. You should at least collect **10-15 answers**.
5. After the event, upload answers **in English** in the SharePoint within the following 15 days (PDF or Excel)

LAUNCH EVENT EVALUATION QUESTIONNAIRE				
<u>I. OVERALL EVALUATION</u>	<i>Please mark your answer</i>			
	VERY MUCH	MUCH	FAIR	INSUFFICIENT NOT AT ALL
How satisfied are you of the event organised?				
To what extent do you feel confident with the general aims of the project?				
To what extent do you consider this project relevant for your territory?				
To what extent do you consider relevant your involvement in the development or strengthening of the innovative strategies for promotion of cultural and natural heritage in your area?				
<u>II. DETAILED EVALUATION</u>	EXCELLENT	GOOD	FAIR	INSUFFICIENT
	VERY SATISFIED	SATISFIED	QUITE SATISFIED	NOT SATISFIED
1. PRE-EVENT ORGANISATION				
Did you receive the invitation in good time?				
Did the invitation offer a clear picture of what the event was about?				
<i>If not through invitation, how did you learn about the event? Please specify</i>				
2. OBJECTIVES				
Do you have a clear picture of your role in the Hub?				
How well did the event correspond to your expectations?				
3. HOW WOULD YOU RATE THE FOLLOWING?				
Quality of moderation and of the Hub team				
Structure and overall design of the event				
Level of interaction among participants				
4. LOGISTICAL ASPECTS				
On-site organisation and support				

Venue's facility (Hub)				
Did the venue offer an environment that supports creativity?				

5. EVALUATION OF THE SERIOUS GAME

1. What are the benefits of the game? What have you learned from playing it?

2. What would you change to make the game more relevant for you (and other stakeholders)?

5. COMMENTS

1. What did you most appreciate during the event?

2. Do you have any recommendation for the improvement of the organization of the next Hub activities?

3. After this event, are you interested in participating in future events?

Annex IV: Debriefing Outline

Debriefing Outline: SHORT VERSION

<i>Step</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Process</i>	<i>Comments</i>
1. Results Overview - WHAT?	Review the game board: What did players invest in (tourism, local production and their types)? Where did they see growth? Where there was no growth? What happened (events, disasters)? What were the results of those disasters?	Whole group 5-10 min.	
	Answer any questions related to the final game board.	Whole group 2-3 min.	
2. Game Process Overview - SO WHAT?	Goals: What was your role in the game? What goals were you able to achieve (in whole or in part)? Challenges: What made the pursuit of your goal(s) difficult? Were there any particular situations that were challenging or frustrating? Cooperation: What interconnections have you observed between you (your decisions) and other roles (their decisions)? How well did you work with other roles?	Team (as they played in the game) reflection, 5 min.	
	Each team summarizes their answers to the reflection questions; the moderator can add comments	Whole-Group 2 min. / team (16 min. total)	

3. Bridging with the Real World - NOW WHAT?	Similarities to the real world What similarities have you observed between the game and the situation of your rural area? <i>Focus on partners from Replicators or Role Models</i> Inspirations What inspirations did the game bring you to do differently / to initiate in your area?	Small-Groups <i>Forming small groups (3-4 people) - find people you didn't interact with too much.</i> 3-5 min.	
	Discussion summary: each group summarizes their discussions briefly	Whole group 2 min / group (10 minutes total)	
4. Closing	Final comments from participants Moderator final remarks	Whole group 2 min.	

Debriefing Outline: LONG VERSION

Step	Description	Process	Comments
1. Results Overview - WHAT?	Review the game board: What did players invest in (tourism, local production, satisfaction, disasters)? Where did they see growth? Where there was no growth? What happened (events, disasters)? What were the results of those disasters?	Whole group 5 min.	
	Answer any questions related to the final game board.	Whole group 2-3 min.	

<p>2. Game Process Overview - SO WHAT?</p>	<p>Goals: What was your role in the game? What were your goals in this role (if you had any)? Why? What goals were you able to achieve (in whole or in part)? How did you go about doing it? Challenges: What made the pursuit of your goal(s) difficult? What did you feel you could overcome and what did you feel were barriers that were too high? Were there any particular situations that were challenging or frustrating? What? Cooperation: Did you cooperate with other roles? How well did you work together? Were there any interesting or challenging situations? Interlinkages: What did you notice about other roles' actions? What do you see as being interconnected? What seemed unconnected? In hindsight, what do you wish was different? What are you satisfied with?</p>	<p>Team (as they played in the game) reflection, 5-10 min.</p>	<p>Participants don't have to answer every question. These are more guiding questions.</p>
	<p>Each team summarizes their answers to the reflection questions; the moderator can add comments.</p>	<p>Whole-Group 3-5 min. / team</p>	
	<p>Give other participants a chance to respond: What was their impression of the same situation? What do they agree with? What do they disagree with?</p>	<p>Whole-Group 10 min</p>	
<p>3. Bridging with the Real World - NOW WHAT?</p>	<p>Similarities to the real world a. REALIZED PROJECTS/ACTIONS: What projects/actions did you realize that would make sense in your region? Are there any projects which you hadn't considered that you now consider important? What made these projects valuable? What were the barriers to achieving these projects in the game? Do you think you will have similar challenges in the real world? What additional challenges would you have? b. UNREALIZED PROJECTS/ACTIONS: What projects/actions did you NOT realize that you wanted to? Would you want to realize</p>	<p>Small-Groups Forming small groups (3-4 people) - find people you didn't interact with too much. 10-15 min.</p>	<p>Participants don't have to answer every question. These are more guiding questions.</p>

	<p>these in your region? Why or why not? What were the barriers to implementing them in the game - do you think you would have similar challenges in the real world? What additional challenges would you have?</p> <p>c. MISSING PROJECTS/ACTIONS: What projects/actions that were missing would you like to implement? Why? Are these important in your region? How do you plan to implement them? What challenges do you expect and how do you expect to deal with those?</p>		
	<p>Discussion summary: each group summarizes their discussions briefly. Other participants have a chance to respond and add ideas.</p>	<p>Whole group <i>15-20 min / group</i></p>	<p>MODERATOR: Take notes on key takeaways, key challenges identified, key successes and key projects identified as important - these can be used in your future participatory and planning sessions.</p>
<p>4. Closing</p>	<p>Final comments from participants Moderator final remarks</p>	<p>Whole group <i>2-5 min.</i></p>	

Guidelines for the Participatory workshop of the RHH

For Rs

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Table 1: Abbreviations

RHH	Rural Heritage Hub
RM	Role Model
R	Replicator
SIA	Systemic Intervention Area
MA	Model Action

2. Objective

2.1 General objective

Extend the **discussion on regeneration plans** to a wider audience and start the **work towards the definition of the actions** to be included in the action plan.

As in previous events, this one should also serve as an **occasion to attract and engage further stakeholders** into the RHHs. Thus, it is worth taking a few minutes to present again the project, its objectives, the role of the stakeholders in it, and the benefits that promoting cultural and natural heritage could bring into the territory.

This workshop aims at entering into the core of the co-development phase of the heritage-led regeneration plan and it is the first occasion to let the stakeholders familiarize with the concept of the SIAs and with the Best Practices collected in RURITAGE Role Models. The participatory workshop is indeed a crucial step to start defining, for the first time together with the stakeholders, possible actions to be included in the action plan and to be implemented in Replicators' territories.

2.2 Specific objectives

- Present your specific objectives within RURITAGE and discuss the overall objective of the heritage led regeneration strategies in your territory
- Present the main SIA your replicator will work on – taking example from RURITAGE Role Models, and provide a general overview of the other SIAs
- Present the replicator baseline developed by CARTIF in Del 1.4
- Present, Discuss and tailor with your stakeholders the practices you pre-selected and the ones you added to the pack of cards as new possible actions
- Focus on the local strategy to be adopted within a regeneration plan

3. How to organize the workshop

3.1 The contents and materials

The workshop strongly relies on the contents of Del 1.4 'Replicators baseline' and the D1.1 RURITAGE Practices Repository (WP1), where a certain number of Best Practices has been identified through the analysis of the Role Models according to the different SIAs. The same Best Practices have also been included in the expectation survey that each Rs and RMs has filled in for building the knowledge exchange visits in WP2, therefore they represent the core activities that Replicators are taking into consideration when it comes to define the regeneration plans (WP3). New ideas for potential actions rather than the one from Role Models that might potentially be implemented can be added by each Replicators in agreement with UNIBO and CE and can be discussed during this workshop.

To the aim of the Participatory Workshop and then to the Business Model Workshop, the Best Practices are hereafter called Model Actions.

To facilitate the workshop dynamic each Model Action has been turned into a card (see Figure 1). The colour of each card is selected according to the colour of the SIA it belongs to. The front side of each card contains the code

and the title of the Model Action. The back of the card has to be filled in by the stakeholders according to the instructions in section 3.3 What to do during the workshop. The back of the card contains some questions that are aimed at collecting the feedback from the stakeholders. The main questions are presented below:

- **Why this action:**
 Why do you consider this action strategic for the territory?
 What benefits could this action bring to your territory (social, economic, environmental, technological)?
- **What you can build on?**
 Please briefly describe if there are some projects/activities already in place that you can use as a starting point to work on this action
- **What difficulties can you envisage in the implementation process?**
 Please mention your main worries in implementing this action in your territory
- **My role in the implementation**
 What can I provide in terms of expertise, funds, practical work?
- **Who would you involve to get additional support? Specifically, for what?**
 Please mention any actor (present or not at this workshop) you believe it could bring support/expertise in this action

The questions in the back of the card can be customized to some extent, in order to get the most from the stakeholders.

Figure 1 – Example of Model Action card coming from the RURITAGE Role Models

Figure 2 – Example of New Action card that can be filled in and added to the pack of cards

RURITAGE
ART & FESTIVAL

Stakeholder name: _____

Why this action: _____

What you can build on? _____

What difficulties can you envisage in the implementation process?

My role in the implementation _____

Who would you involve to get additional support? _____
 Specifically, for what? _____

3.2 What to do before the workshop

Before the workshop, a pre-selection of the Model Actions has to be performed, in order to decide which practices to include in the **pack of cards** to be used during the workshop. As a first step, each Replicator makes a pre-selection autonomously, starting from the results from the ideas gathered at a proposal stage, the Training Workshop in Valladolid, the Development Workshop in Crete, the suggestion included in the Replicators' baseline and the preferences expressed in the expectation survey in particular practices and SIAs. **A number of Model Actions between 10 and 20 should be preselected.** There is no fixed number of actions to be pre-selected. This could vary case by case. As a general recommendation, please discuss this with your contact person at UNIBO and CE. The second step consists in organising a remote meeting among each Replicator, UNIBO and CE in order to explain the rationale behind the selection, and to agree on the pack of cards to be printed and distributed among the stakeholders during the workshop.

The pack should include the cards related with the preselected Model Actions (10-20) (Figure 1) and possibly, some **new innovative actions for rural regeneration** developed by each Replicator (Figure 2).

Once the selection of actions to include in the pack of cards has been completed, the Rs are required to **translate the card selected**, by using the PowerPoint Presentation that UNIBO and CE will make available.

3.3 What to do during the workshop

The aim of the workshop should be presented clearly at the beginning of the event.

Workshop will start with a short presentation of RURITAGE project, its objectives and milestones. After this short

presentation, each Replicator will shortly present the results of Task 1.4 ‘Replicator’ baseline, where a state of the art of the territory and of the area of each replicator has been developed by CARTIF **(10-15 minutes)**.

After this presentation there will be the introduction to the workshop. In this introduction the RHH coordinator should briefly present the SIAs overall concept focusing the attention on the SIAs that are more interesting for its territory – examples from Role models to better explain the SIAs concept are highly recommended **(15 minutes)**.

After this presentation the RHH coordinator will start explaining the workshop dynamic:

1. Few minutes should be dedicated to briefly introduce the name of the cards and to explain the questions in the back. A slide containing the questions in section 3.1 can be left on the screen for the entire workshop, in order to help the stakeholders in filling in the cards. A sheet with a short description of the actions will be printed and provided to all participants. The card can be either send to the stakeholder by email prior to the workshop, to make them familiarising with the contents, or distributed during the workshop for the first time.
2. Each stakeholder attending the event receives a pack of cards to be used during the workshop and RHH coordinator explain the aims and rules **(15 minutes)**. If the stakeholders attending the meeting are more than 20, the suggestion is to divide the participant in two groups from the beginning, to stay split also during the discussing, and to have at the very end a wrap up session with all the participants where the moderator of each group reports to all the main results of the workshop.
3. The stakeholders select individually the cards they would like to complete, therefore each card selected is representative of one action that is interesting from them, either because they can have a role in the implementation of the action, or because they consider the action as relevant to be implemented. Each stakeholder should select **maximum 10 cards** in order to be sure to have time for completing the description and reporting to the rest of the participants **(10 minutes)**. A **Jolly card** can be added to the Model Actions selected and it can be used to include into the discussion possible new actions that do not come directly from the Role Model practices, but that are important to be considered for the definition of the rural regeneration plan;
4. Stakeholders are paired to interview each other in the framework of a bilateral meeting. For example: Stakeholder A selects 5 cards, stakeholder B selects 4 cards. Stakeholder A interviews the stakeholder B by asking the questions and by writing in the back of the card. Then is the turn of stakeholder B who interviews the stakeholder A asking the same questions related to the card that stakeholder B selected **(45 minutes)**;
5. After having completed the card description, the stakeholders explain their choices in a plenary discussion, where the coordinator of the RHH is also the moderator of the discussion. First of all, all the card completed can be displayed on a table to see which card received the most or the least attention. This can provide a first indication on what to focus on during the discussion **(60 minutes)**.
The main issues to be addressed during the discussion are:
 - a. Which is the most selected card/action? And which are the roles of the different stakeholders to implement that specific action?
 - b. Which is the card/action most difficult to put in practice and why?
 - c. Which is the card/action most easy to put in practice and why?
 - d. Are there interesting new ideas for action to be implemented?
6. If the stakeholders attending the meeting are more than 20, there is a wrap up session with all the participants where the moderator of each group reports to all the main results of the workshop **(20 minutes)**.

3.4 What to do after the workshop

After the workshop, the reports in the ANNEXES of this guidelines should be fulfilled and sent to UNIBO and CE, and uploaded in the dedicated folder in the SharePoint. Moreover, an additional remote meeting with UNIBO, CE, WESTBIC and SAVONIA should be organised in order to discuss the results from the Participatory Workshop and to agree on the pre-selection of the Model Actions to be included in the following local Workshop on Business

Models and Investment Strategy.

4. Venue

The venue of the event is the local Rural Heritage Hub.

If the RHH has rather limited space, the organisers might host a part of the event in another location close-by or in an open space next to the Hub. Consider the estimated number of stakeholders participating and how will you make use of the space.

During the workshops, when stakeholders interview each other in pair, they can either stay in the same room and sit one next to the other, or they can be separated in different rooms according to the size of the venue.

If stakeholders attending the meeting are more than 20, at least two different rooms are required in order to do the workshop with two different sessions running in parallel.

5. Target groups

All potential stakeholders, including:

- Policy: regional and local governing bodies, territorial development institutions, management of CNH sites, etc.
- Public: local residents, associations, schools, local action groups, civil society organizations, etc.
- Research: universities and research institutes, etc.
- Industry/services/investors: tourism industry representatives, representatives of key value chains, centres for territorial development, foundations, transport, health and leisure providers, media, press, etc.
- Those that might have a role in the implementation of the preselected Model Actions

6. When to engage stakeholders?

Apart from sending invitations to already engaged stakeholders well in advance (at least 15 days before the event), please refer to the section below on dissemination for further suggestions.

7. Duration

A session of 3-4 hours is recommended. However, this will highly depend on the number of stakeholders participating and the number of Model Actions discussed.

See the proposed agenda for reference.

8. Draft agenda proposed

1. Presentation of RURITAGE project objectives at local level, role of stakeholders and benefits in participating (if new stakeholders are present).
2. Presentation of the Replicator baseline

3. Short presentation of the SIAs concept and main SIAs relevant for the replication – examples from RMs are highly recommended
4. Presentation of the workshop aims and dynamics (also with a view toward the business model workshop)
5. Presentation of Model Actions pre-selected and of new ones added to the pack of cards that might potentially be implemented.
6. Card distribution, choices and discussion (see the details of the steps in section 3.3)
7. Next Hub activities foreseen
8. Promotion of non-related RURITAGE activities that are or could be organized in the Hub space to attract a wider range of stakeholders

9. Expected results

After this workshop, Hub coordinators and stakeholders should have a good idea on the specific Model Actions that could be implemented as regeneration plans. Therefore, a list of Model Actions is expected to be generated and somehow ranked according to the stakeholders' interest.

As stated in section 3.4, after a remote meeting with UNIBO, CE, WESTBIC and each Replicator will be able to decide which Model Actions will be further supported by the different business model canvases to be produced in the following workshop, which will assess their feasibility and viability, including financial viability.

10. Costs

Costs foreseen would be associated with providing catering to participants and printing costs for the cards (**1.000 – 1.500 EUR**)

Possible partnerships and sponsorships: Accommodation providers, restaurants and local food producers (free small catering/snacks), farming companies, investors, non-profit organizations/associations, artists, handcrafters, universities and research centres, transport providers

11. Useful materials

- A pack of cards for each participant
- A list of all the cards/actions with each one described in maximum 5 lines
- Presentation with the cards, the rules and the questions to be addressed
- Projector for presentations
- Signature sheet - for attendance
- Annex IV – Participatory workshop evaluation questionnaire for participants

12. Dissemination

Partners shall refer Dissemination and Communication plan (ICLEI) for the dissemination of this activity. However, some **additional suggestions** are provided below:

- **Before the event:** distribute flyers/invitations, leaflets, make posters visible in key locations etc. in info points, local museums, cultural centres, public buildings. Disseminate the event through your own social media channels and website and also stakeholders’ ones, if possible. Involvement of ‘local heroes’ will increase the reach-out effect. Send out press releases to relevant newspapers.
- **During the event:** place posters, roll-ups, flyers, leaflets and other communication material in visible spots. At the same time, it would be also good to have some ‘live’ dissemination of the event on the social media, posted on the accounts of the partner organisation and by tagging the project accounts and using hashtags, if relevant. Take short (1 to 3 min.) video/ audio interviews. Take a group picture with participants.
- **After the event:** publish pictures, videos and news about your event on the project’s website and your own institutional website, on social media and other relevant channels. Send out press releases to relevant newspapers.

13. Monitoring of the activity

Please refer to the following documents available in the SharePoint folder and upload within 15 days:

- **FOR HUB COORDINATORS**
 Participatory workshop event report – refer to the template in Annex I
 Pre-selection sheet – refer to the template in Annex II
 Wrap-up sheet – refer to the template in Annex III
- **FOR PARTICIPANTS**
 Participatory workshop evaluation questionnaire – refer to the template in Annex IV

14. Annex I: Participatory workshop event report – Hub Coordinator

[Name of the organisation in charge of the event]

Venue	
Date	
Duration	
Type and number of stakeholders involved and role in the event	Please include the name of the different stakeholders involved and also the different SIAs they represent, if applicable i.e. local government invited as speaker

	3 local food company 2 university etc.
Total number of participants	
Number of female participants (indicative)	
Number of male participants (indicative)	
Number of disabled people, if applicable	
Number of migrants, if applicable	

Agenda of the event

Please include the agenda of the event.

Photos of the event

Please provide some pictures from the event (making sure you comply with GDPR regulations)

Event assessment

Overall how would you rate the success of this specific event? (*mark only one option*)

- Very successful
- Fairly successful
- Not too successful
- Not successful at all

Please briefly describe the event including:

Please briefly describe **main success and difficulties** related to this specific event, if any. Please provide suggestions for similar or future events (including improvements you would like to apply in the next events you will organize).

Max. half page

15. Annex II: Pre-selection sheet

Replicator:						
Model action/best practice pre-selected by R		Accepted / Discarded	Reasons for accepting / discarding	Potential challenges in implementation	Potential stakeholders involved	Potential role in implementation
Code	Description					
New innovative actions proposed		Accepted / Discarded	Reasons for accepting / discarding	Potential challenges in implementation	Potential stakeholders involved	Potential role in implementation
Description						

16. Annex III: Wrap-up sheet

Final list of model actions/best practices selected after the participatory workshop	
Code	Description

17. Annex IV: Participatory workshop evaluation questionnaire

Objective

As part of the monitoring procedures in terms of efficacy and efficiency of Hub activities, a qualitative assessment will be made after each event asking for stakeholders’ feedback on several aspects.

Indications

1. Translate the following questionnaire into your **local language** (or in English if considered)
2. Distribute the questionnaire either in **paper format** and/or through an **online Google Form**, or both. In case of paper format, make sure that these are placed in a visible place (e.g. in a stand or table nearby the entrance, next to the registration list). If in Google Form, make sure you send out the link to all participants and that you specify the deadline to fill it out.
3. During the event, take a few minutes to explain **why** this data is being collected and **how** participants should fill out the questionnaire.
4. You should at least collect **10-15 answers**.
5. After the event, complete the online survey placed on your event folder with the participant’s answers OR upload answers **in English** in the SharePoint (Excel), within 15 days.

LAUNCH EVENT EVALUATION QUESTIONNAIRE				
I. OVERALL EVALUATION	Please mark your answer			
	VERY MUCH	MUCH	FAIR	INSUFFICIENT NOT AT ALL
How satisfied are you of the event organised?				
To what extent do you feel confident with the general aims of the project?				

To what extent do you consider this project relevant for your territory?				
To what extent do you consider relevant your involvement in the development or strengthening of the innovative strategies for promotion of cultural and natural heritage in your area?				
II. DETAILED EVALUATION	EXCELLENT	GOOD	FAIR	INSUFFICIENT
	VERY SATISFIED	SATISFIED	QUITE SATISFIED	NOT SATISFIED
1. PRE-EVENT ORGANISATION				
Did you receive the invitation in good time?				
Did the invitation offer a clear picture of what the event was about?				
<i>If not through invitation, how did you learn about the event? Please specify</i>				
2. OBJECTIVES				
Do you have a clear picture of your role in the Hub?				
Do you have a clear picture of the regeneration actions that will/could be implemented in your territory?				
How well did the event correspond to your expectations?				
3. HOW WOULD YOU RATE THE FOLLOWING?				
Usefulness of workshop format				
Quality of moderation and of the Hub team				
Structure and overall design of the event				
Level of interaction among participants				
4. LOGISTICAL ASPECTS				
On-site organisation and support				
Venue's facility (Hub)				
Did the venue offer an environment that supports creativity?				
5. COMMENTS				

1. What did you most appreciate during the event?

2. Do you have any recommendation for the improvement of the organization of the next Hub activities?

3. After this event, are you interested in participating in future events?

RURITAGE

Heritage for Rural Regeneration

Guidelines for the Business Models and Investment Strategy Local Workshop

For Rs

Tuomo Eskelinen, SAVONIA

James Donlon, WESTBIC

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 776465

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Table 1: Abbreviations

BM	Business Model
BMC	Business Model Canvas
CNH	Cultural and Natural Heritage
INTO	INTO tool at into.savonia.fi
MCDS	Multi-criteria decision support
R	Replicator
RHH	Rural Heritage Hub
RM	Role Model
SIA	Systemic Innovation Area

1. Objective

1.1 General Objective

Following the Participatory Workshop, the Business Models Workshop is the next stepping stone in the co-development of heritage-led regeneration strategies for Replicators. The task aims to develop replicable and up-scalable participative business models for the various actions to be implemented in the Replicators' territory that may be developed in a viable and sustainable way.

Using an innovative business model framework, stakeholders will be supported in developing tailored opportunities and initiatives within the six Replicators, with specific recommendations to replicate and tailor the actions identified in the Role Models.

Using the Business Canvas approach applied to CNH, this process is informed by the data gathering in the RURITAGE project, the Model Actions and the Lessons Learnt from the Role Models and from active engagement with the Replicators so that innovative business models and financial strategies can be defined for each scenario. The Canvas Business Models (Del 3.3) will then feed into the next related tasks - heritage-led regeneration plans, strategies and demonstration projects.

1.2 Approach

During RURITAGE the model actions/best practices (Del 1.1, TEC) identified in the Role Models, and discussed in the Participatory Workshop, forms the backdrop for the innovative business modelling process. Participating stakeholders have been identified during the first months of the project following specific guidelines developed by project partners (Del 2.1). The baseline study of the Replicators acts as a starting point (Del 1.4 CARTIF), whilst the Business Models are evaluated by establishing value-based criteria connected to Del. 4.1 (CARTIF).

To guide the business modelling process, the following supports are available:

- An innovative Business Model Canvas for CNH has been developed and pre-tested to support the first steps towards heritage-led regeneration plans, boosting co-creation, prioritising and co-ordination of actions. Further feedback will be collected to learn from the BM processes in each R.
- A detailed Guide is provided on how to use this Business Model Canvas to facilitate the strategy development.
- The Business Modelling process is complemented by the INTO tool – an online platform for making complex decision making faster and more efficient, involving different stakeholders and providing a transparent process. This tool is guided by Savonia, and is tailored to the situation of each Replicator.
- A training workshop was held for Replicators in Crete, along with face-to-face meetings with each Replicator, to explain the process involved and to demonstrate the use of the INTO Tool (into.savonia.fi) as a co-creation process to build actions on business models and investment strategy.
- Support will be provided to prepare for the Business Model Workshop to be held in each RHH.
- Further assistance, through a review and feedback process, will be provided with the tailored Business Model solutions for each Replicator that can be developed in a viable way from a financial and economic perspective.

The Business models process is guided by Savonia (leading task 3.2) and WestBIC, and supported by CE, CARTIF, UNIBO and ICLEI.

1.3 5 Steps Towards Business Models and Investment Strategy

The development process is a creative service design process including both divergent (Idea Development/ Model Actions) and convergent phases (evaluation and decision analysis produces prioritized list of actions). In the case of Business Modelling for Replicators in the RURITAGE project, the backdrop is the Model Actions selected from the Role Models that have potential for replication and tailoring for implementation in Replicator regions. This leads to the following 5 steps:

SAVONIA

CNH Canvas & model actions evaluation at the Replicator

4 Decision analysis with core value

Gives us a prioritized list of actions to support the BM and investment strategy creation. Results will be presented as a draft CNH Canvas, and as a prioritized list of actions with development comments and commitments (who will take lead for further actions)

Savonia Core Value calculation.

Savonia Business Model Canvas

#	Scenarios	Idea name	Description
1	1771	Cooperation	Non-active producer organisations should be brought into a Producer organisations should cooperate with local gover
2	1771	Create a network of local farmers	Make farmers aware of the importance of making network a
3	1771	Create children board	Set up board with local primary school children that will log
4	1771	create public private artstewship	create PPP
5	1771	Customer wants to see excellent views landscape	Customer wants to see excellent views and take photograp
6	1771	Outstations	Outstations

Discussion on results & Action plan BM and investment strategy

5 Expected results:
1) CNH Canvas
2) Prioritized and improved list of model actions

www.savonia.fi

Figures 1a and 1b. CNH Canvas creation and Evaluation of model actions with Into tool. Business models and investment strategy process at Ruritage. Adapted from Kajanus et al. (2014¹ and 2019², Eskelinen et al., 2017³ and RURITAGE Project Plan.

Overview of the Steps

- Step 1 should already be completed as part of the Participatory Workshop, which includes a shortlisting for the proposed Model Actions, stakeholder identification and engagement
- Step 2 is the core Business Canvas completion as part of the workshop, which is organised according to the instruction in Section 3 and also using the Guide in Annex I.
- Using the online INTO tool, <https://into.savonia.fi> Steps 3.1 and 3.2 involves the evaluation of the Actions so that they can be agreed and prioritised, using a range of selected criteria. This is further explained at the end of Annex I Guide.
- Steps 4 & 5, involves decision analysis and discussion of the results as a prioritisation exercise with the input/feedback from the stakeholders at the workshop using the agreed evaluation criteria. Portfolio analysis occupies core index to calculate the results, and to put the Model Actions into a prioritized list (according to Kajanus et al., 2014). The results will be organised within the CNH Canvas framework.

¹ Kajanus, Iire, Eskelinen, Heinonen, Hansen: Business model design: new tools for business systems innovation. Scandinavian Journal of Forest Research 08/2014; 29(6). DOI:10.1080/02827581.2014.949301.

² Kajanus M, et al., What can we learn from business models in the European forest sector: Exploring the key elements of new business model designs Forest Policy and Economics. Volume 99, February 2019, Pages 145-156. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.forpol.2018.04.005>

³ Eskelinen, T., Räsänen, T., Santti, U., Happonen, A., & Kajanus, M. 2017. Designing a Business Model for Environmental Monitoring Services Using Fast MCDS Innovation Support Tools. Technology Innovation Management Review, 7(11): 36-46. <http://doi.org/10.22215/timreview/1119>

2. Timeline

The timeline for undertaking the Local Business Models Workshop is identified below, as part of the process of developing heritage-led regeneration plans.

Timeline and Project input

Figure 2: Timeline and Project Inputs for the development of Rural Regeneration Plans for RURITAGE Replicators

To facilitate this timeline, the Training Workshop for Rs on Business Models took place in Crete at the end of May, along with face-to-face discussions with Savonia to guide the process for the Local Business Model Workshops.

The guidance documents for organising and running the Workshop and the tools to be used are circulated in advance so that the business model workshops will be organized by every local Hub, guided by Savonia and WestBIC, with follow-up support to be provided according to the timeline above.

3. How to Organise the Workshop

3.1 Venue

Ideally, the venue for the event is the local Rural Heritage Hub. The venue should facilitate both plenary sessions with all participating stakeholders, as well as smaller groups (4-7 people each) at round-table workshops, to provide inputs to the Canvas Templates.

If the RHH has insufficient space, considering the estimated number of participating stakeholders and the workshop format, the organisers should identify another suitable venue in a location close-by.

3.2 Target Groups

Similar to the Participatory Workshop, all potential stakeholders at the Replicators, including:

- Policy: regional and local governing bodies, territorial development institutions, mgt of CNH sites, etc.
- Public: local residents, associations, schools, local action groups, civil society organizations, etc.
- Research: universities and research institutes, etc.
- Industry/services/investors: tourism industry representatives, key value chain representatives, centres for territorial development, foundations, transport, health and leisure providers, media, press, etc.

3.3 When to Engage Stakeholders?

Most stakeholders will already be engaged with the RHH at this stage, including for the previous Participatory Workshop. For the Local BM Workshop, it is recommended that invitations to the relevant stakeholders are issued well in advance (at least 15 days before the event), to maximise participation.

3.4 Proposed Agenda

1. Brief Presentation of RURITAGE project objectives at local level, role of stakeholders and benefits of participation (if new stakeholders are present).
2. Brief Summary of the Results of the Participatory Workshop, including selection of Model Actions
3. Presentation of the BM workshop aims and dynamics as part of heritage-led regeneration planning
4. Circulation of Templates and Guides to be used
5. Presentation of the draft Canvas completed for each Model Action (see 3.7 below)
6. Group work to review and complete the Canvas boxes, following the Templates and Guides provided
7. Plenary sessions to present the outputs and agree the results
8. Identification of any additional Actions emerging, and not already considered and complete similar process
9. Introduction of INTO tool for Evaluation of selected Actions and Decision Making on priorities
10. Circulation of BM Workshop Evaluation Questionnaire to Participants
11. Overview of next steps and Hub activities foreseen

Further information on the running of the Workshop is included in Section 3.8 overleaf.

3.5 Duration

A half-day session of 3-4 hours is recommended, according to the proposed Agenda, with a mid-session coffee-break. The actual duration will depend on the number of stakeholders participating, the number of Model Actions selected, the level of engagement and preparatory work already undertaken. However, a longer session is not advised due to potentially reducing the interest of participating stakeholders.

3.6 Preparation and Materials

In order to prepare for the Local BM Workshop, the R's are asked to:

- Understand the role of the BM Workshop as part of the rural regeneration planning process
- Complete the Participatory Workshop to pre-select Model Actions of relevance to the Replicator region.
- Familiarise with the Canvas Templates and the BM process by consulting the guidelines provided
- Familiarise with the INTO tool at <https://into.savonia.fi/about>

The Business Model Canvas template and the Guide to its completion are provided to be used during the workshop, and beforehand for draft canvas preparation, (see 3.7 below). These may also be circulated in advance to Stakeholders as part of the participation invitation, if this is convenient.

3.7 Before the Workshop – Preparing a Canvas Draft

To provide structure to the Workshop and to save time in the event itself, prior to the workshop the Rs should take the selected Model Actions from the Participatory Workshop and develop a draft BM Canvas for each selected Action (using their preferred Canvas Model) and instructed by the guide that is provided in Annex I. Savonia and WestBIC are available to provide feedback on the draft canvases that are prepared prior to the Local BM workshop.

The draft Canvases will then be presented to the Stakeholders at the BM Workshop for discussion and completion.

3.8 During the Workshop

The workshop will follow a participatory format, with plenary sessions and smaller group workshops using the Business Model Canvas Template and Guide provided. The aim of the workshop, the format and the agenda should be presented clearly at the beginning of the event.

According to the Agenda, after presenting the overall RURITAGE project and results of the Participatory Workshop and selected Role Model Actions in plenary session, the next step is to present the Business Model Canvas Template and Guide (Annex I) that will be used. These can best be explained by using the examples of the draft Business Model Canvases that are pre-prepared for the selected Model Actions by the Rs.

Then it is time to arrange the participating stakeholders into round-table discussion groups (e.g. 4-7 persons per group) so that the draft canvases can be discussed, the information can be evaluated and new suggestions provided to improve and complete the canvas according to the guide. As an interactive session, this can be done through the use of sticky-notes to be attached to the relevant boxes of each Canvas Template as part of the review and feedback process, so that it can be presented at a plenary session afterwards, using the template, flipcharts, etc. as aids in the process.

It is envisaged that each draft Canvas will take approx. 30 minutes to review/complete. It will also take a further 5-10 minutes for the plenary presentation of each Canvas and to get feedback from all participants. Depending on the numbers of participants, and also the number of Model Actions selected, it may be feasible for each group to contribute to each draft Canvas and provide specific inputs/feedback. If there are additional draft Canvases for discussion, to complete the workshop within the suggested time limit, it may be more appropriate to divide the draft Canvases into smaller lots across the discussion groups to review, improve and complete. The specific groups can present their completed Canvases and can get inputs from the other participants through the plenary feedback sessions.

Towards the end of the session, assuming successful Canvas completion for Model Actions, it could be discussed about whether there are any other relevant Actions worth considering for the region in the context of heritage-led rural regeneration. If new proposals emerge, then the Canvas preparation work can be undertaken (in groups or plenary) so that a draft may be prepared. This can then be discussed with UNIBO and CE, to discuss the potential and justification for including new Actions within the heritage-led regeneration planning.

The next Steps include the Evaluation, decision making and discussion using the online INTO tool, further explained at the end of Annex I.

At the end of the Workshop, participants should be invited to complete the Workshop Evaluation Questionnaire (Annex II).

3.9 After the Workshop

After the workshop, the draft Canvases should be updated and shared with Savonia and WestBIC for review and feedback so that they can be finalised and then used as part of the heritage-led regeneration planning and investment strategies.

The Replicator/Hub Co-ordinator also needs to complete the Business Model Workshop Event Report according to the Template provided in Annex III.

4. Expected Result

The Principal result of the process is a strategy for CNH business and investment presented in the CNH Canvas framework, focusing on the selected Model Actions. A business model canvas can be completed for each Model Action, using either the CNH or traditional Canvas depending on the Action selected. Each R is expected to have identified and prioritised a number of specific Actions they want to develop further. These can then be used for the further development of their regeneration plans.

5. Costs for Local Workshop

Costs relate to providing the workshop location/facilities and providing catering to participants. Assuming the use of the Rural Heritage Hub as the local workshop venue, the envisaged costs should then be approx. €500 - €1,000. In some cases, local sponsorship arrangements may be possible for some of the costs.

6. Tools and Materials

- The CNH Canvas Framework and guide to its use (Annex I)
- INTO Tool: <https://Into.savonia.fi/about> provides case examples, video and demos on the INTO tool
- Multi-media Projector for presentations, presenting the BM process, the pre-selected Model Actions and draft Canvas(s) that are prepared in advance
- Paper, pens, sticky-notes to assist the participative workshop format
- Flipcharts to present small-group activities in plenary sessions
- Attendance Sheet - for participant signatures
- Business Model Event Evaluation Questionnaire for Stakeholders (Annex II)
- Business Model Event Report – for Hub Co-ordinators (Annex III)

7. Dissemination

Partners shall refer to the Dissemination and Communication plan (Del. 7.1, ICLEI) for the dissemination of this activity. Similar to the Participatory Workshop, **additional suggestions** as provided as follows:

- **Before the event:** distribute flyers/invitations to stakeholders, place posters in key locations, and disseminate the event through social media channels and website. Issue press releases to relevant newspapers.
- **During the event:** place posters, roll-ups, flyers, leaflets and other communication material in visible locations. Potential for some 'live' dissemination of the event on social media, posted on the accounts of the partner organisation and by tagging the project accounts and using relevant hashtags, using short video/ audio interviews and group photos with participants.
- **After the event:** publish pictures, videos and news about your event on the project website, your own website and possibly stakeholder websites as well as on social media and other relevant channels. Issue press releases to relevant newspapers.

8. Monitoring of the activity

FOR PARTICIPANTS:

- Business Model Workshop Evaluation questionnaire (refer to template in Annex II)

FOR HUB COORDINATORS:

- Business Model Workshop Event Report, within 15 days (refer to template in Annex III)
- Completed Business Model Canvas for each Model Action

ANNEX I: The CNH Business Model Canvas Framework & Guide

What is a Business Model?

A 'Business Model' is a common phrase used to explain how the different elements of an 'enterprise' work together to deliver value to the end-user or customer. It describes the rationale of how an organisation creates, delivers, and captures value, in economic, social, cultural or other contexts. It also describes how 'profit' is made from this 'value proposition'.⁴

The term business model is used for a broad range of informal and formal descriptions to represent core aspects of a business, including purpose, business process, target customers, offerings, strategies, infrastructure, organizational structures, sourcing, trading practices, operational processes and policies including culture. Technological development, digitalization, changing consumer values and behaviour are examples of drivers changing business models in several industries.

What is a Business Model Canvas?

A 'Business Model Canvas' is simply a tool to capture a visual format of a Business, centred around the Value Proposition. The original Business Model Canvas, developed by Osterwalder and Pigneur⁵ and illustrated below, consists of 3 key elements:

- **Value proposition:** what the customer or end-user wants?
- **Value creation and delivery:** What is needed to create and deliver the value proposition (Key Partners, Activities, Resources, Customers, Channels, etc.)?
- **Value capture:** This includes an analysis of the proposed Cost Structure and the Revenue Streams, i.e. how much will it cost to deliver the value proposition and how to generate income from the product or service that is delivered?

Figure 3: The Original Business Model Canvas

⁴Magretta, J. (2002). "Why business models matter." *Harvard Business Review* 80(5): 86-92.

⁵Osterwalder, A., Y. Pigneur and C. Tucci (2005). "Clarifying Business Models: Origins, Present, and Future of the Concept." *Communications of the Association for Information Systems* 16(1).

The purpose and use of the original business model canvas is well documented. Some useful video links that clearly explain how to use this Business Model Canvas are given as follows:

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=IP0cUBWTgpY>

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=g4E3fhybhGM>

<https://vimeo.com/89106474>

Business Model Canvas Design for Cultural and Natural Heritage

For RURITAGE Replicators, a specific Business Model Canvas Framework has been developed to capture the various aspects of Cultural and Natural Heritage situations. It is adapted from the original Business Model Canvas (BMC) and from other adaptations of the Canvas applied to related contexts, as an easy-to-use tool to help capture the visual ‘story’ or strategy for heritage-led regeneration initiatives. It learns from various adaptations of the original BMC including the triple-layered sustainable BMC approach by Joyce and Paquin⁶, as well as specific BMC applications to related scenarios, e.g. BMC for Nature Based Solutions⁷.

This CNH Business Model Canvas is illustrated overleaf, which is divided into 4 key parts as building blocks of the overall Business Model:

1. **Value Proposition:** The Value Proposition remains at the centre of the CNH Business Model. However, in the case of heritage-led regeneration the needs and opportunities can be expanded to consider not only economic propositions but also cultural, environmental and other aspects that may be addressed.
2. **Key Infrastructure and Resources:** A key consideration is the Infrastructure and Resources that can be applied to develop heritage-led rural regeneration and resultant value. Both CNH-specific resources that provide a USP as well as other generic resources are required, alongside mobilising the relevant Partners as the building blocks to generate value. Governance is also introduced, which is key to ensure a sustainable and long-term management approach.
3. **Value Creation:** To create value, the development and implementation of key activities is placed alongside the main beneficiaries that are targeted, given their interdependent nature in rural regeneration strategies. The interactions between them are captured within the important Relationships and Channels box.
4. **Financial Modelling/Investment Strategy:** The overall Financial Modelling/Investment Strategy is achieved through implementation of a suitable cost structure for both capital and operational aspects, along with capturing value through appropriate revenue modelling, mindful that direct revenue is not always the only measure of value to be considered. Other measures, including environmental, social and cultural value/returns may also be relevant considerations

These building blocks are further elaborated in the following pages, along with a full guide to its use. A blank CNH Canvas Template is also provided with this guide.

The Canvas may be used for capturing the overall strategic planning for regeneration of the territory, as well as undertaking a Canvas exercise for each identified Model Action selected.

Note: Replicators are free to use the CNH Business Model Canvas, or the original Business Model Canvas if they prefer this format for their local situation.

⁶ Joyce, Alexandre & Paquin, Raymond. (2016). The triple layered business model canvas: A tool to design more sustainable business models. *Journal of Cleaner Production*. 135. 10.1016/j.jclepro.2016.06.067.

⁷ Siobhan McQuaid, Trinity College Dublin & Horizon Nua, A Guide to using the Nature-Based Solutions Business Model Canvas, April 2019

Figure 4: Business Model Canvas (with guide notes) for Cultural and Natural Heritage

2. INFRASTRUCTURE & RESOURCES		1. VALUE PROPOSITION	3. CREATING VALUE	
<p>Key Resources</p> <p>These are the list of key resources from which the value can be created. It includes both the unique CNH resources that gives the region its USP, as well as other relevant resources to be applied.</p> <p>Example CNH Resources:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cultural • Natural • Other <p>Other Relevant Resources:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Financial • Human • Infrastructure • Other 	<p>Key Partners</p> <p>The involvement of Key Partners is usually a prerequisite so that the region can mobilise the resources and work collaboratively to create value for beneficiaries. Examples include:</p> <p>Owners Stakeholders Community Local Authorities Government Chambers NGOs Universities Investors Industry Media Others</p>	<p>Needs & Opportunities</p> <p style="color: green;">The Starting point for the Canvas is here!</p> <p>The initial effort is to consider what needs and opportunities are of value to beneficiaries and the region that can support rural regeneration that can be delivered through key activities, products and services that may be developed. There is wide ranging potential of CNH that can foster rural regeneration, including offering:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Economic Value • Environmental Value • Cultural Value • Social/Societal Value <p>The needs and opportunities identified will be specific to the given territory, but may be inspired by Role Models from other regions. Examples might include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Providing sustainable solutions, services or products • Maximising tourism potential • Enhancing visitor experience • Promoting cultural diversity • Sustainable rural food production • Localised services • Social inclusion • Others 	<p>Key Activities</p> <p>These are the core actions in terms of deliver on the value proposition, addressing needs and capitalising on opportunities identified. Examples include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scenario work • Strategic Planning; • Product/ Service development; • Testing, Piloting, Demos • Marketing/Promotion; • Training & Education • LCA analysis • Co-creation with end-users/customers • Others 	<p>Beneficiaries</p> <p>This is a wide definition to capture the various target customers and user groups (that may also include some key partners) for who value will be created and delivered. Examples may include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Customers • End users • Visitors • Partners • Stakeholders • Community • Civic Society • Others
<p>Governance</p> <p>It is good practice to adopt an effective governance model that captures the inter-dependence of the partners, and allows for efficient mgt and operation of CNH-led activities. Therefore the focus is typically on:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Organisational Structure(s) • Engagement model(s) • Ownership model(s) 		<p style="text-align: center;">Relationships and Channels</p> <p>Methods of communication and engagement with user-groups, including marketing and promotion are critical to success and sustainability of initiatives. Items to consider, relevant to the local context include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Engagement and co-operation • Inclusion issues • Communications • Awareness campaigns • Other marketing and promotion activities 		
<p style="text-align: center;">Cost Structure</p> <p>Both Capital costs and Operational costs relating to developing/delivering the activities are key considerations, both of which may require investment to achieve the potential identified. In some cases, specific cost reduction strategies may be possible to deliver a sustainable cost structure. Therefore consider the following here:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Capital costs and sources of finance • Operational model/costs • Cost reduction potential – volunteers/donations, etc 		<p style="text-align: center;">Capturing Value</p> <p>Value capture may include the traditional economic focus of making money/profit from activities. In the context of CNH, there may also be other considerations of how stakeholders wish to evaluate the value that is created. Therefore a combination of the following may be considered:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Economic – Revenues, grants/subsidies, investments, etc. • Social / Societal – Quality of Life enhancements, Inclusion, Integration, etc. • Environmental – Carbon reduction, recycling, resilience, protection and conservation • Others 		
<p>4. FINANCIAL MODEL / INVESTMENT STRATEGY</p>				

Use of the CNH Business Model Canvas

The Business Model Canvas for CNH is designed to be used as a tool to support the planning and implementation of Heritage-led regeneration in Replicator regions involved in the RURITAGE project. In particular, it has the following identified uses:

Strategic Planning: Focusing on the model actions selected by Rs in the participatory workshop as a starting point, The CNH Business Model Canvas is a useful first step for individuals or groups to plan the implementation of CNH projects and initiatives. It helps in considering all the basic building blocks to develop a successful long-term and sustainable project.

Stakeholder engagement: The CNH Business Model Canvas helps to identify partners or beneficiaries that may be interested in getting involved in the planning and implementation. It is a useful tool to present heritage-led regeneration proposals to stakeholders and to get partners acquainted with the key elements of the project methodology: Systemic Innovation Areas (SIAs), 6 Capitals, and Cross-cutting themes in the RURITAGE approach. It also:

- Provides participants with experiential opportunities to learn about model actions
- Creates opportunity to express diverse stakeholder perspectives and foster mutual understanding
- Creates a safe space for brainstorming new innovative projects.

Investment Strategies for CNH: The CNH Business Model Canvas addresses the core elements of the overall Business Case to be made in creating value, identifying the capital/investment costs, stakeholders/partners and revenue modelling scenarios. In this regard it is a useful tool as the first step in identifying how to finance the development of CNH and heritage-led regeneration proposals.

Taking an innovative approach, it may throw up creative solutions through the combination of various stakeholders and resources to deliver on the value propositions identified and how to reach the target beneficiaries. This is one of the next steps in the RURITAGE approach to heritage led-rural regeneration support for Replicators.

Communication tool: Deriving economic value from CNH is a relatively new concept for some, and may be difficult to explain to stakeholders without the use of easy-to-use and accepted tools. The CNH Business Model Canvas provides a relatively simple way of communicating what you want to do and why, who should be involved and how that can successfully happen. The Business Model Canvas is an approach that is becoming widely understood by people from many different backgrounds.

Guide to Using the CNH Business Model Canvas

The CNH Business Model Canvas is supported by this Guide, a facilitated Group Workshop for Replicators as part of the RURITAGE project and individual consultations with R's, including support for local Business Model Workshops to be undertaken in Rural Heritage Hubs in Replicator regions.

The implementation of the BMC takes into consideration the Good Practices and Lessons Learnt from Business Modelling and Investment Strategies of Role Models within the RURITAGE project. It also draws on the Stakeholder listing, Baseline data and KPIs identified for RURITAGE monitoring as a method of capturing and monitoring the results of the process.

1. The Value Proposition of CNH-Led Initiatives

The first section of the CNH Business Model Canvas to be considered is the Value Proposition, with a focus on the value that can be offered through addressing customer/end-user needs and also for delivering on the opportunities identified for targeted Beneficiaries.

INFRASTRUCTURE & RESOURCES		1.VALUE PROPOSITION	CREATING VALUE	
Key Resources	Key Partners	Needs & Opportunities e.g. Providing sustainable solutions, services or products Maximising Tourism potential Enhancing visitor experience Promoting cultural diversity Sustainable rural food production Localised services Social inclusion Others	Key Activities	Beneficiaries
Governance			Relationships and Channels	
Cost Structure		Capturing Value		
FINANCIAL MODEL / INVESTMENT STRATEGY				

Figure 5: CNH Business Model Canvas – Focus on Value Proposition

From the RURITAGE Role Model analysis, the types of value proposition can be quite wide ranging. In the case of CNH it is important to look beyond the obvious products and services that deliver value but to also consider other potential value that may be relevant as part of rural regeneration, including:

- Economic Value - address key economic challenges in the region
- Environmental Value - addressing environmental challenges
- Cultural Value – Enhancing and promoting existing cultural attributes
- Social/societal value – addressing key social challenges in the community

It is also important to consider if there are further direct, or sometimes indirect value propositions that can be developed through rural regeneration strategies. The list of model actions, along with propositions that are generated across stakeholders may also lead to trade-offs amongst proposals, which can be both positive and negative. This will require further discussion and agreement within the context of the overall Business Model Canvas to achieve the overall aims.

2. Infrastructure and Resources

The second part of the CNH Business Model Canvas to be completed concerns the Infrastructure and Resources from which value creation can be generated. This is divided into three parts on the left side of the Model:

- Key Resources
- Key Partners
- Governance

2. INFRASTRUCTURE & RESOURCES		VALUE PROPOSITION	CREATING VALUE	
Key Resources	Key Partners	Needs & Opportunities	Key Activities	Beneficiaries
CNH Resources: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cultural • Natural • Other Other Resources: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Financial • Human • Infrastructure • Other 	e.g. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Owners • Stakeholders • Community • Local Authorities • Government • Chambers • NGOs • Universities • Investors • Industry • Media • Others 		Relationships and Channels	
Governance				
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Organisational Structure(s) • Engagement model(s) • Ownership model(s) 				
Cost Structure		Capturing Value		
FINANCIAL MODEL / INVESTMENT STRATEGY				

Figure 6: CNH Business Model Canvas – Focus on Infrastructure & Resources

Key Resources: From a CNH perspective, a unique relates to heritage-led regeneration resources concerning cultural and natural and built infrastructure that can form the basis for the specific Value Proposition and set it apart from other regions as a potential USP. This is combined with other relevant resources, including financial, human and physical that make up the overall resource scenario that can be integrated and applied towards value creation.

Key Partners: Despite having many CNH Resources, regions will not fully benefit from its potential without the involvement and participation of Key Partners. As the Stakeholder listing shows, the interested Partners can be wide ranging as depicted above. Of note, often partners in various regeneration projects can also be key beneficiaries from a value creation perspective, discussed later.

Governance: Given the interdependence between various partners and stakeholders and the relevant resources, there is a need to adopt a good governance model for the management and operation of the CNH-led activities. These can sometimes be complex with many different partners and beneficiaries and priorities involved, therefore it is useful to consider this at an early stage to maximise the potential for long term success.

3. Creating Value

The next part of the CNH Business Model Canvas relates to Value Creation - mobilising and organising key resources and developing actions to deliver on the value proposition, which encompasses the following:

- Key Activities
- Beneficiaries
- Relationships and Channels

INFRASTRUCTURE & RESOURCES		VALUE PROPOSITION	3.CREATING VALUE	
Key Resources	Key Partners	Needs & Opportunities	Key Activities e.g. Scenario work; Opportunity identification; Strategic planning Product/ Service development; Testing, Piloting, Demos Marketing/Promotion; Training & Education LCA analysis Co-creation with end-users/customers Others	Beneficiaries e.g. Customers End users Visitors Partners Stakeholders Community Civic Society Others
Governance			Relationships and Channels Engagement and co-operation Inclusion Communications Awareness campaign	
Cost Structure		Capturing Value		
FINANCIAL MODEL / INVESTMENT STRATEGY				

Figure 7: CNH Business Model Canvas – Focus on Creating Value

Key Activities: This is the core of the ‘action’ in terms of deciding how to deliver on the value proposition to address customer needs and capitalise on opportunities identified. Activities may be very focused in nature to deliver specific tasks, but may also be more strategic to develop long-term plans for implementation to address needs in a structured way. The list of Role Model Actions provides a useful starting point for consideration of suitable activities for Replicators.

Key Beneficiaries: The term **Key Beneficiaries** is used as a wide definition to broaden the understanding of who may be the target customers and user groups. In the case of CNH and regeneration there can be many interested and affected parties, including project partners/ stakeholders in some cases. The value proposition and proposed activities should be developed appropriately to meet their varying needs.

Relationships and Channels: The methods of communication and engagement with user-groups and beneficiaries is critical to the success and sustainability of any project. Awareness creation and inclusion are important at the outset whilst focused approaches may be required for specific audiences.

4. Financial Modelling and Investment Strategies

In the final part of the inter-related CNH BMC, the costs associated with the activities and value that can be derived from their delivery are evaluated, aimed at developing a sustainable (or profitable) model and drafting an investment strategy according to the objectives of the proposal being considered.

INFRASTRUCTURE & RESOURCES		VALUE PROPOSITION	CREATING VALUE	
Key Resources	Key Partners	Needs & Opportunities	Key Activities	Beneficiaries
Governance			Relationships and Channels	
Cost Structure Capital costs Operational model/costs Cost reduction potential – volunteers/donations, etc Other		Capturing Value Economic – Revenues, grants/subsidies, investments, etc. Social / Societal – QoL enhancements, inclusion, Integration, etc. Environmental – Carbon reduction, recycling, resilience, protection and conservation Other		
4.FINANCIAL MODEL / INVESTMENT STRATEGY				

Figure 8: CNH Business Model Canvas – Focus on Capturing Value

Capturing Value: In the original Business Model Canvas, Capturing Value normally describes how enterprises make money from their value proposition. In the case of CNH-led rural regeneration, a wider approach is often relevant, reflecting the varied nature of these activities.

In particular, for some types of regeneration initiatives, producing substantial direct revenues, at least at the outset, can be challenging. This can be the case where there is a predominant public or social good, or an environmental or cultural bias. If relevant, such criteria may be used as indicators of Value Capture themselves. In these cases, Model Actions identify other funding sources, including grants, subsidies, donations and other creative options.

Cost Structure: The lessons learnt from the business analysis of Model Actions identifies the need to consider financing solutions and funding for both the capital aspects as well as operational costs as a key part of the business model. Cost reduction strategies may also be relevant, including the consideration of partnership approaches, volunteerism and the methods of sustainable operations.

The combination of these factors will form the basis of the overall **Financial Modelling/Investment Strategy**, aimed at developing a sustainable model for the proposed action(s). This often requires innovative approaches to satisfy the needs of multiple stakeholders.

Multi-Criteria Evaluation of Proposed Actions with INTO Tool

Each Action will be evaluated according to the set criteria. In the fast-track evaluation as part of a workshop, an optimal number of evaluation criteria is around 3-5 and takes about 30-60 minutes to perform.

The evaluation criteria will be decided before the business model workshop and will be added to the Into evaluation environment in local language.

Business models are frequently evaluated by criteria like business potential, competitive advantage, sustainability, feasibility, and potential for economical impact or potential to attract investors. In Ruritage, our goal is that the actions would increase cultural, natural, built, social human and financial capital.

Figure 9. Community capitals by Butler Flora, 2008.

The following criteria are recommended:

Environmental value: Does the action promote environmental sustainability and limit the use on non-renewable resources? 1 not at all, 7 very much

Social value: e.g. Does the action promote social sustainability, transparency, wellbeing, equity, community engagement?, 1 = very little, 7, very much

Economical value: does the action bring potential for sustainable economical impact? Does the action boost new economies? : 1 not at all, 7 very much.

Feasibility: Is the action feasible in short-medium term, 3-5 yrs? Are the resources needed (in terms of knowledge, economic, human capital) available for the implementation? 1 not at all.. 7 very feasible

Idea	(Evaluated 1 / 53)	ENVIRONMENTAL VALUE (1 - 7) : Does the action promote environmental sustainability and limit the use on non-	SOCIAL VALUE (1 - 7) e.g. Does the action promote social sustainability, transparency, wellbeing, equity,	ECONOMICAL VALUE (1 - 7) does the action bring potential for sustainable economical impact? Does the action boost	FEASIBILITY (1 - 7) Is the action feasible in short-medium term, 3-5 yrs? Are the resources needed (in terms of	Comments
Evaluate - DEMO STRATEGIC CNH CANVAS WITH INTO TOOL Info						
The evaluation page expires on 8/10/2019 3:21:09 PM						
Ideas are evaluated against four value-based evaluation criteria:						
Environmental value: Does the action promote environmental sustainability and limit the use on non-renewable resources? 1 not at all, 7 very much						
Social value: e.g. Does the action promote social sustainability, transparency, wellbeing, equity, community engagement?, 1 = very little, 7, very much						
Economical value: does the action bring potential for sustainable economical impact? Does the action boost new economies? : 1 not at all, 7 very much.						
Feasibility: Is the action feasible in short-medium term, 3-5 yrs? Are the resources needed (in terms of knowledge, economic, human capital) available for the implementation? 1 not at all.. 7 very feasible						
Relationships and channels (7 ideas)						
Social media						OUR COMPANY IS EAGER TO DEVELOP A NEW SOCIAL MEDIA APP TO PROMOTE CULTURAL HERITAGE TOURISM IN OUR REGION
Social media						
Meeting with the landowner						
Meetings with the landowner						

Figure 10. Into -evaluation environment can be tested at a demo process CNH CANVAS at: <https://into.savonia.fi/cnh-canvas/Evaluate> Key: Rur2019

Annex II: Business model event evaluation questionnaire

Objective

As part of the monitoring procedures in terms of efficacy and efficiency of Hub activities, a qualitative assessment will be made after each event asking for stakeholders' feedback on several aspects.

Indications

1. Translate the following questionnaire into your **local language** (or in English if considered)
2. Distribute the questionnaire either in **paper format** and/or through an **online form (Google form, Microsoft forms, etc)** or both. In case of paper format, make sure that these are placed in a visible place (e.g. in a stand or table nearby the entrance, next to the registration list). If in online format, make sure you send out the link to all participants and that you specify the deadline to fill it out.
3. During the event, take a few minutes to explain **why** this data is being collected and **how** participants should fill out the questionnaire.
4. You should at least collect **10-15 answers**.
5. After the event, complete the online survey placed on your event folder with the participant's answers OR upload answers **in English** in the SharePoint (Excel), within 15 days.

BUSINESS MODEL EVENT QUESTIONNAIRE				
<u>I. OVERALL EVALUATION</u>	<i>Please mark your answer</i>			
	VERY MUCH	MUCH	FAIR	INSUFFICIENT NOT AT ALL
How satisfied are you of the event organised?				
To what extent do you feel confident with the general aims of the project?				
To what extent do you consider this project relevant for your territory?				
To what extent do you consider relevant your involvement in the development or strengthening of the innovative strategies for promotion of cultural and natural heritage in your area?				
<u>II. DETAILED EVALUATION</u>	EXCELLENT VERY SATISFIED	GOOD SATISFIED	FAIR QUITE SATISFIED	INSUFFICIENT NOT SATISFIED
1. PRE-EVENT ORGANISATION				
Did you receive the invitation in good time?				
Did the invitation offer a clear picture of what the event was about?				
<i>If not through invitation, how did you learn about the event? Please specify</i>				
2. OBJECTIVES				
Do you have a clear picture of the purpose of the Business Model Canvas?				
Do you have a clear picture on the business models and investment strategy process?				
Do you have a clear picture of the purpose of the INTO tool?				
How well did the evaluation criteria fit to your business models process?				
How well did the event correspond to your expectations?				
3. HOW WOULD YOU RATE THE FOLLOWING?				
Business model Canvas usefulness				
INTO tool usefulness				
Quality of presentations – speakers (if any)				
Documentation & Visual aid				

Quality of moderation and of the Hub team				
Structure and overall design of the event				
Level of interaction among participants				
4. LOGISTICAL ASPECTS				
On-site organisation and support				
Venue's facility (Hub)				
Did the venue offer an environment that supports creativity?				
5. COMMENTS				
1. What did you most appreciate during the event?				
2. Do you have any recommendation for the improvement of the organization of the next Hub activities?				
3. After this event, are you interested in participating in future events?				

ANNEX III: Business models event report - Hub Co-ordinators

[Name of the organisation in charge of the event]

Venue	
Date	
Duration	
Type and number of stakeholders involved and role in the event	Please include the name of the different stakeholders involved and also the different SIAs they represent, if applicable i.e. local government 3 local food company 2 university etc.
Total number of participants	
Number of female participants (indicative)	
Number of male participants (indicative)	
Number of disabled people, if applicable	
Number of migrants, if applicable	

Agenda of the event

Please include the agenda of the event.

Photos of the event

Please provide some pictures from the event (making sure you comply with GDPR regulations)

Event assessment

Overall how would you rate the success of this specific event? (*mark only one option*)

- Very successful
- Fairly successful
- Not too successful
- Not successful at all

Please briefly describe the event including:

Your key takeaways from the BM workshop

Max. half page

Feedback on the CNH Canvas. How useful was it? How well did it fit in your local process and workshop?

Max. half page

A qualitative assessment will be made after each event asking for stakeholders' feedback on several aspects, with questionnaire format included in Annex II.

Guidelines for the Round Table of stakeholders

For Rs

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Table 1: Abbreviations

RHH	Rural Heritage Hub
RM	Role Model
R	Replicator
SIA	Systemic Intervention Area

2. Objective

2.1 General objective

The general objectives of the round tables with local stakeholders is to define and detail the activities necessary to carry out the actions of the heritage-led strategies.

After the participatory and the business models workshops, Replicators have now selected the actions they will include in their Action Plan. Now it is time to carefully detailed how to co-implement and co-monitor the actions. During these meetings RURITAGE partners will have to prepare the basis for building the agreements with relevant stakeholders, to define in detail their roles, responsibilities and contribution (financial, human, in kind, etc.). Round tables will take place between October and November 2019.

2.2 Specific objectives

- Define the list of necessary activities to carry out the actions
- Define the role of the stakeholders in the co-implementation of the action
- Define the role of the stakeholders in the co-monitoring of the action
- Start thinking about the sustainability of the action in medium-long term (after the project end)

3. How to organize the round table(s)

3.1 What to do before the workshop

Before the workshop, you need to carefully think about the actions you have chosen to be included in your action plan. To do so, please refer to the Action Plan template, provided by UNIBO.

Throughout that template you will start defining for each action:

- Objectives and targets
- Main beneficiaries of the action
- Stakeholders to be involved
- Role of the stakeholders
- Indicative costs of the action
- Timeline
- Specific activities necessary to carry out the action

Particular attention should be dedicated to define the specific activities needed to carry out your action. The list of activities should be draft before the round table event and integrated with input from your stakeholders. A draft template for list of specific activities is available in Annex I.

Contact your stakeholders quite in advance to set a dedicated meeting with them. You can decide to have bilateral or groups meeting (depending on the role of your stakeholders, the actions you are working on, etc.).

Please discuss with your reference person at UNIBO how you plan to proceed.

3.2 What to do during the workshop

The aim of the round table should be clearly explained to your stakeholder at the beginning of the workshop. We suggest you to proceed in the following way:

- Present to your stakeholder/s the developed action/s– according to the template of the action plan provided by UNIBO
- Ask them to integrate the list of needed activities
- Agree on their role (in terms of specific responsibilities, type of contribution - in kind, human, financial, etc.)
- Identify a responsible person for each action
- Draft the agreement (e.g. binding/ non-binding agreement, support letter, sponsorship)

3.3 What to do after the workshop

After the workshop, you should be able to fulfil Annex 1 and the relative Action plan template. Moreover, an additional remote meeting with UNIBO should be organised in order to discuss the results and the ongoing draft of the Action Plan

4. Venue

The venue of the event can vary. It can be the local Rural Heritage Hub, but it could also take place at stakeholders' premises, replicators' premises, etc.

5. Target groups

Stakeholders that will be involved in the co-implementation and co-monitoring of the action.

6. When to engage stakeholders?

Stakeholders should be contact directly (phone, email, etc.) at least one week before to set a suitable moment to all.

7. Duration

A session of 1-2 hours per each round table is suggested.

8. Expected results

After this workshop, Hub coordinators and stakeholders will have clear ideas on the timing, modality, responsibility and costs of each action, detailed per specific activities. This will be the base of the action plan for heritage-led regeneration.

9. Costs

No particular costs are foreseen for this activity.

Possible partnerships and sponsorships: Accommodation providers, restaurants and local food producers (free small catering/snacks), farming companies, investors, non-profit organizations/associations, artists, handcrafters, universities and research centres, transport providers

10. Useful materials

- Precompiled Action template
- Precompiled Specific Activities (Annex I)
- Example of possible agreement to be signed
- Signature sheet - for attendance

11. Dissemination

Partners shall refer Dissemination and Communication plan (ICLEI) for the dissemination of this activity. However, some **additional suggestions** are provided below:

- **Before the event:** no particular dissemination activities are foreseen since the round table(s) is/are conceived as operative meetings to agree on the activities and responsibilities. Nevertheless, it is good to public your own institutional website, on social media and other relevant channels the date of the event or the calendar of the events in case of more than one event, to make the general public aware of the ongoing process.
- **During the event:** place posters, roll-ups, flyers, leaflets and other communication material in visible spots. At the same time, it would be also good to have some 'live' dissemination of the event on the social media, posted on the accounts of the partner organisation and by tagging the project accounts and using hashtags, if relevant. Take short (1 to 3 min.) video/ audio interviews. Take a group picture with participants.
- **After the event:** publish pictures, videos and news about your event on the project's website and your own institutional website, on social media and other relevant channels. Send out press releases to relevant newspapers.

12. Monitoring of the activity

Please refer to the following documents available in the SharePoint folder and upload within 15 days:

- **FOR HUB COORDINATORS**
Round table report – refer to the template in Annex I
List of specific activities per action – refer to the template in Annex II
Signature sheet - for attendance

13. Annex I: Round table event report – Hub Coordinator

[Name of the organisation in charge of the event]

Venue	
Date	
Duration	
Stakeholders involved	Please include the name of the different stakeholders involved
Total number of participants	
Number of female participants (indicative)	
Number of male participants (indicative)	
Number of disabled people, if applicable	
Number of migrants, if applicable	

Agenda of the event

Please include the agenda of the event.

Photos of the event

Please provide some pictures from the event (making sure you comply with GDPR regulations)

Event assessment

Overall how would you rate the success of this specific event? (*mark only one option*)

- Very successful
- Fairly successful
- Not too successful

Not successful at all

Please fulfil Annex I to define stakeholders' roles and responsibility in each action

Please briefly describe **main success and difficulties** related to this specific event, if any. Please provide suggestions for similar or future events (including improvements you would like to apply in the next events you will organize).

Max. half page

